

THE APPEAL OF THE IDENTITARIAN MOVEMENT:
AN ANALYSIS OF INDIVIDUAL MOTIVES AND
INFLUENCING FACTORS FOR MEMBERSHIP

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Declaration

I confirm that I am fully responsible for the work presented in this thesis. All original contributions are my own, except where explicitly stated in acknowledgments or through detailed citations. I also confirm that this thesis, or any part of its original content, has not been submitted to this or any other institution for the purpose of obtaining a degree.

I further acknowledge that I have followed the University's ethical guidelines for research. I take full responsibility for ensuring that ethical considerations have been thoroughly addressed, potential risks identified and mitigated, and all necessary ethical approvals obtained. I have ensured that the rights of all participants in this research have been respected.

Signed:

Date: 10.04.2025

List of abbreviations

AfD	Alternative for Germany (Alternative für Deutschland)
CDU	Christian Democratic Union (Christlich Demokratische Union Deutschlands)
GI	Generation Identity
IfS	Institute for State Policy (Institut für Staatspolitik)
IM	Identitarian Movement (Identitäre Bewegung)
NS	National Socialist
Pegida	Patriotic Europeans against the Islamisation of the Occident (Patriotische Europäer gegen die Islamisierung des Abendlandes)
TR	Transformative Radicalization Theory
WSD	We are Germany (Wir sind Deutschland)

Abstract

This study focuses on the phenomenon of individuals joining the Identitarian Movement (IM), which has been classified as right-wing extremist by the Federal Office for the Protection of the Constitution in 2019. It makes a novel contribution to the existing body of knowledge by providing empirical findings on the underlying motives for joining the IM. The existing literature on the IM remains limited, particularly regarding studies that adopt an insider perspective on the experiences of those who have joined the group. This study addresses this gap by employing a qualitative approach, including semi-structured interviews with 14 members and participant observations of three regional meetings, two Christmas parties (n = 48) and the observation of one demonstration of the IM. Based on a modified Grounded Theory approach and a sensitising concept mainly built on the Transformative Radicalization Theory, the research reveals age-related differences in motives for joining, identifying two main types: emotional and rational. While emotional motives were focusing on emotional relationships and identity development, rational motives were shaped by a broader societal perspective, driven by a sense of social responsibility that extends beyond personal concerns. The IM offers various points of identification, enabling individuals to relate to the group in ways that reflect their personal values, experiences, and goals. One important aspect was the phenomenon of 'para-social relationships', one-sided emotional bonds with media figures, particularly Martin Sellner, to bind individuals to the extremist ideology by appealing to their individual motives. Furthermore, the study identifies three forms of engagement: high, moderate and low level of engagement. The interviewees differed in both the amount of time they invested in and the ways they engaged with the IM. The level of engagement is found to be influenced by the individual motives, the regional group's structure, pre-existing far-right networks, and length of membership.

1 Introduction

'The fear of extremism is growing', reported the German newspaper *Frankfurter Allgemeine*, highlighting a survey in which 59 percent of 1,000 respondents expressed concern about the rising tide of political extremism, particularly from the right (Albermann, 2024). The fact that this fear is not unfounded is shown by the results of the latest study commissioned by the Friedrich Ebert Foundation which confirmed a rise of right-wing extremist and anti-democratic attitudes in Germany (Zick and Mokros, 2023, pp. 66–67). The study revealed that eight percent of the participants had a clear right-wing extremist orientation, compared to around two percent in previous years (*ibid.*, pp. 70–71). Additionally, a higher number of individuals did not align themselves clearly, and instead positioned themselves between democratic and anti-democratic statements (*ibid.*, pp. 64–65). This finding is particularly concerning, as it indicates that a growing segment of the population remains ambivalent towards democracy.

The rise in right-wing extremism is also reflected in the number of politically right-wing motivated offences. The Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community (Bundesministerium für Inneres und für Heimat, 2024, p. 4) reported a 23.21 per cent increase in politically right-wing motivated offences in 2023 (28.945) compared to 2022 (23.493). Propaganda offences accounted for more than half of the criminal offenses (2023: 16.698; 2022: 14.132) (*ibid.*, p. 5). Hate crime¹ offences (15.087) rose by 47.63 per cent (*ibid.*, p. 11), with politically right-wing motivated hate crimes accounting for 11.603 cases, marking a 38 per cent increase (*ibid.*, p. 12). Among these offenses were terror attacks in Halle, Hanau or Wolfhagen-Istha which highlighted anti-immigration sentiments and Islamophobic attitudes in particular. Given this context, it is unsurprising that the President of the German domestic intelligence services, Thomas Haldenwang, identifies right-wing extremism as the greatest danger to democracy and security in Germany (Süddeutsche Zeitung 2024; see also Zick and Mokros 2023, p. 53).

¹ Offences which are motivated by group-related prejudices (Bundesministerium für Inneres und für Heimat, 2024, p. 11).

These alarming findings align with the observed rightward shift in Germany over the past few years, driven by broader political trends (Pfahl-Traughber, 2022, p. 146), alongside a rise and increasing professionalisation of far-right groups operating within parliamentary and extra-parliamentary spaces, and across media platforms (Quent, 2024, p. 15). The presence of the political party 'Alternative für Deutschland' (AfD) in parliaments, along with the rise of the Identitarian Movement (IM) – the research object of this study – and large Pegida (Patriotic Europeans against the Islamisation of the Occident) rallies, reflect political shifts that were unseen before 2010 (Pfahl-Traughber, 2022, p. 146; Schütz, Kollmorgen and Schäller, 2021, p. 14).

While similar phenomena, such as the Sozialistische Reichspartei in the 1950s, the Republikaner in the 1990s (e.g. Mudde, 2000), or the violent attacks on asylum seekers in Rostock-Lichtenhagen in 1992 (e.g. Panayi, 1994), have appeared in post-war Germany, the simultaneous emergence and persistence of these groups and political parties in recent years may point to a unique and enduring shift in the political landscape. For instance, the AfD election successes were observable in Saxony, where the party reached 28.4 per cent in the state parliamentary elections in 2019 and 25.7 per cent in the federal parliamentary elections in 2021, followed by 30.6 per cent in the state parliamentary elections in 2024 (Statistisches Landesamt des Freistaates Sachsen, 2019, 2021, 2024). This trend continued in this year's federal election, in which the AfD achieved 20,8 percent and thus became the second strongest party after the Christian Democratic Union (CDU) (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025).

In reference to the German Federal elections, Blumenberg (2023, p. 29) claims that these 'are not usually considered to be particularly exciting or even spectacular'. Since the foundation of the Federal Republic in 1949, German governments have largely alternated between Christian Democratic (CDU/CSU-led) and Social Democratic (SPD-led) coalitions, often supported by smaller parties such as the Free Democrats (FDP) or the Greens. The election of Olaf Scholz in 2021 marked the SPD's brief return to government after sixteen years under Angela Merkel (CDU), reflecting political continuity and stability (Blumenberg, 2023, p. 33; Schläger, Engels and Loew, 2025, pp. 2–3).

However, the political landscape has changed. A critique mainstream political parties face is that they 'became indistinguishable' (Winlow and Hall, 2023, p. 65). Winlow and Hall (2023, p. 65) argue that this development has caused politics to 'descen[d] into the mere administration of what already existed'. Campbell and Davidson-

Schmich (2023, p. 2) describe Germany as ‘a system once famed for enviable levels of political stability [that] is now marked by long-term, accumulating, and reinforcing changes’. According to them, the growing complexity and diversification of political conflicts have led to an increase in the number of relevant parties, and ‘the dominance of the catch-all parties has been replaced by a more competitive electoral marketplace’ (ibid.). In 2025, the SPD lost about 9 per cent while the right-wing political party AfD ranked second after the CDU, after losing 2,3 per cent of their voters (10,3%) in 2021, following a more than double increase in 2025. As Campbell and Davidson-Schmich (2023, p. 15) claim, the AfD ‘has established itself as a stable competitor in the German party system’. Besides, the political party Die Linke (a left-wing party) gained 3,8 per cent and was able to move into the Bundestag with 8,8 per cent (Schläger, Engels and Loew, 2025, p. 4).

These developments prompt a critical inquiry into the underlying factors driving these changes in society and politics. Over the years, researchers have extensively examined the reasons behind the growing support for far-right extremist attitudes and conducted studies to explain why individuals affiliate with far-right extremist groups or political parties (Ashe *et al.*, 2021, p. 2). However, as noted by Backes and Moreau (2011, p. 9), the research field is ‘by no means “exhausted”’, indicating that substantial gaps persist in our understanding of this phenomenon. A circumstance that continues to exist due to the fact that the phenomenon evolves over time (e.g. Vissing, 2022).

The rise of right-wing extremist and populist tendencies can be attributed to a complex interplay of various factors. One frequently mentioned aspect is the ‘fear of social decline’² (Küpper, 2017, p. 98). After reunification, historical and structural disadvantages have played a particularly significant role in Eastern Germany (e.g. Ali, 2018, p. 277). Many people had to ‘fight hard for their social advancement’ (ibid., p. 99). Even though pensions have now been equalised (Deutsche Rentenversicherung [German pension insurance], 2025) and real wages and employment have generally improved (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2025b), inflation and rising housing costs have nonetheless eroded the purchasing power of lower-income households (Reuters, 2024; Statistisches Bundesamt, 2025a). Moreover, incomes in the region remain

² All German original quotes used in this work have been translated into English by the author.

comparatively low, and significant wage gaps between East and West persist (e.g. Ali, 2018, p. 99). This economic inequality has fostered frustration and discontent among many.

However, what proves more decisive than economic reality is the ‘subjective interpretation of one’s own economic situation’ (Küpper, 2017, p. 99) and feelings of collective disadvantage and threat (ibid., see also Rippl and Baier, 2005). Küpper, Rees and Zick (2016, p. 89) claim that ‘the feeling of collective threat is largely immune to facts and measures aimed at increasing security or individual protection’, as it feels distant and unrelated to one’s own situation (ibid.).

Furthermore, a general sense of disorientation in the face of globalisation and rapid societal change enables right-wing extremist movements and populist actors to gain support by presenting seemingly clear, nationalistic solutions (ibid.). They deliberately exploit these sentiments by amplifying fears, assigning blame to minorities, and offering simplistic explanations for complex social changes (ibid.).

These dynamics are also a product of crises within society. According to Zick (2023, p. 28) crises are ‘good times’ for extremists as they provide a fertile ground to strengthen their propagated ideology – ‘Populists and right-wing extremists tap into the deeply rooted fears of insecurity and change, and the need for security and certainty’ (Zick, 2023, p. 28). According to Quent (2024, pp. 15–16), many people turn towards nation and identity as a way to cope with the complexity of global responsibilities brought by these crises and the perceived fear of losing control.

These fears are used as a bridge to extremist ideologies which offer seemingly easy solutions to complex problems (Zick, 2023, p. 21). The past years have been marked by multiple crises such as the Russia-Ukraine war and the conflict in the Middle East, public health crisis such as the Covid-19 pandemic; and environmental crises around climate change. However, these crises are not universally accepted; some question their legitimacy, viewing them as tools to justify political agendas (e.g. Moffitt, 2015). Such contested narratives and the resulting societal polarisation have fuelled the rise of far-right movements, exploiting public fears and distrust (ibid.). Over the course of the migration flows in 2014/2015, which are often framed in public discourse as a

refugee crisis, several far-right movements and political parties that propagate the fight against the so-called 'Islamisation' of Europe have gained more attention.

Data from the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (2017, pp. 10, 13) show that the number of people applying for asylum in Germany rose sharply in 2016 (745,545), representing a more than threefold increase compared to 2014 (202,834). In 2016, Syria continued to represent the largest group of asylum seekers in Germany, followed by Afghanistan and Iraq, which both moved up in the ranking compared to the previous year. The most significant increases in applications in comparison to 2015 were recorded for Iran, Afghanistan, Iraq and Nigeria (*ibid.*, p. 18).

In 2016, the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (2016, p. 2) decided on 695,733 asylum applications. The majority concerned applicants from Syria (295,040), with a protection rate of 98 per cent, followed by Iraq (68,562; 70.2 per cent) and Afghanistan (68,246; 55.8 per cent).

The IAB brief report examines how refugees who arrived in Germany in 2015 have integrated into the labour market (Brücker, Jaschke and Kosyakova, 2025). Nine years after their arrival, about 64 per cent of them are employed, compared to roughly 70 per cent in the general population (*ibid.*, p. 1). The occupational distribution among employed refugees is concentrated in a limited number of job sectors. Many are employed in occupations facing labour shortages as well as in essential fields that are critical to the functioning of society (*ibid.*, p. 4).

Various scholars have examined the relationship between immigration and the support for far-right political parties or far-right attitudes. For instance, Fremerey, Hörnig and Schaffner (2024) explored how the arrival of refugees between 2014 and 2017 shaped voting behaviour, focusing on the extent to which it influenced support for far-right parties in the 2017 German federal election. The authors state that although 'support for the far right is strongest in East Germany', this does not coincide with a high 'inflow of refugees' nor with a large proportion of people with migrant backgrounds (*ibid.*, p. 14). According to Küpper (2017, p. 99), 'the mere fear of possible competition with immigrants fuels xenophobia'. A lack of personal contact with immigrants contributes to the development of prejudice and fear of foreigners. Studies show that direct encounters and engagement with refugees help to reduce such biases, particularly in regions with little previous exposure to migration and diversity (Küpper, 2017, pp. 100–

101; see also Ahrens, 2017, pp. 33-39 and the Intergroup Contact Theory by Pettigrew and Tropp, 2006). In Eastern Germany, such encounters have traditionally been rarer because immigration levels have long been comparatively low, reducing everyday opportunities for exchange with foreigners (Küpfer, 2017, p. 101).

One group that emerged in this wake of the refugee movements is the IM. Over twelve years ago, the IM was established in Germany, and for more than five years, it has been classified as far-right extremist based on the fact that its ideology is against the German constitution³ (Bundesministerium des Innern für Bau und Heimat, 2021, pp. 76–81). This group is characterised by a modern appearance, with the intent of projecting a less overtly radical image (Schönfelder, 2020, p. 112). Although the IM employs strategies that had already been used by other extremist groups, they have innovatively adapted these tactics to contemporary contexts (see Section 2.3.4). The danger of these strategies and their associated activism lies in their ability to make right-wing extremist content appear less radical at first glance, making it seem more acceptable and relevant to everyday life. Even though a non-violent approach is promoted as a key characteristic, the IM's goals violate human rights, particularly the principle of equality, by propagating the idea that a certain migration background excludes an individual from being German, even if they hold a German passport (e.g. Bruns, Glösel and Strobl, 2014, p. 176; Aftenberger, 2017, p. 212; Richards, 2019, p. 32). However, because these are masked by seemingly harmless slogans and concepts (Goetz, 2022, p. 393; Abel, 2020, pp. 128, 143), the IM may not be perceived by young people as a potential threat to democracy but rather as a political movement like any other, which increases its appeal.

Just like previous far-right organisations in Germany, the IM use fears within contemporary society as a bridge to extremism (Zick, 2023). However, they publicly distance themselves from the National Socialist (NS) regime and traditional far-right movements, instead promoting far-right ideologies through strategies that resonate with the everyday life of both young people and mainstream society (e.g. Boehnke, 2019, p. 90; Schönfelder, 2020, pp. 111–112). Notably, their extensive use of social media plays a key role in recruiting members and disseminating far-right messages to

³ The constitution, also known as the basic law, is the legal foundation of German society. A crucial element is the assurance of civil rights, for instance, 'human dignity is inviolable', which became contractual in the constitution (Thurich, 2011, p. 25).

a broad audience, even internationally (Davey and Ebner, 2017, p. 29; see also Richards, 2019, p. 3). According to Fielitz (2023, p. 111) ‘the professional digital activism [is] an irreplaceable part of the Identitarian project’. Despite not being a political party, it functions as a front organisation for parties that align with its ideologies, aiming to influence and shift the political discourse (Boehnke, 2019, pp. 97–98). However, just a few months ago, the IM made headlines with its attempt to establish themselves as a political party to participate in Germany’s federal election in February (Deutscher Bundestag, 2025). Although this effort failed due to procedural errors, it underscores the IM’s determination to gain mainstream political influence (ibid.).

This shows that the far-right scene has changed, and new groups seem to contribute to an increased mobilisation potential. Unlike earlier far-right groups and parties, which were often isolated or short-lived, today’s far-right groups are more visible and have a broader network of supporters (Schütz, Kollmorgen and Schäller, 2021, p. 14). Groups such as the IM are therefore more integrated into society, which results in stronger influence compared to that of far-right movements in the past (ibid., see also Virchow, 2021).

But who are those who feel attracted to the IM and what are their motives for joining? At the beginning of the research study, the question arose: why do people join the IM? In order to answer this research question, the existing literature on the IM was first reviewed, with a particular focus on empirical studies concerning individual motives (Chapter 2). The first part of the thesis provides an overview of the topic and the current state of research on the IM. Based on the classification of the IM as right-wing extremist, this chapter looks at definitions of right-wing extremism and further related terms. Moreover, a categorisation of the IM within the phenomenon of right-wing extremism is carried out.

The literature review revealed a limited number of empirical studies that included face-to-face interactions with members of the IM, including ethnographic studies (e.g. Zúquete, 2018; Ebner, 2020; Blum, 2021; Pilkington, 2023). Despite contributing relevant insights into the organisational structure of the IM, there was still a lack of empirical findings concerning individual motives of people who join the IM, particularly with regard to the German branch (see Sections 2.4, 2.5). Through this examination

the research gap was identified, and the following research questions emerged as the questions this study wants to address:

- Which motives and influencing factors contribute to an individual's decision to participate in the IM?
- What creates the perception that the IM is attractive to join?
- What does an engagement look like and do the motives influence how someone engages in the IM?

In order to approach these questions further, the researcher looked at existing research on motives for joining right-wing extremist groups besides the IM to evaluate the extent to which these insights might be applicable to the IM (Section 2.7.2). Even though certain findings could be transferred to the process of individuals who join the IM, these studies differed in terms of their target groups. While most studies focus on violent individuals from predominantly lower socio-economic backgrounds, this study is based on interviews primarily with academics or individuals who had stable jobs and did not report experiencing broken home situations or an affinity for physical violence.

Moreover, the researcher looked at radicalisation research (see Section 2.7.1), since scholars have already examined processes of radicalisation (Borum, 2011a, 2011b; Busher, Malkki and Marsden, 2024). According to radicalisation research the decision to join an extremist group is a product of an interplay between multiple factors, considering the individual, organisational, and societal levels. No individual radicalises without a reason, instead certain experiences in their socialisation process can lead to grievances which can make someone receptive to radical views. Therefore, it is important to examine these factors and individual motives that led individuals to the decision to join an extremist group.

In order to investigate the individual motives for joining the IM, it was essential to engage in face-to-face interactions to gain a deeper understanding of the internal perspectives of these individuals. By analysing their narratives, the researcher gained valuable insights into how personal experiences are constructed to justify extremist beliefs and explain their decision to join the IM. As Ulmer (1988, pp. 19–20) demonstrates in his analysis of conversion narratives, that such stories are not merely

reflections of personal experiences but are shaped by the social and cultural contexts of the groups to which individuals belong.

This led to the decision to conduct semi-structured interviews. Since the state of research was limited, the researcher decided to apply a modified Constructivist Grounded Theory approach (Charmaz, 2006). The modification of the approach was reasoned in the access to the field, which was only possible through snowball sampling. Therefore, Chapter 3 includes an introduction to the methodological approach, including the epistemological and ontological consideration, which lay the ground for the chosen constructivist research approach. The methods for data collection (semi-structured interviews and participant observation) and data analysis are also outlined in this chapter.

Moreover, in order to answer the research question and approach the research data and analysis, a sensitising concept had been developed which explains how the researcher dealt with theoretical knowledge. The sensitising concept provided a methodology to approach the data without a fixed theory in mind and therefore allowing new ideas to emerge. Since the aim of the study was the exploration of individual motives, the researcher chose concepts that focus on the development / construction of subjective meaning and perception.

The study's sensitising concept is primarily derived from the Transformative Radicalization Theory (TR) proposed by Wilner and Dobouloz (2011). This theory postulates that significant events in the socialisation process of an individual can lead to a re-evaluation of existing beliefs. This represents a time in which an individual can become particularly receptive for radical / extremist ideas, resulting in the possibility to join extremist groups. With this perspective in mind the researcher looked for key events or critical milestones in the interviewees' narrations that might have contributed to such processes.

Moreover, the concept is supplemented by incorporating elements of Schütz's (1932) Social Action Theory, Havighurst's (1974) Developmental Theory and theories of media reception and reception cascades (Horton and Wohl, 1956; Krotz, 2007) which will be explained in more detail in Section 3.5. Building on the sensitising concept, the coding steps outlined by Charmaz (2006) were applied, providing the foundation from which the central themes and findings emerged. In the subsequent Chapters 4 and 5

the results of the data analysis and its discussion will be presented. These results provide empirical findings on the underlying factors and motives of engagement within the IM, including different modes of ideological appropriation and different forms of engagement. A conclusion is drawn, and an outlook provided in the final Chapter 6.

2 State of research on the Identitarian Movement

The purpose of this chapter is to evaluate the state of knowledge on far-right extremism in Germany. The following paragraphs provide an overview of pertinent empirical studies, academic literature, and ongoing discussions that inform this study. This chapter synthesises the existing research regarding the IM, including its historical development, categorisation within the far-right spectrum, and an examination of its structure, strategies, objectives, and ideology. Additionally, the chapter reviews the current empirical research focusing on the individual motivations for joining the IM.

2.1 German Identitarian Movement and its developmental history

The IM first emerged on digital platforms in October 2012 (Bundesministerium des Innern für Bau und Heimat, 2021, p. 76), with its origins traced to France, where the so-called 'Génération Identitaire' was established in September 2012 (Camus, 2017, p. 239; Pfahl-Traugher, 2019, p. 169). This group functioned as the youth wing of the Bloc Identitaire which was founded by former members of the right-wing extremist movement Unité Radicale (Uhlig and Uhlig, 2021, p. 69; Winkler, 2017, p. 47).

A significant event contributing to the growth of the German branch of the IM took place in October 2012 in Poitiers, France. Members of Génération Identitaire climbed onto the roof of a mosque and unfurled a banner reading '732 Generation Identitaire' accompanied by a lambda symbol (France24, 2012; Virchow, 2015, p. 177). The number 732 refers to the year 732 of the Battle of Tours and Poitiers, where Martell defeated a Muslim army of the Umayyad Caliphate (Šima, 2021, p. 79), symbolising a victory against Muslim people for members of the IM. The IM uses such political narratives as a vehicle for their mobilisation (Wagner, 2017, p. 206), which also reinforce the group's anti-Islam beliefs (see Sections 2.3.2, 2.3.3).

The lambda, the eleventh letter of the Greek alphabet, became the emblem of Génération Identitaire and was subsequently adopted by other branches of the movement. Originally, the symbol was used by the Spartans, who successfully held their ground against a vastly superior Persian force, a historical reference popularised

by the film '300' (Schönfelder, 2020, p. 117). However, this symbol has since been banned in certain countries where the IM has established offshoots, such as Austria (Auer and Strohmayer, 2020), and a similar ban has been imposed on the entire French IM (e.g. Jacquet-Vaillant, 2021, p. 1; Willsher, 2021). This has now led the German branch to adopt another symbol which looks like the letter A without a crossbar (Identitäre Bewegung Deutschland e.V., 2024) and resembles a stylised lambda symbol (Λ).

One month prior to the mosque incident, Génération Identitaire (2013) released a video on Facebook titled a 'declaration of war' (Virchow, 2015, p. 177). The video features close-ups of various young individuals discussing the perceived ethnic divide resulting from migration, which they argue must be halted (France24, 2012; Zúquete, 2018, pp. 27–28). This video attracted significant media attention, leading to the rapid establishment of various European offshoots of Génération Identitaire, including the German branch which translated and shared it on their own Facebook website (e.g. Virchow, 2015, p. 177; Blum, 2023, p. 25).

Krahn and Allgaier-Honal (2022, p. 89) outline the development of the IM through the lens of four stages of team development. The period between October 2012 and May 2014 corresponds to the phase of organisation and orientation, referred to as '*Forming & Storming*' (ibid., original emphasis). This phase concluded with the establishment of a registered association and the creation of various regional groups (ibid.). With the formal establishment of the association, the phase of consolidation and implementation commenced (ibid.). Nils Altmieks, who had previously been involved with the neo-Nazi youth group 'Heimattreue Deutsche Jugend (HDJ)', which got banned in 2009, was elected as chairperson of the association (ibid.). Following 2014, the IM worked on its organisational structure and planned and carried out different actions (see Section 2.3.4). For a more detailed overview on the IM's development, see Krahn and Allgaier-Honal (2022) and Goertz (2021a).

Since 2016 the IM had been monitored by the German domestic intelligence services until it had been officially declared to be a new far-right extremist movement in July 2019 (Goertz, 2021b, p. 67). The classification was based on evidence that the group's ideology is fundamentally opposed to the German constitution, particularly its

principles of human rights and the prohibition of discrimination (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2024, p. 101). The following section will further explore the ideology espoused by the IM. This will be accompanied by a discussion on the broader categorisation of the IM within the far-right spectrum. However, first it is important to discuss certain terms which will be employed in this study.

2.2 Right-wing radicalism, -extremism and the New Right

When reading articles on the IM, terms such as right-wing radicalism, right-wing extremist and New Right are often mentioned in connection with it. But what are we talking about when we use such terms? In the academic context, there is a proliferation of terms and definitions, leading to variations in how these terms are understood (e.g. Mudde, 1995, p. 203; Virchow, Langebach and Häusler, 2016, p. 1). Based on this, the following section looks more closely at the understanding of the term right-wing extremism in distinction to radicalism.

The aim is not to cover all aspects of these phenomena as this would exceed the scope of this study. Rather, it is to provide an overview of prevailing scholarship on the phenomenon of right-wing extremism in relation to the research subject. The subsequent sections shed light on the understanding of relevant terms that will be employed throughout the study, the underlying reasons for the IM's classification as right-wing extremist, its associations with the 'New Right', and its placement within the far-right landscape.

2.2.1 Between extremism and radicalism

'The extreme right in Europe is no longer a terra incognita of research' (Backes and Moreau, 2011, p. 9). It is a rapidly evolving field, resulting in the fact that scholarly work has become 'almost unmanageable' (ibid., see also Mudde, 2024, p. 148). However, even with a growing volume of annual publications (Virchow, Langebach and Häusler, 2016, p. 1), the research field is far from being comprehensive (Backes and Moreau, 2011, p. 9). New facets of the highly heterogeneous field of right-wing extremism emerge and / or other dimensions lack empirical evidence (e.g. Hart, 2023;

Scrivens, 2024). Knoop (cited by Holbrook and Taylor, 2013, p. 1) said that right-wing extremism 'is a moving target. It is ever changing and evolving whilst being studied' (see also Van der Valk, 2013, p. 130).

Despite the amount of literature, researchers agree on the fact that there is no universal definition of right-wing extremism. Moreover, a plethora of different terms and understandings exists (Salzborn, 2020b, p. 13), and it is not uncommon for terms to be used synonymously (Mudde, 2000, p. 13, 2019, p. 5). One reason why the term 'right-wing extremism' is highly contested is the absence of a universally accepted legal definition of 'extremism' within statutory law; instead, a governmental definition is typically applied. According to the Federal Ministry of Interior and Community (2023) extremist actions are

'those which oppose our democratic constitutional state and its fundamental values, norms and rules [described in the basic law], and aim to overthrow the liberal democratic order and replace it with one in line with the ideas of the respective group'.

Further characteristics are the non-acceptance of basic and human rights and the acceptance of, or willingness to use violence (ibid.). This definition is narrowly defined, which is necessary, as based on these criteria, certain laws can be applied, such as, for instance, the prohibition of a political party. An example in this context are the proceedings regarding an attempted ban of the National Democratic Party of Germany (NPD)⁴ (e.g. Backes, 2019; Hogan, 2022).

⁴ Constitutional organs such as the Federal Council of Germany tried twice, in 2003 and 2013, to have the party banned by the Federal Constitutional Court. However, both attempts were unsuccessful: first, because of procedural reasons and second, because of the party's low level of danger to Germany's democracy given its minuscule polling results. The decision by the Federal Constitutional Court confirmed that the NPD is unconstitutional due to its disregard for human rights. However, a sufficient legal basis for banning the party is not given. In sum, the NPD has been deemed to be unconstitutional but there is a lack of importance as well as potential to implement their aims in order to harm society that would justify the ban of the party. This decision invoked different opinions. On the one hand, it is an odd argumentation, because, conversely, this means if the NPD increased their votes and the party became more important and influential within society, a ban of the party would be highly probable. On the other hand, the court supports the freedom of opinion. This also shows that the balance between unconstitutional behaviour and freedom of speech is an interesting aspect to discuss. It shows that the ban of political parties comes with high thresholds as political parties are an essential element of a representative democracy (e.g. Backes, 2019; Hogan, 2022).

Looking at the scholarly debate, the government's definition fits the normative concept of extremism which defines extremism as 'the rejection of the democratic constitutional state and its fundamental values and rules' (Backes and Jesse, 1993, p. 40; see also Mannewitz, 2018). According to this definition, extremism is considered to be dependent on the applicable legal system (Salzborn, 2018b, p. 16). One variant of the extremism theory is the so-called Horseshoe Theory, in which the horseshoe is employed as a visual representation to illustrate the division between the democratic centre and the boundaries of left- and right-wing extremism (Backes, 1989, pp. 251–252). The theory postulates that although far-left and far-right groups represent different ideologies, they exhibit a convergence in their anti-democratic tendencies, placing them closer to each other than to the democratic middle (ibid.).

However, the extremism theory and its developments have been criticised over the years, highlighting three aspects – 'Dichotomization', 'Abstraction' and 'Ideological Fixation' (Mannewitz, 2018, pp. 31–32). The understanding of a clearly distinguishable democratic centre and extremist borders is not tenable as current results in attitude research show (Zick and Mokros 2023; Virchow 2016, p.15). Furthermore, the equation of far-right extremism and left-wing extremism is criticised as it would not consider the differences, especially regarding the underlying motives and conditions of origin (Virchow, 2016, p. 15). These critiques suggest that the normative concept of extremism, as it is traditionally understood, may not adequately capture the complexity of political ideologies and movements, and it may be prone to misuse, particularly in political discourse (Mannewitz, 2018, pp. 31–32). Moreover, researchers criticise that the concept is not able to respond to the fluid and rapidly shifting nature of political discourse (Gessenharter, 1998, p. 26).

Despite the critiques, this understanding of extremism offers a distinction from radicalism, particularly in reference to the democratic constitution. Right-wing extremism is unconstitutional, while right-wing radicalism encompasses a form of political conduct that can still be constitutional (Virchow, 2016, p. 14). So, in contrast to extremism, people who are radical or join radical groups aim to 'get at the root [...] of social problems and conflicts without harming the democratic order or rule of law' (Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community, 2023). This is in line with Mudde (2019, p. 5) who distinguishes between the 'extreme right' and the 'radical right'. While

the extreme right dismisses the core principles of democracy, the radical right claims to support it, 'at least in theory' (ibid., p. 30). In practice, however, the radical right 'fundamentally challenges key institutions and values of liberal democracy, including minority rights, rule of law, and separation of powers' (Mudde 2019, p. 30; see also Gessenharter 2010, p. 2). This shows that 'being radical [...] can mean entirely different things in different places, contexts, and periods of history' (Neumann, 2015, p. 2). Neumann (2015, p. 2) further illustrates this with the example of freedom of speech: embraced in Western democracies, yet perceived as a 'dangerous form of radicalism' in other parts of the world.

Coleman and Bartoli (2014, p. 2) outline key aspects to consider when defining extremism: They state, for example, that an activity can be seen as an 'extremist act' and at the same time not be considered one because it relies on the 'observer's values, politics, moral scope, and the nature of their relationship with the actor' (ibid.). Pilkington (2022, p. 330) emphasises that extremism 'is a relational concept in emic as well as etic understandings'. The perception of extremist acts depends on their historical and social context, which can change over time (Coleman and Bartoli, 2014, p. 2). One example is Nelson Mandela who utilised guerrilla strategies to achieve political change, which is seen by some as a positive extremist act, while others might view his actions negatively (Coleman and Bartoli, 2014, p. 2). Power dynamics also influence these judgments — actions by less powerful groups are often seen as more extreme than similar actions by those supporting the status quo (ibid.). Hassan et al. (2023, p. 578) claim that the definition of extremism 'is neutral in nature' but that it can have 'both positive and negative instantiations'. The authors refer to Martin Luther King Jr. (1963, p. 4) who claimed, 'The question is not whether we will be extremists, but what kind of extremists we will be'. Against this background, deciding what counts as 'extremist' or 'ordinary' is always relative to the given system and ultimately a 'political matter' (Coleman and Bartoli, 2014, p. 2).

The same applies to 'radical acts'; their definition depends on different aspects such as culture, history and current politics. Based on this, radical acts can be seen as positive and as negative at the same time depending on who is asked. Consequently, 'being radical' involves holding positions that are markedly extreme compared to what is typically regarded as normative, traditional, or part of the accepted status quo (Mandel, 2009, p. 105; Bartlett and Miller, 2012, p. 2; Kruglanski *et al.*, 2014, p. 70;

Pickel and Pickel, 2023, p. 4). Bötticher (2017, p. 76) argues that the term 'radicalisation' has become narrowly associated with terrorism, which is problematic. This narrowing of meaning risks delegitimising all forms of radical protest — even justified opposition to oppressive regimes — and may, in turn, push democratic radicals towards genuinely extremist movements (ibid.). It is important to keep in mind that 'all forms of extremism are radical [...] but not all forms of radicalism are extremist' (Hassan *et al.*, 2023, p. 577).

This distinction is also the subject of criticism as researchers argue that a clear-cut distinction between the radical and extreme right does not exist due to 'growing links between the illiberal-democratic and anti-democratic far right' (Pirro, 2023, p. 103; Salzborn, 2020b, p. 16). However, these blurred lines between extremism and radicalism are used as a strategy by far-right extremist groups, including the IM (see Section 2.3.4).

2.2.2 Defining right-wing extremism

Even though an agreed definition of right-wing extremism in the academic debate does not exist, researchers (e.g. Bjørgo 1997) have tried to gain a better understanding of this phenomenon by identifying the most common characteristics. Mudde (2019, p. 24) writes that even though the field of the far right is 'highly diverse [...] there are many ideological features and political issues that are shared across groups and parties'. One example is the consensus definition which has been developed by different researchers with the aim to make empirical results that measure right-wing attitudes comparable. The group of researchers agreed on six elements: advocacy of a right-wing authoritarian dictatorship, chauvinism, xenophobia, antisemitism, social Darwinism, trivialization of National Socialism (Kreis, 2007). According to the researchers, right-wing extremism is

'an attitude pattern whose unifying characteristic is the notion of inequality.

These manifest in the political sphere as an affinity for dictatorial forms of government, chauvinistic attitudes, and a trivialisation or justification of National Socialism. In the social realm, they are characterised by anti-Semitic, xenophobic, and social Darwinist attitudes.' (Kreis, 2007, p. 12).

Similar results are reached by Mudde (1995, p. 206) who combined 26 definitions of right-wing extremism and extracts five characteristics which show the highest rate of overlaps: 'nationalism, racism, xenophobia, anti-democracy, and the strong state' (see also Bjørgo, 1997, p. 21). Carter (2018, p. 175) confirms that these characteristics continue to hold their validity and justification and adds 'populism' to the list.

To illustrate the meaning behind such concepts, a definition by Jaschke (1994, p. 31) serves as an example: He defines right-wing extremism as 'attitudes, behaviours and action' which are based on 'a racist or ethnic understanding of inequality of humans'. The aim of right-wing extremists would be achieving an ethnic homogeneity of nations which go against the principle of equality of the Human Rights Declaration. The subordination of the individual to the community as well as the rejection of a liberal democracy are further core elements (ibid.). This is in line with the German domestic intelligence service (Bundesamt für Verfassungsschutz, 2025) which states that right-wing extremists claim 'a person's value is determined by the ethnic group or nation they belong to'. Along the notion that people are not of equal value (Van der Valk, 2013, p. 131), right-wing extremists construct an understanding of society as comprised of 'us' versus 'them', whereby 'they' have a lower value.

However, it needs to be stressed that elements which characterise right-wing extremism (nationalist, antisemitic, racist and xenophobic ideology) can vary, so not all elements must always be present when speaking of right-wing extremism (Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community, 2023). For instance, the trivialisation or justification of National Socialism is an element which is not a key characteristic of newer far-right extremist groups, including the group under study, but something these people distance themselves from. The same applies to the use of violence as its prevalence varies between different groups, as well as within each group itself. Therefore, not all far-right extremists promote violence or include members who engage in violence (e.g. Scrivens *et al.*, 2023). The group under study is an example of propagating a non-violent approach (see Section 2.3.4).

Simultaneously, distinct characteristics may manifest in varied ways, meaning that the presence of certain criteria alone does not necessarily label an individual as an extremist (Dienstbühl, 2019, p. 72). For instance, not every person who holds xenophobic views is automatically a far-right extremist. There are different types of

racist/xenophobic beliefs and behaviour which can be found within the mainstream society as well as far-right extremist groups (Bjørge, 1997, p. 23).

For this study, the researcher uses two definitions: the governmental definition of right-wing extremism, which views right-wing extremism as efforts directed against the democratic constitutional state and its fundamental values, such as human equality and Heitmeyer's (1995) sociological definition. The first definition is important as it serves as the reference point for the IM's narratives and argumentation. This means that the IM argues its categorisation as right-wing extremist is unjustified. Consequently, this definition plays a crucial role in the interviews, as members of the IM position themselves in relation to the constitutional definition.

Heitmeyer's (1995) definition of right-wing extremism is applied to analyse the underlying motives and to further answer the research questions. Heitmeyer (1995, p. 15) criticises narrow legal or constitutional definitions, as they fail to address key questions regarding the causes and evolution of right-wing extremist orientations from a sociological perspective. Instead, he incorporates economic and social factors to provide a broader and more comprehensive understanding (ibid.). According to him, right-wing extremism consists of two core elements: 'the ideology of inequality of humans' and 'the perspective and acceptance of violence' (ibid., p. 16): 'the ideology of inequality of humans' encompasses the following elements:

- 'Nationalistic or ethnocentric self-aggrandisement'
- 'Racist perspective / xenophobia'
- 'Distinction between worthy and unworthy life (e.g., through eugenics)'
- 'Assertion of natural hierarchies (via sociobiology)'
- 'Emphasis on the right of the stronger (Social Darwinism)'
- 'Totalitarian understanding of norms, i.e., exclusion of "otherness"'

'The perspective and acceptance of violence' includes the following characteristics:

- 'Rejection of rational discourse / glorification of irrationalism'
- 'Emphasis on the daily struggle for existence'
- 'Rejection of democratic forms of regulation for social and political conflicts'
- 'Emphasis on authoritarian and militaristic forms and styles of interaction'
- 'Violence as a normal form of action for regulating conflicts'

Not every aspect needs to be fulfilled, but the combination of these two core elements is essential to define right-wing extremism (ibid.). It is important to note that, according to this definition, physical violence is not required to meet the criteria for right-wing extremism. In relation to the IM which propagates a non-violent approach this definition fits as the IM uses violent elements in their narratives (see Section 2.3.4). Even though the physical violence is not something which is a characteristic of this group, violent elements can be identified in their rejection of the political discourse and their suggestions to change it, for instance by forced repatriation (see Section 4.4.2).

In sum, right-wing extremism can have different forms of expression, but all forms have in common that their ideology conflicts fundamentally with the Basic Law. Therefore, an ideology of inequality is at its core (Heitmeyer, 1995, p. 16; Zick and Mokros, 2023, p. 61). Based on this, it is difficult to speak of 'the' right-wing extremism – it is rather a phenomenon, encompassing political parties, movements as well as attitudes, beliefs and ideologies that are expressed in various ways in the offline as well as online world (Zick and Mokros 2023, p. 53). One of the actors of this broad field of the far right is the IM which is frequently classified as an actor of the New Right (Bruns, Glösel and Strobl, 2014, p. 56; Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2023, p. 73). Another term which requires further explanation.

2.3 Identitarian Movement and the New Right

The term 'New Right' has been used to describe various manifestations in the right-wing spectrum (Virchow, 2016, p. 18) but researchers have not used the term uniformly (Pfeiffer, 2004, p. 51; Pfahl-Traughber, 2022, p. 25). Therefore, the scholarly landscape encompasses conflicting views as well as elements researchers agree on when explaining the New Right (Gessenharter, 2010, p. 4). This also applies to the classification of the IM which is not universally accepted (Pfahl-Traughber, 2022, p. 20). Various researchers have already published comprehensively about the New Right, its history of origin as well as comparisons with today's far-right extremism, especially in the fields of political science and history⁵. Accordingly, this section does

⁵ For a more detailed overview and discussion, reference is made to the work of Weiß (2018), Pfahl-Traughber (2022) and his analytical criteria of the New Right - ideology, organisation, strategy (pp. 18-19) - as well as Wagner (2017).

not seek to address all aspects of the New Right, as that would surpass the scope of this study. Rather, it elucidates its relevance to the subject under investigation.

2.3.1 What is the New Right and who belongs to it?

The Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2024, p. 99) defines the New Right as ‘an informal network of groups, individuals, and organisations where national-conservative to right-wing extremist forces collaborate to promote, through various strategies, partially anti-liberal and anti-democratic positions in society and politics’. The statement shows that the term ‘New Right’ is an umbrella term and includes a broad range of groups, from national conservatives, who operate within democratic systems but oppose liberal values, to right-wing extremists, who reject democracy and propagate extremist ideologies. Even though these groups share similar goals such as stopping the so-called ‘Great Replacement’ (see Section 2.3.3), it is crucial to distinguish between them to avoid oversimplification and understand their different strategies and impacts on political discourse. According to Salzborn (2018b, p. 81), the development of the New Right happened in two steps: first, the development of new institutions and organisations; and second the development and implementation of new forms of social movements such as the IM. Pfahl-Traughber (2022, p. 19), on the other hand, points out that actors of the New Right are loose groups of intellectuals who agree on certain ideological aspects but can also differ in terms of ideology. These people often publish articles, books or give speeches in conferences (ibid.). Vorländer, Herold and Schäller (2018, p. 61) speak of a ‘network with many decentralised hubs, which attempt to create links to many further milieus’.

While the Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community and different scholars (e.g. Nissen, 2020, p. 85) classify the IM as an actor of the New Right, Pfahl-Traughber (2022, p. 20) believes that the IM does not align with the New Right. According to him, its members adhere to a comparable ideological framework, but see themselves as a youth movement, as opposed to a group of intellectuals (ibid.). Consequently, the difference can be attributed to the strategic approach, leading to the conclusion that IM should be classified as an ‘independent phenomenon’ (ibid., p. 116). Nevertheless,

this does not preclude the IM from being a 'significant actor in the context of the New Right' (ibid., p. 115).

Therefore, even though scholars take different positions when it comes to categorising the group, most of them see ideological parallels between the IM and the New Right. This aligns with Goertz (2021b, p. 58) who states that the IM is on an ideological level closely aligned with the New Right. These ideological parallels are evident in the IM's adoption of key New Right concepts, such as ethnopluralism, anti-globalism, and the rejection of liberal democratic values. The IM also follows the New Right's focus on metapolitics⁶ but uses modern communication tools to reach especially younger individuals. To draw on Salzborn's (2018a, p. 164, see also 2020a, p. 28) description of the Identitarian Movement as the 'activist arm of the New Right', it can be said that the IM tries to turn the New Right's theoretical ideas into practical activism. These aspects will be explored in more detail in the following sections.

However, to understand the ideological alignment, it is first important to understand how the New Right was established in the first place, starting with the adjective 'New'. This creates the impression that we are dealing with a new phenomenon within right-wing extremism (e.g. Salzborn, 2020a, p. 23). However, the ideological framework of the New Right goes back to ideas and works of authors belonging to the Conservative Revolution of the Weimar Republic (e.g. Weiß, 2018, pp. 37, 44–54). The Conservative Revolution was a group of intellectual thinkers who rejected the liberal democracy and the consequences of modernity such as parliamentarism, human rights as well as pluralism (Pfahl-Traughber, 2022, p. 39). Known representatives were for instance Moeller van den Bruck, Oswald Spengler and Carl Schmitt (e.g. Jaschke, 2016, p. 119; Weiß, 2018). But what led to the emergence of the New Right in the first place?

The political party NPD faced failure, young right-wing oriented individuals began to distance themselves from the NS era (Gessenharter, 2010, p. 4; Salzborn, 2020a, p. 22), prompting them to seek a new political identity and image (Virchow, 2016, p. 18). Thus, the emerge of the New Right is based on processes of restructuring (Weiß, 2018, p. 30). A melting pot for actors of the far-right who wanted to distance

⁶ Strategy that focuses on influencing the pre-political sphere (see Section 2.3.4).

themselves from the NS Regime emerged (Gessenharter, 2010, p. 4; Weiß, 2018, p. 30). However, the distancing from the NS Regime was mostly of strategic nature (Weiß, 2018, pp. 27–28). Nevertheless, despite the far-reaching historical references and the ideological similarities with the old right, the question is whether there is something new in the New Right.

One innovation was based on ideas by Alan de Benoist, who was an important figure of the Nouvelle Droite and criticised the old right for being fixated on historical systems (Pfahl-Traughber, 2022, p. 22). He suggested to put the cultural area more into focus (ibid.). The New Right's ideology was significantly influenced by Alan de Benoist's ideas of ethnopluralism (e.g. Aftenberger, 2007, pp. 112–113; Hermansson *et al.*, 2020, p. 14) the IM (Aftenberger, 2017, p. 210; Speit, 2018, p. 69). Besides Benoist, Hennig Eichberg also popularised the term (Schäller, 2019, p. 200). The concept of ethnopluralism is closely connected with the concept of the Great Replacement theory, which serves as an ideological concept for the IM as well. These concepts will be explained in the next sections.

2.3.2 Key ideological concept of the IM: Ethnopluralism

Ethnopluralism is, according to Camus (2022, p. 69), 'the core of the New Right's vision of the world' – a perspective that also aligns with Mudde (2019, p. 27). However, Salzborn (2020b, p. 78) points out that besides the concept of ethnopluralism there is nothing new in the New Right ideology, a perspective that Minkenberg (2018, p. 374) also holds. The connecting element of inequality of humans can be found as well, however, in comparison to the old right, actors of the New Right do not want to achieve anti-pluralism by annihilation but instead by the idea of segmentation (Salzborn, 2018b, p. 78). Supporters of ethnopluralism distance themselves from the idea of genetic homogeneity, which is a main feature of the classic far-right ideology (Havertz, 2023, p. 2). This idea has been partly replaced by 'a cultural definition of race' by far-right extremist groups which aim at appealing to a larger audience as such a perspective is considered to be 'more compatible with mainstream beliefs' (Blee and Yates, 2015, p. 131). Ethnopluralists argue that people possess different incomprehensible cultural identities and mixing different cultures will lead to 'the elimination of such differences' and 'the destruction of their culture' (Havertz, 2023, p.

2). In other words, they do not claim the superiority of their own nation explicitly, but every nation should stay on its own so that ethnic diversity can be prevented (von Beyme, 2019, p. 62). Mudde (2019, p. 27) summarises it saying, 'people are divided into ethnic groups, which are equal but should remain segregated'.

Under Ethnopluralism, ethnic background determines whether a person belongs to the receptive nation or not, a concept that scholars also characterise as 'cultural racism' or 'racism without racism' (Bendl and Spitzmüller, 2017, p. 7,9). Bartett, Birdwell and Littler (2011, p. 26) point out that there is a shift 'from traditional far-right concerns about race to more nuanced positions relating to values and culture'. This shift helps to give the far-right scene a different image and distance itself from the 'fascist-inspired ideology' (Campani and Lazaridis, 2017, p. 5). As activist Mario Müller (2017, p. 79) explains, '[b]y granting each culture its ancestral place, ethnopluralism renders chauvinistic racism and the antisemitic fetish unnecessary, thus drawing a decisive dividing line from the Old Right'.

Publications by the IM itself explicitly state that ethnopluralism is the 'central star of Identitarian thought' (Müller, 2017, p. 78; see also Sellner, 2017b, p. 9). According to the Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community (2024, pp. 100–101), by employing this concept the IM advocates for an 'ethnically and culturally homogeneous state', based on the idea that 'every race is a different species, and that humanity consists of a mosaic of races' (Davis, 2025, p. 431). This conviction leads to the view that 'all races are of equal value, but every race has its place' and '[a]ny race that is not in its proper place is out of place' (ibid.). According to ethnopluralism, the ethnographic background serves to determine who is considered to be a member of the German people. This undermines the value of ethnic minorities and conflicts with human rights principles, particularly human dignity and the prohibition of discrimination (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2024, p. 101). As previously mentioned, the IM's narratives are rooted in anti-Islamic beliefs, and consequently, individuals with an Islamic ethnic background are viewed as incompatible with German culture (e.g. Dahl, 2023, p. 13).

2.3.3 Key ideological concept of the IM: Great Replacement

As mentioned, closely connected to the concept of ethnopluralism is Renaud Camus' (2018) conspiracy theory of the Great Replacement (Pfahl-Traughber, 2022, p. 93). Supporters of this theory believe that 'there is a secret plot to dilute and destroy the ethnic character of the European population by replacing it through immigration of non-white people' (Bjørgo and Braddock, 2022, p. 5; see also Davey and Ebner, 2019, p. 7; Havertz, 2023, p. 8). According to activist Martin Sellner (2017b, p. 184), head of the Austrian IM, a degree of ethnocultural homogeneity is necessary to have a functioning democracy and welfare state. He further explains:

'[w]ith the concept of the Great Replacement, we unite the many symptoms such as Islamisation, rising crime, foreign infiltration, and social abuse, and direct the resistance against the true enemy: the »replacers«. It is not the individual immigrant, but the process of mass immigration and the political actors who push it forward and hinder an open debate about it, who are our true opponents' (Sellner, 2017b, p. 185).

By adopting Camus' concept, members of the IM strategically employed a modernised rhetorical framework, enabling them effectively to insert their agenda into public discourse (Goetz, 2019b, p. 109).

Van Prooijen and van Lange (2014, pp. 249–250) state that conspiracy theories serve as a social mechanism for making sense of perceived intergroup threats. They allow individuals to rationalise feelings of marginalisation by attributing power and malicious intent to an out-group, thus reinforcing in-group cohesion and solidarity (ibid.). The IM thus adopts these ideological concepts of the New Right and attempts to spread them to broad sections of the population using different strategies. The following sections will explore the strategies that are characteristic of the IM.

2.3.4 Strategies of the IM

In accordance with the preceding section, one strategy of the IM is to sell an image of a group that distances itself from the NS time and rather represents a modern and

professional movement founded upon well-developed theories. On their website, the IM (2024) presents itself as a 'pan-European patriotic youth movement', which stands up for values such as 'nation, freedom and tradition' in the form of 'peaceful activism, political educational work as well as community and cultural activities'. In their explanation they put an emphasis on the influence of the pre-political space and stress the fact that they are non-partisan (ibid.). According to them, Europe suffers from various problems due to migration and their aim is to protect the European cultural heritage and ensure that European citizens don't become a minority in their respective countries (ibid.). The IM sees its duty in 'fighting for a peaceful and secure future' (ibid.). The next section will shed light on how the IM operates by explaining its different strategies.

2.3.4.1 Distancing themselves from right-wing extremism

The previous sections showed that the Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community and different scholars position the IM as one actor in the field of the New Right. However, looking at the IM's homepage, the group responded to this classification, stating that the term New Right is 'imprecise and associated with various abstractions and generalisations' (Identitäre Bewegung Deutschland e.V., 2024). According to them '[a]nyone who is willing to recognise and preserve the peoples of Europe as an independent subject of a historically grown ethnocultural identity can participate politically on our side' (ibid.). This statement reveals two strategies. First, by framing the ideology in this way, the IM avoids an overtly right-wing extremist presentation, making it less immediately recognisable as such. Second, the IM provides a simplified way of entry, which involves only the willingness to preserve the historically grown ethnocultural identity.

The term 'right-wing' is seen by the IM as a 'necessary provocation' as well as 'self-positioning in the fight against the left-liberal mainstream' (Identitäre Bewegung Deutschland e.V., 2024). However, Zúquete (2018, p. 4) says that 'other self-descriptions are favored: from "patriots" to the "true Right", adherents to the "beyond Left and Right" line of thinking, or, simply, Identitarians'. Moreover, the IM (2024) claims that "'right-wing" thinking is more than just the stereotypical clichés of shaved heads and combat boots. Behind it lies a buried intellectual tradition that should be rediscovered and must also be part of societal pluralism' (ibid.).

Murdoch and Mulhall (2019, p. 13) developed 'a glossary of identitarian coded language' to demonstrate that the IM's ideology is inherently racist, contrary to the moderate image they attempt to project. Radical ideas are often hidden in propaganda that is not easily recognisable at first sight. The propagated topics of the IM can 'be understood as ciphers, with which older nationalist concepts and right-wing ideological backgrounds are semantically recoded' (Vorländer et al. 2018, p. 62-63). By using such codes, it becomes more difficult to detect far-right views, and it prevents the legal deletion of such content.

Research also shows that far-right activists possess a keen awareness of what they can openly express and what they should refrain from articulating directly. Instead, they often employ veiled questions and statements that could potentially lead to criminal prosecution but are nevertheless understood and condoned within their like-minded social circles. Bruns, Glösel and Strobl (2014, p. 193) refer to the strategy of a 'semantic confusion game', which includes the reinterpretation of terms. Actors of the New Right trivialise themselves and what they do and try to appropriate democratic terms such as freedom of speech for their purposes (Küpper et al. 2023, p. 95). Pfahl-Traugher (2022, p. 21) describes the strategy of the New Right saying that the 'rejective attitude against a liberal democracy is adopted in a new guise to topics of the present'. This is in line with Šima (2021, p. 83), who speaks of a 'promising strategy [...] with strong anti-hate-speech legislation'.

The IM aims to be more relatable and accessible to mainstream society by addressing political and societal concerns and fears, using them as a bridge to spread their extremist propaganda (Zick, 2023; see also Aftenberger, 2007, p. 195).

Therefore, attempts to distance themselves from a far-right extremist image is of strategic nature to appear more connectable with mainstream society. The IM uses terms for their propaganda which can be found in conservatism or patriotism and are not per se extremist, for instance, the love of the homeland. To be proud of the receptive homeland does not make someone an extremist but if this love for the homeland means the exclusion of certain people from belonging to the German nation, even if they belong to it according to the law, then such terms alter in meaning. Zick and Mokros (2023, p. 55) put an emphasis on the development of a convergence between right-wing extremist actors and the mainstream over the last few years. These developments require a closer look as new right-wing extremist groups have found ways to connect with the societal mainstream.

The IM's strategy focuses on influencing the pre-political sphere, often referred to as metapolitics (e.g. Hermansson *et al.*, 2020, p. 29), with the goal of establishing cultural hegemony and gradually embedding their ideas into mainstream society. The concept of cultural hegemony goes back to the Italian Marxist Antonio Gramsci (Salzborn, 2018b, p. 76). These references to the political left-wing can be repeatedly detected in the strategies of the New Right (Salzborn, 2018b, p. 76; Weiß, 2018, pp. 33–34). This is not different in the IM which draws on strategies traditionally employed by the left and uses them as a blueprint for their actions (Bruns, Glösel and Strobl, 2014, p. 57). Martin Sellner (2017b, p. 97) even dedicated an entire chapter to this approach in his book entitled 'Learning from the Left'. Gramsci developed the idea of influencing the political mainstream by spreading terminologies with clear aims which are not immediately recognised as such (Salzborn, 2018b, p. 76). The goal is to subtly influence the discourse and implement terms in the public sphere (Küpper, Sandal-Önal and Zick, 2023). Sellner (2017b, p. 98) formulates this explaining that over the last years the boundaries of what can be said have shifted to the left, and this trend must be reversed, moving the boundaries further to the right. He speaks of the Reconquista which stands for the 'reclamation of one's own space of thought and language' (Sellner, 2017b, p. 99).

As Rogner (2022, p. 150) observes, the IM and its actors attempt to frame their radical ideology in a seemingly intellectual and philosophical tone to broaden its appeal beyond their core audience. In addition, the IM propagates a non-violent approach and emphasises that they carry out peaceful political activism (Identitäre Bewegung Deutschland e.V., 2024), to underscore its non-extremist image. However, according to Richards (2019, p. 32) who examined the Generation Identity (GI), the group's propagated actions contradict this approach as its members advocate the forced return of migrants, particularly migrants with a Muslim background. This is in line with research on the relationship between conspiracy theories and violence (e.g. Bartlett and Miller, 2010). Rottweiler and Gill (2022, p. 1486) examined this relationship and found that a strong conspiracy mindset increases 'violent extremist intentions', especially in individuals with low self-control, weak legal morality and high self-efficacy. In contrast, high self-control and strong legal morality mitigate this effect (*ibid.*, see also Davey and Ebner, 2019). Bartlett and Miller (2010, pp. 4–5) state that

conspiracy theories can act as a 'radicalizing multiplier' that reinforce group cohesion and can drive individuals towards a more extreme or even violent behaviour.

Despite the IM's distancing from far-right extremism and the use of violence, references to right-wing extremist groups, including violent histories are frequently encountered or discovered. These appear either through past affiliations of members of the IM with such groups (e.g. Boehnke, 2019, p. 91; Neumann, 2023, p. 56) or through connections in the context of their activities (Goetz and Winkler, 2023, pp. 224–225). As previously mentioned, the chairperson of the IM had been previously involved in a neo-Nazi group. Martin Sellner had also been involved in right-wing extremist groups before, but brushes this time of his life off as a mistake of his youth / juvenile misconduct and said that he was a Neo-Nazi until 2011 and then distanced himself from the scene (e.g. Balke, 2019).

Moreover, the IM projects an image of members who can defend themselves and protect their nation focusing on the idea of physical strength for protection, as shown in many videos from their so-called summer camps (Aktionsmelder, 2023) and national camps (Aktionsmelder, 2022). Goetz (2019a, p. 17) argues that much of the social media content is directed at a male audience, emphasising the need for 'defensive patriots' who not only safeguard the nation but are also able to fight against their chosen enemies. In an article Martin Sellner (2017a) describes 'nonviolent discipline' as a strategic decision and outlines various advantages such as the ability to attract broader support and the fact that the form of activism is cost-effective and offers lower barriers to participation, both physically and logistically. Sellner (2017a) explains that this approach does not mean 'defencelessness'. According to him, anyone who attempt to disrupt their events or attack IM's activists must face clear consequences - 'Every Identitarian and patriot, therefore, has the duty to be able to defend themselves' (ibid.).

Goetz and Winkler (2023, p. 226) argue that the IM is connected to right-wing terrorism through shared ideological elements and personal ties. In addition, the authors claim that the IM's actions can be described as a discursive groundwork for attacks, functioning as 'message crimes', which demonstrate a close connection to right-wing terrorism (ibid.). An example is the Christchurch attack by Tarrant, whose manifesto is

based on the ideology of the Great Replacement, and whose sympathy for the IM is evidenced by his donation to the group (Hartleb, 2023, pp. 168–169).

2.3.4.2 Professional and youthful

Researchers also point to the professional presentation of the IM to the outside world, which is intended to differentiate it from extremism and in particular from National Socialism, as well as to increase its attractiveness for young people. According to Bruns et al. (2014, p. 56) the IM has certain characteristics which distinguish it from other groups and enable a low-threshold entry: 'youthfulness, actionism, pop culture and cooperate identity'. Boehnke (2019, pp. 89–90) emphasises the professional design of their external communication which is characterised by a high degree of adaptability. In this context, a highly professional use of the internet can be noticed and plays a crucial role in disseminating their extremist messages.

Members of the IM strategically utilise social media to amplify modest actions, often undertaken by a small number of individuals, and present them as large-scale, sensationalised events to create the illusion of widespread support (Goetz, 2017, p. 96). The IM's media strategy is to make something small appear big. Šima (2021, p. 79) speaks of 'media-attractive forms of protest that are not based on the number of protesters but on performative creativity'. Therefore, the IM uses social media to gain publicity without needing a large group of activists who carry out offline actions. Sellner (2017b, p. 53), describes in his book that this strategy follows the motto 'p.o.d.h. – Pics or didn't happen'.

Publicity is therefore essential for the IM. When high profile actions such as displaying a banner reading 'Secure Borders, Secure Future' on the Brandenburg Gate are covered by the media, the group regards it as a triumph, as it advances their objective of gaining visibility in the news. The 'Defend Europe' action which aimed at stopping refugees on their journey to Europe even made headlines in various European and non-European countries, ultimately playing into the hands of the activists. The IM hired a boat and attempted to hinder tugboats by presenting a big slogan 'No way. You will not make Europe home' (Geibel, Fozdar and McGaughey, 2024, p. 1290). The interesting aspect is that even though this action faced many difficulties and did not go

as planned, the activists received the publicity they were striving for (Faiola and Mekhennet, 2024). Therefore, for journalism the line between informing the public about current news and being used as a platform that contributes to spreading the propaganda of far-right movements is a fine one (Goetz, 2017, p. 98; Vorländer, Herold and Schäller, 2018, p. 196). According to Šima (2021, p. 79), '[t]he actionist element lies in the way their anger is expressed' as the IM carries out 'audacious, visually attractive protest' which shows parallels to the strategies of NGOs like Greenpeace.

Moreover, to further enhance its visibility, the IM utilises various social media channels, managed by a few activists, including Sellner, who provide daily or weekly content and reach a broad audience. Sellner's channels demonstrate a high reach (Urman and Katz, 2022, p. 910); for instance, his Telegram channel 'Martin Sellner [TELEGRAMELITE]' (Sellner, 2025) has 74,093 subscribers, whereas the Telegram channel of IM Germany (2025) has merely 9,651 subscribers (last accessed on 04.03.2025). Sellner is often described as the 'spokesperson' for the Identitarian Movements and 'key communicator of identitarian ideas' (Murdoch and Mulhall, 2019, p. 21). Faiola and Mekhennet (2024) stated in an article by the Washington Post: 'With studious glasses, philosophical references and the vibe of an intellectual, Sellner has become a major force in normalizing words and concepts considered unsayable only a few years ago'. According to the authors, Sellner is 'a charismatic pied piper who expounds far-right thought with disarming charm' who provides 'a sense of direction and purpose' (ibid.).

Schäller (2019, p. 193) observes how Sellner demonstrates 'the image of a young man who, as a talented speaker, spoke well above the level usually seen from the Pegida stage, whose body language and style of dress conveyed a charismatic appearance for younger audiences, and who exuded a certain casualness with his Viennese dialect'.

Abel (2020, p. 141) argues that Sellner possesses significant 'symbolic capital' within the IM, as his opinions are being widely accepted, recited, and legitimised by its members. This gives Sellner the ability to spread certain narratives to a wide target group and by doing this he largely influences the IM's discourse. One example in this context is his reaction to a documentation by the TV channel RTL (2024) that showed

a female member of the Junge Alternative (Young Alternative – the youth wing of the AfD) at a party of the Identitarian Movement in Vienna, who stated violent fantasies about harming Muslims, which further highlights the connection to right-wing extremism and violence (see previous section). Martin Sellner reacts with a video and speaks of a ‘bizarre accumulation of coincidences’ and accused the TV channel of belonging to the so-called ‘lying press’. A few days later he published a video together with another activist to speak again about this situation. The most interesting part is not only how they try to tell a different story but the scenery the viewer sees. Sellner and the other activist are wearing summer shirts and sitting in a garden between them a barbecue and in their hands a drink. They seemed amused and relaxed and used this context to speak about the negative media coverage. The whole scene was well staged and aimed at giving the impression that nothing bad has happened and they want to explain calmly what caused all the media trouble by giving the viewer an alternative explanation (Sellner, 2024b). They used humour to draw a different narrative and offered their members an explanation they can use.

According to Richards (2019, p. 42), the IM wants to address ‘young, digitally native, relatively affluent, and center-right-wing “mainstream” populations’ by using a ‘relatively idiosyncratic online activity’. Based on this, the IM attaches great value to their online presence as this gives the group the opportunity to reach a high number of people and spread their content even across borders. The original Facebook page and its follow-up pages are no longer available. However, the number of likes on the Facebook page – 62,485 – was disproportionately high compared to the estimated number of members (500) (Blum, 2023, p. 25). Even though measures such as deplatforming are effective in disrupting the reach of propaganda (Kinskofer, 2023, pp. 109–114), they have also led extremist groups to use alternative platforms (Kuchta et al., 2021, p. 5; see also Bjørge, 2009, p. 31; Reinemann et al., 2019, p. 30). This also happened with the IM whose members established channels among other on Telegram. Kuchta et al. (2021, p. 4) claim that Telegram serves as ‘a gathering place’ for users who have been excluded from other social media platforms due to content removals. This shows that even if the offline activism is small the online activism can draw a completely different picture which the IM uses for their purpose.

The internet, particularly social media, plays a key role in right-wing movements by providing a platform for communication, recruitment, propaganda, and organising events (e.g. Bartlett, Birdwell and Littler, 2011, p. 29). Miller-Idriss (2020, p. 138) highlights that engagement with extremist content no longer needs physical presence, it 'beam[s] right into our homes and schools'. This enables individuals to support or join groups 'with just the click of a mouse' (Bartlett, Birdwell and Littler, 2011, p. 33).

Alternative platforms often act as 'echo chambers', reinforcing extremism and accelerating radicalisation (Miller-Idriss, 2020, p. 141). Vorländer et al. (2018, p. 2) examined this in the context of the protest movement Pegida, which also began as a Facebook group and utilised social media to reach a wide audience. The authors found that by implementing such social media platforms, they created a space, 'in which already polarised supporters mutually reinforced each other's views and became radicalised' (Vorländer 2018, p. 23). This leads to the absence of a corrective as members of these social media groups are only confronted with like-minded views. Vorländer et al. describe this missing corrective as follows: 'the organisers [of Pegida] were able to pass on their messages directly to their supporters without the filter of journalistic editing and classification' (2018, p. 25). Online interactions within like-minded groups can therefore intensify beliefs and limit exposure to opposing views.

The IM also applies a modernised appearance that appeals to youth by selling their own clothing brand online, which no longer resembles the clothing of a stereotypical neo-Nazi. Accordingly, it is not always clearly recognisable to outsiders that it is clothing from a right-wing extremist group. Blum (2021, p. 202) describes that the offering of clothing affiliated with the IM plays a significant role in 'constructing a sense of belonging'. Besides clothing, on the IM's official homepage one can see that the IM offers different activities individuals can take part in, ranging from music events, hiking, action-orientated activism, barbecue or reading circles (Identitäre Bewegung Deutschland e.v., 2024).

2.3.5 Organisation and networking

Looking at the numbers of members of the IM, the IM constitutes a mere fraction of the official statistics on right-wing extremism. Of the 40,600 individuals classified as

belonging to right-wing extremism, the IM is part of the non-party-affiliated structures, which account for 8,500 individuals, 500 of whom are attributable to the IM (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2024, pp. 78, 127). Nevertheless, it needs to be kept in mind that not all people who sympathise with the IM also become official members.

According to Blum (2023, p. 26) the IM's members are 'diverse' in contrast to the 'homogeneous image of a white, young and modern organization' the group presents and its aim to build a homogeneous nation. So found Blum (2023, pp. 26–27) in her research 'people of different ages, origins, religious affiliations, sexual orientations, and ethnic backgrounds'. Moreover, the diversity can be seen in different forms, for instance due to devaluation of women in terms of stereotypical gender roles. In case the diversity does not serve the IM's purpose it remains unaddressed, for instance if someone does not represent heteronormative gender roles. In that case other attributes of the individual play a role for the movement (Blum, 2021, pp. 214–215). Blum (2021, p. 213) concludes that the 'ideological orientation and the organisational goal as well as the diversity of the members are diametrically opposed phenomena'. The group is divided into various regional subgroups, enabling the IM to operate nationwide in Germany (Goetz and Winkler, 2023, p. 207). Moreover, connection exists to other groups in other European countries (ibid.). However, the IM does 'not act in isolation' (Zúquete, 2018, p. 4) or 'in a political vacuum' (Bruns, Glösel and Strobl, 2014, p. 56), instead various connections with other actors within the far-right spectrum can be observed. In recent years, several journalists and scholars have conducted in-depth analysis of the network of the New Right (Fuchs and Middelhoff, 2019; Stegemann and Musyal, 2020), including the IM (Speit, 2018). The authors identify a broad network among members of the IM, which is challenging to fully comprehend from an outsider's perspective. This is also reasoned by the fact that much networking takes place online and if certain groups / accounts get deleted, the same people appear under different account names (e.g. Kinskofer, 2023, p. 112).

In recent years the IM's network to other countries and similar groups, both online and offline, has been growing. For instance, media coverage shows members of the IM with actors of right-wing extremist groups such as 'Junge Tat' in Switzerland or the American 'Patriot Front' (Krahn and Allgaier-Honal, 2022, p. 197). Looking at the

online network, one can see that different social media actors are cross-linked or are interview guests in each other's channel program (e.g. Malenki, 2019).

These interconnected networks were made visible by the revelation of a far-right meeting in Potsdam in 2024, which brought together well-known members of the IM, advocates of the political party AfD, the ultra-conservative Werteunion as well as business leaders (Bensmann *et al.*, 2024). According to the authors of the Recherche Collective the topic of this meeting was '[n]othing less than the fine tuning of a plan for the forced deportations of millions of people currently living in Germany' (ibid.).

According to media coverage, Sellner 'proposed a project of "remigration" which would see "unassimilated" immigrants forced to leave Germany even if they had citizenship' (Osborne, 2024). This is all written down in his book 'remigration' (Sellner, 2024a) which he later promoted through public readings, many of which were interrupted by police interventions (e.g. Stenull and Jost, 2024). Instead of seeing these disruptions as a problem, he used them to gain more attention and grow his audience as evidenced by his social media activity surrounding these events.

At the same time, the growing success of right-wing political parties in Europe and around the world persists. A notable example is the FPÖ in Austria, led by Herbert Kickl, who has connections to the IM. This is evidenced by photographs taken during the party conference, where IM members were seen displaying the White Power symbol (Sager, 2024). In an interview, Kickl even referred to the IM as an 'interesting and worthy project' (ibid.) and referred to them as a 'NGO from the right' in an earlier interview (Plus 24 News, 2021). These developments, occurring just months before the completion of this dissertation, illustrate the importance of understanding the motivations behind membership in the IM.

Important actors in the periphery of the IM include Götz Kubitschek and his self-labelled Institute for State Policy (IfS). The IfS was established in May 2000 and dissolved in 2024 after being classified as a right-wing extremist by the Federal Office for the Protection of the Constitution (Spiegel Politik, 2024). The institute aimed to establish opportunities for independent, institutionalised education and research work within the New Far Right (e.g. Speit, 2018, pp. 35–36). It also focused on building right-wing (intellectual) networks to build a basis for a broader shift of public and

political discourse to the right (ibid.). Their method to achieve this aim was the publication of various articles as well as organising different events, such as the summer academy which also targets members of the IM (ibid.). Furthermore, Kubitschek is the head of the publishing company Antaios (Röpke, 2018, p. 13) which has printed the books written by Martin Sellner (2017b) and Mario Müller (2017). Sellner (2017b, p. 26) describes the IfS and the far-right magazine Sezession as the 'intellectual resources' and 'compass' for members of the IM.

This shows that, even though the IM has a comparatively small number of members, the circle of people who sympathise with and support it is significantly larger. This makes it easier for the group to navigate within the right-wing network and spread its propaganda.

2.4 Empirical studies on the IM

The previous sections provided an overview of the IM, encompassing history of its development and defining characteristics, with a focus on its ideological foundations and strategic approaches. Since its development, different researchers have examined these aspects and often placed an emphasis on the IM's historical connections and its relationship to right-wing extremism. However, researchers also criticise the quality of published literature stating that some analyses are partly shaped by a leftist activist perspective, limiting their objectivity (e.g. Schäller, 2019, pp. 207–208).

Nevertheless, in comparison to other forms of right-wing extremism, the state of research on forms of 'right-wing Identitarianism' such as Generation Identity or the German IM remains limited (Richards, 2019, p. 33). Even more limited is the number of studies focusing on individual motives: The literature review revealed a significant gap in research exploring the personal reasons behind individuals' decisions to join the IM, particularly with regard to the German IM. According to Fielitz (2020, p. 643), the IM is a research area 'where more is spoken about than with the research subjects'. This sheds light on another lack as the examination of individual motives requires the individual perspective of people who join the IM.

Up to this point only a few researchers conducted empirical studies that include a direct interaction with members of the IM. Blum (2021, p. 6) claims that there were several attempts to get in contact with members of the group by journalists (e.g. Schroeder, 2024) as well as other actors but there was no attempt to approach the IM from a scholarly perspective. In light of this, the subsequent paragraphs present a review of the empirical studies that are of relevance to this study.

Zúquete (2018, p. xiii) conducted one of the first ethnographic studies on the phenomenon of the French IM and explored 'what Identitarians have to say and how they imagine and present themselves'. The author stressed the importance of analysing the IM 'from the inside out' and avoiding quick, 'uninformed' judgments (ibid.). He conducted email interviews with theorists, activists, and supporters, none of whom were members of the German IM (ibid., p. xvi). His emphasis was on the theoretical / ideological foundation of the IM, activism against globalism and Islam, and its geopolitical visions (ibid., p. 3). It highlights key mobilisation frames like 'remigration' and opposition to the 'Great Replacement,' underlining their role in shaping anti-globalist and Islamophobic narratives (ibid., pp. 152-154). He examined how individuals who have an affiliation with the IM, mostly authors who have written something relating to the topics of the IM, verbalise, for instance, their aims. Zúquete (2018, p. 4) also investigates their cultural and political strategies, examining their connections to broader right-wing networks.

Accordingly, while there are isolated references to underlying motivations (e.g. Zúquete, 2018, pp. 103, 191), these are more of a by-product as the author approaches the topic from a different analytical perspective. For instance, Zúquete (2018, p. 285) highlights how personal experiences of violence and exclusion serve as catalysts for Identitarian activism.

Julia Ebner (2020, p. 2) went undercover to listen to extremist's stories to learn more about recruiting strategies, 'social dynamics that keep members inside a group' as well as ideological views of extremist groups. Among others she went undercover in the GI (ibid.). Ebner (2020, p. 31) gained in-depth insights into the group. Her book includes statements from members that, for example, highlight the use of social media for recruitment or emphasised how the IM distance itself from traditional far-right extremism (ibid.). Ebner (2020, p. 49) concludes that media actions 'made them [IM] grow significantly'. According to the author, the use of social media made 'recruitment

a great deal easier' (ibid., p. 49 - 50). Moreover, it provides insights into how the IM selects its members and the role the members' education level plays in their activism (ibid., pp. 41 - 47).

Alice Blum (2021, p. 6) conducted an ethnographic study as well and examined the organisational structure, recruitment methods, and the ways in which the German IM's self-image is maintained and represented. Additionally, she explored what makes the Identitarians particularly appealing to younger audiences and examined how their ideologies managed to gain widespread support in such a short period (Blum, 2023, p. 24).

One of the findings in Blum's (2023, p. 29) research is that diversity within the organisation requires a range of narratives to appeal to different individuals. So, there are narratives which serve the need for combative activism as well as narratives of home which serve the need of developing organisation practices (Blum, 2021, p. 219). The author states that collective narratives do play an important role in extreme right-wing movements, for instance conspiracy theories such as the 'Great Replacement' (Blum, 2023, pp. 29–30). Meiering, Dziri and Foroutan (2018, p. 10) claim that such narratives 'structure patterns of perception, attributions of belonging, and options for action, and thereby act as transmission belts for radicalisation processes'. According to Blum (2023, p. 30), the IM uses fears and experiences of injustice and offer 'salvation through direct action'.

Moreover, Blum (2023, p. 32) argues that Identitarians shape the personal identity of their members, influencing their 'everyday life'. The boundary between private life and involvement in the IM becomes blurred (Blum, 2021, p. 220). The IM strengthens their member's commitment by assigning them different roles and tasks (Blum, 2023, p. 32). Through an active engagement the IM offers a sense of self-realisation and lead individuals to a stronger identification with the IM's aims (ibid.).

The author concludes that Identitarian demonstrations and actions serve not only 'a political purpose' but also strengthen members' 'sense of belonging' (ibid., p. 32). For members who show greater activity it creates the opportunity to receive a higher degree of recognition (ibid.). The combination of participation, excitement, and secrecy fosters a strong group identity and reinforces a collective "'we" feelin[g]', deepening members' connection to the organisation (ibid.).

However, this identification with the group in all aspects of life can result in social exclusion, such as the loss of personal relationships, which can increase their loyalty to the organisation (ibid., p. 34). While Blum (2021, pp. 224–225) examined aspects that attract individuals to engage in the IM, she states that further research is needed in terms of individual motives that make people join as well as the effectiveness of the organisation's political agenda and its corresponding concepts are important to look at.

Another ethnographic study on new right-wing political parties and groups, including the IM, AfD, Junge Alternative (Youth Alternative), and Pegida, supplemented with narrative interviews, forms the foundation of Fröhlich's (2023, p. 3, 2019, p. 223) analysis. She explores how these groups and parties create a victimhood narrative to justify their ideology (Fröhlich, 2023, pp. 2–7). A key part of this strategy is the idea of collective suffering, which strengthens group identity and defines outsiders as enemies (ibid.). This shared sense of victimhood unites members, reinforces nationalism, and incorporates non-violence rhetoric, helping the groups appear legitimate while holding on to exclusionary beliefs (ibid.). Moreover, Fröhlich (2019) examines how criticism in the new right-wing groups is framed as concern for the nation, highlighting its role in mobilisation through perceived victimhood.

Against this background, similar to Zúquete, while these scholars obtained interesting findings, they did not explore sequences of key events that led individuals towards the IM or placed a particular focus on individual motives and factors that make individuals join. Studies which have addressed the gap in understanding the motives for joining remain limited.

A more recent study focused exclusively on women, exploring their psycho-cultural motives for joining GI through four Skype and email interviews with female members from the UK and Europe (Gibson, Veneti and Voutyras, 2024, pp. 23, 28). The interviewees were between 18 and 25 years old, with two being college students and two undergraduate students (ibid., p. 28). Gibson, Veneti and Voutyras (2024, pp. 29–36) examined how emotions, identity, and gender roles influence the women's involvement. The authors highlight that these women often feel alienated from mainstream politics and experience grief, insecurity, and anger, which GI reframes as

a reaction to societal decline (ibid.). The group promotes traditional gender norms, presenting women as both 'mothers, daughters, and containers of the state' and 'as victims of immigration' (ibid., p. 33). Immigration and globalisation are seen as existential threats, reinforcing a shared sense of crisis, often amplified through social media (ibid., p. 32, 35). The authors explained that the low number of interviews 'reflects the challenges of recruiting respondents on a sensitive and divisive topic' (ibid., p. 29). Researchers examining the personal backgrounds of individuals involved in radical right groups in Poland and Germany encountered similar challenges (Myrczik *et al.*, 2024). Although they aimed to include members of the IM in their study, these individuals 'refused to be interviewed' (ibid., p. 7).

One ethnographic study with a research question and methods closely related to this research is that of Pilkington (2023) who examined trajectories of individuals within the extreme right. She conducted participant observations and semi-structured interviews with individuals from various right-wing groups in the United Kingdom, including members of the GI (ibid., p. 5). However, her focus was not on a particular group but rather on 'a milieu in the sense that it is a space – physical and virtual – in which actors encounter, engage with and respond to radical or extreme messages' (ibid., p. 5). She provided valuable insights into the different pathways of a radicalisation process and argues that 'we need not only to recognize non-radicalization as an outcome, but that there are multiple non-radicalization trajectories' (ibid., p. 21). The author categorises three types: 'partial, stalled and non-radicalization' (ibid., p. 1).

This demonstrated that radicalisation does not always need to end up in the use of violence. In line with radicalisation research, Pilkington (2023, p. 22) found that pathways of individuals joining extremist groups are highly individual. Her findings emphasise 'the importance of the relational and emotional dimension of radical(izing) milieus' as well as the significance of distinguishing between 'political and personal grievances' in understanding radicalisation (ibid.). Her analysis highlights that 'personal grievances [can] become political, and political grievances [may] take on profoundly personal significance', influenced by 'situational or affective factors' such as 'social isolation/longing for community' or socialisation instances such as family or peers. These dynamics can fuel radical engagement, but can also lead individuals to disengage from extremism (ibid., p. 7). Additionally, life events, negative activism

experiences, or shifting priorities often result in withdrawal from radical engagement (ibid., 7-8).

Besides these qualitative empirical studies, other researchers have, for instance, focused on different factions of the IM, including its North American branches, and the potential factors influencing its success in recruiting new members. Hermansson et al. (2020, p. 72) highlight that compared with European members, those in North America are less successful at 'bringing supporters away from the web and out onto the streets'. One reason for this, they argue, is the difference in 'the level of infrastructure' – in Europe, the movement benefits not only from well-organised activist groups but also from a broader network of institutions that are either run by identitarians or aligned with their views (ibid.).

2.5 Research gap

A review of the literature revealed that research on the IM is still limited and tends to focus on structural and ideological aspects. Researchers have examined the organisational structure, classification, and role of the IM within the context of the New Right, as well as its ideology, aims, and strategies (see Chapter 2). As delineated in the preceding sections, distinct content analyses focus on the examination of the IM's social media content and the propagated narratives. Furthermore, researchers have scrutinised the evolution of IM and its references to historical contexts. These studies and literature are mainly based on non-face-to-face interactions with IM members. There are only few empirical studies that include field research methods with members of the IM. Previous scholars mainly conducted ethnographic studies. Among them, only Blum (2021) focused specifically on members of the IM in Germany, whereas other scholars examined different IM groups across Europe. However, most of these studies included not only IM members but also participants from other far-right groups; and thus did not focus exclusively on the IM. Even in cases where German IM members were part of the sample, they were studied alongside individuals from other right-wing extremist groups.

Moreover, some scholars conducted interviews, but often only as a supplementary method in studies that did not focus exclusively on the IM. The few interview-based studies that specifically focused on the IM primarily relied on Skype and email interviews rather than face-to-face interactions.

Although most authors explored the motives of members to a certain extent, their primary focus was largely on the structural aspects of the IM. Hence, Blum indicates that further research is required regarding the underlying individual motives for joining the IM. This is consistent with Krahn and Allgaier-Honal (2022, pp. 176–177) who provided a summary of prevention strategies regarding the IM, highlighting the significance of examining the push and pull factors. Push factors are those that render an individual person susceptible to radicalisation, whereas pull factors refer to the strategies and incentives offered by extremist groups (*ibid.*). This highlights the necessity of acquiring comprehensive insights into the individual motivations of someone joining the IM.

In sum, studies that use semi-structured interviews to explore the individual motivations of IM members, particularly those of the German IM, are notably scarce. To the author's knowledge, there is currently no interview-based study that exclusively examines individuals' motives for joining the German IM. Consequently, there is a lack of empirical evidence concerning the individual motives of those who engage with the German IM.

2.6 Research questions of the study

Against this background, this study aims to address the existing research gap and offers a distinctive perspective on the underlying motives for engaging in the IM. It employs a qualitative research approach, including semi-structured interviews and participant observations. Given the plethora of far-right extremist groups and the inherent complexity of radicalisation processes, an in-depth examination of a particular group provides a valuable opportunity to gain deeper insights.

The purpose of this study is to answer the following questions:

- Which motives and influencing factors contribute to an individual's decision to participate in the IM?
- What creates the perception that this group is attractive to join?
- What does an engagement look like and do the motives influence how someone engages in the IM?

By answering these questions, this study will make a novel contribution to knowledge by gaining a more nuanced understanding of the underlying motives among individuals joining the IM.

2.7 Approaching the research questions

In light of the lack of empirical studies on the IM in general, and especially on individual motives for joining, most notably at the outset of this research, the author drew on theoretical and empirical radicalisation research. This literature was used to inform the analysis and to assess the extent to which these findings could be applied to the specific context of the research subject. The next sections will give a brief overview of the state of radicalisation research and selected studies that examined individual motives for joining far-right extremist groups.

2.7.1 Radicalisation research

Similar to the research on right-wing extremism, the growing interest in the development of radicalisation processes and the related prevention of such processes has led to 'an explosion of research' on the subject (Marsden, Malkki and Busher, 2024, p. 1). For a more detailed overview see Busher, Malkki and Marsden (2024) and Borum (2011a, 2011b). Various researchers have developed different approaches (theories and models) to explain radicalisation processes and generated empirical studies to examine the underlying motivations of people joining far-right extremist groups. The following sections present the main lines of argumentation in radicalisation research, with a focus on individual factors that contribute to radicalisation.

The terror attacks on the 11th of September 2001 mark an important point for radicalisation research (Neumann, 2015, p. 1; Peels, 2023, p. 610). Those attacks, as well as, for example, the bomb attacks in Madrid in 2004 and in London in 2005 (Bjørge and Horgan, 2009, p. 3; Koehler, 2017, p. 2) 'created a massive demand for explanations' (Neumann, 2015, p. 3), ergo a growing research interest in radicalisation. However, looking at the political and academic debate around the phenomenon of radicalisation, it quickly becomes clear that an agreed definition of the term does not exist (Neumann, 2013, p. 874). This circumstance has been criticised (e.g. Sedgwick, 2010, p. 1) and it has been stressed that a clear definition is needed to have a common basis for a political, public or academic discussion (Peels, 2023, p. 2). However, one challenge that had been pointed out is that radicalisation research is not located within a particular discipline but rather within and across several different disciplines, resulting in the non-existence of a 'coherent academic field' (Neumann, 2015, p. 1).

This is not inherently negative, as it is important to view the phenomenon from different perspectives. However, it complicates the creation of a common understanding and thus makes it difficult to compare results. The Federal Criminal Police Office (Bundeskriminalamt, 2024) defines radicalisation as 'the increasing inclination of individuals or groups towards an extremist mindset and behaviour, along with a growing willingness to endorse, support, and/or use illegitimate means, including the use of violence, to advance their objectives'. The consideration of the political context plays an important role. In democratic societies, radicalisation is identified by its opposition to the principles of democracy (Pickel and Pickel, 2023, p. 4). Abay Gaspar et al. (2018, p. 5) define radicalisation 'as the increasing questioning of the legitimacy of a normative order and/or the increasing willingness to fight against the institutional structure of that order'.

2.7.1.1 Models and theories

To contribute to a better understanding of radicalisation processes, researchers have developed different types of models (Ravn, Coolsaet and Sauer, 2019, p. 29), such as the Two Pyramids model (McCauley and Moskalenko, 2017). However, most of them predominantly focus on Islamic radicalisation (e.g. Coolsaet, 2015, p. 6; Koehler,

2024, p. 266). The majority of these models describe a pathway towards terrorism illustrated in different forms. For example, Moghaddam (2005, p. 161) uses a 'narrowing staircase' metaphor which explains the pathway into terrorism through a structured progression of stages. The staircase to terrorism is envisioned as consisting of a ground floor and five ascending floors, each defined by certain human behaviour as a result of specific psychological processes (ibid., pp. 161-162). The ground floor is marked by 'perceptions of fairness and feelings of relative deprivation' (ibid., p.162). Dissatisfied individuals climb to the first floor to enhance their situation. If unresolved, they climb to the second floor, where some project blame onto a foe partly under a leaders' influence (ibid.). The third floor marks a critical shift as individuals adopt terrorist ideologies, viewing violence as justified (ibid.). On the top floor, they are prepared to commit terrorist acts (ibid.). Most people, despite feeling injustice, remain on the ground floor (ibid.). Therefore, each floor needs to be reached to get to the next floor and a person can also stay on the first floor without going any higher further ascending. According to Moghaddam, this metaphor serves as a 'general framework', not 'as a formal model' (ibid.).

Another model has been developed by the New York Police Department to explain Islamic terrorism (Silber and Bhatt, 2007, p. 6). Silber and Bhatt developed a four stages model including the following ones: 'Pre-Radicalization', 'Self-Identification', 'Indoctrination' and 'Jihadization' (ibid.). Each stage encompasses specific signs and patterns of behaviour that characterise each stage of the radicalisation process (ibid., p. 7). For instance, the stage of 'Self-Identification' describes the time at which a person starts to learn more about 'Salafi Islam' resulting in distancing himself from his former beliefs, and instead engaging with 'like-minded individuals' and gradually embracing this ideology (ibid.). This process occurs when an individual experiences a 'cognitive opening, or crisis', that challenges their previously held beliefs, making them more open to adopting new perspectives and ideologies (ibid.) According to the authors such a process can be influenced by a number of different factors that have a catalysing effect, for instance political conflicts or experiences of discrimination (ibid., p. 7). However, not everyone who starts the process goes through all of the stages (ibid., p. 6). Instead, there are people who distance themselves from the process at one stage or another (ibid.). Moreover, even though the process includes stages which have a certain order, 'individuals do not always follow a perfectly linear progression'

(ibid.). However, if a person goes through all the stages, there is a high possibility that this person will take part in 'planning or implementation of a terrorist act' (ibid.).

Wiktorowicz (2005, p. 5) argues that diverse experiences such as discrimination or a socioeconomic crisis can serve as a 'cognitive opening'. A cognitive opening often prompts individuals to question previously held beliefs, making them more receptive to new ideas and perspectives (ibid.). Movements can also create these openings 'through activism and outreach' that raises awareness, challenges existing ideas, and convinces people that 'old ways of thinking' can't solve current social, political, and economic issues (ibid.).

Borum's (2003) 'Terrorist Mindset' seeks to explain the psychological and social processes that lead individuals to become terrorists. Borum (2003, p. 7) formulated four stages, starting with the first one at which 'an extremist individual or group' notice an 'unsatisfying event or condition', for instance, a lack of jobs. This is followed by the second stage that comprises the evaluation of this event or condition as being unjust (Borum, 2003, p. 8). At the third stage people who find themselves in an unfair situation, start blaming this on another person or group, such as minority groups (ibid.). The last step results in seeing this person or group as 'bad' or 'evil' (ibid.). This stigmatisation can further encourage the use of violence (ibid.).

What these models all have in common is that they attempt to explain the pathway of someone becoming radicalised, ending in committing violent behaviour. However, such models have also faced critique. Given the fact that researchers tried to capture the complex phenomenon of radicalisation in one model, such models 'tend towards simplification' (Marsden, Malkki and Busher, 2024, p. 5). Ebner and Whitehouse (2024, p. 88) concluded that most models fail to clearly differentiate between 'psychological causes of violent extremism and mere correlates or consequences of the radicalisation process'. According to them, it is important to note that not everyone who displays beliefs or behaviours linked to radicalisation are necessarily breaking the law (ibid.). In fact, many of these individuals may never actually engage in violent extremism (ibid., see also Pilkington, 2023).

The distinction between radicalisation that leads to the use of violence and radicalisation that does not end in violent behaviour is an important one. Schuurman (2020, p. 14) argues that research should prioritise understanding the factors that lead

most extremists to refrain from committing acts of violence. Therefore, researchers agree that someone can '*cognitively* radicalise' (original emphasis) – meaning 'radicalize in one's beliefs, ideas, thoughts, and way of thinking' without reaching a point at which he or she uses violence (Peels, 2023, p. 2; see also Bartlett and Miller, 2012). Furthermore, the occurrence of radical behaviour does not automatically indicate that the individual in question holds radical beliefs. Such actions can be driven by a range of other factors, including an 'admiration for a group leader' or some type of grievances (Peels, 2023, p. 3).

In addition, researchers also addressed the negative connotation associated with the term radicalisation and examined forms of 'benevolent radicalisation' (Reidy, 2018, p. 277; see also Ravn, Coolsaet and Sauer, 2019, p. 23). Veldhuis and Staun (2009, pp. 17–18) argue that phase models are not suitable for answering questions like 'why some people radicalise in a non-violent direction, abandon the radicalisation process at a premature stage, or do not radicalise at all'. According to the authors, such models neglect circumstances, such as the political or societal situation as well as the 'individual's personal history and life path' (ibid., p. 18). This means that not every person goes through a radicalisation process the way it is described in these models. Therefore, the authors suggest that the focus should be more on 'individual circumstances' when it comes to elucidating the phenomenon of radicalisation (ibid., p. 19). This is in line with Abbas (2024, p. 237) who believes that to examine this phenomenon requires 'nuanced understandings'. Similarly, Githens-Mazar (2008, p. 22) stated in relation to Islamic radicalisation that 'the story behind how and why each individual may come to be a radical violent Islamist is as unique as a fingerprint'. This can be also applied to right-wing radicalisation.

2.7.1.2 *Radicalisation mechanisms*

Because most models do not explain how individuals move from one stage or phase to the next one, McCauley and Moskalenko (2008) developed twelve mechanisms of radicalisation. They state that radicalisation can take place at the 'individual, group, and mass-public level[s]' (ibid., p. 418). For example, one mechanism embraces the individual experience of resentment which can lead to radicalisation (ibid.), whereas

another mechanism comprises radicalisation 'in response to political trends or events' (ibid., p. 419).

At the individual level, McCauley and Moskaleiko (2008, p. 419) describe the 'Slippery Slope' mechanism, wherein radicalisation is portrayed as a 'slow and gradual' process. This involves an individual joining a radical group and progressively moving through stages of involvement (ibid., p. 419). Initially, individuals are tasked with non-violent activities before they are eventually assigned to carry out violent actions (ibid., p. 419). Cases of individuals becoming radicalised in a short period are exceedingly rare (ibid., p. 420). Another mechanism contains 'Group Radicalization in Like-Minded Groups' (ibid., p. 422). In relation to this mechanism, terms such as 'group extremity shift' or 'group polarization' are used (ibid.). It describes a dynamic of people who share the same or a similar view of a problem coming together, leading to the creation of an 'average opinion' (ibid.). This most shared view becomes dominant within the group and individuals who share this view then tend to turn their own view into a more extreme view (ibid.).

McCauley and Moskaleiko state that their developed mechanisms are not a definitive list and that none of these mechanisms can provide the necessary clarification for political radicalisation (2008, p. 429). The authors conclude that political radicalisation is a dynamic process and therefore does not occur in isolation (ibid., p. 430). It is often a response to the actions of others (ibid.). To understand these processes, it is crucial to recognise that political radicalisation, whether of individuals, groups, or the general public, follows a pattern of action and reaction, in which state actions frequently play a key role (ibid.).

2.7.1.3 Radicalisation as highly individualised process

It has thus far become evident that radicalisation is a complex phenomenon. However, what the models show and what researchers agree on is that radicalisation is a process that is influenced by various factors (e.g. Centre for the Prevention of Radicalization Leading to Violence, 2024) and the question left is 'why some individuals become radicalized and other do not' (Siegel *et al.*, 2019, p. 412). As Neumann (2013, p. 874) explains, no researcher assumes that 'individuals turn to

extremists overnight or that their embrace of extremism is caused by a single influence'. For instance, Bailey and Edwards (2017, p. 265) observe that 'the start and endpoints of radicalisation journeys are diverse' and do not follow a clear or linear path (see also Veldhuis and Staun, 2009, p. 6). On the contrary, radicalisation is an individual and 'non-predetermined' (e.g. Centre for the Prevention of Radicalization Leading to Violence, 2024) process shaped by multiple factors, leading to a significant shift in both 'attitudes and behaviour' (Veldhuis and Staun, 2009, p. 6). Borum (2011a, pp. 8–9) defines it as a process in which a person establishes 'extremist beliefs' which provide the basis for violent offences, which is in agreement with McCauley and Moskaleiko's (2008, p. 416) view.

Therefore, the absence of a precise definition for radicalisation can be attributed to the highly individualised nature of a radicalisation process. Researchers agree that there is no monocausal explanation for radicalisation (Borum, 2011a, p. 9). It is always an interplay between multiple factors, considering the individual, organisational, and societal levels (Feddes *et al.*, 2023, p. 7,14). Hafez and Mullins (2015, p. 959) speak of a 'radicalisation puzzle' and point out that 'we lack the representative image that informs us how best to put them together'. However, even though an agreed definition does not exist, there are aspects that researchers agree on when it comes to radicalisation (Neumann, 2017, pp. 15–16).

Schneider (2023) presents the results of a qualitative content-analysis of interviews with experts in the field of radicalisation. These experts mentioned multiple factors on the micro, meso and macro level that can contribute to a radicalisation process (*ibid.*, p. 38). The distinction in the micro, meso and macro level has already been used by Crenshaw (1981, p. 380) who examined the causes that led a person to terrorism. Experts agreed that 'group-based prejudices or notions of inequality' as well as black and white thinking play a relevant role on the micro level for a radicalisation process (Schneider, 2023, p. 70).

For the meso level, the role of the extremist ideology, family, as well as the peer group have been stressed (*ibid.*). On the macro level, the internet and social media, the current climate within society, crises as well as political decisions in other countries have been emphasised (*ibid.*). Divergent opinions exist regarding the influence of, for

instance, experiences of individual or collective discrimination, or broken home situations (ibid.).

The Significance Quest model (Kruglanski *et al.*, 2014, p. 69) describes that the 'quest for personal significance' serves as a strong motivational factor that can contribute to the process of someone engaging in violent extremist activities. The authors distinguish three important components. The first one is the 'motivational component' (ibid.). It encompasses the objective someone aims for as well as 'the fundamental desire to matter, to be someone, to have respect' (Kruglanski *et al.*, 2014, p. 69, 73, 2009; Schuurman, 2020, p. 16). This can be triggered by experiencing 'humiliation' or 'a loss of significance', fearing or anticipating such a loss, or perceiving an opportunity to enhance one's significance (Kruglanski *et al.*, 2014, p. 74). The second item is the 'ideological component' which contributes to the belief that violence is a legitimate means for fulfilling their object (ibid., p. 69). The last component is the 'social process of networking and group dynamics' which provides the individual with an opportunity to engage with and adopt 'violence-justifying' ideologies, ultimately using them as a means to enhance their sense of significance (ibid.). Therefore, Kruglanski, Bélanger and Gunaratna (2019) emphasised three central causes for radicalisation – needs, narratives and networks.

Feddes *et al.* (2020, pp. 72–77) outline four types of needs: 'Identity seekers', 'Justice seekers', 'Significance seekers', and 'Sensation seekers'. These categories reflect different psychological drivers influencing the radicalisation process (ibid.). Identity seekers are attracted to extremist groups as they offer a sense of belonging, security, and self-esteem, particularly when individuals perceive threats to their identity (ibid., pp. 72-74). Adolescents are especially vulnerable due to their developmental focus on identity formation (ibid.). Justice seekers are motivated by perceived injustices, while sensation seekers are driven by the pursuit of excitement and novel experiences (ibid., pp. 74-77). According to Feddes *et al.* (2020, p. 75), individuals driven by significance seeking are motivated by a need for social recognition or a sense of purpose.

This line of thinking can also be found in the Theory Social Disintegration (e.g. Anhut and Heitmeyer, 2000) which says that a lack of integration in key societal dimensions – 'social-structural', 'institutional', and 'socioemotional' – can result in a loss of

recognition and belonging, thereby increasing the likelihood of deviant or violent behaviour (Heitmeyer and Anhut, 2008, p. 28).

Bjørge (2011, p. 277) states that individuals can take part in terrorism and other forms of violent extremism for 'a variety of reasons, political or non-political'. He points out that certain individuals take part in such activities because they want to 'fulfil a dream, a need or an urge to do or achieve something' (ibid.). However, Bjørge (2011, p. 277) argues that individuals often do not achieve what they were planning to achieve, with the result that they often disengage from these activities, because they notice that they got 'disillusioned'.

Ebner (2020, p. 49) states that people can join extremist groups for different reasons: Some individuals join due to ideological beliefs, while others did not show any political engagement at first. For some, the main motivation is the appeal of belonging to 'an exclusive community, a cool counter-culture' (ibid.). However, a common pattern among new members is the search for identity, often linked to low self-esteem or personal struggles (ibid.).

Researchers distinguish between push and pull factors. Push factors are those which promote a radicalisation process such as feelings of fear, frustration, or the experience of discrimination (Pickel and Pickel, 2023, pp. 6–7). Pull factors can be described as factors that contribute to the process of an individual becoming receptive to extremist thinking (ibid.). For instance, a charismatic leader can be a pull factor as this person might offer an apparent easy solution for the individuals push factors (ibid., p. 7).

Neumann (2017, p. 21) speaks of 'well-researched »components«' of radicalisation. Neither component offers an explanation for radicalisation by itself but all of them can have an influence on processes of radicalisation (ibid.). The components are grievances, needs, ideas, people and violence (ibid., pp. 17-18). These components refer to, for instance, personal situations, desires, receptiveness to radical ideas, group processes and extremist ideologies (ibid.). In order to understand radicalisation, it is important to look at all these different factors. For instance, an ideology 'reduces complexity, channels frustration' and offers aims as well as guidelines (Neumann, 2017, p. 85). However, Neumann (2017, p. 17) points out that there are many factors

and processes that can be found in radicalisation which are, however, not specific to radicalisation. For instance, many people who become radicalised went through personal crises and were searching for a feeling of belonging (ibid.). Yet, neither is this a general observation nor does such an experience necessarily lead to radicalisation. This makes the phenomenon difficult to understand as even those who fit into many of the factors in radicalisation processes may not become radicalised. According to Neumann (2017, p. 17) it is often the everyday stories that lead to a dangerous development when looking at the radicalisation process in retrospect.

Borum (2003, p. 8) emphasises that understanding radicalisation requires examining an individual's unique perspective shaped by values, beliefs and experiences as these create their 'internal "map" of reality, not reality itself'. Recognising this 'social cognition' can help anticipate and interpret their actions (ibid.). Therefore, in order to gain a better understanding of the causes of radicalisation, it is necessary to take the 'perspective of the radical' into account (Veldhuis and Staun 2009, p. 19). Secondly, the interplay between the receptive person and their circumstances is also of relevance. (ibid., p. 19-20). Against this background, various researchers conducted qualitative studies focusing on the insider perspective of individuals joining far-right extremist groups.

2.7.2 Empirical studies on individuals joining far-right extremist groups

Over the years, researchers have conducted different empirical studies to gain deeper insights into the reasons why individuals join right-wing extremist groups. Among the significant and well-known German studies are, for instance, research by Willems (1993) and Frindte and Wahl (2001). Moreover, the Bielefeld Study on Right-Wing Extremism (Bielefelder Rechtsextremismus Studie) which aimed to explain the causes and processes of the development of right-wing extremist orientations (Heitmeyer *et al.*, 1992). These studies examined different motivational factors, though with varying methodological approaches and research groups. For instance, Heitmeyer *et al.* (1992, p. 5) conducted a qualitative longitudinal study in the years 1985 to 1990 with 31 male participants in the age of 17-21 years. The authors found that a focus on material success and social status among youth fosters an instrumental mindset,

where actions and relationships are viewed through a cost-benefit lens (ibid., pp. 601–604).

This reflects broader societal dynamics, where economic pressures and the ambivalence of individualisation contribute to the normalisation of xenophobic attitudes and violence (ibid.). One interesting finding was that not employment alone does function as a preventing factor for right-wing extremist attitudes but the 'quality of employment relationships is crucial', meaning it must be perceived by the receptive person as something meaningful (ibid., p. 595). The focus on socio-economic circumstances as a motivational factor for right-wing extremism was also a finding of other studies. However, Möller and Schumacher (2007, p. 220) found that an individual's subjective perception of their economic situation, such as feeling systematically disadvantaged, is more important than their actual economic status. This aligns with research on relative deprivation (e.g. Smith *et al.*, 2012).

Besides longitudinal studies such as the Bielefeld Right-wing extremist study most of the empirical studies used reconstructive methods, meaning the research participants were either former extremists who had left the scene or convicted right-wing extremist offenders reflecting on their process of joining and leaving extremist groups. One example is the study by Möller and Schumacher (2007, p. 13) who examined the reasons for young people joining and leaving the Skinhead scene by conducting repetitive surveys between the years of 2002 to 2005. The authors identified four different types of processes - the process of affinisiation, consolidation, fundamentalisation and distancing (ibid., p. 53). The phase of affinisiation describes the phase of a young person turning towards the Skinhead scene (ibid., p. 126), followed by the phase of consolidation which means that an individual is firm in his views and group membership (ibid., 234). This leads to the final phase of the process of turning to a scene – the fundamentalisation which is the stage in which a person is embedded in the scene and takes responsibility to varying extent (ibid., p. 323). Since the authors examined the process of disengagement – the fourth phase encompasses the distancing from the scene (ibid., 358). The authors concluded that there is no single pathway into the scene, but rather a variety of motives and influences that shape such a process (ibid., pp. 219-220).

Besides the socio-economic circumstances, researchers examined different motives and influencing factors, including the role of different agents of socialisation such as family. For instance, Heitmeyer and Müller (1995, p. 174) concluded that 'it is almost always a lack of attention, care, recognition, and emotional closeness' that makes someone receptive to far-right extremist attitudes. Other studies came to similar results (e.g. Copeland and Marsden, 2020, p. 7). Lützing (2010, p. 67) found that regardless of the phenomenological extremist scene, extremist groups provided orientation, support in their daily life, and acted as family substitutes for individuals coming from precarious family environments marked by stress and dysfunctional coping strategies.

It is not only a lack of emotional relationships that has been identified as risk factor but also the exposure to right-wing extremist beliefs during their upbringing (ibid.). Research shows that children and adolescents can be shaped in their behavioural development and political attitudes by their parents' upbringing (e.g. Benbow and Bellman, 2010, pp. 291–293). Therefore, certain parenting styles influence whether children and adolescents exhibit problematic behaviour and adopt authoritarian or right-wing beliefs (ibid.), which underscores the importance of family influence and social interactions in the development of prejudiced beliefs (see also Raabe and Beelmann, 2011).

This is in line with research on the transmission of values from parents to their children. For instance, Schönpflug (2001, p. 175) speaks of 'transmission belts' which refer to mechanisms that facilitate the transfer of values, for instance parenting techniques and the quality of the relationship between the parents (see also Urban and Singelmann, 1998). While parenting approaches that lead to 'a positive emotional interaction between parent and child' enhance the transmission of values, authoritative and strict parenting can prevent such an interaction, resulting in reducing the effectiveness of value transmission (Schönpflug, 2001, p. 175).

Some parenting styles serve as effective mechanisms for transmitting values, while others hinder this process. However, not all studies confirmed the significance of certain risk and protective factors. Willems (1993, p. 163) analysed court rulings and did not find a clear pattern in terms of the role of the family; different family situations were found, showing offenders coming from both stable families and those with hidden conflicts that distanced youths from their parents. This aligns with Rommelspacher

(2006, p. 33). Hopf (1993, p. 458) emphasises the importance of 'secure autonomous' relationships as a protective factor against individuals' susceptibility to right-wing extremism. However, according to Möller (2020, p. 823), the interaction between individual and societal factors, especially in family socialisation, and the development of right-wing extremist attitudes has still not been sufficiently addressed in theoretical research. While parents and other family members such as grandparents pass on far-right views, there is no direct causal link to the development of younger generation's attitudes (Möller, 2022, p. 826; see also Boehnke, Hagan and Merkens, 1998).

One of the interesting aspects of the previous studies was to explore the function that belonging to a group serves for the individual. For instance, in relation to family socialisation, researchers found that if individuals lack emotionally stable relationships, groups such as the Skinhead scene can serve as a 'compensation agency' for unmet needs (Willems, 1993, p. 177). These groups provide social integration and identity-building, functioning similarly to other leisure-based communities formed around shared interests such as music or films (ibid.). This aligns with Frindte and Wahl (2001, p. 162) who conducted an interview study to examine biographical information and motives of xenophobic violent offenders who were in jail at the time of the interview. The participants were mostly young, male with a low educational background (Frindte *et al.*, 2001, p. 318). The authors found that the socialisation process of becoming such an offender encompasses different stages, from difficult family situations, problems in school, delinquent behaviour, and early contact to peer groups in which a radicalisation into a xenophobic ideology starts (ibid.). The authors describe it as 'the exacerbation of limitations on positive developmental resources and opportunities' (Frindte and Wahl, 2001, p. 267). The study showed how the interaction of personality development, biographical processes, the socialisation within and outside the family, the job and crises in youth phase can lead to violence, criminality and xenophobia (Frindte *et al.*, 2001, p. 320). The phase of puberty was especially important as young people joined peer groups and were susceptible to Skinhead- and other groups which 'fulfilled the emotional and social needs of the young people and influenced their feelings, thinking and behaviour' (ibid.).

Lützing (2010) conducted a qualitative study focusing on biographies of extremists and terrorists, exploring life circumstances that foster the affiliation with extremist

groups and politically motivated crime. She found that dysfunctional learned or adopted coping strategies within the family lead to further conflicts in the social environment of the interviewees, such as problems in school or social exclusion (ibid.). Miklikowska, Jasko and Kudrnac (2023) showed that 'personal experiences of harassment increase the risk of radicalism' (ibid.), but they point to the need for further research on the role of peer harassment in youth political radicalism.

Moreover, interviewees of Lützing's (2010, p. 67) study reported that a phase of loneliness as well as disorientation contributed to a long-term involvement in the extremist group. An important value had the first extremist group participants joined as this group functioned as 'catalyst' by offering 'interpretation- and prefabricated argumentation patterns that allowed the as yet unsorted, personal attitudes and emotional state to be organized and succinctly articulated' (ibid., p. 70). The study shows that an interest in a specific group was mostly not based on ideological reasons but rather because of the image, appearance or clothing of the receptive group (ibid.). The author also found out that social support, understanding as well as structure were the main motives rather than political topics (ibid., p. 71). An exception were interviewees who were 28 years old or older as clear political aims could be detected (ibid.). For younger persons the motivation to join was more emotional- experience-orientated than politically motivated, though ideological beliefs were later adopted (ibid., pp. 71-73). The group membership offered a sense of belonging and validation (ibid., pp. 75-76).

The role of ideology is a subject of controversial debate. Blee (2017, p. 117) who examined women who joined the Ku Klux Klan found that firm ideological views are not the main driver for joining. Instead, it was the pursuit of friendships, access to better educational opportunities for their children, or a desire to ensure their own safety in a perceived dangerous environment (ibid.). In the academic literature there exist differing views on whether right-wing beliefs drive right-wing activity or emerge as a result of it (Blee and Creasap, 2017, p. 207). Crone (2016, p. 588) claims that common explanations of radicalisation 'overemphasize the role of ideology', neglecting the importance of political, social, and physical dimensions of the process. Moreover, there are examples of individuals who shifted from one extremist ideology to another (e.g. Koehler, 2020). For instance, Horst Mahler who was a former member of the

'Rote Armee Fraktion' (RAF) and became a right-wing extremist. Another example is Julian Fritsch, alias MaKss Damage who used to follow communist views and described himself as Stalinist, but later became a neo-Nazi (Radke and Staud, 2014).

Besides these studies, researchers have also examined groups that emerged as a reaction to migration movements and related grievances. As outlined before, the IM arose from dissatisfaction with migration policies and its consequences fuelled by fears and anger. The group specifically opposes the Islamic religion and migration from predominantly Islamic countries. A similar focus can be observed in groups like Pegida or the English Defence League (EDL). For instance, Winlow Hall and Treadwell (2017) conducted an ethnographic study with individuals who joined the EDL. They describe this group as a 'fringe political group' with 'no system of formal membership' (ibid., pp. 6-7). Its main characteristics stem from 'a dissatisfaction with immigration policies and a desire to mobilise against the spread of what it sees as the hostile alien culture of radical Islamism' (ibid.). Similar to the IM, members of the EDL seek to protect the 'native population' from the perceived negative impacts of migration (ibid., p. 7). In Winlow, Hall and Treadwell's (2017) study, participants denied that they are racist and emphasised their aims of not wanting to become a minority in their own country (p. 96), which aligns with the narrative the IM uses as well. According to the authors:

'The refusal of neoliberal media and academia to talk honestly about our precarious future intensifies this fear and creates space for conspiracy theories, the consolidation of pre-existing prejudices and the construction of various scapegoats' (ibid., p. 51).

The study claims that mainstream political parties have failed to address the economic interests of working-class people, leading to a vacuum that right-wing groups have exploited (Winlow, Hall and Treadwell, 2017, pp. 2-6). Economic hardship has fostered resentment towards immigrants, with the EDL emerging as a voice for those who feel abandoned by traditional politics (ibid., pp. 6-7).

Another form of right-wing organising which is also worth mentioning is the protest movement Pegida - which shows parallels to the IM as well (Vorländer, Herold and

Schäller, 2018). It was established in October 2014 and has its roots in Dresden which is the capital of Saxony (ibid., p. 1). Similar to the IM, the migration flows created a breeding ground for the Pegida's propaganda (Berntzen and Weisskircher, 2016, p. 558) and contributed to a high mobilisation rate (Vorländer, Herold and Schäller, 2018, p. 197). The authors stated that Pegida had evolved into 'a clearly anti-asylum and anti-immigration movement' (ibid.), even though activists have attempted to present themselves as more moderate by publicly rejecting racism and showing partial acceptance of immigration (Berntzen and Weisskircher, 2016, p. 559). However, Pegida has struggled to uphold this self-image (ibid.). According to Berntzen and Weisskircher (2016, p. 556), the movement 'grew into the biggest radical right mobilisation effort in Germany since 1945.' This is in line with Vorländer, Herold and Schäller (2018, p. 1). The people who attended the weekly demonstrations 'were mainly [...] middle-aged men' (ibid.). However, other attendees represented a potpourri of 'married couples, young people, pensioners' as well as members of the 'hooligan or neo-Nazi scene' (ibid.).

Contrary to the assumption that the majority of the people who joined Pegida marches are unemployed and have low socio-economic backgrounds as well as low educational levels, the majority of the Pegida participants were employed and a high rate ('one third') were academics and people with higher educational levels (Vorländer, Herold and Schäller, 2018, pp. 74, 80–81). These results have been repeated in various other empirical studies (e.g. Daphi *et al.*, 2015; Geiges, Marg and Walter, 2015).

When examining the motivations for joining Pegida, the most frequently cited reason was 'a dissatisfaction with politics', followed by reasons relating to 'critics of the media and the public' (Vorländer, Herold and Schäller, 2018, p. 87). Additional reasons included expressing prejudices and resentment towards immigrants and asylum seekers (ibid.). Vorländer, Herold and Schäller (2018, p. 201) claim that Pegida was a 'melting pot for feelings of resentment, attitudes'. They also suggest that Pegida fostered an environment where right-wing extremist offenders felt encouraged (ibid., p. 39) and that the regular Monday marches reinforced a 'feeling of belonging to a community of like-minded people' (ibid., p. 199).

However, what is interesting is that the level of mobilisation in Dresden could not be reached in any other German city or European country (Berntzen and Weisskircher, 2016, p. 558). Pegida's success was largely driven by 'pre-established radical right activists' (ibid., p. 565). In areas like Austria, Pegida members 'were embedded in a broader radical right network and were able to mobilise its "core" for street activism' (ibid., p. 567). The groups observed during the Pegida marches – for instance in Austria – included, among others, student fraternities, neo-Nazi groups, football hooligans such as HOGESA (Hooligans against Salafists), members of the FPÖ or the IM, among others (ibid., pp. 566-567).

Scholars have tried to capture the diversity of right-wing extremism by developing categories for different types. For instance, Willems (1995, p. 169) found four 'types of perpetrators' drawing upon a qualitative analysis of police records as well as the qualitative analysis of criminal sentencing records. The first type is the '[p]olitical motivated, right-wing extremis[t]' (ibid., p. 171). Individuals who are considered to belong to this type take part in parties or groups that have a right-wing extremist background (ibid.). The support of 'right-wing and neo-Nazi thoughts' and its propagation are important aspects (ibid.). It can be granted that the use of violence against the receptive individual, according to their ideology, is accepted. The use of violence is mainly 'racially motivated' but not exclusively directed to 'foreigners' (ibid.). Individuals of this type often achieve good grades in school and obtain good jobs.

The second type of perpetrator is the 'xenophobic youth' who, in comparison to the first type, does not take part in any of the groups previously mentioned and does not hold any beliefs of right-wing political parties (ibid.). Furthermore, young people who belong to this type, are often members of 'the skinhead, hooligan, and fascist subcultures' as well as other youth groups. Characteristics of these individuals are different; they reach from 'hostility to hatred against foreigners' (ibid.). Further characteristics are 'xenophobic prejudices and nationalist mottos' which, however, does not put them on a level with members of right-wing parties (ibid.). In contrast to type one, the use of violence is, among others, driven by 'diffuse feelings of threat, disadvantage, and unequal treatment [...] Racist prejudices and stereotypes, however, can easily follow' (ibid., pp. 171-172). With regard to their personal situation, the young people of this type are often uneducated, unable to obtain a job and have

problematic school and family situations. The third type is the '[c]riminal and marginalized youth[h]' (ibid., p. 172). Individuals belonging to this type are usually older than individuals who belong to types one and two (ibid.). Furthermore, these young people cannot boast about a successful history, neither work-related nor private, and, in many cases, these people have already committed other offences (Willems, 1995, pp. 172–173). The last type, the '[f]ellow-travellers' are individuals who are, in general, from advantaged backgrounds. These young people take part in the 'youth skinhead and fascist groups'. They most enjoyed participating in leisure activities that offered them 'community orientation and group solidarity' (ibid., p. 173). Violence and the commitment of 'xenophobic crimes' are mostly driven by 'group dynamic[s]', for instance, the need to put themselves to the test, witnessed by their friends (ibid.).

Newer approaches have developed categories such as 'the mainstream', '[i]mmigration obsessives', '[t]he unpolitical[ly] correct and proud', '[m]archers' and '[o]rganised resistace' (Radicalisation Awareness Network, 2017, pp. 2–3). Nonetheless, these typologies risk excluding individuals who 'do not fit in', or 'fall between the ideal types and become indistinct' (Bjørgero, 2011, p. 278).

This indicates that there is no standard template for individuals radicalising towards far-right extremism. The endeavour to develop categories to detect these individuals has been discussed controversially due to the high risk of 'producing too many false positives as well as false negatives' (ibid.).

In other words, 'people who fit the stereotype of (potential) terrorists without being a (potential) terrorist; and real terrorists who go undetected because they do not fit the stereotype' (ibid.). This is in line with Neumann (2015, p. 5) who claims that 'there will be hundreds, if not thousands, of people who match the exact same criteria, fit the same profile, adopt the same behaviours, or have gone through similar processes but did *not* become terrorists' (original emphasis). Moreover, the involvement in terrorist activities has been considered 'a highly complex and unstable process' that is influenced by various, 'often unpredictable', factors (Neumann, 2015, p. 6). As a result, no such models or theories can develop criteria that can be used for the prediction of every individual who becomes a terrorist (ibid.). These statements also apply for people who become radicals or extremists as a plethora of factors that could lead a person to become radicalised exists and there is no template of a radical or extremist.

Although, radicalisation cannot be predicted with complete accuracy, there are particular factors whose existence can ‘increase [...] [the] likelihood’ (Neumann, 2015, p. 6) of a person becoming radicalised.

To address this, Bjørge (2011, pp. 278–279) developed a ‘more dynamic approach’, introducing the concept of ‘dimensions’ and ‘continuums’ where individuals can shift along a spectrum throughout their lives or extremist careers. For instance, someone may initially lack extremist views but adopt them through group engagement, or conversely, join a group due to pre-existing ideologies (for further details, see Bjørge 2011).

In sum, the previous paragraphs show the variety of research on different forms of right-wing extremism. While some focused on Skinhead-groups, other explored the Ku Klux Klan, protest movements such as PEGIDA or groups such as the EDL. Moreover, while some looked at male members of a certain age group, other studies differed regarding the composition of the sample. Therefore, even though findings of other studies serve as ‘point[s] of reference’ (Kajta, 2020, p. 136) it is crucial to account for the unique nature of the group under investigation. One cannot disregard the factor of time (i.e. when was the research conducted) and the national context (i.e. where does the group under study operate) (ibid.). For instance, a few years ago the Skinhead scene was explored by various researchers, but over the times the field of right-wing extremism developed, and new groups emerged. Previous studies also had a particular emphasis on right-wing motivated violence (Logvinov, 2017, p. 7), but as presented earlier, the IM is a group that deliberately propagates a non-violent approach, which as scholars point out, remains under-explored in the literature (Pilkington, 2023, p. 4). Orofino and Allchorn (2023) have emphasised the necessity for research into non-violent extremism. The authors point out that the scholarly field tends to describe non-violent extremism as a preliminary stage, ‘assuming that sooner or later all non-violent extremists become terrorists’ (ibid. 2023, p. 3).

This shows that right-wing radicalisation is a complex phenomenon, and it is important to develop a nuanced understanding which includes a differentiated view of different actors within the field of the far-right extremist scene and the motives why people join. Even though former empirical studies offer valuable findings, these findings cannot be directly applied to the IM as the target groups of the studies differ.

The subsequent chapter outlines the methodological approach of this study, including the use of theoretical knowledge.

3 Methodology

In order to provide an outline of the methodological and theoretical framework of this study it is essential to reflect on the ontological and epistemological perceptions that frame this research. As Bryman (2012, p. 5) notes, researchers must be aware of their understanding of the '*relationship between theory and research*' (original emphasis) as differing philosophical assumptions lead to divergent methodologies (Burrell and Morgan, 1979, p. 1). It is therefore important to gain an understanding of the different philosophical assumptions that encompass different perspectives on social reality. A primary focus on methods without consideration of the underlying philosophical assumptions carries the risk of failing to take into account one's own position (Crotty, 1998, p. 3). The researcher's own view of the world will inevitably have an impact on the research process (Bryman, 2012, p. 5), consequently, it is essential to reflect on the researcher's position. This chapter presents the underlying philosophical perspectives of this study, followed by the methodological approach and the methods for collecting and analysing the data.

3.1 Ontological and epistemological considerations

For this study a constructivist approach has been adopted, which postulates that a plurality of realities exists, and that knowledge needs to be interpreted to discover the underlying meanings (Guba, 1990, p. 17). According to Flick (2009, p. 70), constructivism is based on the idea that 'the realities we study are social products of the actors, of interactions, and institutions'.

A constructivist perspective is informed by relativist ontology and subjectivist epistemology (Guba and Lincoln, 1989, pp. 86–87). Ontological assumptions concern 'what we believe constitutes social reality' (Blaikie, 2000, p. 8; Bryman, 2012, p. 6). The researcher must consider whether reality is of an objective nature, existing independently in the world, or of a subjective nature and therefore a 'product of individual cognition' (Burrell and Morgan, 1979, p. 1). The question thus arises as to whether the social phenomenon under study is an outcome of social interchange or whether it exists independently of our involvement (Bryman, 2012, p. 6). This implies

that the researcher needs to have an understanding of the nature of social reality and whether this reality is influenced and constructed by individuals or whether it exists independently of any human action.

Epistemological assumptions refer to the ways a researcher acquires and disseminates knowledge (Burrell and Morgan, 1979, p. 1). Crotty (1998, p. 3) describes this as 'a way of understanding and explaining how we know what we know' (see also Denzin and Lincoln, 2005, p. 183). Consequently, epistemology is defined as 'the theory or science of the method or grounds of knowledge' (Blaikie, 2000, p. 8). It forms a fundamental part of the methodological framework, along with ontology. Epistemology provides guidance on the appropriate methodology for conducting research (Bryman, 2012, p. 6).

In examining these philosophical perspectives, it becomes evident that a range of positions exists. With regard to ontological positions, it is possible to distinguish between objectivism, constructivism, and realism (e.g. Matthews and Ross, 2010, p. 24). Constructivism suggests that social phenomena are 'constructed ideas' that evolve over time as individuals engage in interaction and critical reflection (ibid., p. 25), while objectivism stands in contrast to this position. Burrell and Morgan (1979, p. 3) speak of the 'subjective – objective dimension'. The view of a single reality that is out there would be along the lines of the objectivist approach, whereas the belief in multiple realities which are constructed by individuals is at the heart of the subjectivist approach. Objectivism can be defined as a position that asserts the existence of social phenomena as a reality that is independent of human action (Matthews and Ross, 2010, pp. 24–25).

Epistemological perspectives are discussed between the two opposing poles of positivism and anti-positivism (Burrell and Morgan, 1979, p. 3), such as interpretivism and realism (Matthews and Ross, 2010, p. 26). The tenet of positivism is the existence of a social reality that is distinct from both the researcher and the subjects under study (ibid., p. 27). The positivist position is based on the notion that knowledge is shaped by 'what can be observed and recorded', as opposed to 'subjective understandings' (ibid.). If researchers adopt a positivist stance, they typically seek to gather data for the purpose of testing their assumptions which are derived from existing theories.

Furthermore, the data often consists of large quantitative data and the chosen analysis is of statistical nature (ibid. 2010, p. 27). While positivists view knowledge as 'hard, objective and tangible', anti-positivists understand knowledge as 'personal, subjective and unique' (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007, p. 7).

Anti-positivists dispute the idea of establishing hard facts and generalities and therefore, 'objective knowledge of any kind' (Burrell and Morgan, 1979, p. 5; see also Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007). Instead, researchers need to put an emphasis on 'the subjective experience' of the person under study and how the person 'creates, modifies and interprets the world in which he or she finds himself' (Burrell and Morgan, 1979, p. 3; see also Blaikie, 2000, p. 52; Matthews and Ross, 2010, p. 28). It is therefore important to consider the subjective view of the individual who is engaged with the phenomenon under study. In light of this understanding, it can be argued that every individual possesses a unique reality that may differ to a varying extent from the concept of reality as perceived by other individuals. The objective of the researcher is to gain an understanding of the 'socially constructed meanings' that underpin the 'everyday social world' (Blaikie, 2000, p. 116).

In consideration of the research study, this form of approach (anti-positivist) is suitable to answer the research question. Research relating to the IM has tended to favour the use of methods that did not involve face-to-face interactions. Whilst providing useful data, such approaches do not provide a deeper understanding of why young people join the IM. Only by focusing on the views and experiences of the research participants can the researcher gain an understanding of their individual motives and thus answer her research question. This viewpoint is supported by Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007, p. 11) who criticise the positivist approach for not being able to capture the 'immense complexity of human nature'. Qualitative methods are therefore appropriate for research into phenomena 'about which is little yet known' (Strauss and Corbin, 1990, p. 19; Charmaz, 2006, p. 14).

It is important to note, however, that a distinction must be made between the subjectivity of the participants and position of the researcher within the process. Those employing a constructivist approach must consider their own role in the research process. As Charmaz (2006, p. 187) notes, 'their interpretation of the studied

phenomenon is itself a construction'. Glaser with the assistance of Holton (2004, p. non-paginated) states that '[t]here is always a perception of a perception as the conceptual level rises. We are all stuck with a "human" view of what is going on and hazy concepts and descriptions about it'. Therefore, the fact that the researcher's own perspective acts as a filter in the interpretation of the results was taken into account in the analysis and continuously reflected upon. The following section explores the constructivist paradigm that is applied to this study further and presents the methodological approach on which the research is based.

3.2 Theoretical framework

Blaikie (2000, p. 8) critiques the tendency of researchers not to distinguish between the concepts of methodology and methods, and to use them interchangeably. Methods are 'techniques or procedures used to collect and analyse data', whereas methodology encompasses 'discussions of how research is done, or should be done' as well as a reflexion of the applied methods (ibid.). Methodology addresses the question of 'how new knowledge is generated and justified' (ibid.). The following section will first present the methodology, and subsequently provide an overview of the methods employed.

This study is informed by a modified Constructivist Grounded Theory approach (Charmaz, 2006). Before explaining this methodology with a particular focus on its developments and Charmaz's approach, it needs to be acknowledged that the author of this study did not employ the Grounded Theory in its purest form. One aspect that did not allow its full application was the inability to apply the methods of theoretical sampling and theoretical saturation (see following section) as the researcher planned to interview members of hard-to-reach groups, and to include a diverse range of individuals in her sample. Therefore, she was reliant on her interview participants and the forwarding of her contact details to other individuals. Consequently, this study applied a Grounded Theory approach and adapted it by integrating other methods or replacing specific elements of Grounded Theory with alternative techniques, such as the snowball sampling for the data collection (see Section 3.6.1.3).

This still allowed the research questions to be addressed in a comprehensive and flexible way, leading to deeper insights and understanding. Combining different

analytical approaches and methods has already been advocated by Mayring (2002, p. 133). According to him, researchers should not rigidly follow one method but rather integrate them with each other (ibid.). This would enable the researcher to develop a more 'creative, qualitative-orientated research [which] signifies diversity, not one-sidedness, it means subject-relatedness, not fixation on methods' (ibid.). How the researcher combined the different qualitative methods and why she did not employ the Grounded Theory in its purest form will be addressed in Sections 3.4, 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7. The following section outlines the Grounded Theory and its developments.

3.3 Grounded Theory

Grounded Theory was first developed by Glaser and Strauss (1967, p. 34) with the aim to let 'substantive concepts and hypotheses to emerge first, on their own' and not 'forcing it to fit a theory'. This approach allows the researcher to take a more objective and less theoretically biased perspective, resulting in generating a theory that emerges from the data and is not pre-influenced by existing theoretical concepts (ibid., p. 34). The development of Grounded Theory was a response to the tendency of limiting social science research to a deductive approach of testing theories (ibid., pp. 15 – 16).

Glaser and Strauss developed certain criteria for their research approach. First theoretical sampling as well as theoretical saturation. Theoretical sampling is defined as 'the process of data collection for generating theory' (ibid., p. 45). This process is distinguished by its mutual relationship between data collection and data analysis, which do not follow a linear trajectory (ibid.). The researcher collects data, develops codes which emerge from the data analysis and these codes are edited while collecting more data (ibid.). Therefore, decisions about which data to collect next are driven by the theory that is emerging from the data analysis. The researcher develops codes and categories and refines these categories by looking for data that can confirm, expand, or challenge the emerging theory (ibid.). This sampling strategy continues until no new insights are being generated, a point referred to as theoretical saturation (Glaser and Strauss, 1967, pp. 50, 61). Consequently, the coding process is another key element of Grounded Theory which will be further explained in Section 3.7.

Various researchers have criticised this approach, particularly concerning its handling of theoretical knowledge. Kelle and Kluge (2010, p. 18) use the term 'inductivist misunderstanding' to describe Glaser's and Strauss' methodology, which involves researchers approaching the field as if they were blank slates. This means that a researcher follows a purely inductive approach without acknowledging that researchers bring to their study preconceived notions, theoretical sensitivities, and understandings that influence their interpretation of the data (ibid.).

In their book Glaser and Strauss (1967, p. 3 Fn. 3) addressed some limitations to their approach by saying: 'Of course, the researcher does not approach reality as a tabula rasa. He must have a perspective that will help him see relevant data and abstract significant categories from his scrutiny of the data'.

Glaser and Strauss (1967, p. 46) speak about 'theoretical sensitivity' and acknowledge the necessity for researchers to develop a 'sufficiently' theoretical insight, which enables them to effectively interpret, and construct theories based on the emerging data. The authors posit that a developed theory and its concepts will have points of reference to existing literature that has demonstrated usefulness (Glaser and Strauss, 1967, p. 46). Moreover, they argue that a researcher's theoretical sensitivity is compromised when they rigidly adhere to a single 'preconceived theory' (ibid.). This dogmatic approach would prevent them from objectively considering alternative perspectives or theories – as the researcher 'can no longer "see around" either his pet theory or any other' (ibid.).

It should not go unmentioned that the concept of Grounded Theory has been changed over the years. In later works Glaser and Strauss placed an emphasis on theoretical prior knowledge; but while Glaser continues to adhere to this approach, Strauss and Corbin (1990) developed it in a different direction despite Glaser's explicit disapproval (Heath and Cowley, 2004, p. 142). Glaser advocated a more flexible approach closer to what he and Strauss had developed. On the other hand, Strauss and Corbin advocated for coding techniques and the combination of inductive and deductive elements (see Section 3.7). According to them, a theory does not 'arise like magic out of the page' – instead there needs to be a constant 'interaction between the analyst and the data' for the theory to evolve (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 144). This means that the researcher is 'constantly moving between inductive and deductive thinking'

(Strauss and Corbin, 1990, p. 111), and 'data collection, analysis, and theory stand in reciprocal relationship with each other' (ibid., p. 23).

Furthermore, other researchers have modified the approach over the last few years, for instance Charmaz (2006) who is known for her Constructivist Grounded Theory. Charmaz advocates a more flexible dealing with the Grounded Theory approach. She argues that 'grounded theory methods consist of systematic, yet flexible guidelines for collecting and analysing qualitative data to construct theories from data themselves' (ibid., p. 2). Charmaz (2006, p. 14) describes the Grounded Theory approach with the following metaphor: It is '[l]ike a camera with many lenses, first you view a broad sweep of the landscape. Subsequently, you change your lens several times to bring scenes closer and closer into view'. This understanding of Grounded Theory illustrates that using the theory is an ongoing process in which the research continuously modifies the data collection.

Grounded Theory has been implemented by various researchers, however, Urquhart and Fernandez (2006, p. 459) referred to Lehmann Urquhart and Myers who found out that many researchers did not fully apply the approach. Lehmann, Urquhart and Myers (cited in Urquhart and Fernandez, 2006, p. 459) state that some scholars fully apply the approach, some use it to generate concepts, some use the approach in combination with other research methods and some claim they are using it but do not apply any basic technique of Grounded Theory.

As stated, this study used elements of the Grounded Theory in combination with other research methods, or as Charmaz states, 'grounded theory methods can complement other approaches to qualitative data analysis, rather than stand in opposition to them' (2006, p. 9). The next section outlines how the researcher dealt with theoretical knowledge.

3.4 Using sensitising concepts for dealing with theoretical knowledge

One important discussion revolves around how to deal with theoretical knowledge. Strauss and Corbin (1998, pp. 43–53) state that every researcher has some

background knowledge on the subject of study before entering the field and it is important to acknowledge that. However, it would be crucial to leave a comprehensive literature review to the end as otherwise the researcher would risk being restricted in their creativity due to the literature (Strauss and Corbin, 1990, pp. 50–51; Corbin and Strauss, 2008, pp. 35–53). Kelle and Kluge (2010, p. 21) posit that an exclusive reliance on data to inform theoretical concepts bears the risk of ‘facing a large amount of unstructured data material helplessly’.

To address this issue researchers use sensitising concepts. According to Charmaz (2006, p. 16) sensitising concepts are used to ‘give you initial ideas to pursue and sensitize you to ask particular kinds of questions about your topic.’ They offer ‘a place to *start*, not to *end*’ (ibid. p. 17, original emphasis). In the words of Blumer (1954, p. 7): ‘Whereas definitive concepts provide prescriptions of what to see, sensitizing concepts merely suggest directions along which to look’. Therefore, sensitising concepts help the researcher to shape the research study without reducing the data analysis to certain theories and approaches. However, it provides an orientation for the researcher to avoid drowning in the data. Kelle und Kluge (2010, p. 14) state that it is less about enabling the researcher to formulate precise hypotheses, but rather about theoretically sensitising the researcher to relevant aspects of the data material.

At the beginning of the study the scholarly landscape was notably sparse, with a particular deficit in empirical studies – a circumstance that persists. This is especially evident in the lack of empirical research on the underlying motives for joining the IM, with particular regard to the German branch. Therefore, the use of sensitising concepts was a good way to approach this gap. It offered an orientation where to look at without subsuming the IM and its members under a certain theory. The latter would risk not to capturing all aspects relevant to understanding the motives of the individuals. Therefore, it is important that the concepts used are concrete enough to facilitate theoretical understanding, while remaining abstract enough to allow for broad application (Sitzer, 2009, p. 43). Thus, there is no set theory on which this study will be based on. Instead, the theory / key concepts will emerge gradually during the research study from the data while using existing theories and concepts as sensitising concepts.

3.5 Sensitising concept of this study

The present study is concerned with the question of why individuals join the IM. Accordingly, the objective was to investigate the motivating factors that influence an individual's decision to join the IM. The literature review presents an overview of existing research on the IM, as well as scholarly work in the broader field of (right-wing) radicalisation. Researchers examined the idea of radicalisation as a process with various phases an individual goes through, with multiple factors contributing to such a process. However, as outlined in the literature review, the research field of radicalisation still leaves many questions unanswered. In relation to this study there exists little knowledge on the motives for why people join the IM. In order to examine the research question, a sensitising concept was developed which provided a methodology for approaching the research data with preliminary ideas, without limiting the possibility of allowing new ideas to emerge. Following Sitzer (2009) it was therefore essential that the concepts and theories employed in the study be sufficiently flexible and abstract.

The study's sensitising concept is derived from the Transformative Radicalization Theory proposed by Wilner and Dobouloz (2011). Moreover, the concept is supplemented by incorporating elements from theories of media reception and reception cascades (Horton and Wohl, 1956; Krotz, 2007), Schütz's (1932) Social Action Theory and Havighurst's (1974) Developmental Theory. The Transformative Radicalisation Theory is therefore the overarching sensitising concept, while the others serve as auxiliary concepts. The following sections provide a brief explanation of each theory and how this is used for this study, starting with the Transformative Radicalization Theory.

However, before presenting the sensitising concept of this study in more detail, it is first necessary to clarify the concept of motivation. Given its central role in understanding human behaviour, motivation has been defined and conceptualised in various ways. In motivational psychology, the focus lies on goal-directed human behaviour, aiming to explain the reasons behind specific actions and the processes through which they occur (Heckhausen and Heckhausen, 2010, p. 1). Heckhausen and Heckhausen (2010, pp. 1–2) describe human action as being fundamentally

shaped by two universal principles. First, individuals strive to be effective within their environment. Second, they regulate their behaviour by focusing on certain goals while disengaging from others (ibid.). Such goal-directed behaviour involves the coordinated use of cognitive, emotional, and behavioural skills to achieve desired outcomes or to withdraw from goals that are unattainable or no longer meaningful (ibid.). Central to this perspective is the understanding of motivation as a product of both person and situation. The authors emphasise that 'the current motivation of a person to pursue a particular goal [...] is shaped by person-related and situation-related influences' (ibid., p. 3).

Motivation arises from the interaction between individual and situational influences. Person-related factors include basic human needs and the general 'striving for effectiveness,' that is, the desire to have an impact on one's environment (ibid.). In addition, there are 'enduring individual motive dispositions,' which can be divided into implicit motives - 'emotionally tinged preferences learned in early childhood' - and explicit motives - 'conscious, verbally represented [...] self-images, values, and goals that a person ascribes to themselves' (ibid.). The situation, in turn, affects motivation through incentives, understood as aspects that give an action or its potential outcomes a particular 'inviting character' by 'promising or suggesting something positive or negative' (ibid, pp. 3–5). The authors emphasise that motivation does not depend solely on external conditions but on how an individual subjectively perceives and evaluates a situation (ibid.). Only through this personal interpretation does an action or goal acquire motivational value. In other words, what becomes motivating arises from the individual meaning a person assigns to a given situation (ibid., p. 6).

This perspective provides a useful transition to the sensitising concepts adopted in this study, which also emphasise the development and construction of subjective meaning and perception. The subsequent sections will elaborate on these sensitising concepts and illustrate how they facilitate the exploration of individual motives.

3.5.1 Transformative Radicalization Theory

The rationale for employing this particular theory is based on two key considerations: First, the theory currently lacks substantial empirical support, thus opening up an avenue for further investigation. Second, the understanding of radicalisation as a

learning process. Wilner and Dobouloz (2020, p. 37; 2010, p. 50) view radicalisation as a 'cognitive and emotional' transformation that primes and motivates individuals towards violent actions. Throughout this process, people adopt new beliefs — 'political, social, ideological, and/or religious' — that rationalise and endorse their violent actions (ibid.).

The development of Transformative Learning Theory is largely attributed to Mezirow (1991). Mezirow (2003, p. 212) aimed to understand adult learning and the process by which individuals critically examine their existing beliefs, assumptions, and values, leading to a shift in their worldview. His theory had been applied by Wilner and Dobouloz (2010, p. 33) to the phenomenon of homegrown terrorism, despite the fact that the original theory was not intended for negative forms of transformation (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2020, p. 49). According to Mezirow transformative learning seeks to develop the fundamental awareness and knowledge required for undertaking meaningful social action in a democratic context (2009, p. 96). Wilner and Dubouloz (2020, p. 49) are aware of this circumstance and point to a research gap. The authors argue that applying Transformative Learning Theory to negative transformations, such as in radicalisation, reverses the traditional focus on positive changes (ibid.). They emphasise that this approach needs further theoretical and empirical research to better understand the learning and adaptation processes involved in radicalisation (ibid.).

Wilner and Dobouloz (2010, p. 45) based their approach on the five main concepts as well as stages which Mezirow developed for adult learning. The first one is 'meaning schemes' which encompass specific beliefs, attitudes, and emotional responses that structure how individuals interpret and respond to experiences (ibid.). The second concept, 'meaning perspectives', represents the framework of assumptions that shape how new experiences are absorbed and transformed based on past experiences during interpretation (ibid., Mezirow, 2003, p. 201). Mezirow (2003, p. 201) suggests that these perspectives are largely adopted without critical evaluation during childhood, shaped through socialisation and often influenced by emotionally intense relationships with parents, teachers, or mentors. In line with the literature review, statements about the interviewees' time in, for instance, school or their peer group can provide valuable information for understanding their experienced way into the IM.

Another key concept encompasses '[d]istortions' which are '[m]eaning perspectives that no longer fit the individual's current reality' (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2010, p. 45). This is followed by '[c]ritical [r]eflection'. According to Mezirow (2003, p. 199) '[r]eflection enables us to correct distortions in our beliefs and errors in problem solving'. An individual questions the underlying assumptions and preconceptions that underpin his or her beliefs (ibid.). The fifth key concept involves the '[p]rocess of [t]ransformation' which presents the 'personal change' that either happens 'abrupt[ly] or gradual[ly]' (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2010, p. 45).

According to TR, an individual goes through three stages: 'the trigger phase, the process of changing phase [...] and the outcome phase' (ibid., p. 48). First, a radicalisation process is initiated by significant social, political, and environmental factors (ibid.). According to the authors, individual radicalisation happens in the changing phase as an individual transforms by engaging in personal reflection, gaining new knowledge, and reevaluating their identity (ibid.). The result of this process is the use of violence (ibid.).

As aforementioned, transformation can emerge in two distinct ways, either 'abrupt and focused in time' or as 'a more gradual and cumulative process' (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2011, pp. 421–422). The former can be the result of a triggering experience which instantly disrupts one's existing beliefs and understanding, while the latter is 'the product of many small, successive, and incremental events that trigger change' (ibid.). This transformation results in 'new roles, relationships, and behaviors' (ibid., p. 421). As individuals gain confidence in their new perspectives, they integrate these changes into their daily lives, ultimately adopting a transformed worldview that allows them to overcome the initial crisis and adapt to new circumstances (ibid.).

In relation to the present study, these key concepts and stages offer further lenses – to use Charmaz's metaphor – through which to look at the data. This is in agreement with Wilner and Dobouloz (2020, p. 49) who believe that Transformative Learning Theory 'opens new doors for exploring radicalization at the psycho-cognitive level'. According to them, their framework offers 'a more nuanced appreciation for the cognitive aspects' of a radicalisation process (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2020, p. 37). Even though the authors examine the process of violent radicalisation, these different

phases are employed in this study to understand non-violent radicalisation, which lead people to join the IM.

Based on this framework, this study looked for certain aspects in the narrated paths of the interviewees that contributed to their change of thinking and / or their decision to join. Building on the previous accounts in motivational psychology, motivation is a product of individual and situational factors (see Section 3.5). Therefore, the researcher examined this interplay and the aspects that may have contributed to the way towards the IM. In this context the examination of 'disorienting dilemmas' is of importance and therefore the question of whether the interviewee described certain experiences of their socialisation as a disorienting dilemma which contributed to a change of beliefs and behaviour. Moreover, the researcher examined whether the decision to join the IM was triggered by an event that contributed to an abrupt change or the outcome of a gradual process. Furthermore, following the theory, individuals develop meaning schemes and perspectives which might predispose them to radical ideas, for instance, triggered due to dissatisfaction with political conditions or perceived threats to their identity or society. Therefore, disorienting dilemmas can challenge existing meaning schemes and perspectives. Following motivational psychology, incentives that render certain actions or outcomes particularly attractive or unattractive play an important role in an individual's decision to join a far-right extremist group. For this study, the focus was on how interviewees described their meaning schemes and perspectives and what might have contributed to individuals questioning these or led to a reinforcement of their existing opinions.

3.5.2 'Because' and 'in order to' motives

To gain a more nuanced understanding of the underlying motives and to capture the development of these motives for joining the IM, the researcher applied elements of Schütz's (1932) Social Action Theory to the study. This involves his idea of 'because' and 'in order to' motives, which supplement the phases of transformation. According to Schütz (1932, p. 100), social actions are based on these two types of motives. He believed that an action is social if it is directed towards another person (ibid., p. 162). In this context he speaks of 'intentional experiences of consciousness related to an alter ego [meaning another person]' (ibid.). Schütz summarises the difference between

social behaviour and social action as follows: 'If conscious experiences related to an alter ego arise from spontaneous activity, then, according to our definition, social behaviour would be present, and if this behaviour is planned, it would constitute social action' (1932, p. 163). Such planned behaviour is based on 'in order to-motives'. According to Schütz (1932, pp. 94–95), 'in order to' motives are future-oriented, meaning that certain actions lead to their realisation. Therefore, such motives are related to the ends or purposes that an action is intended to achieve. Because motives are imbedded in past experiences which provide an explanation why an individual acts in a certain way (ibid., pp. 99-100). To illustrate, an individual may join a political party with the intention of contributing to the political discourse. This could be driven by an underlying motive of having learned during their childhood that political activism is important as their parents were involved in it themselves.

To clarify the difference between these motives, Schütz (1932, p. 100) gives the following explanation:

'While the "in-order-to" motive, starting from the plan, explains the constitution of the action, the genuine "because" motive explains the constitution of the plan itself from past experiences'.

In relation to Heckhausen and Heckhausen (see Section 3.5), Schütz' differentiation between 'because' and 'in order to' motives helped the researcher to examine implicit and explicit motives and how these relate to each other. Therefore, this sensitising concept provided the researcher with a further lens through which to look at her data. Combining the motives with TR, one can say that 'because-motives' play a role in the early phases of transformative learning by explaining the reasons and causes for the current situation. The 'in-order-to motives' become central in the later phases as they determine the person's future goals and actions.

To understand the steps of the process of transformation, Mezirow (2009, p. 94) divided the transformation process into ten distinct, consecutive phases which Wilner and Dobouloz applied to their theory as well:

- (1) 'a disorienting dilemma';
- (2) 'self-examination with feelings of fear, anger, guilt or shame';
- (3) 'a critical assessment of assumptions';
- (4) 'recognition that one's discontent and the process of transformation are shared';
- (5) 'exploration of options for new roles, relationships and action';
- (6) 'planning a course of action';
- (7) 'acquiring knowledge and skills for implementing one's plans';
- (8) 'provisional trying of new roles';
- (9) 'building competence and self-confidence in new roles and relationships';
- (10) 'a reintegration into one's life on the basis of conditions dictated by one's new perspective'.

Referring to the two universal principles of human action: striving for effectiveness within one's environment and regulating one's behaviour by focusing on, or disengaging from certain goals (see Section 3.5) – the process of transformative radicalisation can be interpreted as a sequence of motivational adjustments. As the phases of transformation indicate, a disorienting dilemma (Mezirow 2009, p. 94) can trigger such a motivational shift. When an individual realises that their previous patterns of thinking or behaviour no longer lead to desired outcomes, this recognition challenges their sense of effectiveness. Consequently, they may disengage from prior goals and begin to search for new ones that restore a sense of purpose and agency.

Therefore, drawing from Schütz's (1932) theoretical framework and TR, the researcher sought to uncover the individual 'because' motives, which refer to past experiences that explain why an individual acts in a particular way. In the context of this study, this approach involved identifying elements that shed light on the interviewee's decision to affiliate with the IM, as well as examining the factors that contributed to their process of engagement. This includes, for instance, the progression of the interviewees' political ideologies and the factors that shaped them. Additionally, whether the interviewees previously engaged in political activism, thus demonstrating the manifestation of their political convictions in practical endeavours. In addition, the researcher looked at the 'in order to' motives. It can be said that individuals pursue certain 'in order to' motives by joining the IM which are based on 'because' motives.

Therefore, the author looked for answers to the questions of ‘what made interviewees receptive for joining the IM’ – ‘because motives’ and ‘what do interviewees want to achieve by joining the IM’ – ‘in order to motive.’ By undertaking this analysis, it was possible to examine patterns that emerged in the narrations provided.

Moreover, Schütz emphasised the subjective experiences of individuals and the socially constructed nature of reality which is in line with a constructivist approach. Considering this, the researcher placed an emphasis on how individuals presented themselves in the interview. This encompasses the image that an individual projects of him- or herself, as well as their appearance during the interview, including their clothing, mannerisms, and verbal expression i.e., is this a consistent image or are there any contradictions or ambivalences.

3.5.3 Developmental tasks

In addition, elements of Havighurst’s (1974) theory have been considered as well, though not at the beginning. The sensitising concept of this study developed over the time as the data analysis brought out aspects that the researcher had not previously considered (e.g. Charmaz, 2006, p. 17). This applied to the wide age range of the interviewees. The data collection revealed that individuals of different age groups joined the IM (see Section 3.6.2.1). This also led the researcher to rethink her research question as she addressed it to younger people based on their self-presentation. Based on the age range, the question arose whether younger interviewees differed in their motives in comparison to older interviewees.

The researcher considered Havighurst’s perspective to acknowledge the developmental phases an interviewee was in at the time of joining and the interview. According to Havighurst (1974), an individual must solve different tasks at a certain time in life. A developmental task is

‘a task which arises at or about a certain period in the life of the individual, successful achievement of which leads to his happiness and to success with later tasks, while failure leads to unhappiness in the individual, disapproval by society, and difficulty with later tasks’ (ibid., 1974, p. 2 original emphasis).

According to him, these tasks relate to three areas: 'physical maturation', 'cultural pressure of society', and 'personal values and aspirations' (ibid., p. 5). Therefore, every individual is confronted with the fulfilment of these tasks and its interaction with these three sources. Considering the stage of life a person is in helped the researcher to compare the interviewees and their different motives, showing that younger and older members of the IM might have different reasons to join the IM as they were confronted with different developmental tasks.

For instance, a family father might have different motives for joining in comparison to an 18-year-old student. The father might worry about the future and well-being of his family while a younger member might join the IM to find like-minded individuals or because of the opportunity to experience thrill and action. Therefore, looking at the developmental stage and the required developmental tasks an individual must fulfil provides further information to understand the different narrated paths. Interviewees might be talking about problems during school which might be a result of unsolved developmental tasks or difficulties they faced with these tasks, contributing to their decision to join.

3.5.4 Media reception and reception cascades

Since the literature review showed that the use of social media plays a significant role in the dissemination of the IM's content, the researcher included elements of the theories by Horton and Wohl (1956) and Krotz (2007) that focus on media reception and reception cascades.

Krotz (2007, pp. 231–234) developed the 'reception cascade model' and claims that the meaning of a media text is co-created by the audience, influenced not only by the content itself but also by the recipient's cultural and social environment, as well as their everyday experiences and living conditions. According to Krotz (2009, p. 214), communication is not a simple, linear process; it is deeply intertwined with culture and society, making it far more complex than linear models suggest.

The author speaks of a cascade of diverse reception acts unfolding over time and across social contexts (ibid.). Moreover, reception is strongly shaped by the nature of

social relationships with whom one discusses the viewed content, whether these interactions are real or imagined (ibid., p. 234).

Horton and Wohl (1956) coined the concept of '*para-social relationship*' (original emphasis). The authors described that consumers of different forms of media such as TV 'give the illusion to face-to-face relationship with the performer' (ibid., p. 215). According to the authors, public figures can create a sense of intimacy with large audiences of strangers, mimicking personal connections (ibid., p. 216). This perceived familiarity is built through observation of their behaviour and expressions across different contexts, resulting in the fact that it is highly influential and fulfilling for those who engage with it (ibid.). Due to mass communication channels such as television, people who create the content provide a large group of people the opportunity to take part in their public and even personal life (ibid.). Horton and Wohl (1956, p. 216) claim that the recipient develops a sense of personal connection with the creator, believing they have a deeper understanding of their character, values, and motivations than others. The relationship between the content creator and the audience is inherently one-sided, lacking 'effective reciprocity' or the potential for 'mutual development', as the interaction is controlled entirely by the creator (ibid., p. 215). Consequently, the responsibility for creating the illusion of intimacy rests almost entirely on the creator and the content they produce (ibid., p. 217). Horton and Wohl (1956, p. 223) summarise that for most audiences the para-social interaction 'is complementary to normal social life'. They offer a social context where the norms and dynamics of everyday group interactions are reflected and reinforced (ibid.). Therefore, para-social relationships refer to the relationship that individuals form with media personalities or characters, despite the lack of real-life interaction.

Based on these theories, the researcher looked at how interviewees appropriated the content so that they decided to join and explored the role of social media for their decision process. The sensitising concept presented enabled the researcher to gain a theoretical sensitivity. It served as a flexible starting point that has been developed and adapted throughout the research process. Therefore, it gave an orientation and allowed the development of new ideas to emerge from the data. After presenting the methodology of this study, the following section outlines the methods that have been used for data collection as well as analysis.

3.6 Data collection methods

The methods for data collection include semi-structured interviews with members of the IM (see Section 3.6.1) and participant observations of three regional meetings, two Christmas parties of the IM and the observation of one demonstration (see Section 3.6.3). The initial plan was to conduct an interview study exclusively; however, this was modified due to an extended access to the field (see Section 3.6.1). Therefore, the researcher modified her data collection approach and employed a triangulation of methods to the study (e.g. Ayoub, Wallace and Zepeda-Millán, 2014). This approach enabled her to gain a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study, which is compatible with the constructivist approach applied to this study.

While semi-structured interviews provide an opportunity to gather in-depth data, participant observation offers insights into how members of the IM present themselves, as well as how the regional groups are structured and operate. These methods will be presented in more detail in the following sections.

3.6.1 Semi-structured interviews

This study is informed by semi-structured interviews. Interviews as method in qualitative research enable researchers to gain data on ‘the ways in which subjects experience and understand their world’ as it offers ‘a unique access to the lived world of the subjects’ (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2018, p. 10; see also Rahman and Deuchar, 2024, p. 38). To gain information on the inner perspective of individuals who have joined the IM, it is essential to engage in personal communication (e.g. Winlow, Hall and Treadwell, 2017, pp. 5–6). A semi-structured interview is an interview based on a questionnaire that contains mostly open-ended questions, allowing the interviewee to answer in as much detail as he or she feels comfortable (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007, pp. 320–321). Moreover, open-ended questions provide the possibility to investigate complex phenomena that cannot be addressed with ‘simple answers’ (ibid., p. 321).

Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007, p. 321) advocate for ‘a word-based qualitative approach’ if the objective is to gain ‘rich and personal data’. A semi-structured

interview has the character of a conversation which is not structured from beginning to end (Bryman, 2012, p. 470). This offers the researcher the opportunity to guide through the interview and to speak about things which have not been covered in the interview questions before. In addition, it offers the opportunity to ask further questions in case some information needs more explanation.

The decision to conduct face-to-face interviews was a deliberate one. As mentioned in Section 2.4, for instance, Zúquete (2018) and Gibson, Veneti and Voutyras (2024) conducted email interviewees. This type of interview would have been less suitable. This is because email interviews are limited to a certain set of questions. The interviewer does not have the chance to ask additional questions that come up during the interview. One could send the receptive interviewee follow-up questions in a second email. However, this does not impact on the second weakness of emailed questions: The interviewees can formulate their answers in the way they find acceptable while the answers during a face-to face interview come up more spontaneously and authentically. The interviewees have less time to think about the wording of their answers which often leads to more honest and less rehearsed responses. Furthermore, the researcher recognises gesture and facial expressions which helps to put the answers into context.

Jacquet-Vaillant (2023, pp. 92, 107) also criticises the approach of conducting email interviews, describing it as 'imperfect method' due to several limitations (ibid.). First, she argues that the exchange lacks the conversational quality of an interview, which reduces both depth and spontaneity (ibid.). Second, she faced the problem of never receiving an answer to additional questions she sent. Furthermore, Jacquet-Vaillant (2023, p. 107) points out that not all participants were native English speakers, which may have influenced the quality and accuracy of their responses. Finally, she highlights the uncertainty regarding the identity of the respondents, stating that 'we did not know exactly who was behind the keyboard,' as the replies were sent from 'a general address and were signed by the branch' (ibid.). Lamnek and Krell (2016, p. 326) emphasise the 'personal aspect' of a qualitative interview and note that non face-to-face interviews would be of an impersonal, anonymous nature.

In adopting a constructivist perspective, it is not merely the content of a statement that is of relevance, but also the way in which it is expressed. This implies that the way an individual presents themselves generates valuable data as well. Therefore, not only the spoken word was of importance but also the nonverbal communication, such as body language, facial expressions, posture, and gestures. This applies to the entire interview process, including the time before and after the interview. For example, interviewees often appear more relaxed once the recording stopped, offering additional insights. Based on this, face-to-face interviews were the most suitable method for achieving the research objective. This also does justice to the exploratory approach of this study.

Moreover, the researcher decided to interview mostly active members. Pilkington (2023, p. 4) claims that radicalisation is seen as a dynamic process best studied by examining individuals at different stages and social contexts. She criticises the common approach of relying solely on retrospective accounts from those who have already reached the presumed final stage of radicalisation, such as engaging in political violence (ibid.). One important aspect which Winlow, Hall and Treadwell (2017, p. 5) reflect on is that some scholars have criticised the methodology of presenting individual views of people that are categorised as extremists, arguing that this approach may inadvertently provide undue attention and platform to these individuals (see also Ebner, 2020, p. 48). Lepper, Encke and Weiß (2025) provide a recent discussion on the challenges and strategies in dealing with new right-wing movements from a journalistic and academic perspective. Winlow, Hall and Treadwell (2017, p. 5), who conducted an ethnographic study with members of the EDL (see Section 2.7.2), refer to their research and state:

[s]ome will no doubt decline to pick up this book, convinced that we know as much as we need to know about these retrograde fascists. Some will claim that writing about them gives them the attention, publicity and credibility they don't deserve. But those who simply oppose what they do not understand are running away from the political reality of our times. If social scientists are to assist in the task of making sense of that reality, we can't simply praise the nice people and condemn the bad. We have to go deeper. We have to expose ourselves to challenging topics, and we have to be honest about what we find' (ibid.).

Throughout the research process, the researcher was required to critically reflect on the varying statements provided by the interviewees, recognising the inherent challenge of maintaining an unbiased interpretation. The knowledge that the IM is classified as right-wing extremist introduces subconscious biases, making it difficult to avoid interpreting certain statements through a predetermined lens. However, as previously presented, one's own personal view cannot be completely disregarded, but critical reflection on it is of great importance.

This allowed the researcher to examine different aspects that interviewees found relevant for their decision to join the IM. This is particularly important as radicalisation research showed that the interplay of different risk and protective factors can facilitate the radicalisation of an individual (Beelmann, 2020). Therefore, it is important to understand how certain aspects are interrelated. This is in agreement with Schröder et al. (2022, pp. 178–179) who point out that while surveys measuring right-wing attitudes provide valuable insights into how prevalent these attitudes are, they fall short of revealing the complex interplay of underlying factors. This is where qualitative research becomes essential – it not only identifies what attitudes exist but also explores how various factors are interconnected. Qualitative approaches allow for a more nuanced understanding of the dynamics at play, which cannot be fully captured by quantitative methods alone.

The qualitative questionnaire encompasses a range of main topics and is primarily composed of open-ended questions for each topic. Given the lack of research on the IM, the researcher included questions about both individual motivations and the organisational structure of the IM. This was due to the necessity of gaining an understanding of, or further insight into, the IM in order to better contextualise statements about the interviewee's individual motivations. However, as previously stated, the author acquired knowledge about specific topics that were relevant to her research question during the data collection process, and as a result, additional or modified questions were incorporated into the study. Accordingly, the researcher utilised the questionnaire as a point of reference during the interview. A letter of consent and a participant information sheet were developed and provided to the participants prior to the interview.

3.6.1.1 Steps before starting the data collection

The research study was granted ethical approval by the School of Education Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland in October 2018. The application for ethical approval marked the starting point of the data collection process. As Rahman and Deuchar (2024, p. 4) argue, 'ethical responsibility' is essential at every stage of the research process. In retrospect, applying for ethical approval was an important obligation as the process helped the researcher to think about the research in a more comprehensive way. This included thinking critically about the ethical and practical challenges that might accompany the study and potential ways to overcome them. Rahman and Deuchar (2024, p. 5) emphasise the importance of 'reflexivity,' which requires researchers to 'take responsibility for one's position within the study and the consequences that their inputs may have'.

However, even a thorough examination of the ethical and practical challenges cannot prevent encountering new obstacles along the way that need to be dealt with. Therefore, the author had repeatedly reflected on and adapted her own research steps. The next section outlines some of the challenges she faced.

3.6.1.2 Access to the field

'Access is what matters' states Ebner (2020, p. 283), emphasising the importance of obtaining valuable data. According to her, every researcher 'knows the hassle' (ibid.). Gaining access to the subjects under study has always been an important and often challenging task within a research project. This challenge becomes even harder when researching potentially sensitive topics or hard-to-reach groups. Blee and Yates (2015, p. 129) report on the struggles researchers can face when they want to speak to conservative and far-right groups. They state that researchers often experience reluctance towards them because potential participants may be concerned with being portrayed 'in a negative light' when talking to them (ibid.). For the study, this underscores the importance of the first impression the researcher makes on participants, as their willingness to take part often depended on it. To address this, being transparent about the researcher's role as a PhD student and the research goals was essential in building trust and encouraging participation.

After receiving ethical approval, the researcher started the data collection by contacting potential participants through social media. The use of social media platforms carries two inherent risks. Firstly, it is not possible to distinguish between genuine and fictitious profiles. Secondly, there is no guarantee that the person with whom one is communicating is who they claim to be. Various researchers have reflected on the safety risks involved when doing research with hard-to-reach groups, resulting in choosing different methods which do not include face-to-face interactions. Mudde (2014, p. 1) states that researchers struggle to 'reach and study' far-right extremists, as they are considered to be 'often hostile and violent'. Blee (1998, p. 388) who conducted face-to-face interviews (see Section 2.7.2) referred to her fieldwork and wrote: 'For me, fear was ever-present'. Mudde (2024, p. 142) speaks of his 'fair share of (anonymous) threats' as a consequence of his research on the far right. Given these considerations, a two-step approach has been proposed as a way to reduce the risk of sensitive information being disseminated uncontrollably on social media, for example, by individuals who may not approve of the researcher's study. Based on this, the researcher chose to first contact potential participants with a general message that provided just rudimentary information without including detailed contact information. Once people expressed their interest in participating, the researcher followed up with additional information.

The IM has a contact form for each state in Germany which the researcher used for her first requests. She drafted a message that she sent to each of the 16 regional groups. Some states (Berlin, Bavaria, Saxony, Baden-Württemberg) have more than one group in operation, so the researcher contacted in total 24 groups. Nevertheless, the response rate to the interview requests remained disappointingly low. A single reply was received from the head of one regional group. He indicated that the researcher could either send him the questions or arrange to meet with him in person on the university campus where he is currently enrolled.

After four months, the author sent a repeated follow-up request to all regional groups except the one that had already responded. Two weeks later, a female regional leader replied, expressing regret that she and her colleagues could not participate due to their busy schedules as they carry out their activism alongside their daily life. She acknowledged the researcher's interest in the IM and wished her well. A week later,

another regional leader offered an interview on the condition of a 60 Euro donation per interview for their 'good' cause.

It was clear to the researcher that she is not going to donate any money in exchange for an interview. There are three underlying factors contributing to this decision: firstly, the author had no intention of aligning herself with the organisation's objectives. Secondly, to provide financial support, there is a possibility that the organisation may seek to leverage this for its own advantage. Such an action could be perceived as an attempt to discredit her credibility. Thirdly, there are ethical and scientific considerations that conflict with this proposal, for example in terms of objectivity.

This scenario exemplifies the complex interplay between access, ethics, and methodological integrity in qualitative research, particularly when studying hard-to-reach groups. It underscores the necessity for researchers to navigate potential conflicts of interest and maintain scientific rigor while negotiating field access (Deuchar, 2016).

In addition to the contact form on the homepage, the researcher intended to contact the IM members identified on the organisation's official website. In 2018, Facebook removed the official account and numerous members' accounts due to the presence of far-right extremist content. Based on this, the researcher initiated contact with the activists referenced on the organisation's website via Facebook. The brief message that the researcher utilised for contacting them via the contact form has been slightly modified and employed in these contact requests as well.

Given the challenges associated with accessing active members, the researcher contacted an exit program to explore the feasibility of conducting interviews with people who had initially joined the group but decided to distance themselves from it. Exit organisations typically provide assistance to individuals who are willing to disassociate themselves from right-wing extremist groups. Her inquiries were declined on the grounds that, on the one hand, there were few individuals leaving the IM, and of the few who did, none were willing to participate in an interview. One exit program was able to establish contact between someone who left the IM and herself. She was informed that the exit program is in touch with two former members of the IM, a female

and a male. The female former member declined to participate in an interview, citing a desire to refrain from discussing her involvement with the IM. The male former member expressed interest in participating in the research study. The fact that two individuals have expressed a desire to leave the group is particularly noteworthy, as it provides further insight into the structure of the IM. This is based on the assumption that the exit from the IM might be easier in comparison to other far-right groups. However, if these former members asked for help to leave the group, there must be something which makes it difficult for them to do so by themselves.

In conclusion, the researcher encountered significant challenges in gaining access to the field, which required a large time investment and different approaches for establishing contact. However, she was able to gain access to the field through two regional leaders. Consequently, the virtual contacts resulted in the initial personal contacts with members of the IM, marking the start of data collection through snowball sampling.

3.6.1.3 Snowball sampling

The snowball sampling is a method to gain access to research subjects. According to Vogt (2005, p. 300) this technique can be described as follows: '[o]ne subject gives the researcher the name of another subject, who in turn provides the name of a third, and so on'. Thus, it was anticipated that the contact persons will put the researcher in contact with other members of the movement. One of the limitations with this technique is that the contact persons might put the researcher in contact with members who joined the IM for similar reasons/motivations as they did, rather than those who joined for multiple reasons. This could potentially distort the results.

As previously stated, the application of the Grounded Theory in its purest form was not feasible. One aspect that did not allow its full application was the inability to apply the methods of theoretical sampling and theoretical saturation. In analysing the interviews, the researcher sought to include a diverse range of individuals in her sample. However, she was reliant on her interview participants and the forwarding of her contact details to other individuals. Overall, the opportunity to conduct interviews with women was limited. Nevertheless, the researcher was able to conduct interviews

with individuals who differed in terms of socio-demographic data, as well as the length of membership (see Section 3.6.2.5).

3.6.1.4 *Conducting interviews*

Conducting interviews involves more than just the interview itself, when the recording device is running, and the researcher asks questions. Rather, it encompasses the entire process, including before and after the interview, which can influence the quality of the interview. To enhance the quality of the interview, it is essential to consider several factors before, during, and after a researcher conducts an interview.

Given the inherently staged nature of an interview, it is crucial to establish a pleasant atmosphere that encourages the interviewee to feel comfortable to participate in the interview (e.g. Brinkmann and Kvale, 2018, p. 62). Before the receptive interview took place, the researcher asked each of her participants for a location to meet so that the interviewee could choose a place at which he or she wanted the interview to take place. A number of interviewees selected a location that was their usual meeting place, while others chose a different place, for instance, a public café. One interviewee selected the premises of his business as the location for the interview. By asking the interviewees to select the location for the interview, the researcher provided them with the opportunity to choose a setting with which they were already familiar and/or in which they felt comfortable.

Moreover, the author placed an emphasis on her interactions with the participants before the recording started. As Brinkmann and Kvale (2018, p. 62) highlight '[t]he first minutes of an interview are decisive' as interviewees need to develop a sense of trust in the interviewer before feeling comfortable enough to share their experiences and emotions openly with 'a stranger'. According to them, a '*briefing*' and '*debriefing*' is important (ibid., original emphasis). Based on this, the researcher placed an emphasis on small talk before the interview, so the interviewees had the possibility to get to know her a little bit before the recording started. She was also able to get to know most of her interviewees days or weeks before the actual interview. With regard to those she interviewed on the same day she met them, the researcher ensured there was time for small talk which probably helped some of the interviewees to feel more comfortable. It was often the case that the researcher met the interviewee at an agreed

meeting place from which they walked to the interview location. This provided time for casual conversation.

However, some interviewees seemed nervous during the interviews which led to challenging situations for the researcher: For instance, one situation made the author feel uncomfortable when one interviewee was sitting next to her and started to lean backwards while he was sitting on his chair. By doing this, he put his foot on a metal bracket which was attached under the seating surface of the researcher's chair. It felt like he was crossing the normal degree of distance. However, the researcher had the feeling that this might be a displacement behaviour as he was quite nervous at the beginning of and during the interview.

However, not all interviewees were nervous; some of them were already experienced in giving interviews, so the first contact was more relaxed. Therefore, it was a crucial task for the researcher to observe the situation and adapt to it in order to make the interviewees feel more comfortable.

Three aspects that occurred during data collection are noteworthy. One was the official classification of the IM as far-right extremist by the German Federal Office for the Protection of the Constitution. The researcher expected some of the interviewees to withdraw from the participation in the study as a result. Fortunately, the classification of the IM had no negative effect on the planned interviews and participant observations. The second aspect was that one interview turned out to be a group interview which was not originally planned but emerged from the situation. The researcher scheduled an interview with a regional leader and when she arrived at the meeting point, he was sitting on a bench in front of a bar with three other persons who he brought along as he assumed that the researcher was interested in meeting more members. This was a situation where the researcher distanced herself from her planned method and integrated a group interview in her sample. Additional assessments with the interviewees who participated in a group interview were scheduled, to conduct one-on-one interviews with each of them. This is due to two factors. First, by conducting one-on-one interviews, the researcher was able to use the same method, which is important when it comes to comparing the data. Secondly, one of the interviewees was quite dominant in the group interview, therefore it is possible that the other interviewees did not answer the questions in the length they would have done if they had been interviewed separately. However, she was only able

to conduct two additional assessments because one interviewee had left the IM shortly after the interview, and another interviewee called in sick.

Blaikie (2000, p. 243) highlights that collecting qualitative data can be 'messy and unpredictable' or, as Bryman (2012, p. 15) phrases it, 'social research is often less smooth than the accounts of the research process you read in books' (p. 15). The methods employed in this study were also modified due to unanticipated data collection opportunities as well as the circumstance that planned methods could not be put in place as planned.

The third aspect was the Covid-19 pandemic which had an influence on scheduled interviews and further participant observations as they were not feasible anymore. However, the researcher was able to conduct a sufficient number of interviews as well as data from the participant observations before the lockdown was put in place. This is based on the fact that the research study follows a qualitative approach and therefore does not seek statistical validity but aims at generating in-depth insights. A small sample size enables the researcher to provide such results in contrast to large sample size, which offer a basis for further research (e.g. Pilkington, 2023, pp. 5–6). The following section gives an overview of the interview data sample.

3.6.2 Overview of the interview data sample

The data sample was derived from thirteen interviews with fourteen interviewees. As aforementioned, one of the interviews was a group interview, followed by additional one-on-one interviews. The researcher interviewed thirteen members of the IM and one former member. Of the thirteen people, two were female. She interviewed one female member one-on-one and the other female during a group interview. The shortest interview was 54 minutes and the longest was two hours and 16 minutes long. In total, the researcher conducted 16 hours and 34 minutes of interview data. The following sections present the distribution in terms of the sociodemographic data: age, gender, the living environment, education status as well as marital status. Moreover, what the researcher found was that interviewees had been members for different durations and to varying extent, which will be looked at as well.

3.6.2.1 Age structure and gender

The researcher interviewed 14 interviewees and, as stated, two of them female. The age range went from 18 to 42. The average age was 27,6 years. Two of the interviewees were under 20, three interviewees were between 21 to 22 years old, five interviewees were between 27 and 29 years old, three interviewees were between 34 and 37 years old and one interviewee was 42 years old.

Following Havighurst (1974), the interviewees were in three different developmental age groups: adolescence (n = 5), early adulthood (n = 5), and middle age (n= 4) at the time of the interview.

Adolescence 12-22 y.o.	Early adulthood 23-30 years	Middle age 31-50 years
2x 18 years (female, male), 1x 21 years 2x 22 years (female, male) (n = 5)	3x 27 years 1x 28 years 1x 29 years (n = 5)	1x 34 years 1x 35 years 1x 37 years 1x 42 years (n = 4)

3.6.2.2 Living environment

The interviewees were from five different federal states. To protect anonymity, specific cities are not disclosed and the researcher distinguished between West and East of Germany in her study. One interviewee was studying abroad, all other interviewees had their residence in the cities where the interviews took place.

3.6.2.3 Education and employment

Looking at the distribution in terms of the educational level, half of the interviewees have completed an academic degree or were in the process of completing one. The subjects of the courses of studies differed - from Media Informatics, Political Science and History to Economics, Education, Mathematics, and Civil Engineering. One of them even did a PhD at the time of the interview.

The other half of interviewees undertook job trainings within the fields of car mechanic, insurances, logistics, crafts, hairdressing, physiotherapy, and transport. One of the interviewees even set up his own business.

Academics / Studies	Non academics / Type of job
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Media Informatics, - Political Science, - History, - Economics, - Education, - Mathematics, - Civil Engineering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - car mechanic, - insurances, - logistics, - crafts, - hairdressing, - physiotherapy, - transport

Based on this, the members of the IM who the researcher interviewed were engaging in different kinds of jobs and areas of studies. Therefore, not only a range of age groups could be observed but also a range of educational backgrounds.

3.6.2.4 *Marital status*

Looking at the relationship status, the following picture emerges: Five of the interviewees were in a relationship during the time of the interview. The researcher interviewed two of them who were in a relationship with each other. Three of the interviewees were married. One interviewee was divorced, and two interviewees were single. Three of the interviewees had children. No data relating to the relationship status was available for three interviewees.

3.6.2.5 *Length of membership and age at the time of joining*

Against the backdrop of sociodemographic diversity, another variety was found in the data sample: people who were new to the IM – from a few weeks up to six months and people who had already been members for at least a year. The author categorised them as ‘newcomers’ and ‘established ones’ and differentiated between the ones who joined less than a year ago and the ones who joined at least a year ago. This differentiation was based on the assumption that one year is mostly enough time to get to know a group and its structure whereas people who have been just for a few weeks or months in the IM might not have had the chance to get to know it that well.

Therefore, a newcomer is someone, as the name suggests, who joined the IM just recently, meaning less than a year ago. An established member is someone who joined the movement more than one year ago. In total the researcher interviewed eight newcomers and six established members.

	Age of the participant at the time of the interview	Age of the participant at the time of joining	Lengths of membership (Approximately)
Newcomer	2x 18 years	2x 18 years	6 months
	1x 22 years	1x 22 years	6 months
	1x 28 years	1x 28 years	3 months
	1x 29 years	1x 29 years	2 months
	1x 35 years	1x 35 years	3-4 weeks
	1x 34 years	1x 34 years	3 months
	1x 37 years	1x 37 years	4 months
Established	1x 21 years	1x 19 years	2 ½ years
	1x 22 years	1x 15 years	Almost 8 years
	3x 27 years	1x 25 years 1x 24 years 1x 22 years	1 ½ years 3 years 5 years
	1x 42 years	1x 38 years	4 years

Looking at the distribution of newcomers and established ones it shows that most interviewees joined the IM in their adolescence and early adulthood. Fewer interviewees joined the IM in their middle age, consisting of three newcomers and one established one.

An interesting finding is that three of the older members were new to the IM at the time of the interview and even the older established member joined the group when he was middle aged (38 y.o.). Based on the self-representation of the IM as a youth movement one would assume that the older members would have been in the IM for a longer time and had joined it in their adolescence or early adulthood. As mentioned in the context of the sensitising concept, the age difference led to the question of whether the younger ones and older ones differ in terms of their motives.

3.6.3 Participant observation

In addition to the interviews, this study is informed by data gathered through participant observation. According to Marshall and Rossman (2011, p. 140) participant observations 'demands firsthand involvement in the social world chosen for study'. In this context, the researcher assumes the role of both 'observer' and 'participant', although the extent of the roles can vary (ibid.).

The researcher was able to attend three regional meetings (first meeting n = 8; second meeting n = 5; third meeting n = 7), two Christmas parties (approximately: West of Germany: n = 15; East of Germany: n = 24) and one demonstration – the so-called summer festival in Halle on the 20.07.2019. Of the individuals who had been interviewed, twelve also participated in the meetings with varying levels of attendance. Apart from the interviewees, the researcher encountered approximately 29 other people. Given the circumstance that she observed the behaviour and interaction of the interviewees in these meetings, she was not able to collect sociodemographic data of all the participants. However, through her observations and conversations with some of them, she identified similarities to her interviewees. The range of sociodemographic data was reflected in the meetings as well. For instance, at one Christmas party the researcher met at least nine of 24 participants of the party who were older than 25 years old, six of them were even older than 35 years. The youngest participant was 18 years old. During the regional meetings as well as during the Christmas parties she met at least six more persons who had children. In terms of employment a similar distribution in comparison to the interviewees can be shown. The forms of employment went from a university professor, economic students to security staff. Therefore, not only a range of age groups could be observed but also a range of educational backgrounds.

Participating in regional meetings as well as in Christmas parties offered an invaluable perspective on the organisational structure and functioning of the group (e.g. Flick, 2009, p. 222).

However, given that the researcher cannot observe every detail of the meetings, since every person has a selective perception, her aim was to examine the structure and organisation of the meetings, including its level of professionalism, the number of participants, and the topics discussed.

Based on a statement from one interviewee, who mentioned that he did not know the regional group in the West of Germany or its members interviewed by the researcher, the question arises as to how these groups differ from one another and what influence these differences might have on their membership.

Additionally, this raises the issue of whether regional variations impact group dynamics, recruitment strategies, or levels of engagement. Moreover, the researcher observed the interactions between the participants to gain further impressions how interviewees express themselves in the group.

In each meeting, all attendees were made aware that the author was present for research purposes.

Shortly, after every meeting the researcher had joined, she wrote down the minutes in order to put as much memory as possible into writing. Emerson et. al. (2011, p. 1) emphasise the role of fieldnotes in ethnographic fieldwork. According to them, ethnographic fieldwork includes 'firsthand participation in some initially unfamiliar social world and the production of written accounts of that world that draw upon such participation' (ibid.). These written accounts or fieldnotes are inherently interpretive, as scholars 'cannot take in everything' and must filter observations through their own perspective (ibid., p. 4). Therefore, 'there is no one "natural" or "correct" way to write about what one observes' (ibid., p. 6).

Rather than offering a direct reflection of the participants' perspectives, they convey the events and meanings as filtered through the ethnographer's own viewpoint and understanding (ibid.). However, timing is crucial – 'Writing fieldnotes *immediately* after leaving the setting produces fresher, more detailed recollections that harness the ethnographer's involvement with [...] the day's events' (ibid., p. 49 original emphasis). Delaying the process risks losing detail, as memories fade and observations become overly summarised (ibid.).

The researcher of this study took a small book to every meeting and sometimes used a toilet break to write down some observations. Moreover, since she often had long drives to the locations, she used her phone to dictate some of her observations which she later wrote down and added to.

In terms of the demonstration, the original plan was to participate in the summer festival of the IM. However, due to the large presence of police and counterdemonstrations, as well as incidents of property damage (burning cars) and physical violence between some members of the IM and left-wing activists, the researcher was unable to reach the activists. Instead, she remained in contact with some of them via mobile phone and was only able to observe the event from a distance. However, even though she could not join directly, observing the event and how the activists expressed themselves during the event and dealt with the large counterdemonstrators offered her valuable insights, which she also discussed with some of her interviewees afterwards. Therefore, the data she collected during these meetings encompasses unique insights into the group under study and represents a supplementary data basis for the interview data.

3.7 Data analysis methods

In preparation for the data analysis, the interviews were transcribed and listened to a second time to ensure the accuracy of the transcripts and to verify that all data was anonymised. The edited transcripts were uploaded to the qualitative data analysis software MaxQDA where the data had been analysed. A coding scheme based on an inductive-deductive process was developed, meaning the process of coding did not follow a linear process but one which goes back and forth. New codes were developed based on additional interview data or existing codes were renamed, deleted, or merged with other codes.

Following Grounded Theory, the aim of the study was not to prove an 'a priori' hypothesis (see Section 3.3) but exploring the motives of interviewees that led them to join the IM. For the data analysis the researcher employed the coding techniques by Charmaz who distinguishes between 'initial and focused coding' (2006, p. 42). Charmaz claims that '[t]hrough coding, you define what is happening in the data and begin to grapple with what it means'. (2006, p. 46).

In the initial phase, researchers explore data and 'remain open to all possible theoretical directions' (p. 46). In the focused phase, the most significant categories are identified and developed (ibid.).

In the initial phase, numerous single codes were developed based on close readings of the transcripts. For instance, the researcher identified several statements referring to the time participants dedicated to the IM, the challenge of balancing family life and activism, and the specific forms of activities they were involved in. These aspects were initially coded as separate single codes.

During the focused coding phase, these codes were then grouped under a broader, more abstract category - level of engagement. This key category emerged through the data analysis and served to cluster various related codes. It captured the different intensities and forms of participation within the IM. In a subsequent step, this categorisation enabled the researcher to examine each level of engagement in relation to other key categories.

As outlined in Section 3.5 the researcher used sensitising concepts which helped her to guide the analysis, without narrowing her focus to fixed theoretical frameworks. For instance, the researcher looked for influences that contributed to the interviewees' decision to join the IM. In this context, Schütz's distinction between 'because' and 'in order to' motives was used to identify factors that made individuals receptive to the IM, as well as their reasons for joining. Another example is the analysis of key experiences. Following TR, which suggests that individuals undergo a change process through disorienting dilemmas, the researcher examined the interviewees' narratives for moments that may have played a significant role in such processes.

Opposed to the original form of Grounded Theory (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 146), where the aim is the development of one core category that should have the 'ability to pull the other categories together to form an explanatory whole', Charmaz (2006, p. 132) is of the opinion that several key categories (see Chapter 5) can be the result of an analysis. According to her, a constructivist approach enables researchers to examine 'the complexities of particular worlds, views, and actions' (ibid.).

This chapter outlined the methodological approach of this study. It explained the theoretical framework and described how the researcher used theoretical knowledge through a developed sensitising concept. Furthermore, the employed methods were discussed, and an overview of the data sample was provided. The next chapter presents the findings of the data analysis.

4 Findings

This study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of why individuals join the IM based on semi-structured interviews and participant observations. The state of empirical research on the motives of individuals joining the IM, particularly the German IM, was very limited which revealed the research gap addressed in this study. Based on the overarching sensitising concept which follows the idea of radicalisation as a learning process (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2020) and the auxiliary concepts (see Section 3.5), the researcher examined the motives and influencing factors that interviewees described as relevant for their decision to join the IM. This includes the exploration of whether specific triggers or key experiences influenced the interviewees' decision-making process.

As previously outlined, it is important to acknowledge that the narratives are told by the individuals themselves, so the researcher cannot know whether their pathway towards the IM really happened as they described it. However, it is important to emphasise that such verification is not the primary focus of this study; instead, it sought to understand the individual motivations to join the IM as the interviewees constructed them. Therefore, it was examined how each interviewee articulated their motives and narrated specific facets of their life stories. To cite Presser and Sandberg (2019, p. 133,) 'the *story*, and not the *factual information it provides*, is the phenomenon of interest' (original emphasis). It is therefore irrelevant whether the story given by the interviewees is accurate or not (Sandberg, 2010, p. 448). Rather it is important to look for answers to the question, '[w]hat do the informant's statements reveal about his feelings and perceptions and what inferences can be made from them about the actual environment or events he has experienced?' (Dean and Whyte, 1958, p. 38).

The following sections present the results of the data analysis, which are organised into five main topics:

- 1) Level of engagement,
- 2) Reason-based and goal-orientated motives,
- 3) Appropriation of ideological frames,
- 4) Attractiveness of the IM and
- 5) Regional structure.

4.1 Level of engagement

One finding that emerged from the analysis was that interviewees engaged to a varying extent within the IM. Not all interviewees attached the same importance to the IM which resulted in different manifestations of engagement based on two distinguishing characteristics – time and action. Interviewees differed in terms of the amount of time they spent on the IM as well as in the form how they engaged in the IM. They displayed either a high, moderate or low level of engagement. These different manifestations were derived qualitatively and represent an analytical distinction that illustrates the variance between respondents and facilitates comparison.

It is noteworthy that one former member was interviewed, and one member who left the movement a few weeks after the interview. They were categorised by the level of engagement they showed during their time as members, with the reasons for their exit also being explored. The following sections provide an explanation of the criteria before analysing them in the next sections.

Time

Three aspects were taken into account when examining the criterion ‘time’:

- Firstly, the amount of time each interviewee reported spending on the IM. Some interviewees indicated that they spent almost no time on the IM, apart from participating in regular meetings, while others stated that they were dealing with the IM every day for several hours.
- Secondly, the priority of the IM, which is closely related to the first aspect. Does someone place a high priority on the IM and accordingly, spend a lot of their free time on their involvement in the IM, or does someone place the IM lower on their list of priorities and accordingly, spend less time on the IM.
- The third aspect is the extent to which individuals perceive the time they invest in the IM as a sacrifice. For instance, some interviewees said that the IM fits into their daily schedule and that they do not miss out on anything, while others used their free time to work on the aims of the IM, which they would otherwise have spent differently.

Action

The criterion 'action' encompasses the form of engagement someone shows in the IM.

- Firstly, the extent of responsibility someone assumes for the IM. Some interviewees actively took on responsibility for a role or a task to contribute to the IM's progress regardless of personal benefit. Others, however, engaged more passively - consuming social media content and attending meetings without assuming responsibilities.
- Secondly, the alignment between the verbalised priority and the actual effort invested. While some attached great importance to the IM, their actions did not always reflect this commitment, showing significantly less effort compared to highly involved members. Therefore, it could be the case that an interviewee indicated that he or she spent a lot of time on the IM, but only to the extent that it fitted into his or her personal life and did not conflict with any other responsibilities.
- Third, the willingness to take risks. Some interviewees were willing to take risks, while others tried actively to avoid those. For instance, some openly identified as members despite potential career consequences, while others actively sought to avoid such risks.

Against the background of the question of why individuals join the IM, the question arose why some interviewees showed a varying level of engagement. Therefore, the researcher first examined these levels and then related them to the individual motives.

4.1.1 'Going the extra mile' – high level of engagement

Interviewees who showed high levels of engagement had in common that they placed a high priority on their involvement in the IM. This resulted in them spending a lot of their free time working on the group's aims. The empirical results have shown that they would have otherwise spent that time, for instance, with their family or building up a professional career, as will be illustrated in the following paragraphs. However, this was a necessary sacrifice for them in order to contribute to the IM's development. In addition, they all took responsibility for a specific role or task, ranging from organising, planning and carrying out actions to fulfilling a leadership position to actively contributing to the IM's progress. Moreover, these interviewees described their

willingness to take personal risks, for instance, getting fired from their job or limiting their career opportunities because of their involvement in the IM.

This can be illustrated by Lars⁷, who described himself as an activist, a Youtuber, and someone in a leadership position⁸. According to him, he is *'the face to the outside world'* and *'responsible for press enquiries and external communication'* as well as for *'structural'* and *'youth work'*. The time he spends for the IM would differ from five up to 30 hours per week. Besides creating videos, he organises regional meetings and events, meets people who can provide some structural support such as meeting rooms or legal support for activists. Lars was one of the established activists, which became evident during the first encounter with him. He approached the researcher in a relaxed manner, showing no signs of nervousness – a behaviour that, considering his leadership role, highlighted his experience interacting with the *'outside world'*.

Lars has a family of his own and emphasised its priority, which is congruent with the importance of family written on the IM's website (Identitäre Bewegung Deutschland e.V., 2024):

'Family comes first, [...] that's the most important thing, but it doesn't clash with the IM either, for me it's a consistent continuation [...] that when I speak of a nation, then family also has a high value for me'.

Nevertheless, he devotes time to the IM alongside his family responsibilities, even though he is aware that it means compromising his professional career: *'in the time that I am doing IM, I could also be working on my own company and be economically successful'*. He admits interest in other causes, such as environmental protection, but wouldn't dedicate as much time to them as he does to the IM for free. Consequently, Lars prioritised his involvement in the IM over his work:

⁷ All names are pseudonyms to protect the identity of the interviewees. In Lars's case, he even stated that he would be fine with his real name being used; however, the researcher chose to anonymise all participants.

⁸ To preserve anonymity, the researcher will refer to individuals in leadership positions without distinguishing between leaders of regional or local groups, or those responsible for specific areas within the organisation.

'the IM definitely comes before any job [...] work is something you can find anywhere if you have a certain level of education [...] I would never stop my IM commitment for a job [...] or because a recruiter says it would be good'.

Therefore, Lars is aware of potential personal disadvantages associated with his involvement. He had already experienced violent attacks and property damage. However, he corrected the researcher when she labelled such experiences as disadvantages: *'I wouldn't see it as a disadvantage, it's a hurdle or it's an annoying side effect, but the whole thing also has an advantage at the same time'*. He reported dealing with these setbacks and motivating younger activists to take away their fear of experiencing such incidents:

'Our ancestors in the last thousand years died on battlefields and let themselves be killed for their idea of a better world and really sacrificed a lot more than we did [...] and here a car is burnt down [...] I think we can somehow cope with that'.

According to him, physical violence is not something one wishes for, but it would contribute to a person's strength:

'it does something to you and it changes you and above all it makes you stronger [...] much more self-confident [...] it is something that you can experience as a man and that doesn't necessarily make you come out of it weaker if you have already felt what it is like to be in a really dicey situation'.

The statements suggest not only a certain level of experience with activism, including encounters with violence, but also a certain perception of masculinity, including physical strength, self-confidence and the ability to face danger. Lars described that risky situations can be positive transformative experiences, particularly for male members. This aligns with their promotion of summer camps, where they propagate the narrative of strong masculinity and frame violence as a legitimate means of defending their homeland (Goetz, 2019a, p. 17).

Interviewees who showed a high level of commitment hold a specific standard of activism, which they view as necessary to achieve goals. This perspective will be further illustrated through statements from other interviewees.

Like Lars, other interviewees prioritise their involvement in the IM over their work. For instance, Tom believed *'work is for survival' – 'I call my work with which I earn money, 40 hours a week, a part-time job'*. This aligns with Leo who noted that pursuing his dream job is *'a bit difficult with the political career'*. According to him, choosing the political pathway is *'a life decision in the end, and you should be aware of that, I say that to everyone [...] who hasn't shown their face yet, you'll be burnt'* or as Andreas phrased it: someone who engages in the IM *'has a cut in their biography'*⁹. This shows that the interviewees not only invest much time in their involvement but are also willing to make personal sacrifices. Tom spoke about the extent of risk-taking, stating that one must answer 'yes' to the question, *'can you imagine sacrificing your life to politics?'*, a question he had already affirmed for himself. He believes that:

'people have to come because they really want to, we only need people [...] who are independent [...] it's no good us having a bunch of soldiers who only do what they're told [...] they won't find fulfilment'.

This view is supported by Leo who saw no benefits in being a member of the IM: *'personally you have no advantages at all [...] I think if you really join the IM, it's out of your own free will, out of a sense of duty'*. According to him, being an activist is not about joining a regional meeting; by just doing this nothing would be achieved.

However, even though everyone demonstrated a high level of commitment, they expressed it in different ways. While some individuals, like Lars, enjoyed being the public face, giving interviews and representing the group externally, others were drawn to the action and thrill of activism, such as climbing buildings and displaying banners. In addition, there are those who took on quieter, behind-the-scenes roles, often due to family obligations. These different dynamics will be further explored in the following sections. At this point it is noteworthy that the researcher found differences in terms of the forms of action between the interviewees based on regional circumstances (see Section 4.5). Not all regional groups were similarly well developed. While some groups had greater financial resources and a comparatively larger number of members, others

⁹ A 'cut in a biography' refers to a damaging event or association, such as membership in a far-right extremist group, that negatively impacts a person's opportunities, like limiting their eligibility for certain jobs, due to the stigma attached to their involvement in the IM.

had only a few members and no additional financial support. For example, Eric, Thomas, and Jan personally covered the costs of materials for actions from their own private funds, thereby fostering the growth of the regional group and enabling the implementation of activities. Moreover, not all interviewees had extensive experience with activism. One regional group was relatively new at the time of data collection, and although some members were less experienced, they demonstrated a high level of commitment. This will be explored further at a later point in the analysis.

In sum, this type is characterised by:

- Placing a high priority on their involvement in the IM.
- Spending a lot of their free time working on the group's aims.
- Taking responsibility for a specific role or task.
- Willingness to take personal risks.

4.1.2 Moderate engagement – the regular group member

Interviewees who showed moderate levels of engagement participated in the IM to a lower extent in comparison to the ones previously described. These interviewees mainly showed a strong interest in the topic, dealt with it frequently and participated in regular meetings as well as actions. However, their engagement appears to be more supportive than actively involved; they attend meetings, contribute ideas, and provide support to those who take on more active roles within the IM. Unlike the previously presented interviewees, they did not see their engagement as a sacrifice, as they had integrated it into their weekly schedule to an extent that they did not need to give up anything unrelated to the IM. Moreover, compared to the other interviewees who were willing to take risks, these interviewees either actively tried to avoid risks or did not see a high possibility of experiencing such risks. This level of engagement will be illustrated using Chris as an example, supplemented by statements from other interviewees. Chris engaged with the IM daily for up to several hours:

'Well, if you add everything up [...] then quite a lot [...] you watch videos of Martin Sellner or something in the morning while you're showering, you tweet a bit at lunchtime during the break [...], networking does take a bit of time.'

This is in line with Mike who described reading far-right literature such as *'Finis Germania'* or *'Compact'* when lying in bed and checking his phone every morning to catch up on news particularly on attacks against right-wing supporters. According to him, *'there really is a common thread running through daily life [...] from morning to evening, in the car, at work, everywhere'*.

Nevertheless, not all interviewees spend as much time consuming online content. For instance, when asked about the time he spends consuming IM online content, Simon answered: *'almost nothing, I have a lot to do at work, I work with my head more than 90 per cent of the time, which means I don't want to use it for anything [...] I need shallow entertainment'*. However, he said that he participated in offline meetings such as a weekly regional meeting, social events and the actions they carried out. Nevertheless, Simon had a clear ranking of his priorities:

'Value, erm, so basically everything fits so that I don't have to [...] ignore anything else, but of course, my family is the most important to me, I never skip work either, if there is an IM event on a day, I would normally have training [...] I attend the event'.

He said that sports take up much of his free time as he trains 4-5 times a week. Therefore, even though he prioritises IM events when they coincide with his training schedule, he does not allocate additional time to the IM beyond these occasions. This shows that the IM is a lower priority for him compared to the previous group, which aligns with Mike who, when asked about whether the IM is a priority for him, said: *'Yes, since I don't play football anymore,'* indicating it ranks nearly equal to sports and hobbies after his partnership and family.

Chris was self-employed and prioritised the IM after his daughter and his company. He gave the IM high priority because, in his view, the so-called replacement of the German population was *'a burning problem'*, but he said that he not only cannot join offline events that much, he also does not want to. This interviewee explained his level of engagement by stating that since the IM is a youth movement where all efforts come from young people who carry out the actions, he views his responsibility as that of financial support. Consequently, Chris stated that he had not attended seminars at the IfS, even though he was interested in them: *'it wouldn't help me that much, because*

[...] I don't see myself in the front row of activists and also not in the front row of theorists, therefore it's actually a waste of effort'.

One interesting observation was that Chris integrated his involvement in the IM into his own workplace. When meeting him there, the researcher noticed a corner with IM merchandise such as posters, books, stickers and a slideshow of pictures of IM actions that he put together by himself. Chris, who was wearing a T-shirt of the IM, saw the researcher looking around and said: *'yes, it is a bit unconventional'*. According to this interviewee, he would not fear any outing-actions: *'well, I'm doing it publicly, so I can't do more than out myself'*. He acknowledged the potential vulnerability to violence from the far left but noted the comparatively subdued activity of the left-wing movement in his locality. Consequently, if he lived in a city with a larger left-wing movement, he might be more cautious about showing his support for the IM so publicly at work. Although his involvement has not yet led to any adverse repercussions, Chris anticipates such consequences in the future:

'If a customer or acquaintance were to come and say, "I'm not happy with what you're doing here, I have to end our contact," or something like that, then it is what it is, it will surely happen eventually, but that's just how it goes'.

In line with Chris, other interviewees were more forthcoming about their involvement in the IM but emphasised their insignificance as they have not attained a level of prominence that would increase the risk of negative consequences. According to Simon, for example: *'not as a small fish [...] but should I reach a certain kind of prominence, against the odds, then of course there are all the consequences'*. He named examples like arson to his car or doxing, which means the publication of personal information by the political enemy – *'yes, the bottom line is that I accept that at some point my name may appear somewhere in context with the IM'*.

However, not all interviewees dealt openly with their engagement. Some kept it from parts of their family, their employer or the public. As Mike says:

'I stay out of the public eye a lot, simply because [...] if I came to work [...] and was attacked somewhere, whether by Antifa or [...] even by the police [...] and broke my

nose or something, then it would be tight¹⁰, and that's why I currently stay out of big, public things with direct contact with people'.

The interesting word in his statement is 'currently', suggesting that this could change. However, Mike even corrected the researcher by saying that he is not a member but *'just only there'* which he explained by mentioning that the group has no membership lists and therefore no one is a member. While it was important for him to clarify that he was not an official member, other interviewees from the same regional group did not react in this way. This shows how some interviewees reduced the risk of experiencing personal disadvantage by hiding their membership from certain parts of their lives. Other interviewees took risks by dealing openly with their membership but also admitted that the risk of negative consequences was rather low due to their small role and / or the area in which they carried out their activism.

In comparison to the interviewees who showed a high level of engagement, these interviewees were committed to the IM but to a lesser extent. They tried to get involved as much as they could without neglecting other parts of their lives. Therefore, they did not take on binding commitments or specific roles or tasks. Even though interviewees spent a lot of time on IM-related issues and/or content of the IM, they did not see this time as a sacrifice, but as something they enjoy doing and that fits into their daily schedule. While the interviewees previously presented mentioned that they could imagine doing other things instead of activism, these interviewees described that they enjoy attending the 'social events' of the IM, which highlights that they appreciate the fun aspects, but are unwilling to bind themselves too closely to the group. For instance, Simon said: *'if it weren't for the overlaps in content, I wouldn't be here [...] but the community is something that I enjoy'*.

In sum, this type is characterised by:

- Showing a strong interest in the topic, including dealing with it frequently.
- Engagement is integrated into their weekly schedule to an extent that they do not need to give up anything unrelated to the IM.

¹⁰ Meaning negative reactions from his employers.

- Engagement is more supportive than actively involved; thus, they do not take on responsibility for specific tasks or roles.
- Risks are either actively avoided or the possibility of experiencing those is not estimated as high.

4.1.3 Low level of engagement - being in the IM as something one went along with

In contrast to the previous groups, interviewees who showed a low level of engagement did not participate on a regular basis and consequently did not spend much time on their membership. This aligned with the lower priority the IM had for them in comparison to their daily life. Moreover, similar to those who demonstrated a moderate level of engagement, these interviewees either actively tried to avoid taking risks or mentioned that they did not perceive a high likelihood of encountering them. This applied to both of the female interviewees.

Kira, kept her engagement with the IM from her parents and friends:

'my parents don't know that, simply because I haven't had the opportunity to talk to them about it [...] I made a few hints [...] that I had become aware of them and that they actually represented my opinion well, but that was it'.

She further said that if she told her friends, *'they would push it away and don't want to have anything to do with it'.*

This interviewee admitted that the IM is not a top priority for her – *'I would say that it's not as important to me as it is to you (pointing to other interviewees) [...] so it's important to me, but I would have to invest more time in it'.* This shows that her social environment seemed more important to her than her involvement in the IM. According to her, she is, unlike others, not able to deal with the IM for two hours per day because of work but she tried to follow the IM news every day – *'instead of surfing through Facebook and Instagram, to focus on something meaningful'.*

Amelie placed herself at the bottom of the 'food chain' in terms of roles and responsibilities as she studies abroad and is not able to engage locally that often. According to her, it would not be a problem to climb up the food chain but '*the more you climb up the more present you become*'. She referred to Lars who is a well-known public member and said '*of course, you need to know whether you want that too*'. Nevertheless, this interviewee had already been harassed on a train after she had visited the summer festival in Halle and appeared in a video by the IM in which her face is shown. She said:

'yes, you do get scared [...] one's own safety is now no longer guaranteed [...] that does not stop me from strolling through the city, but it is [...] dangerous, I would not walk alone through [name of a part of a city in the East of Germany]¹¹, as [...] my face is known'.

Even though she said that she could live with the risk, she said:

'I don't know whether I would be so publicly committed to the IM if I were studying here [East of Germany], at least whether I would show my face, but of course it's relaxed with me, nobody is interested in that there¹², because they don't really know the IM'.

Although Amelie said that the IM has a higher priority in comparison to her studies and she will be back '*when it's going tough*', at the time of the interview, she did not see the need for it. Consequently, she did not invest much time in her involvement apart from reading the online content and staying in touch with other members –

'in our chat [...] I check and read whatever is shared, we almost have daily contact with each other. But yes, I think if I lived here and were active, then I could spend about two to five hours a week. One can always do something [...] if you had that much free time'.

The type 'low level of engagement' is characterised by:

- No engagement on a regular basis.

¹¹ Area known for a large support for left-wing views.

¹² Referring to the city abroad where she is studying.

- Spending less of their free time on the IM.
- Engagement is more of a supportive nature than an actively involved one.
- Risks are either actively avoided or the possibility of experiencing those is not estimated as high.

In summary, this study identified different levels of participation in the IM: low-level, moderate-level, and high-level engagement. Interviewees varied in both the amount of time they dedicated to the IM and the ways in which they engaged in it. This raises the question of why some people are more actively involved than others. Do specific motives shape the level of engagement or is it the result of other influencing factors? Therefore, the next sections explore how the interviewees narrated their paths towards the IM, offering explanations for the differing levels of engagement.

4.2 Reason-based and goal-orientated motives for joining

In alignment with radicalisation research (see Section 2.7.1) the data analysis identified different motives and factors that influenced the interviewees' decision to become involved in the IM. Inspired by Schütz's (1932) categorisation into 'because' and 'in order to' motives, the researcher distinguished into reason-based and goal-orientated motives. The study found that, in addition to similarities, interviewees shared a number of significant differences.

All except one interviewee had expressed prior political interest, with some engaging in active political participation, influencing their decision to affiliate with the IM. This aligns with the widely held assumption among scholars and practitioners that no one undergoes sudden radicalisation (Neumann, 2013, p. 874). The majority of interviewees (n = 10) described a gradual process, emphasising that their political views had developed over an extended period, and some depicted a continuous refinement of their political perspectives. However, the extent of their political views differed, ranging from a brief political interest to firm, long-standing political ideologies. Other interviewees had previously (actively) engaged with left-wing thinking and described a turning point at which they questioned their beliefs and started sympathising with right-wing views (e.g. Koehler, 2020). Notably, one interviewee

diverged significantly from the others in several aspects and therefore provided a strong contrasting example.

The analysis revealed age-related differences in the reasons for joining; interviewees in adolescence were primarily motivated by personal grievances, whereas those in early adulthood or middle age often referred to political grievances. Although these motives were often interrelated, one type tended to be more prominent than the other. Building on this, a closer examination of individual motives identified two main underlying motives for joining: emotional motives, supplemented by experience-oriented ones, and rational motives.

All of these are linked to identity negotiation processes. However, the focus of these processes can vary depending on the individual's developmental stage, which will be explained in the subsequent sections. Therefore, the pathways described by the interviewees prior to joining the IM demonstrated considerable diversity. To illustrate these motives and the influencing factors that shaped the interviewees' decisions to join, the following sections present selected individuals whose narrations serve as strong examples of the underlying main motives. In a second step, these will then be contrasted – both in terms of minimal and maximal contrasts – with other narrated trajectories.

4.2.1 Group 1: Emotional motives – Interviewee Amelie: from being the outsider to one of many

Emotional motives are closely tied to identity negotiation within the context of social relationships and belonging. These motives often emerge during phases of life where the development of personal and social identity is at the forefront (e.g. Havighurst, 1974). This includes the need for building connections, seeking validation, and exploring relationships that shape one's sense of self, as well as establishing a place within social groups and forming interpersonal bonds as part of developmental tasks (ibid.).

Amelie who showed a low level of engagement serves as an example of someone whose reason for joining was grounded in emotional motives, specifically the desire to

find a like-minded peer group. She experienced early political socialisation but faced significant challenges in building connections and gaining acceptance due to her political convictions. Amelie was 18 years old when she joined the IM and gave the interview. This interviewee had just finished high school and started her bachelor's studies abroad. The researcher met her during one of the Christmas parties where Amelie agreed to participate in the research study. She and the researcher met in a café in the East of Germany, where Amelie presented herself as friendly, self-assured, and composed, showing no signs of nervousness. She was rather cheerful and thanked the researcher for the opportunity to participate in the study at the end of the interview, saying:

'I just want to thank you for this opportunity, because I really think it's a great thing that we can show ourselves as we are, and yes, that you will hopefully do a good job with it all in your dissertation (laughs) [...] I'm really excited to read it, and I just want to thank you, because I don't think we've had such an opportunity in this context before.'

This statement highlights several aspects. First, it reflects a desire for self-representation, as Amelie expressed the importance of showing the IM and its members as it is. This suggests a perception that the IM's public image has been distorted or insufficiently understood. Second, the gratitude and appreciation for the opportunity to be heard indicate a sense of being marginalised or excluded from broader societal discourse. The expressed excitement to read the dissertation and the hope for a 'good job' reflect both an expectation of an objective representation and a degree of cautious optimism. Overall, this statement illustrates how Amelie perceives the study as a valuable platform for recognition and hopes it will provide an honest portrayal of the IM. To better understand the verbalised wishes, it is worth looking at how Amelie narrated her pathway towards the IM. She emphasised two aspects: her upbringing and experiences of discrimination during her time at school.

4.2.1.1 Upbringing

Amelie started developing a political mindset at an early age when she had been confronted with politics and certain views both within and outside the family. Her mother was a member of the political party CDU, and politics had always been a topic:

'Throughout my entire childhood, my mother always took me to her events. I always talked with adults, and there, politics is a very prominent topic [...] so I had to deal with politics at a young age. At the age of 13, I thought, okay, now I want to be able to participate in the discussions at the events and not just say what mum says. So, I started educating myself, and my political interest developed'.

This statement illustrates how early familial socialisation can shape political interests and attitudes (see Section 2.7.2). Amelie's exposure to political events through her mother highlights the role of parental influence and early engagement with discussions among adults. It also shows a process of autonomy, as Amelie transitioned from only adopting her mother's views to developing her own political perspective through critically evaluating her family's opinions. The interviewee further said:

'I mean, in elementary school, you don't really care [...] since I was in high school, I noticed that my family has opinions [...] and [...] I first thought about it, is that for me, what they're saying, is that my opinion too? Because you don't necessarily have to share the same opinion as your parents, [...] and then I realised, yeah, in some points, our views do overlap'.

The topic of migration was one of them which had been discussed in her family and Amelie agreed with her parents on the viewpoint that migrants would burden the economic system. Her negative opinion on people who fled only because of economic circumstances had been strengthened when, according to her, she and her sister were harassed by the so-called '*economic refugees*'. She compared friends of her family who have a Slavic cultural background and migrated to Germany with migrants who came to Germany in 2015. According to her, the migration of people with a Slavic background was never a problem, suggesting that this does not apply to the latter group of people. These statements illustrate how Amelie adopted her parents' political views. She described having an emotionally stable relationship with her family which became evident when she stated – '*I talk openly about everything with my family anyway, I really tell them everything*'. Empirical studies concluded that the experience of "secure-autonomous" bonds tend to have a protective effect' when it comes to the development of far-right extremist views (Möller, 2020, p. 4; 2022, p. 822). However, in the case of Amelie, the stable and emotionally positive familial relationships did not prevent her from participating in far-right extremist activities. Rather, it provided a

space where she could openly discuss any topic, allowing her to challenge her parents' views and develop her own political opinion without risking the loss of their close bond. These quotes highlight how early parental influence played a role in sparking a political interest.

4.2.1.2 *Being the Nazi bride*

Amelie referred to members who took part in the left-wing scene before and said: *'I'm one of the few [...] who hasn't changed their opinion yet, which has always been more on the conservative, right side'*. Moreover, she said that most women were not interested in politics, which she observed in her peer group. Girls at her age would be more interested in Instagram. Therefore, Amelie narrated that she had always been an outsider due to her political opinion, resulting in encountering social and institutional challenges, for instance at school:

'I was the only one in my class who had such an opinion. And when you have political education classes and express such views, it doesn't go down well' – 'the others also started to express their political opinions, which were naturally very contrary to mine'. 'I had to take a lot of heat for it, and even my grades suffered because of it; they [teachers] weren't as neutral as one would hope at school. Yeah, my classmates, well, a few of them greeted me every morning with 'Good morning, Nazi bride', or other insults, but somehow you could just brush it off' – 'it was more in jest than serious since we were still friends, but I was always the token Nazi in the class, that's what they called me'.

The statements illustrate how Amelie perceived herself as an outsider at school due to her political views. Miklikowska, Jasko and Kudrnac (2023, p. 477) examined the 'role of peer harassment in radical political behavior'. They found that adolescents who experienced harassment had a higher risk of radicalism; however, 'supportive relationships' with teachers or parents served as a protective factor, reducing its negative effects (ibid., p. 488). Since Amelie described having a good relationship with her parents, this may have influenced how she coped with and made sense of her experience of exclusion at school (e.g. interpreting it as joking rather than genuinely hostile) and perceived mistreatment by teachers. Therefore, in case of Amelie one

could argue that a protective factor, including her close bond to her parents, becomes a risk factor for radicalisation as her parents supported her political views.

4.2.1.3 Independence from parents and finding a stable peer group

At the time of joining Amelie was in the phase of adolescence when an important task is the development of stable relationships with peers (Havighurst, 1974, p. 45). Moreover, the process of becoming independent from parents and to develop 'a set of values and an ethical system' (Havighurst, 1974, pp. 55; 69) were of importance. However, the values Amelie had been taught by her family conflicted with those of her classmates. Following TR, the experience of exclusion and discrimination at school can be seen as a 'disorienting dilemma' which Amelie tried to resolve by looking for contexts in which her views are more accepted. Between the age of 14 and 16 she wanted to go to Pegida events but although her family shared her political views, they thought it was too dangerous, and she should stay out of it. This demonstrates that Amelie was at a developmental stage where she sought a stable peer group. Since she did not find it among her classmates, she began searching somewhere else. As a result, the experience of the disorienting dilemma (discrimination due to her political views) made her more receptive to alternative social contexts that could provide her with a sense of belonging.

4.2.1.4 Becoming aware of the IM through a friend

Amelie became aware of the IM through a friend who suggested going to a demonstration. She had never heard of the IM before at that point. She did an online search to see whether she agreed with their content and after realising that the group is in line with her political views, she went to a summer event in Halle, met members of the IM and decided to join. There was no key experience that triggered an impulse decision to join, it was rather an opportunity she became aware of, but not something she was actively looking for. According to TR, a transformation can emerge either abruptly or as a 'more gradual and cumulative process' (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2011, pp. 421–422). In case of Amelie her decision to join was not based on an event that triggered an abrupt change. Rather, her transformation process had already started before she encountered the IM due to her search for like-minded people who accepted

her political views. The IM's content resonated with the meaning schemes she had developed through her socialisation process, allowing her to quickly adapt the content.

4.2.1.5 *Feeling at home*

According to Amelie, it was not her original plan to get involved in a political movement as she just accepted that she was the only one in her class with an outspoken political opinion. However, when she encountered the IM, she said: *'and then, of course, to find a group with the same political opinion, which is around my age, was [...] very appealing to me'*. Amelie emphasised the community aspect of the IM, which she particularly liked. For instance, she referred to the Christmas party and said:

'what I like about the IM initially is the sense of unity. When we first met, it was my first meetup [...] and one immediately felt at home. There was no barrier of formality; everyone was addressed informally, [...] greeted so kindly. You could talk to everyone'.

Moreover, she enjoyed that conversations were not limited to politics but also included everyday topics – *'it is simply a group that is there for itself and also has cohesion'*. This further illustrates that Amelie was seeking environments where she could not only discuss her political views but also socialise with peers, which was particularly important given her developmental stage and the important role of peer groups in her identity formation.

She noticed that her prejudices against the IM were not justified as the people expressed themselves in an elaborate way: *'of course, I wouldn't join a movement, where the aim is to represent one's opinion by swearing and violence'*. According to her, even those in the group without an academic background were still very intelligent and would express themselves well; this is what she appreciated – having high level discussions. Referring to the previous aspect of self-presentation, this statement shows that Amelie places great importance on distinguishing the IM from traditional violent far-right extremist groups. It demonstrates that she seeks to construct a positive right-wing¹³ political identity that is socially acceptable.

¹³ The term right-wing refers to political positions that operate within democratic frameworks. In contrast, far-right or right-wing extremism refers to ideologies that reject democratic principles.

Moreover, the IM not only offered her a space with like-minded individuals but also the chance to develop a different gender expression. Besides experiencing exclusion, she was also seen as an 'unconventional female' as she shared a strong political interest. During the interview she presented herself as being different from other women. This can be underlined when she talked about the possibility of experiencing personal disadvantages: *'If violence were to be used against me, I would not leave [...] I joined knowing the risks [...]. It's obviously not for everyone, but I could live with it'*. It shows that Amelie was at a stage where she was looking for connection and acceptance. The interview with Amelie was particularly interesting. At the beginning, she expressed gratitude for the opportunity to participate. Moreover, when saying goodbye, she hugged the researcher - a gesture that took the researcher by surprise but felt genuine and natural for Amelie. While other interviewees were far more cautious in their interaction with the researcher, Amelie seemed to enjoy the interview and valued the opportunity to present a perspective she felt needed to be expressed. This moment underscored the importance of emotional connections in her interactions and her desire to feel accepted with her views, without being labelled as someone who does not belong in society.

4.2.1.6 Fighting for freedom of speech as a nice pastime activity

Amelie articulated that her biggest fear would be a potential loss of freedom of speech, as she believes that everyone has the right to have a political opinion. She emphasised that individuals expressing a right-wing political opinion are subject to disdain and threats to their lives - *'one is despised here for their political opinion, one gets blocked on Instagram [...], comments get deleted on Facebook'* and individuals with the *'wrong political opinion [...]* get beaten up'. Even though the fight for freedom of speech refers to a rational motive, for Amelie this is reasoned in her wish to feel accepted with her political opinion. Therefore, her decision to join was primarily influenced by personal grievances rather than political ones, while the latter provided the basis for connection. This was also reflected in her low level of engagement in the IM (see Section 4.1.3). The engagement in the IM was something which gave her the opportunity to spend time with like-minded people but nothing which was so important that it was worth interrupting her studies abroad. According to her, the political interests are in the foreground but *'the personal benefits come along nicely as well'*.

'I don't want to call it a pastime, but it's a good thing, you have a certain feeling that you're doing something important and not just studying and living, you can help people out, not just politically, but also privately'.

This presents an interesting aspect as her personal motives transform into political ones, meaning a 'because' motive (discrimination due to political views) shifts into an 'in order to' motive (advocating for freedom of speech). This aligns with Pilkington's (2023, p. 7) findings (see also Section 2.4).

4.2.2 Comparison

As previously mentioned, interviewees differed in their narrated pathways towards the IM. However, there were also striking similarities that allowed grouping them together. Based on this, the following paragraphs include comparisons with other interviewees who, like Amelie, emphasised emotional motives for their decision to join the IM.

All interviewees were in their adolescence when they joined and at the time of the interview (Amelie: 18 y., Kira: 22 y., Paul: 18 y., Tom: 19 y. / 21 y. and Leo: 15 y. / 22 y.¹⁴). As mentioned earlier, adolescence is marked by key developmental tasks that shape a person's identity. At this stage, individuals strive for mature peer relationships (Havighurst, 1974, p. 45). Additionally, the formation of a political identity gains relevance, involving the acquisition of values and an ethical framework as a guide for behaviour (ibid., p. 69). Some of the interviewees were at the end of adolescence and thus at the transition to early adulthood, where the emphasis shifts towards 'preparing for marriage and family life' (ibid., p. 59) and achieving 'socially responsible behavior' (ibid., p. 75). This stage includes forming intimate partnerships and contributing meaningfully to society. Therefore, a progression from identity exploration in adolescence to the development of a stable identity in different parts of life as well as a greater relational and social responsibility in adulthood takes place.

These interviewees faced disorienting dilemmas related to their developmental tasks, such as establishing a peer group, a romantic relationship, fostering personal growth, and seeking meaning in their actions. Therefore, the emotional motives include two

¹⁴ Tom and Leo had joined several years ago in contrast to the other three interviewees who joined for less than one year.

dominant aspects: the need for building connections and gaining acceptance and the pursuit of meaningful engagement.

4.2.2.1 *Joining despite not having firmly held right-wing beliefs*

Unlike Amelie, the other interviewees had less developed right-wing political views. Therefore, the analysis shows that not all IM members entered with firmly established right-wing beliefs. Two interviewees did not mention any certain political stance and described themselves as previously being *'apolitical'* or belonging to the *'mainstream'*. While Paul said: *'I was always very historically interested in the history of Germany, Europe and the whole world, so I was always a bit patriotic'*, Kira did not mention an interest in politics: *'I [...] didn't really have a connection to it before [...] when I was at school, I didn't really get involved in politics that much'*. Two other interviewees (Tom and Leo) previously had joined the left-wing scene before they came across the IM.

From all of these interviewees, only Leo emphasised, like Amelie, his upbringing which he described as not a political education – *'I wouldn't say that I was brought up politically'*; however, it was also not based on left-wing beliefs – according to him, it was *'reasonable'*. He further explained that most patriots did have a *'normal'* upbringing, meaning that he also watched Sponge Bob, played computer games, built shanties and his parents did not read the Nibelungen Saga¹⁵ to him. He said, *'that was our youth, it had nothing to do with politics [...] of course, somehow subconsciously you are always influenced or pointed towards one direction'*. The interviewee said that he had been led towards patriotism by his parents and because he considered himself a patriot, he would pass this on to his future children – *'being a patriot, of course I would not convince my child of the opposite'*. Even though Leo did not perceive his upbringing as political, he emphasised the importance of patriotism, which suggests that his upbringing may have been more political than he retrospectively described. Alternatively, this could be explained by the fact that patriotism is perceived as something which is normal for him rather than inherently political.

¹⁵ The Nibelungen saga is a medieval German epic which tells the story about heroic figures. Right-wing extremists misuse the story for their own political purposes by interpreting it as a symbol of superiority of the German culture and the rejection of other cultures (e.g. Schuppener, 2024).

However, unlike Amelie, Leo first sympathised with left-wing thinking or as he described it ‘culturally left-wing’ views, meaning the mainstream political view and had joined a punk scene when he was a teenager (see Section 4.2.2.4).

Based on these findings, the key question is what led these interviewees to the IM and what similarities do they share with Amelie since none of them described having firm right-wing political views before joining the IM? As previously mentioned all emphasised emotional motives, including two aspects that were dominant in the analysis: the need for building connections and gaining acceptance and the need for experiencing meaning in their doing.

4.2.2.2 *Building connections and gaining acceptance*

The desire to build connections was expressed either through a focus on stable friendships and acceptance from peers or through a romantic relationship with a member of the IM. For instance, Paul who showed a moderate level of engagement lacked stable friendships and believed things like friendships and community had become superficial – he missed depth. People would rather stay isolated at home, spending time on their phones instead of having a deep conversation. According to him, the IM offered ‘*traditional values*’ and the opportunity to return to ‘*traditional lifestyle [...] through various gatherings*’, like a North German evening where ‘*one has the opportunity [...] to participate in community which was very important to [him]*’. Therefore, he refers to traditional values which mean for him a strong sense of community and a less fast developing world in which he can discuss openly about his political views.

Paul observed a shift in mainstream politics and blamed media coverage and teachers for influencing his political views:

‘you always get this AfD bashing from the media [...] at school my teacher [...] said [...] AfD voters are all stupid anyway [...] and logically you take that on board, because you don't really know the other opinion and you don't really listen to it and I was just an AfD opponent and laughed about Trump [...] climate change is the biggest problem of all time, refugees should all come in’.

According to Paul, him being patriotic *'didn't really fit in with this left-wing world view and patriotism is absolutely not in the mainstream at the moment'*. What he misses in society is *'daily patriotism'*. Like Amelie, he was aware of the fact that mainstream society shares the view that *'everything that is right-wing is absolute evil'* – meaning you get excluded from society if you follow right-wing views.

Paul started developing political views when he came across the videos of Martin Sellner and the IM in general. He depicted his first contact with the IM as follows:

'I think that was like most people through the internet, I was on YouTube, a video of an action was simply suggested to me, then I watched it, and then [...] others were suggested [...] I came across the videos, saw Martin Sellner, and at first I thought, what a Nazi. But then I watched the videos, really thought about it [...] the arguments he presented [...] and then I came to the conclusion that I actually agree with him on quite a lot and that he's somewhat right [...] one thing led to another, I watched more and more videos [...] and then I came here'.

Although Paul had been initially sceptical towards the IM, the content seemed logical and convinced him eventually. This demonstrates how seemingly persuasive arguments, and repeated exposure can push someone from curiosity to active involvement.

This aligns with existing research, which highlights how online groups can act as gateways to offline engagement by providing platforms for connection, information, and shared values (e.g. Conroy, Feezell and Guerrero, 2012). In contrast to Amelie, Paul gradually adopted the IM's content over an extended period until he was convinced that he wanted to support it. Amelie, on the other hand, first encountered the IM through a real-world contact and later through social media. Since she had already developed a political mindset in line with the IM's content, she was able to connect with it more quickly and did not require an extended period to become convinced.

Both expressed the sense that right-wing views are socially stigmatised, and that openly expressing them leads to exclusion. While Amelie's first contact with the IM occurred through offline encounters, Paul's engagement began online. In this sense,

the virtual and offline settings may be seen as functional equivalents: Although their first contact with the IM occurred in different contexts, both settings enabled the initial appropriation of the IM's ideological narratives, influenced by emotional motives. In Amelie's case, the virtual space also served as a means to further engage with and process the ideology. The function – facilitating ideological appropriation – was similar, although the means and dynamics varied. What differs, however, is the nature of initial scepticism and trust-building: Paul's ideological shift happened through the perceived logic of online arguments and the familiarity created through repeated viewing, whereas Amelie's was driven more by finding her political views mirrored in the offline and virtual contact.

When contrasting the interview situations with Amelie and Paul, it became evident that while Amelie was self-confident and showed no signs of nervousness, Paul appeared nervous and insecure. Even though Paul told the researcher: *'I do show my face, I stand up for my values, I stand up for my politics'*, he feared negative consequences such as being excluded from university or being outed in his neighbourhood. According to him sitting at home and writing comments anonymously would reinforce the opinion *'that these values are something to be ashamed of'*. At the same time Paul (18 y.) started laughing – *'Haha no'* - when asked whether his parents know about his engagement. Asked whether he was deliberately keeping it from them, he said:

'I don't really care, but I don't necessarily feel like telling them because I don't want to end up having a conversation with them about it, and then my parents telling me, 'Yeah, you need to be careful,' you know how mothers are, they're always a bit cautious'.

Unlike Amelie, who reported about mistreatment by her teachers due to her political views, Paul waited until he had finished school to join the IM because he was afraid it would lead to bad grades. Therefore, while Amelie established a political mindset which she presented with self-assurance, Paul was at a stage where he started to develop his political views and gained first experiences with political activism. His uncertainty might be reasoned in the fact that he did not yet feel completely comfortable in his new role.

Paul explained that the IM serves both a place for discussing political ideas and a social community:

'one joins because of the content values and stays because of the community [...] at least this was the case for me [...] you want to represent your politics, then you join the IM and then you realise that you are accepted into this community and then you realise what you are currently missing in the real world'.

This statement highlights how emotional connections and relationships can be important for staying in the group even if the initial contact with the IM was based on a political interest. In contrast to Amelie's low level of engagement, Paul's moderate level of engagement can be explained by his desire to take part in a community. Unlike Amelie, he did not study abroad, which gave him the opportunity to engage in local activities. However, the regional area where he lived also prevented him from becoming more actively involved. This became obvious when he explained that he wished he could have joined more IM events during his semester break as he experienced boredom. At the same time, he said that he loses motivation when IM events are far away from where he lives –

'I always see all the events, major campaigns, everything is always in central Germany, Austria [...] including the academies, whenever I want to go, I always check Google Maps to see how far it is, and then it's a 10-hour drive, oh no, I'm just not in the mood anymore'.

Therefore, even though he had a lot of free time and experienced boredom, he was not willing to drive that long to take part in an IM event. According to him, since university was about to start, he needed to figure out how to combine his engagement in the IM with his study responsibilities. At the same time, he said that he would rather go to an IM event than study because he could always study or do another semester, but for him an IM event had a higher priority in terms of community. This again underlines the importance of taking part in a community of like-minded individuals rather than working actively on the IM's political goals.

4.2.2.3 Love as motive

Kira was the only one who had not engaged in any form of political activity before joining. As previously mentioned, she kept her membership from friends, however, the claim that her friends did not want to deal with it, seemed unconvincing. Since her boyfriend held a leadership position, it can be interpreted that her decision to join may have been something she went along with to please her boyfriend rather than a well-considered decision – as this statement underscores: *'I came to the IM through him [she pointed towards her boyfriend] so due to my boyfriend and didn't really have a connection to it before, but he introduced me to it a bit'*. Kira's lack of engagement with political topics was evident in her interview responses, which were brief and often paraphrased statements previously made by other interviewees in her own words. When asked when she became a member of the IM, she passed the question to her boyfriend who answered, *'this year'*. Kira stated the more she reads and realises what is happening, the more she becomes aware of how politicians want to inculcate society with left-wing views. This led her to the decision to do something about it as she does not want to be told by the government what to think. She further stated that freedom of speech is most relevant to her as she does not want to be pigeonholed because of her political opinion. She said that she did not notice any change in terms of her mindset, but the will to engage actively and to do something had become stronger. This seems like a contradiction as she previously claimed she had not dealt with political topics before. This can be interpreted as if Kira was not expressing her own opinions but restating something she heard without reflecting on it herself. Her statements about the importance of freedom of speech without being pigeonholed seemed too general. This is corroborated by the fact that the IM plays a minor role in her life in comparison to the other interviewees. To enhance the role, she needed to invest more time for the IM. It became evident that Kira did not see herself as a fully committed member. At one point of the interview, she referred to the IM and its members as *'them'*, indicating that she does not belong to the circle of members yet. This contrasts with Amelie, who despite a similarly short membership, already spoke in the *'we'* form. This would also explain why Kira kept her engagement from family and friends because she could not fully identify on a content-related basis. In relation to developmental stages, Kira was in a phase in which finding a partner as well as achieving stable relationships with both sexes play a role. Finding a stable peer group

did not play a role as she already had one. The researcher had the feeling that if it had not been because of her boyfriend, she would probably not have joined. This may also explain her low level of engagement with the IM. While the group itself was less significant to her, her relationship with her boyfriend played a central role in her decision to join. She primarily joined to please her partner rather than out of intrinsic motivation. This also explains why she did not share her engagement with her parents and friends. It seemed as if she tried to engage in two separate lives and was not willing to sacrifice one of them.

One limitation is that the researcher interviewed her in a group interview, which may have led to her being more passive. A one-on-one interview was not possible as she called in sick on the day this was planned. However, the researcher had the chance to spend some time with her during the Christmas party and regional meetings. These interactions resulted in a similar impression of her, leading the researcher to believe that Kira did not join the IM because of strong political grievances but because of her boyfriend.

4.2.2.4 Disillusion and searching for meaning in their doing

The two interviewees who had previously joined the left-wing scene reported experiencing a change of mind that led them towards the IM. Tom, who came from a family that *'partly represents left-wing tendencies'* placed an emphasis on his peer group when it comes to the development of his political views.

'it is a long story [...] I have always been oppositional and rebellious, for instance at school, often against teachers, against their views and at some point, I came across left-wing structures. We had a skate park close by and there were mainly radical and extreme left-wing activists, and they were also supposedly oppositional and rebellious and then I joined those especially'.

This interviewee referred to his engagement with left-wing political topics at the age of 15/16, for instance, by reading theories such as the 'Communist Manifesto' by Marx. However, he stated:

'I have never been happy with it; well, you were always against something, but you did not do something for yourself, for the group, but rather always inciting against others,

especially those who have a political opinion, and we did not have a political opinion, we just raged against those who had one'.

This aligns with Leo who wrote an article for a new-right magazine describing his time in the punk scene around the age of 13, when he wore anarchist signs on his backpack. Looking back, this scene was an aimless rebellion for him, where chaos and anarchy were more important than political aims. According to him, it was a case of *'just being a little bit against it, just a kind of rebellion'*. He explained his former sympathy for left-wing views by the subculture influence. According to him, he was young and at an age when one does not have a consolidated world view; he just copied what his older siblings and friends did. He said that he had never been left-wing, only in terms of the adventurous parts, meaning the chaos, and the aim to abolish government.

Leo explained that his personality and political mindset developed at the age of 15/16, a time which he called his 'political awakening'. During that time, he joined peace vigils in his hometown for the Ukraine conflict and other conflicts. He also joined the right-wing civic movement 'WSD - Wir sind Deutschland' ('We are Germany'), which politicised him. However, he did not like the fact that the movement had been too insular and even though they carried out two demonstrations and regional meetings there was not that much publicity. He said that he had the feeling that this movement was not the right fit for him.

Tom experienced a change of mind in 2015 when he saw a video by the IM where activists climbed up the Brandenburg Gate. This made him realise that while IM members faced significant state repression in contrast to the left-wing scene – *'and that's when I realised what I did back then was complete nonsense'*. He noticed a *'real opposition'* by the new right which is missing in the left-wing scene. While Tom came across the IM through social media, Leo was introduced to it by a friend. However, Leo's decision to join occurred after he watched the first video by Sellner, shortly after the IM had been developed (see Section 4.4.1).

The peer group was an important agent of socialisation for both Tom and Leo, and they were attracted by the adventurous aspect of political activism of the far left.

However, at some point they became disillusioned, resulting in them leaving the left-wing scene. Therefore, both experienced a disorienting dilemma which led to reflecting critically on their previous actions. They described the change from left-wing to right-wing as something that suddenly happened. It seemed as if they needed a narrative to justify this part of their lives. However, looking at their age, around 15 years old, it can be seen as a typical rebellion phase of youth. According to Havighurst (1974, p. 55), rebellion is a developmental task of independence from parents or other adults. During youth the peer group becomes more important than the parents, so young people want to differentiate themselves from their parents (e.g. Little, 2020, pp. 4599–4502). The IM offered new roles in which they experienced their doing as more meaningful.

Shortly after Leo had joined the IM, he also experienced what he called, ‘*a blatant experience*’, that had a strengthening effect on his decision to join the IM: ‘*I was sitting in Math class and suddenly I should see the headmaster of the school and then I had to explain myself*’. He further said that the headmaster railed against the IM which was intimidating for the interviewee.

‘He did not want to understand me [...] I tried to say something against it as I needed to justify myself [...] he interrupted the conversation with the words “I do not want to see something like that and if something like that happens again then you will be expelled from school”’.

The reason for having that conversation with the headmaster was because the interviewee had sprayed the IM’s lambda and the letters IM on some plastic foil around trees in context of a school project. He could not remember the exact year, but he said it was at the time from eighth to tenth grade. This was an experience where Leo felt unfairly treated, which continues to appeal to him on an emotional level. He stated that if he had the chance, he would like to inform people of this act of repression. He concluded that this had only strengthened his decision to join.

Both interviewees became disillusioned with their previous political activism and found meaning in their actions through their membership in the IM. However, they articulated different goal-oriented motives in their pursuit of meaning. While both enjoyed the thrill

and action aspect of political activism, it remained more important to Leo in contrast to Tom. Therefore, Leo serves as an example of the sub-type 'emotional & experience-oriented' (see subsequent section), while for Tom the emotional motives had become more relevant.

Tom emphasised his process of personal maturity. For instance, at one point in the interview he asked the author how old she thought he was based on his appearance. The interviewer already knew his age but told him that she thought he was 25 before he revealed his age. He replied: *'that is also my goal, and I work very hard on it every day'*, meaning appearing older. He reported that he went through a change process which has made him age mentally since he had joined the IM.

'I've undergone a really big change in the last 2 or 3 years, I've become extremely serious, independent, which means I could now support a family at the age of 21, I'd like to do that too, if I could find the right woman, ehr and many people in my non-political circle of friends tell me that I'm extremely aged / matured mentally'.

He also emphasised traditional family models and described 'old-school values' such as the man takes care of the bill – he addressed the researcher and said: *'that I take care of your bill'*. Tom wanted to revive old values such as starting a family and caring for them his whole life, which would be the epitome of happiness for him. He added:

'For me, it's mainly about the old values and values such as fidelity to one's wife, which has been lost a lot nowadays, the many divorces that occur nowadays - that's very important to me, simply restoring the enchantment of the world'.

According to him, the IM helped him to achieve this maturity. Tom reported that during the past three years in the IM he has acquired a diverse set of skills, particularly in media technology, and has gained significant life experience that *'one would typically accumulate over the course of ten years'*. According to him, numerous opportunities have contributed to his personal growth. He talked about making a video which he needed to finish under time pressure. These would be things that challenge someone – *'so you just grow and know how to deal better with such [...] pressure situations'*.

The statements reveal several key needs: a desire for stability and responsibility, shown in the readiness to support a family as well as the narrated wish to preserve traditional values; the need for belonging and connection, expressed in the search for 'the right woman'; and a need for recognition and validation, reflected in the strive for self-development and maturity.

This shows how he acquired a new role in contrast to his engagement in the left-wing scene. He took on a leadership position and spent a lot of time on his engagement in the IM. Tom joined the IM at the age of 18 and was 21 at the time of the interview. He was therefore at an age when the development of a political mindset and the preparation for family and marriage were important. Moreover, it highlights how previous emotional & experience-oriented motives shifted towards more emotional motives, encompassing personal growth and maturity.

4.2.3 Experience-oriented motives - Interviewee Leo: from aimlessness rebellion to meaningful political activism

As mentioned earlier, the data analysis revealed emotional motives accompanied by experience-orientated ones. The latter motives are driven by a desire for thrill and physical action (e.g. Wippermann, Zarcos-Lamolda and Krafeld, 2002, p. 175). These motives resonate with a need to feel alive and engaged, which can be part of testing personal limits or finding meaning through direct action. This adrenaline-fueled engagement also serves as a means of asserting and shaping one's identity.

In addition to the previous statements by Leo regarding his time in the left-wing scene, this section further explores his experience-oriented motives. It needs to be noted that other interviewees, like Tom, did not entirely dismiss the importance of participating in activism, but they did not emphasise it as strongly as Leo did.

The researcher met Leo at a car park, where she arrived first. When Leo arrived, the song Europa by Komplott sounded from the inside of his car quite loudly. Komplott¹⁶ was a musician in the new right-wing scene and the song Europa was quite popular

¹⁶ Patrick Uli Bass, alias Komplott, left the movement and started working as a lawyer (Komplott-Komplott, 2017; Dr. Brauer Rechtsanwälte, 2025).

within the IM. According to Leo, it is the hymn of the IM. The interviewee greeted the researcher in a friendly way and seemed relaxed and self-confident. This interviewee was a well-known and established member of the IM, having joined the group eight and a half years ago, which explained his self-confident appearance.

In the interview, Leo explained that he noticed that one cannot say certain things out loud (meaning stating right-wing views in public), otherwise one gets labelled. He said *'well, that's what interests a young person, forbidden fruits taste the best in that sense at the beginning and then an interest develops'*.

The statement suggests that engaging in activism and publicly expressing right-wing views is something that is socially stigmatised. However, for him this has an appealing effect. Using the metaphor of 'forbidden fruits' indicates that this kind of social prohibition sparks curiosity and excitement and thus can function as entry into political engagement which might lead to a deeper interest. This highlights how the allure of the forbidden can sometimes attract youth rather than deter them.

When asked what he liked about the IM he placed an emphasis on the aspect of youthfulness and said that the IM *'is the only one which is patriotic and not a political party'*. According to him, party work is boring, and one must listen to topics for hours that are not that important. He described being in the IM as being free, one can be creative and develop ideas for actions:

'of course, for a young person it is more interesting to think about how can I enter a building, how can I climb up a building [...] put up a banner, what are my exit strategies [...] like in an action film'.

Spending 'nights, several days for actions' at unconventional times represents, for Leo, *'the real activist's lifestyle'*. Leo said that in the IM he is doing exactly what he wants to continue with. He is not sure whether the activism he does will be in the name of the IM, but he knows that he wants to continue with meta politics. This underscores his interest in the exciting and dynamic nature of activism.

He spoke about his ideal circumstance in terms of activism. According to him, there are only a few people he can count on and then there are people who only take part in actions if he asks them. His ideal vision would be having 45 members so there are

always at least 15 people who can take part in actions and a secretary who is responsible for the whole organisation, and he would be responsible for putting things into practice. Further, Leo said that such a lifestyle is stressful and not quite compatible with a normal family life, and one needs to find a balance between both. However, he had no children of his own and was therefore able to invest a large amount of time in it.

In contrast to Amelie and Paul, Leo did not place an emphasis on community: *'I don't need the IM because I want to find a community, I have friends of my own, so I would know how to spend my time differently'*. According to him, it is a question of time:

'of course you could do more for the community, but then you have to cut back on activism [...] but I think that's what you should focus on, of course one doesn't work without the other [...] a community is important for activism, but activism should be the main thing'.

When asked which aims are important to him, Leo replied *'well, as I said, the main goal is to stop the population exchange and the reversals, help on the ground, the basic demands'*. In comparison to his answers on activism, this answer was quite short and more of a theoretical nature. Even though he dealt with the ideological frames of the IM, it shows that his interest lies more in carrying out activism which is also underlined by the following statement in which he refers to interviewee Lars:

'Lars is a pragmatist like me, we always said when we read some books and it is such a drivel where nothing comes out of it, it could make us angry [...] maybe you just have to be the type for all this IfS stuff, all these books and I am not the biggest reader either, I have to admit, and I do not count myself as belonging to any intellectual circles or anything'.

What he calls 'IfS stuff' involves events and publications of the Institute for State Policy. This suggested that Leo preferred the thrill and action of the IM rather than the possibility of having philosophical, political discussions.

Leo further described his function in the IM with the following words: *'there are still enough who form the silent majority [...] for them I want to be a voice'*. He added that

many people cannot speak their mind openly because they would compromise their reputation and therefore, he wants to be for them what they cannot be, because his reputation is already damaged.

Furthermore, even though he hopes to achieve a patriotic change, it is not his main motivation: *'it's important to me to do something [...] to be able to look at myself in the mirror and say something about this madness [...] and simply to have lived a bit honourably'*. The statement demonstrates that Leo gains a sense of self-efficacy through his activism. His primary motivation is not achieving a patriotic change but rather contributing in a meaningful way.

Leo and Tom were both highly engaged members (see Section 4.1.1). While Paul and Kira kept their engagement from their parents and further social environment, Tom and Leo dealt openly with it. When, for instance, Leo was asked whether he would keep his membership from his parents he answered: *'why should I hide it, I am a family man, I like being with my family'*. This aligns with Amelie. According to Leo, his family is patriotic and therefore there is no conflict, apart from the worry his mother has when he carries out actions in the name of the IM. He explained that his mother often reacted with the words *'don't let them catch you'* - meaning police activities such as arrests. Therefore, his engagement in the IM had already become a stable part of his everyday life. Leo sacrificed his professional career and prioritised his bachelor's studies only temporarily as he viewed his degree merely as a means to earn money. Therefore, he was not aiming for high grades. Tom, who, according to his own statement, has sacrificed his life for politics, reported about social rejection and said: *'some of my friends and family have turned their backs on me [...] and no longer want to have anything to do with me'*.

The reason why Tom's and Leo's level of engagement is high is rooted in the fact that they found meaning in their actions through the IM's involvement. This also explains why they have already stayed in the group for several years even though it was a lot of *'buildup work'* (Leo) until they were able to carry out their first action. For the other interviewees, connecting with like-minded people was enjoyable, but it wasn't a priority for their personal development. In contrast, Leo emphasised his engagement as a means of living honourably and Tom saw it as a way to strengthen his personal identity.

In sum, while all interviewees shared the fact that their decision to join was rooted in emotional motives, they differed in the underlying reasons (reason-based motives) for these motives. This means that each interviewee brought different experiences into their IM membership, and the IM therefore served different functions for them. Accordingly, interviewees experienced various disorienting dilemmas, which were closely tied to their developmental tasks such as the need for building connections and seeking validation.

While Amelie and Paul struggled with finding a peer group, Kira was not searching for a peer group but rather wanted to maintain her relationship with an IM member. Amelie was introduced to the IM through an offline contact due to her pre-existing political views, whereas Paul was still in the process of developing a political mindset, which gradually evolved through social media consumption. In contrast, Leo and Tom, who were already politically active, reached a point of disillusionment, resulting in an immediate decision to join and their engagement with the IM helped them process these feelings. However, while Tom emphasised his goal of starting a family, viewing the IM as a means to mature for this step, Leo found meaning and purpose through political activism.

This demonstrates that different dynamics between reason-based and goal-oriented motives shaped the decision-making processes of the interviewees, influencing their paths towards joining the IM.

4.2.4 Group 2: Rational motives – Interviewee Thomas: from alienation in political discourse to finding like-minded people

Besides the interviewees who emphasised emotional motives, others placed greater emphasis on rational motives when narrating their pathways. Rational motives are linked to identity formation in relation to societal responsibility. The empirical findings showed that interviewees described experiencing disorienting dilemmas that conflicted with their previously developed political opinions.

In contrast to the previously presented group, these interviewees were at a life stage where they faced challenges related to societal expectations / responsibility, meaning their concerns extended beyond their personal sphere, for instance, advocating for freedom of speech to protect their children's future. Additionally, some interviewees encountered difficulties with previously resolved developmental tasks, requiring them

to reassess their perspectives due to new experiences, such as feelings of disillusionment from previous political activities.

Nevertheless, as previously discussed, rational and emotional motives are interconnected, even when one appears more dominant at a given stage. Therefore, initial motives can evolve over time, with emotional motives potentially gaining greater significance. At this point it is important to keep in mind that these are narratives told by interviewees themselves. Even though emotional motives can be observed, these interviewees' narratives focus on rational motives and emotional motives are more placed outside their own person.

Thomas (37 y.) who showed a high level of engagement serves as an example of someone whose reason for joining was grounded in rational motives, specifically the desire to change the political discourse and protecting freedom of speech. This interviewee described reaching a point at which he could no longer identify with the current political discourse, resulting in joining the IM.

4.2.4.1 Upbringing

This interviewee reported that he had been confronted with certain values at an early age which had a lasting impact on him. Thomas described himself as a political person who had '*always been conservative*', and recalled certain values he was taught by his family: '*conservative values like being with only one woman, no sex before marriage, having children only with one person*'. Moreover, he positively remembered his childhood church visits with his family, indicating a lasting affinity towards Christianity. The church and being a Christian persisted to be an important element in his socialisation process. He talked about conversations with his grandfather in which topics such as the meaning of home were consistently present. He recounted that his grandfather, a displaced Silesian, struggled after the reunification of Germany, as he observed the incorporation of Silesia into Poland.

4.2.4.2 Political development

Thomas was already politically active, having joined the youth section of the political party CDU when he was younger, and he was still an active member of the party at the time of the interview. However, he did not experience any discrimination or

exclusion from his peer group when he was in his adolescence. He referred to his political convictions and added:

'But before that time [meaning the time he felt his conservative values are disappearing], I never really saw much reason to insist on it [his political views]. If the majority opinion was left leaning, I just didn't really participate in the conversation much [...] you don't want to be the party pooper'.

When Thomas entered the middle age phase, he was startled by the endorsement of topics that contradicted his conservative views. He explained:

'I began to notice more and more that my main conservative reference points, the Catholic Church and the CDU, are increasingly abandoning conservatism [...] I started to think, "Is there something wrong with me, or are the others actually becoming less conservative?"

He described a decline in the depth of social cohesion and conservative values. According to him, even the Catholic church has a seemingly more progressive attitude towards non-conservative ideas such as same sex marriage. He criticised the fact that he needed to add the word *'traditional'* to make sure people know what he means by family in the classical sense. He referred to changed family structures such as patchwork families or homosexual couples. Furthermore, he gave more examples such as the possibility of artificial insemination or adoption and said that such things would erode conservative values.

4.2.4.3 The internet: the only place where Thomas' views were shared

The only place where he still found like-minded people was, according to him, the internet. There, he discovered groups where he felt he was no longer alone in holding his political opinions:

'I first came across online groups that shared the same views as I do, where I felt like, "Ah, you're not the only one who thinks like this". Over time, I also stumbled upon a video by Martin Sellner, then I looked into the IM, and I thought, "Yes, I like this".'

Thomas became aware of Martin Sellner and the IM through a social media activist called 'Vulgäre Analyse'. Vulgäre Analyse was a YouTube channel by Aron P.¹⁷ alias Shlomo Finkelstein which had been developed after the attack on Charlie Hebdo in Paris (Alshater, 2022). Shlomo Finkelstein agitates against Islam, Jews, politicians or other people who fight for democratic values as well as women and queer people (ibid.). In his videos he urinates on the Quran or grills pork on it and claims that he despises the ideology of Islam (ibid).

This statement highlights the role of online spaces in intensifying and radicalising pre-existing political views. The interviewee began with firmly held conservative beliefs, which were gradually shaped into more extremist positions through exposure to social media channels. The progression, from engaging with like-minded communities to discovering figures like Martin Sellner, illustrates how digital spaces act as catalysts, amplifying and solidifying ideological shifts towards more extreme positions (e.g. Köhler and Ebner, 2019), ultimately leading to active involvement in the IM.

4.2.4.4 Treatment of Sellner after the Christchurch attack as trigger to join

Thomas' radicalisation process was further triggered by the manner in which Sellner was dealt with by the security agencies and society after the Christchurch attack which led to his decision to join the IM. Sellner was questioned by the police after Christchurch attacker Brenton Tarrant donated money to the Austrian IM (see Section 2.3.4). Thomas drew parallels to his own experiences and said that he had been met with hostility every time he acknowledged his political views. He thought that if he did not act now, he would not have the chance to do so later. This interviewee used the phrase 'Matthäi on the last word' to support his decision. According to Jäckle (2020), if someone says this phrase, one is on the brink of disaster. The interviewee used this phrase to make clear that he sees the rights of everyone who shares his views as (being) threatened.

¹⁷ In 2020, Aron P. received a one-year suspended sentence for spreading hate and displaying Nazi symbols in his videos. After failing to pay fines and disappearing, his probation was revoked in 2024, as stated by the Cologne prosecutor's office (Trammer and Bascheck, 2024).

Thomas drew a comparison to other political topics and states that he wants to speak openly and anywhere about problems of mass migration and the great replacement just as others speak about climate change. It was his goal to go against the current political changes and bring the CDU back to its conservative values which were the reason why he became politically active. In contrast to Group 1, Thomas consistently referred to social institutions and political representatives. While previous interviewees focused on developing a peer group or searching for meaning in their actions, Thomas was at a stage where he had already established these aspects: he was married with children, had a stable peer group, a firm political opinion and was politically engaged. However, due to perceived negative political changes he began to see his way of life as being under threat. This illustrates how his political motives became deeply personal as he felt a growing need to defend and preserve what he had built. For instance, the developmental task 'achieving adult and civic responsibility' (Havighurst, 1974, p. 98) needed to be reassessed as he feared negative consequences for both society and his own family if the political changes he disliked continued. Therefore, Thomas was firmly convinced of his conservative values and was not at a stage where he sought to further develop them. However, he reached a point where he could no longer identify with his sources of reference, similar to the disillusionment experienced by interviewees in Group 1. The key difference, however, is that while other interviewees questioned their political views, Thomas remained committed to his political stance but felt discontented that key social institutions, such as the CDU or the Catholic Church, had shifted towards a more progressive approach.

4.2.4.5 *Second-row activism*

While interviewees in Group 1 were, for instance, searching for a peer group, Thomas was not actively seeking new social connections. Rather, he was searching for like-minded individuals to pursue shared political goals since he perceived a shift within his traditional sources of reference. As illustrated below, his search for a community was differently motivated in comparison to interviewees in Group 1:

'I don't really want to go out on the streets because otherwise I wouldn't know what to do with my time, I'd much rather spend more time with my family or sleep better at night because I have more time to sleep, instead of reading some political book'.

Thomas ranked his engagement in the IM as his second priority, after his family: *'and if there is still time, one of my most important priorities at the moment is to work on the IM'*. He described his evening routine saying:

'when [...] the children are in bed and then the wife has gone to bed [...] I'm usually up for another 2,3 hours, then I watch videos, I work on flyers, I read books on the subject [...] but more is simply not possible'.

He said that he had failed some exams and that it was important for him to pass his studies to take care of his family.

Thomas used his available free time to plan, organise and carry out actions or create flyers, even though he does not see himself in 'front row activism' long term:

'If we had 20 young people here now, I wouldn't mind stepping back, limiting myself to sticking and folding flyers at home, throwing money at you (pointing to the other interviewees) and letting you do it'.

In comparison to Group 1, this illustrates that for Thomas rational motives related to society responsibility were dominant, particularly the preservation of conservative values. Thomas did not see the IM as a central part of his life but as a means to achieve changing the political discourse. He showed a high level of engagement as he felt an urge to change the political discourse to bring back conservative values. However, since he had already been engaged in political activism, the IM was not a group he was looking for in the first place as he felt satisfied with his life before he noticed the political discourse is changing. Nevertheless, his rational values were connected with emotional motives, as he felt responsible for changing the political discourse to protect his family.

4.2.5 Comparison

Similar to the previously presented interviewees, others placed greater emphasis on rational motives, rooted in a growing sense of societal responsibility. Their engagement was less driven by immediate personal circumstances and more by

content-related concerns, such as dissatisfaction with political developments or perceived threats to core societal values. Almost all interviewees were in their early adolescence or middle age phase when they joined the IM and at the time of the interview – one interviewee was at the end of adolescence when he joined (Lars: 22 y. / 27 y., Andreas: 24 y. / 27 y., Jan: 25 y. / 27 y., Simon: 28 y., Mike 29 y., Florian: 34 y., Eric 38 y. / 42 y.). The following paragraphs illustrate how these rational motives emerged and how they were embedded in the interviewees' narratives.

4.2.5.1 *Expanding political engagement to prevent negative future scenarios*

Interviewees encountered the IM either through offline contacts or via social media, as was the case with Thomas. The former had already been actively engaged with content aligned with the IM's ideology besides the consumption of such content on social media. These interviewees described a long-term development of their political views, with two highlighting the impact of their upbringing. For instance, Lars (27 y.) said:

'my socialisation in this political area happened relatively organically. There wasn't this sharp turn where I suddenly realised at 22 that my left-wing worldview was wrong [...] I've always leaned towards [...] a neo right-wing mindset. There's been a consistent thread'.

Like Thomas, he shared insights into his families' living circumstances and how these circumstances influenced certain values, saying that his family grew up in the German Democratic Republic resulting in them being less receptive to new, modern ideas such as those espoused by the far left. He further explained:

'My family isn't explicitly political, and they probably wouldn't identify themselves explicitly as neo-right, but terms like homeland, people, family, nation have always been positively connotated in my family'.

Mike (29 y.) referenced his upbringing as well, but highlighted his grandparents' influence for adopting a deep connection to his homeland, despite his parents' lack of support:

'I've always been a type of person, even from a young age, who was quite proud of things [...] who strongly felt attached to my homeland. My grandparents were farmers, then worked in the steel industry here [...] and through that, you do feel a certain connection to what's your own'. – 'my mother is completely against national thinking-my father, let's say a little'.

The statements show that interviewees developed certain meaning schemes and perspectives they acquired during their childhood. As presented in Section 2.7.2, the upbringing is a crucial stage in which individuals among others develop concepts and values which help them deal with the world around them (Havighurst, 1974, p. 27). The interviewees described that they were confronted with certain values that later became important to them. As stated in Section 3.5.1, Mezirow (2003, p. 201) argues that people mostly acquire their perspectives uncritically as children, primarily through social interactions and emotional bonds with influential figures like parents (see also Schönplflug, 2001, p. 175).

Not all interviewees underscored their upbringing and the guidance of their parents or relatives as an important influence for the development of their political views. In fact, some even expressed apprehension, noting that their parents or relatives might not endorse their endeavours. This suggested that the family did not play an important role in the formation of their political perspectives, otherwise, they might have openly talked about it. Due to age differences, the influence of parents and concern about their reactions varied among participants. Older interviewees, such as Simon (28 y.), had already established independence and were less affected by parental opinions: *'I've already shocked my mother with so many things, so she probably wouldn't care either'*. In contrast, the interviewees in Group 1 were still in the process of establishing an independent life.

In contrast to Thomas, Lars and Mike addressed negative experiences with migrants that contributed towards their path to the IM. Lars says:

'at around 13, 14 I already had the first problems with migrants at school, like many German youths also in West Germany and there I actually already began to ask myself [...] what is going wrong in my country or [...] somehow realised that something can be as it should be'.

Both interviewees described that their driving motivation to join the IM were based on the events around the refugee movement in 2015; according to Mike, this was the 'mass migration' where he saw the social system collapsing. When Lars saw the pictures of refugees on the Balkan route towards Germany, he thought:

'this is going to end really badly, it's going to be really grim, something has to be done [...] it also triggered a sort of awakening within me [...] where I said, okay, I need to channel this feeling of powerlessness or horror about what's happening here [...] I can't just let it stand and do nothing, deal with it on my own [...] I had to find some outlet where I could channel it'.

Mike talked about his ex-girlfriend's negative experiences with migrants, which led him to the conclusion: *'talking about it at home does not have much effect'*. Similar to Thomas, this illustrates how their political aims gradually took on greater personal significance. Like Thomas, Lars emphasised the protection of his children. He felt a responsibility to let his children live in a country which they call their home country and where they hold a positive view of one's nationality. He did not want them to be suppressed and to have to justify why they do not want to become a minority in their own country. Lars serves as a good example of someone who did not stop his engagement following the birth of his children. Rather, in line with Pilkington (2023, p. 12), the transition into family life 'did not disrupt but confirmed the purpose of activism'. He underscored the importance of considering whether one desires to live in a country with no freedom of speech, where individuals are subjected to attacks for holding, according to him, legally permissible political views. He does not want to live in a country *'where a majority oppresses a minority, and our public streets and parks become a danger zone'*. He elucidated on the prevalence of violence, arson, as well as challenges encountered in work and academic environments. Lars further illustrated the extent of societal polarisation, citing the following incident: *'even my bachelor thesis supervisor had to take two days to decide whether he could supervise my bachelor thesis because I am an evil right-wing populist'*. He argued that it is untenable for individuals to face significant negative repercussions in their personal and professional lives simply for openly expressing their political beliefs.

Both interviewees had been politically engaged before they joined the IM, however, in contrast to Thomas, this engagement started due to their dissatisfaction with the migration politics. Lars joined a far-right group which they renamed to a sub-group of the IM around 2016 / 2017, and Mike had already distributed Martin Sellner material and volunteered as an election worker for the political party AfD before coming across the IM through a mundane activity – getting a haircut. Mike spoke about his first contact with a member of the IM who happened to be his hairdresser: *‘we both took a full risk, it could have gone completely wrong, one of us could have been from the other side, residence clear, workplace clear’* (meaning they exchanged personal information).

Andreas (27 y.) reported that he had already been politically engaged in IM-related activism since he was 21 years old: *‘before I joined the IM, I had been engaged in many new-right circles, so the IM did not change the environment as it might be the case for others’*. This interviewee had been writing for different new-right magazines. He was approached by IM members because he was wearing a T-Shirt with the image of Ernst Jünger which he had bought in the shop ‘Phalanx Europa’¹⁸. Ernst Jünger was an advocate of the Conservative Revolution, held antidemocratic views and aimed to destroy the Weimar Republic (e.g. Neaman, 2019). The reason why he joined the IM was the fact that he wanted to get away from ‘theorising and criticising from the sidelines’. Andreas formulated his aim saying: *‘that Germany remains Germany [...] I mean [...] we are relatively pragmatic, it is simply about maintaining a demographic hegemony, as simple as that’*. What Andreas meant by this is the exclusion of people who are born in Germany but have a different ethnic background (see Section 4.3.1). There was no triggering event that made him question his views as these had already developed before he joined the IM. Like other interviewees, he had been made aware of the IM and because it aligned with his political convictions he joined. Consequently, it is possible that Andreas would not have become involved with the group had he not been approached in person, given that he was already engaged with the right-wing scene.

While Andreas publicly displayed his political opinion by wearing clothes that visibly convey a certain political opinion, Mike took a more cautious approach, which was also reflected in his moderate level of engagement. This interviewee was still new to

¹⁸ An online shop well-known within the far-right scene.

the IM. He described that he enjoyed participating in social gatherings, including philosophising together about topics that happened in Germany and around the world as well as talking about normal things such as work and sport. He described a familiar interaction with each other: *'it's really like when I'm sitting at home with my mates, watching football, drinking a beer'*. Although he enjoyed the social aspects of participation, he was unwilling to risk losing what he had already built for himself, for instance, his professional identity. At the time of the interview, he described his engagement more as a hobby, ranking it alongside other leisure activities.

The high level of commitment shown by Andreas and Lars can be explained by the fact that both had integrated the IM as meaningful part of their lives. For them, political engagement was not limited to isolated actions – it became part of their identity and everyday routine.

4.2.5.2 *IM's social media content as trigger to join*

While the previous presented interviewees came through an offline contact across the IM, for other interviewees social media paved their way to entry. These interviewees had also engaged with political topics for an extended period before joining the IM but had not previously been actively involved in IM-related activism.

One interviewee, Chris (35 y.), was, like Thomas, actively involved in the youth branch of the CDU as a county executive for 3-4 years during his time in the army. However, he did not like the internal hierarchies, i.e., that only the children of popular people got offered good positions in the party. Given this experience, he decided that he would never join a party again.

The other interviewees denied having been politically active before but acknowledged their prolonged dealing with political topics on social media. For instance, Simon said: *'well, I am pretty radical in my political views and in my opinion, political parties always degenerate into finding some middle ground that does not satisfy anyone'*. This interviewee self-identified as a libertarian and since no libertarian party exists, he saw no benefit in engaging in party politics. While libertarians share similarities with the right-wing spectrum, there are distinct differences, depending on the receptive stream of libertarianism. As sociologist Andreas Kemper (cited in Lenze, 2021) explains, individuals who identify as libertarians do not seek freedom from all authority, but

particularly from governmental oversight. More precisely, their objective is the complete dissolution of the state. Right-libertarians reject the state. For example, they do not want to pay for public health insurance if they do not require any medical treatment and are in good health (ibid.). Furthermore, right-libertarians propagate that only people in employment should have the right to vote, and not those on social benefits (Hechinger, 2022, p. 55). Based on this, socialism is something that right-libertarians are against as it would stand in contrast to free market and entrepreneurship (Lenze, 2021). The interesting aspect is that these views stand in contrast to Mike's socially oriented yet nationally framed perspective, in which he emphasised the economic dimension of migration and advocated for prioritising the well-being of German citizens before extending help to others.

'I have the attitude that in every country, whether it's due to illness, single mothers, or early retirees [...] it must be ensured that they can live a carefree life because there are enough financial resources available in the state and if that's all covered, I'm really the last person who has a problem with giving help to people who really need it'.

This again shows the heterogeneity among the interviewees. Both interviewees voted for the AfD, although Simon admitted that his ideological views are mostly not in line with the political party, especially with the AfD's views on society and the economy. He explained that many former far-left activists are in the AfD as they do no longer feel represented by the new left-wing activists, which led to socialist demands within the party. However, he sees the AfD as something that is necessary to change the political discourse and is therefore forced to vote for it.

Most of the interviewees were aware that their political opinions were met with disapproval, which had already caused conflicts for some. For example, Chris recounted experiences during his school years:

'well, everyone who knows me, knows my attitude towards life. I am not just a recent outsider, but actually always have been [...] you always have problems, I had problems at school because if you do not adapt to, and do not represent the mainstream, then of course you will always have problems'.

However, he is now at an age where he might not lose any friends because of his political views as it has sorted itself out who is his friend and who is not during the last 30 years. In the interview, Chris seemed relaxed and when the researcher told him that she expected more scepticism towards her, he replied: *'well, we'll see what you make of it'*. According to him, criticising the research project in advance would be wrong but if the study comes to the conclusion *'that the IM is just full of neo-Nazis, then in retrospect you just say, ehr, you should have known beforehand'*.

Like Thomas, these interviewees utilised alternative online 'spaces' to engage with and articulate their views. Looking at the social media content they consumed one can see that these actors are known for spreading far right, xenophobic and/or conspiracy content via their online channels (see Section 4.4.2). For these interviewees social media played a crucial role in their decision to join the IM.

For example, Simon explains:

'In 2015, I practically became aware of new YouTubers, which today one would classify as belonging to the right-wing spectrum, via several ways on YouTube, because I had always been part of the sceptic community'.

He named, for instance, Styxhexenhammer as his favourite YouTuber who is categorised as far-right (Rauchfleisch and Kaiser, 2021, p. 9). Chris mentioned social media content by the New Right actor Tim Kellner (e.g. Alshater, 2019), through which he came across the IM.

According to Simon, the IM would not exist without *'the mass migration'* event of 2015. He did not know that much about the IM, only became aware of it through Martin Sellner. Simon was sceptical at first but after informing himself about Sellner on certain platforms such as Discord, he realised he agrees with him and started following him.

In alignment with Thomas, some of those interviewees were triggered by how Sellner was dealt with after the Christchurch attack. For Simon, *'joining the IM [...] was actually a kind of impulse decision'*. He claimed that it was an unfair treatment, *'putting Martin Sellner on trial with state means'*. Moreover, he feared that if Sellner was out of the

picture, the IM would suffer the same consequences and decided: *'then I have to jump on board, too, to be able to influence the whole thing metapolitically'*. According to him, if the topics were discussed openly and honestly the whole situation would change for the better. He believes that citizens do not want what is happening, meaning the waves of migration, however they only say this over a beer in a trustful environment where they do not feel watched.

This is in line with Noelle-Neumann's (1974) work who claims that people adjust their willingness to express opinions based on their perception of the majority view. However, this perception can be distorted, as widely expressed opinions may not always represent the actual majority (ibid.). People assess opinion trends and speak out only when they believe their view is gaining support. For the individual *'not isolating himself is more important than his own judgment'* (ibid., p. 43).

Other interviewees described the media coverage of Fridays for Future or of the refugee movements in 2015, which gave them an urge to act, as they wanted to set a counter pole. These interviewees envisioned negative future scenarios, which they aimed to prevent. For instance, Chris said that he had the responsibility to protect his daughter from group rape which migrants would commit.

Therefore, these interviewees experienced a situation that served as a *'disorienting dilemma'* and led to the decision to join. None of these interviewees were planning to join a political movement as they had already found spaces to interact with like-minded individuals. However, through different situations they experienced an urge to take matters into their own hands and contribute to a changing the political discourse.

One interviewee, Jan, acted differently as he did not describe a key experience that served as trigger to join, for him it was the frequent consumption of social media that lead him to the IM. Jan stated that he decided to join *'because everything fitted [...] IM was what fitted perfectly, like if I had founded the whole thing'*. He explained that there was nothing else that fitted with his opinions – *'that is one to one how I would have written it down'*. He further added that he did not find the characteristics in other movements, i.e., attachment to their country, preserving traditions, freedom of speech. The IM was the first movement that fitted 100 per cent. The interesting part is that it

took him several years to come to this conclusion. He reached a point where he believed that he cannot express his opinion openly: *'You are defamed in any case, you are pushed into a corner, especially into an extreme corner [...] that can also lead to serious consequences, whether socially or professionally'*. Jan described himself as having always been close to his homeland and patriotic. However, he denied being involved in a political group previously. He had followed the IM for around three years before deciding to join. In comparison to the other interviewees, Jan had engaged less intensively with political ideas prior to joining. While others actively engaged with social media content, Jan encountered the IM more by coincidence. Over the time, the gradual consumption of such content led him believe that his patriotic values were under threat, which ultimately led him to join.

Therefore, these interviewees could no longer identify with the political discourse and through social media consumption they modified their previous meaning schemes and perspectives and adopted more and more the views propagated by social media actors.

In comparison to interviewees in Group 1, who were seeking stable relationships, and in line with previously discussed participants, the interviewees in Group 2 also denied pursuing such a goal. They were already somewhat settled in life, having stability in terms of family, friendships, job, and political views. For instance, Simon (28 y.) was a PhD student at the time of the interview, and based on his narrations he had already built his own life which is shown by his statement that his friends would stand by him if he were accused of murder.

When, for instance, Chris talked about developing friendships with other members he said: *'Yeah, so everything can of course evolve [...] but since, [...] I can't or don't want to go places often, personal friendships might develop more slowly'*. He added:

'due to the fact that the IM is not so large in Germany, you don't have such a huge community, so you can't do something with 5,6 members of the IM every weekend, right, and I think if you really only seek community, you're really better off in other groups'.

This underscores the importance of rational motives and since he decided not to spend much time with the IM a moderate level of commitment. This aligns with Simon who was satisfied with small achievements:

'it is not necessary to reach the ideal goal, it is already enough getting one stone, the one stone, rolling and of course we alone [...] can't achieve these ambitious goals but maybe if we mobilise enough people [...] something positive can be created'.

In contrast to interviewees who showed a high level of engagement, these interviewees did not aim to integrate the IM into their everyday lives in a way that would lead them to neglect other aspects. Rather, their motivation was to participate to counteract political developments they opposed, with most feeling satisfied by contributing on a small scale.

Jan developed a high level of engagement over the time and took on a leadership role. He liked the fact to be responsible for developing a group and contributing to a cause that is in line with his political views. However, since the group was still in their building-up phase, he differed from interviewees like Lars (see Section 4.5). This was also reflected in the circumstance that his engagement in the IM was not public knowledge yet as this statement concerning his own business showed: *'I don't think that would go down well in town if some people knew where I'm active [...] I am aware that this could happen and I stand by it'*. However, at the same time he uses his business to get in contact with potential members.

4.2.5.3 Drop-outs

As previously mentioned, two interviewees, decided to leave the IM; Florian left the group after the interview and Eric had already left the IM at the time of the interview. Both described, like the previously presented interviewees, long-standing political views. However, while Eric (42 y.) supported conspiracy views and referred to conspiracy books like 'Lies of a Century' (Schrang, 2016) and similar social media content, Florian (34 y.), reported formerly holding left-wing views. In both cases, their decision to join and later leave the IM was closely tied to their personal relationships even though rational motives initially paved the way for their entry.

Florian's support for left-wing views changed when he was around the age of 30. According to him, in 2014/2015 he could not identify with left-wing thinking anymore as he felt that it had distanced itself more and more from the views they propagated. Influenced by the consumption of social media, Florian spoke of a manipulation by media and politics which made him keen-eared:

'I then realised that a lot of things were being set up by the media, by politics, where I more or less woke up and realised that something was wrong here, something was wrong with society, what they were up to, where they wanted to go.'

Eric stated that he always had some national pride and since his time in the army he became interested in alternative blogs and critical books about certain topics such as about the NS regime and German history. However, like Lars and Mike, he referred to the migration movements in 2015 that triggered an urge to act for him.

Florian described a similar reaction to Sellner's videos as previously presented interviewees. After following Sellner's content, he saw strong parallels between his own views and Sellner's. Florian referred to the treatment of Sellner after Christchurch as a trigger moment: *'that he was put directly in the pillory, and it was said that he was also guilty, that was ultimately the point where I said, now I have to do something because it can't be like this.'*

This interviewee said that he tried to discuss political topics with his wife, but she was not interested. This contributed to his initial decision to join the IM:

'because she never wants to hear about things, actually, political or something like that, she always says when I start talking about it "no stop, I'm not interested", [...] I don't want to hear about the problems, find someone to talk to about it' and that was one of the reasons why I'm here (laughs).'

This interviewee started to participate regularly in the meetings and helped with the preparation of activities, thus showing a moderate level of engagement. However, when the researcher tried to meet Florian for a second interview, she was informed that his membership found an end due to conflicts with his wife who was against his

involvement in the IM. Florian's neighbour, who was also his brother-in-law, became aware of his involvement in the IM and talked to his wife about it, which resulted in him leaving the group. According to the regional leader, Florian did not want to leave and said that if it were only the neighbours he would not have left, but because of his wife he left the group. This suggests that the IM was not of high importance for Florian as he left directly after his wife asked him to do so. However, it also aligns with his priorities, ranking family first. Therefore, rational motives led him to join the IM, while emotional motives made him leave the IM. Against this background, it becomes evident that Florian did not have sufficient time to develop a deeper level of involvement, as he left the IM shortly after joining.

In contrast, Eric told his wife about the IM and said that she was fine with it at first, but as his involvement started taking up more time, it caused friction between them. As he became more involved with the IM, his wife's wishes became less important to him; he wanted to be engaged in the IM and therefore, he did not consider his wife's needs:

'later on, the more time-consuming it became, the more problematic it became and because I was in such a circle at some point, where I said I didn't really care what my wife wanted sometimes, because I wanted to do it and then I did it'.

Eric added: *'somehow I was absorbed in it at that moment, it was somehow, it also fitted in a bit with my family situation, I'll say, things weren't really going so well between my wife and me when I joined IM'.*

He attached great importance to the weekly meetings of the IM: *'we met once a week, the day was blocked, whatever happened, so I went there, and I didn't let that be taken away from me'.* Moreover, he was usually the one who always offered help – *'and often you also did spontaneous things [...] now we're doing a poster campaign, who has time [...] yes okay, I'll do it, I'm in, so I rarely said no'.* This demonstrates that Eric's rational motives gained personal significance as the IM became a place where he could escape from his personal problems for a while. Therefore, his high level of engagement was initially driven by his dissatisfaction with migration policy and later reinforced by his personal circumstances.

Interestingly, at the time of the interview Eric was in the process of leaving the IM and his exit was initiated by the leader of the regional group. The interviewee explained that he was asked to leave the group due to differing political views. His critical stance on how a terror attack was portrayed in the media, was not well received and was quickly dismissed as conspiracy thinking. These disagreements ultimately led to his exclusion from the group.

After his exit, he stayed in contact with other former members. He did this because he knew that some former members maintain contact with active members, and this offered him the chance to stay updated about the IM's activities. This shows that he did not want to leave based on his own free will and developed ways of keeping in touch with members of the group.

When asked if he would still be in the IM had the regional leader not made him leave, Eric says no – he was unhappy with the change in the organisational structure, meaning that activities were not decided within the group anymore. It is interesting that Eric did not find what he was looking for as he wanted to do more rebellious things. He stated that it was clear for him from the beginning that he would be confronted with resistance, which appealed to him. According to him, there were many people who wanted to do more, who wanted to go into areas which were known for their left-wing community to put up stickers there to provoke a response – however, this did not happen, and the IM did not engage with the left-wing scene that much. Instead, it was limited to activities such as putting up banners and stickers, sometimes joining a workshop. Therefore, it can be interpreted that Eric used the activities in the IM as a vehicle to escape from personal problems.

4.2.6 Summary:

Analysing the different reason-based and goal-orientated motives that made interviewees decide to join the IM revealed age-related differences. While interviewees in Group 1 placed an emphasis mostly on personal grievances and thus motives on the individual / emotional level, interviewees in Group 2 placed an emphasis on political grievances and thus motives on the macro / rational level. The difference between emotional and rational motives lies in the level at which identity development takes place: While emotional motives are rooted in the personal and social sphere,

focusing on belonging, emotional relationships, and peer group integration, rational motives are shaped by a broader societal perspective, focusing on social responsibility, and one's role within the social and political order. However, it is important to note that both types of motives play a role for the interviewees with one being more dominant or decisive for joining the IM.

As previously outlined, motives can evolve over time; those that were initially more prominent may play a less central role, while others may gain more significance – illustrating how personal motives can become political, and vice versa. This demonstrates that different dynamics between reason-based and goal-oriented motives shaped the decision-making processes of the interviewees, influencing their paths towards joining the IM.

When considering the different manifestations of the level of engagement against this background, it becomes apparent that, although age-related motives are relevant influences, additional aspects also play a role in shaping it. These findings will be further discussed in the subsequent sections.

4.3 Appropriation of ideological frames

The previous sections demonstrated that interviewees joined the IM for a variety of reasons. As outlined in Chapter 4, research on media reception and reception cascades focuses on the process between media content and the individual. It emphasises that media content is appropriated in different ways and highlights the dynamic nature of this process. The individual's specific conditions and context play a crucial role in how content is interpreted and internalised (see Section 3.5.4). Building on this, the researcher examined whether interviewees also differed from each other in terms of their understanding of the IM's important ideological narratives – the concept of ethnopluralism and the great replacement (see Sections 2.3.2, 2.3.3), and how they acquired these narratives.

The analysis showed that not all interviewees expressed a uniform understanding of ethnopluralism. One of the main differences in the understanding of the concept related to the interviewees' views of who belongs to the German nation. Some articulated the view that the immigration of individuals from non-European countries,

particularly those of Islamic background is not desirable due to the existence of significant cultural dissimilarities that would hinder a successful integration. Conversely, other interviewees did not explicitly reject the integration of people with a different ethnographic background but only under certain conditions. They emphasised the need for immigrants to fully assimilate into German culture.

This is illustrated by statements from the interviewees in response to the question of how individuals with a German passport, but a different ethnographic background align with the concept of ethnopluralism. This question turned out to be a kind of seismographic question to measure how radical each interviewee interpreted the concept. Interviewees focused on differed aspects; for instance, some talked at lengths about the concept and related it to socio-political events and / or personal concerns, while others simply reproduced what was written on the IM's website and remained on a theoretical level.

4.3.1 Cultural aspects preventing someone from being German

Interviewees who viewed a different ethnographic background as an excluding criterion for being German were mostly in their early adulthood or middle aged. They placed a strong emphasis on creating a state in which Germany remains German. All of them were either established members and / or had developed a firm political mindset long before they joined the IM.

For instance, Andreas held the opinion that, to maintain a '*demographic hegemony*,' people with different ethnographic backgrounds should be sent back to their home countries. The researcher questioned his answer and said that these people were born and brought up in Germany. He replied laughingly: '*I think the sections of the population we are talking about already have a very strong identity of their own*'. He described the visit of the Turkish President Erdogan to Germany for electoral purposes, where one could see a large amount of support from German citizens. He concluded: '*so you can't say that they are particularly German*'. Andreas' view highlights an ethnicity-based concept of being German, where descent is a key criterion for national identity.

When asked how the implementation of ethnopluralism would work, he said:

'The biggest problem would actually be people who have been here for a very long time, because they can't build a new life elsewhere, but that could be relatively easily resolved by expanding repatriation agreements mainly to younger individuals [...] I mean, those who have been here longer, pension systems, even if there are problems in some way, they are simply beyond the point where they still have children, that means, that can be grown out of in the long run, we need to consider that if we want to defuse this somehow, these parallel societies will grow out of it in the long run (...) I think and ultimately that is more or less consensus also in the IM, that any other attempt to solve this, either becomes very very bloody or (...) somehow also ends with the end of our state order (laughs).'

What he described was an ethnic cleansing through forced repatriation stemming from the aforementioned very narrow view of German citizenship.

The alleged innate connection to the homeland was explained by Tom. He believed that people with a migrant background would never feel at home in Germany in the same way as they did in their 'home countries' even though they were born in Germany:

'the people from Iraq, having a German passport, who live here, I can't imagine that they are doing well, I think people have been uprooted, are detached from their family and I don't think it can make them happy'.

According to him, these people *'still lack their tradition which they have in their country [...] the cultures, the rituals'*.

This is in line with other interviewees who spoke about different criteria for being German but believed that having a different ethnic background inhibits them from belonging to the German people. This is underlined by Lars who believed that the integration of people from Africa is difficult, even impossible, in contrast to the integration of those from European countries. This is, in his eyes, due to a *'certain basis'* which enables people to understand each other. In particular, the shared history of European people makes their integration more feasible than the integration of Sudanese people – *'what history do I share with someone from Sudan, none'*. He claims that Europeans who come to Germany are hard to distinguish because they

behave similar to Germans – thus implying that people from outside Europe would behave differently.

'they wouldn't realise it if my grandparents [...] or my parents were [...] [from another European country], they would probably notice it in the name [...], but they wouldn't notice it in their behaviour [...] because we are so similar and share such similar values'.

Another interviewee, Chris, did not want to say that one culture is better than another, but still claimed that 'they' (Muslim migrants) do not fit in with the German culture. According to him, migration has brought so-called Islamisation as people from Islamic countries bring their own traditions to Germany. They supposedly have a different view on women and the constitution in contrast to Germans. He said integration is possible to a small extent as one can show Muslim people how to live, and if they do not adapt to the culture, they would be outsiders. However, if half of the population was Muslim then there would be no reason for Muslim people to adapt and problems would arise. He called it a clash of cultures and because humans are animals the principle of the stronger applies. That would be the agony of Islamism, as they would be more archaic and *'blessed with a lower threshold for violence'*. Even though he stressed the fact that every nation and culture is of equal worth, such statements undermine the value of the Muslim population by using racist attributions. Furthermore, he mixes the Islamic religion with Islamist extremism and makes clear that he does not see a difference between the religion and the form of extremism. Asked whether a person from Iran could join the IM, he replied:

'yes, he can, it depends on his views [...] of course if he is an Iranian who is a strict Muslim or something like that, then it would probably not fit, but an Iranian Christian or convert would probably fit'.

Chris explained that different cultural areas would exist, and as long as people were from the same cultural area this would be in line with ethnopluralism. According to him, Turkey would not belong to the European cultural area as it is Islamic. This shows a devaluation of other cultures as he implies that Turkish people are unable to integrate into the European culture. He mentioned a friend of his who is half-Indian and said

that this is not a problem since he comes from the same cultural area. He expressed the same view about one of his apprentices, who is Polish and whom he also considers part of this cultural area. When asked if someone who adapts to the German culture would fit, he accepted that it would only work to a certain extent. According to him, it is possible to integrate 100 Muslims per year without having a parallel society. However, *'as soon as they have exceeded a critical mass, they live their own thing, in our cultural space'*. He summarised it saying, *'there is always suffering and misery when two cultures meet that are not supposed to meet'*.

These statements show a lack of acceptance of the German constitutional system. The view that people with a migration background cannot belong to the German people even if they were born in Germany, simply due to cultural attributes, goes against the German constitution and the human rights.

Most of them connected the concept with personal aims and / or explained the concept in a way that showed their political convictions. For instance, Lars and Chris emphasised negative consequences for their children and attributed negative attitudes to migrants by speaking about 'danger zones' and the risk of gang rape through the so-called Islamisation (see Section 4.2.5). They emphasised cultural incompatibilities and connected ideological elements to personal aims, such as the protection of their families.

In some cases, individuals interpreted the ideology through the lens of their own negative experiences with, in their view, migrants and refugees. For instance, Tom referred to violent attacks carried out by migrants and highlighted his desire to have a family and protect them from this. These interviewees had already engaged with similar content, such as that produced by the IM.

Interviewees who joined the IM due to emotional motives, like Tom, expressed an understanding that cultural aspects prevent someone from being German, appropriated the ideology primarily as a way to represent the group, while their engagement was driven by emotional needs, such as finding meaning in their actions or supporting their personal development.

However, not all interviewees linked the ideology to personal aims. For instance, due to Andreas's previous involvement in the far-right scene and his academic background

in political science, he engaged with the ideology on a more theoretical level. When asked about ethnopluralism, he started by explaining at length the biography of Eichberg who contributed to the development and distribution of the term as well as its historical background.¹⁹ This resulted in asking him what he meant exactly with these explanations. Andreas summarised it as follows: *'it was above all a demarcation from the old chauvinism from the Nazi scene, so to speak'*. It is noteworthy that he asserted the concept's significance for individuals with a history of involvement in the neo-Nazi movement, such as Sellner. According to this interviewee, former neo-Nazis:

'needed something to identify with, let's say, what is ours now [...] what distinguishes us from them. I myself never had a history of conversion, I was never involved in the Nazi scene, for others, it's more important [...] they were looking for something like that back then and then they dug up this term ethnopluralism'.

However, even though Andreas seemed to have more theoretical knowledge on these political topics compared to others, his long and complicated answers gave the researcher the impression that he was doing it intentionally as a distraction strategy to avoid answering certain questions. During the interview, he responded with counter-questions to challenge the researcher. Nevertheless, in comparison to other interviewees he did not verbalise personal fears and remained more on an abstract and theoretical level.

¹⁹ 'this word is yes, it has a relatively interesting history, it originated, if I see it correctly, with Henning Eichberg back then, I don't know whether the name means anything to you, that was a rather strange person [...] in his youth he was once, he had a displaced persons background and then in his youth he was in all the displaced persons associations and so on, then somehow he didn't really switch to the Greens, but, he's now dead, so he's a bit, yes, I think he was still born before the end of the war, but, then he switched to the Greens, then, then he just had this ethnopluralism [...] I think, he later joined the Danish Liberal Party, which is somewhere between the SPD Left and the Greens in Denmark and he ended up as a someone who studies cultures [...] he invented this term back then, it was something quite pastoral with Eichberg, he didn't leave Germany for Denmark for no reason, it really was like that, on a very (...) regional, local level, the Hyggelighed, that's, in the Scandinavian language there's that, in Germany it can't really be translated [...] that's actually this, a bit of Scandinavian country life, maybe a bit of Astrid Lindgren behind it, that's what it means, that's how it was with him, he was also against the European nation states, he wanted Europe to be somehow in what I know in 100 regions or something'.

4.3.2 Being German after fully adopting the German values

Contrary to the previous statements, other interviewees tended not to express such a strong opinion regarding migrants becoming German citizens. They argued that someone can become German if they fully adapt to the German culture. Therefore, some of them, like Paul, shared the opinion that a German passport does not automatically make someone German. Being German means origin, language, someone can become German if one assimilates and accepts the values:

'just as well as an Arab who comes here and fully assimilates and commits himself to the whole German values and culture can also become German for me, but to what extent that happens, that's really another question [...] at the moment there are so many that there is no reason to integrate, let alone assimilate, and that's why there are so many people with a German passport, but in the end they are not Germans for me'.

This is in line with Simon who would identify someone as being German even from abroad if this person *'adopt[s] the German culture to the best of their ability'*. He further said that *'of course we would also accept them practically as Germans and if they want to become active with us, we will welcome them with open arms'*. However, the key question is what this means in practice; and from the interviewees' answers one can see that the interviewees themselves are not completely sure about it as the following statement shows. Leo who shared a similar view as Simon said that the key question is how to decide who is German:

'Is the Turk who has lived here for years, runs his kebab shop but sits at home on a carpet and prays, is that a German [...] that is difficult to say [...] for me [...] someone is a German, not depending on biological mechanisms, who respects our values, who identifies himself as German, someone who would say [...] I am a German'.

He expands the example saying that if a Turk grows up in Berlin-Kreuzberg and has Turkish parents, who lives Turkish at home and when he goes to school only spends time with his Turkish community, *'then for me he is not a German'*. He said that a person can feel like a German, but he is not one as he grew up differently, in comparison to a Turk who grew up in [city in East of Germany] and lives there with German friends'. At a later point of the interview, he said that the trickiest questions

are the ones about the *'ethnic thing'*, so *'more or less, [...] who belongs to it [the German nation] and who does not'*. He went on saying that there is no law describing it and that people with a high status in the IM had also not clearly defined it either. According to him, there is no need to do so, because they do not want to make policy, they want a cultural change and no specifications as to how this will be done. These perspectives are diametrically opposed to those expressed by the aforementioned interviewees. While Paul said that even Arab people are able to immigrate to Germany and adapt to German values (and in Simon's view, can then even join the IM), interviewees such as Tom or Chris reject this. Amelie stated that people misunderstand the IM's use of ethnopluralism:

'[They says it's] a nice word for absolute racism, of course, it's not like that [...] saying that it's racist not to mix, but nobody says that. It's just about everyone being proud of their cultural heritage and living as they are. And if I really wanted to, and I moved to America and wanted to become American and live out the culture there, that would be fine too, if you integrate and then want to join a new culture. [...] You just have to find yourself, know what you want, find your culture, revive it, and love your homeland'.

Interestingly, Amelie said at the same time that she had friends *'who fall into the category'* (having a German passport but a different ethnic background). According to her:

'some of them live out their German culture completely and [...] that's because they've discarded their real home or culture, which I think is a shame, somehow you have to keep your culture a little bit [...] but then of course there are also some who [...] live their culture completely here in Germany, so they don't adapt to German culture and I have to say, what you do within your own four walls is your own business, but if you've decided to live here [...] then you should also adapt to the culture'.

Besides the differences stated above, this also shows that Amelie shares a different understanding in comparison to, for instance, Paul. While Paul speaks of assimilation, Amelie speaks of integration. The difference between both terms is an important one. According to Thurich (2011, p. 28), integration does not necessitate the complete abandonment of one's cultural background, including aspects like 'religion, native

language, customs, and traditions'. Such a scenario would instead be considered assimilation, which entails 'full adaptation to the majority culture', often at the expense of losing the language and cultural heritage of one's country of origin (ibid.). However, even though Amelie spoke of integration, part of her answer also includes the view of assimilation.

Most of these interviewees placed a strong emphasis on the preservation of the German culture without strongly emphasising criminal behaviour committed by migrants or using racist attributions for migrants that prevent them from migrating to Germany. Some even described friends with a German passport and a different ethnographic background. However, their views still show an ethnocentric worldview and / or extremist view. For instance, questioning citizenship even though someone has a German passport violates Germany's Basic Laws. Moreover, many statements of the interviewees questioned the equality of people. So spoke Mike of a '*character core of the human being*' that would be the same everywhere '*if we now blindly mix everything on earth*'.

Interestingly, some interviewees acknowledged that members might not share the same understanding of ethnopluralism or that they themselves might not have the correct understanding. When asked whether it is important to understand the concept to engage in the IM, Simon said '*what do you mean by understand completely, I don't know if I understood it completely*'. When asked how people with a German passport, but a different ethnic background would fit with the concept of ethnopluralism Mike said: '*Phew, yes, I think everyone will have a slightly different opinion on that too*'. This is interesting as he is not sure about the official IM wording of this concept. This shows that not only do different understandings of this concept exist, but knowledge about the concept varies among the interviewees. In accordance with TR (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2011), it shows that these individuals were in the process of integrating the concept into their political mindset. In contrast to the interviewees in Section 4.3.1, these interviewees represented all age groups and were mostly newcomers. Most of them followed the IM online but did not deal with its propaganda to the same extent as the previous interviewees did. Thus, they were in the process of reflecting on the concept and familiarising themselves with their new role as a member of the IM. This resulted in varying understandings of the concept.

Most of them did not connect the concept to personal aims or explained it with personal examples. Some merely repeated the IM's propaganda. For instance, Jan said:

'So in no way is it racist or right-wing extremist; the goal for the whole world is actually that everyone can live peacefully in their homeland, which means we are more friends of humanity than enemies of humanity.'

According to him, members of the IM *'are more like the constitutional protectors'*. These answers seemed poorly reflected and superficial. This also fits to the answer he gave when asked what attracts him: *'yes, that you can express your opinion freely and openly, that loving your homeland is not a crime'*. However, it shows how he adapted the wording of the IM, and one can assume that with time, his understanding of the IM's narratives becomes more established.

When asked what the concept of ethnopluralism meant, Leo's response was difficult to understand and ten minutes long. It seemed that he was repeating what he had read. He used explanatory models, saying ethnopluralism would mean the variety of nations. He continued by explaining the term 'ethnic' and then describing a multi-level model to connect it to the Identitarian idea. He referred to Europe and talked about four different stages – regional, national, civil, continental, and said that all of them have the same right to exist, which is also the reason they do not see themselves as nationalists. He said that this model describes the concept of ethnopluralism best, and stressed again the variety of nations. These remarks correspond to content that was originally published on a website of the IM, which is no longer accessible, but the specific passage is cited in Abel's (2020, p. 135) dissertation. For him, the opposite of ethnopluralism would be globalism. He illustrates this with the example of McDonald's, which exists around the world and is open 24 hours; the uniformity of McDonald's is similar to the uniformity that globalism would bring – the world would become more and more the same: *'the human being loses its specific characteristics, he becomes the same everywhere in the modern world'*. Leo said that it would need a turnaround to stop globalism and the process of unification. At a later point in the interview, he stated that explaining the concept in such depth would be an indicator that someone is well versed in the topic. This aligns with Tom (see previous section) – Leo appropriated the ideology primarily as a way to represent the group, while his

engagement was driven by emotional motives and therefore, the ideology was less important.

These statements show that interviewees appropriated the ideology differently. Some interviewees, particularly older ones, engaged with the ideology primarily out of frustration with broader political developments. Their focus was on opposing societal changes to preserve conservative values and freedom of speech. They did not articulate exclusionary views but emphasised the scale of migration and the negative consequences for society.

In other cases, ideology was adopted on a superficial level or interpreted in a way that differed from its original intent. The ideology served as a means of identity-building or group belonging rather than reflecting deeply held beliefs. This dynamic was common among younger and / or new members, who often uncritically repeated ideological slogans without fully understanding them.

In sum, the analysis of ideological appropriation within the IM revealed a range of reception dynamics that differ in motivation, depth, and personal relevance. Following Krotz (2007) multiple factors influence how individuals appropriate an ideology, and while this study can only offer a limited insight, several distinct dynamics were identified:

- (1) Experience-based interpretation: Individuals connected ideological elements to personal experiences, using them to rationalise existing attitudes. The appropriation was shaped by personal experiences rather than abstract beliefs.
- (2) Politically motivated disappointment (issue-focused appropriation): Ideology was appropriated as a reaction to dissatisfaction with political developments. Their focus was on resisting societal change to preserve conservative values and free speech, highlighting the scale of migration and its perceived societal impact without overtly exclusionary rhetoric.
- (3) Pre-structured mindsets through social media or political activity - often formed through prolonged consumption of right-wing social media or prior right-wing political engagement. In these cases, the ideology was appropriated on a more theoretical level.
- (4) Emotional appropriation (superficial or symbolic appropriation): Especially among younger members, ideology was adopted less for its content and more as a

framework for group belonging and personal meaning. They often verbalised ideological slogans and remained on a more superficial level or interpreted it in a way that differed from its original intent. Moreover, for some, recognition as a 'real' member often depended on visible alignment, even if deeper ideological understanding was lacking. In this sense, ideology served as a vehicle for emotional orientation rather than ideological conviction.

Despite these differences, all interviewees had engaged with the IM's propaganda and related content to a significant degree. However, a distinction emerged between established members and newcomers: the former displayed a more consolidated ideological alignment, while the latter were still in the process of forming their views, often unsure whether they shared the core convictions of most IM members. Newer members needed more time and exposure to develop a stronger ideological commitment. However, individuals with prior involvement in ideologically similar activities tended to adopt the IM's worldview more quickly. Established members had undergone a longer process of reception, reinterpretation, and reinforcement, making them more deeply embedded in the ideology.

4.4 Attractiveness and unique selling points of the IM

The previous sections have shown that the pathways interviewees described showed a large variety. However, despite their divergence, all of them ended up joining the IM, thereby raising the question of why this is so. The previous sections already presented aspects interviewees liked about the IM that contributed to their decision to join. These will be summarised and expanded on further in the next sections.

The interviewees highlighted unique qualities of the IM that influenced their decision to join. Almost all of them mentioned that nothing comparable exists, each emphasising different aspects of what sets the IM apart. These aspects provided further insight into the interviewees' personal motivation for joining. Interviewees placed varying emphasis on the following aspects:

- (1) Social media
- (2) Not a far-right extremist movement

- (3) Activism with class – youthful & professional
- (4) Coolness factor – youthful & activist
- (5) Meta politics instead of political party work

4.4.1 Social media and parasocial relationships

Despite the varied paths through which the interviewees encountered the IM, and their differing levels of prior political engagement, they all shared the common experience of social media being an essential influence on their decision to join (e.g. Rafael, 2018, p. 127). In most cases the interviewees had engaged with IM-related content on social media before they became aware of the IM through these channels. Other interviewees came across the IM through their loose interest in political topics, starting to follow its social media presence leading to their decision to join. Others used social media to inform themselves about the IM hearing about it through a personal contact. The data analysis shows that the social media content resonated with interviewees on different levels by reflecting their political views and aligning with their personal circumstances.

All participants had in common that they described a specific connection with social media content. In particular, the videos by Martin Sellner played a significant role, as well as videos produced by the IM that achieved a high level of public visibility, such as the event where Identitarians climbed up the Brandenburg Gate. This section sheds more light on the role of IM social media content, particularly by Martin Sellner, and its effect on the participants of this study.

In the interviews, the name of Martin Sellner was mentioned at various points. Several interviewees mentioned that they encountered the IM and / or were triggered to join the IM through the videos of Sellner. Most of them had followed Sellner and the IM for several months or even years before deciding to join. Their decision to join was either impulsive or the result of a gradual process, as their continuous media consumption eventually convinced them of the IM's views, leading them to take the step of joining.

These findings support the concept of 'para-social relationships' (see Section 3.5.4). Interviewees described such relationships, though in different ways. Older members

described a moral outrage and an urge to act when they saw media coverage of how Sellner had been treated after the Christchurch attack, which served as a trigger to join. Interviewees perceived his treatment as unfair and saw it as restriction of freedom of speech. This triggered an impulse to actively engage in the IM to be able to do something against the perceived change in the political discourse. In relation to the sensitising concept, these statements illustrate that this event triggered a form of moral outrage and addressed the fear of being restricted or losing their right to freedom of speech. They developed a parasocial identification with Sellner, and his social media content could resonate with them in a way that triggered an emotional reaction. At this point, it is important to note that interviewees joined the IM at different points in time so events such as the Christchurch attack and the treatment of Sellner occurred after some interviewees had already joined.

One interesting aspect is that not all interviewees had a positive attitude towards Sellner at first – some were sceptical and thought he was a Nazi. However, through the consumption of his content, interviewees started thinking about him differently and agreed with his thinking. This illustrates that Sellner was able to present himself in a way which was appealing to the interviewees and even though some of them were sceptical towards him, he was able to address this scepticism.

Interviewees in Group 1 directed their attention more towards Sellner as an individual and decided to join because they sympathised with him as a person as well as with his views. For instance, Paul said: *'and then at some point I came across Martin Sellner and I watched his YouTube videos and that has fascinated and excited me'*. Leo even said: *'I speak a lot about Sellner because he is an idol for me'*. According to this interviewee – *'he [Sellner] has accompanied me from the beginning'* and was the *'key turning point in terms of [his] world view'*. The videos convinced him as he liked how Sellner purported his clear and understandable statements in a sympathetic way to the audience. For these interviewees, it was not a single event that triggered an immediate urge to act. Rather, the content on social media resonated with them and led to the decision to join the IM. The social media content either triggered a process of questioning previous views or connected with views which are similar to the ones of Sellner and strengthened these.

Leo stated that he mainly watches content by Sellner: *'I find it to be a good source of information because he's simply a guy [...] you can trust'* and where he would know exactly that he gets the relevant information filtered -

'I don't think [...] that I'm one-sidedly informed because I'm now pretty fixated on this person, because I still try to reflect on everything, but you never have the time to listen to a thousand different people [...] of course, you click through, [...]. But this is a person [...] also because of his charisma, I know that too, but you can also subscribe to that, because I wouldn't find anything [...] great about him where I would say that's inauthentic or that I can't necessarily subscribe to'.

As Newman et al. (2023, p. 10) explain, young people tend to inform themselves about political topics by consuming social media content from influencers or celebrities rather than journalists.

Yet Leo and Paul also criticised Sellner for making too many videos and claimed that some are a waste of time or that Sellner *'degenerated into a news programme'*. Therefore, even though Leo described him as an idol he does not necessarily like everything he does or says, and he would not read something only because Sellner recommended it. This raises the question of whether and when the initial enthusiasm for social media actors like Sellner can start to wane.

It is crucial to acknowledge that Sellner has effectively established himself as a prominent figure within the IM, and it is reasonable to assume that over time he has developed his ability to persuade individuals to join or support the IM. This could also be an explanation why most of the newcomers mentioned Sellner as reason for joining.

Following Krotz's (2007) concept of reception cascades, it becomes evident that the interviewees went through a process of reinterpreting Sellner's arguments. Paul, for example, initially described himself as mainstream and had developed negative views about the AfD and figures like Sellner due to his environment. According to Krotz (2007), individuals bring their prior experiences and societal discourses into media reception, shaping their initial interpretations. However, as Paul continued to consume Sellner's content, he began to question his previously held beliefs. He started blaming his teachers and the media for shaping his earlier negative perception of Sellner and

the AfD. Over time, Sellner's narratives became more familiar to him, and echo chamber effects reinforced Paul's reinterpretation. His view shifted from perceiving Sellner as a Nazi to seeing him as a fascinating figure. This illustrates how media consumption does not occur in isolation — interactions with like-minded individuals further reinforce and solidify emerging beliefs (see also 'Extremity shift in like-minded groups' - McCauley and Moskalenko, 2008, pp. 418, 422).

4.4.2 Not a far-right extremist group: peaceful & patriotic resistance

One characteristic the interviewees mentioned as to why the IM was the only choice for them included the opinion that the IM is not a far-right extremist and non-violent group. For instance, Lars said:

'The unique selling point is uniqueness, there was and is nothing comparable to the IM, at least in German-speaking countries [...] patriotic resistance, peaceful activism did not exist at all from the patriotic camp [...] the IM was the only thing that was [...] a real option'.

Simon said: *'name me another patriotic youth movement, is there another one?'* According to him, besides the IM, there were only groups which are not compatible with the mainstream and not attractive for people who grew up 'normally'. Other interviewees also strongly distanced themselves from right-wing extremism, as illustrated by Paul's comment: *'right-wing extremists - of course, I don't want to have anything to do with that'*. Regardless of the age of the interviewees, all agreed on the fact that the IM is non-violent and non-extremist. However, during the interviews, the researcher was confronted with multiple explanations as to why the IM is non-extremist. Many of them used the political party NPD as a comparison to draw the line to right-wing extremism. For instance, Mike said:

'I was simply interested in participating in something, that happens on a completely peaceful basis [...] otherwise, I could have become some weirdo who votes for the NPD somewhere and sits in the village pub on Sundays and shaves his hair off'.

He referred to the election posters of the NPD to explain that members of the NPD are operating on a lower intellectual level:

'you can already see that the express train has passed through from right to left at birth and has taken the brain with it [...] they are simply people who long for war or some other kind of nonsense'.

Tom explained that the old right did many things wrong, emphasising violence and their views on national socialism. By contrast, he claims *'the IM argues with non-violence, with intellectuality and with real theory and above all youthfulness'*. While others agreed with such an opinion, Amelie admitted similarities between NPD and IM but concluded that the NPD is too radical. It was interesting that not all interviewees had knowledge of the NPD and its involvement in the far-right scene, resulting in the fact that not all were able to explain differences between the NPD and IM. For instance, Thomas raised the assumption that members of the NPD might be treated just as unfairly as members of the IM –

'I've always stayed away from them, because back then they were at least as demonised as we are today [...] maybe, only maybe, they'll be talked about just as badly as we are, but unfortunately, I don't know'.

Another noteworthy observation was the assertion by some interviewees that a previous affiliation with far-right extremist groups was justified by the fact that no comparable group had existed before. According to them, joining right-wing extremist groups was the only option people had if they wanted to be politically active –

'so if you don't want to go into the far-right [...] then there was nothing before, no, that's why many come from even more extreme groups, who themselves weren't really that extreme, but just didn't have any other connections' (Chris).

This is in line with Paul who said:

'So until 2012 there were no real political alternatives to the NPD [...] and if you wanted to get politically involved for your country, for your people, there was no real alternative [...], except to do nothing, and I think a lot of people joined the NPD who didn't really

agree with all the issues, were then also radicalised within the NPD and then after the IM and AfD emerged, people were able to see a real alternative [...] new right ideology and then they were able to return to their actual values'.

Both argue that people accepted the views of the NPD in order to carry out political activism, even though they did not share them fully. This shows that according to them, far-right ideology can be condoned if there is no other right-wing non-extremist group available; a change from the NPD to the IM is therefore easily possible as there was no alternative to the NPD before. Sellner's past in neo-Nazi movements can also be explained through this lens, allowing him to take on a central role in the IM and be accepted by members. However, at the same time Chris said, in line with others, that he would not like to have a former member of the NPD in the IM, who could be a person who fits his description above – being someone who formerly joined the NPD because no alternative existed.

Even though all interviewees distanced themselves from far-right extremism, one statement by Chris was interesting. He mentioned that he would leave the IM if it drifted into right-wing extremism. At the same time, he was the only one who admitted a closeness to extremism:

'we are already hard on the border, that's already clear, but basically we're all not extremist, because I say, if I'm a right-wing extremist, then violence is already part of the agenda, so to speak, if someone is extreme, tries to enforce it with extreme means'.

What he meant was drawing the line between conservative and right-wing extremism, as what the IM does, goes in both directions. However, as long as it stays within reason, he can live with it because the term right-wing extremism, according to him, is a term which has nothing to do with the original term – *'I say, you're almost a right-wing extremist if you don't hop along with Fridays for Future, well, if someone were to call me a right-wing extremist, I wouldn't have a problem with that either, to be honest'.* Therefore, he is not bothered by such ascriptions as long as no one calls him a neo-Nazi – *'I don't want to be pushed into that corner'.*

The comparison with Fridays for Future and the fact that those who do not support it are labelled as far-right extremists normalises the extremist ideology. It suggests that it does not take much to be labelled a far-right extremist. It diminishes the negative connotations associated with the term. Chris also uses neo-Nazism as a distinction from modern forms of right-wing extremism, according to the motto that 'what they do is not as bad as what neo-Nazis do'. As outlined in the literature review, the IM uses the modern approach as an attempt to normalise its propaganda. Most interviewees argued that the IM's described non-violent nature precludes it from being classified as a far-right extremist movement. Eric phrased it like this: *'right-wing yes, if that is how it is now interpreted, the IM definitely is; extremist no, due to the fact that all actions are actually non-violent'*. This shows that members stick to the argument that the IM is non-violent when carrying out its actions. They emphasise that their activism consists of symbolic protests rather than physical aggression. However, while climbing onto the Brandenburg Gate and displaying a banner might not necessarily be violent, the message conveyed by such actions tells a different story. The slogans on the banners convey specific messages, for instance, the call for forced repatriation under the term remigration, which promotes an idea that inherently entails violence. This highlights how the IM strategically frames its activism as peaceful while still advocating for ideological positions that align with far-right extremism. If one relates this to Heitmeyer's (1995, p. 16) definition, which emphasises the '[r]ejection of democratic forms for social and political conflicts', the extremist approach becomes clearly visible: IM members, for instance, reject the democratic structures of asylum policy and instead call for forced repatriation.

Therefore, Eric's argument is interesting in two respects. On the one hand, the presumption of non-violence can provide a false sense of security and justification for not being involved in extremism, especially for those at the beginning of a possible radicalisation process. On the other hand, the aspect of non-violence can be used by already radicalised members as a facade behind which they can hide their propaganda. For instance, Paul, who just turned 18 and described himself as apolitical and mainstream portrayed his first impressions when he met members of the regional group like this:

'I liked the people because I did not feel like there were any bald heads [meaning people who belong to the Neo-Nazi skinhead scene] sitting there. But they were all quite sociable and had the same political views and then I stayed'.

In relation to the sensitising concept, it became apparent that the self-image the IM presents, including a non-violent and non-extremist nature, had been adopted by almost every interviewee. All interviewees stated that they want to carry out peaceful and non-extremist activism. However, despite interviewees' strong disassociation from right-wing extremism, their previous statements in terms of social media consumption and the understanding of ethnopluralism do not corroborate this stance. This is underscored by interviewees' understanding of freedom of speech which will be presented in the following section.

Convinced that their right to freedom of speech is restricted

The participants stated that by joining the IM they aimed to change the political discourse to allow discussions about certain political topics without getting socially excluded for it. This is illustrated by Florian's statement:

'if you are on the left you are always right, if you are radical on the left you are almost always right, if you are in the centre you are half right, if you are on the right you are no longer right at all and if you are on the far right then your opinion can be beaten to death'.

According to Tom, the IM offers people the opportunity to express their political opinion: *'we can say what we want, and we do not need to hide in opinion corridors'*. This assertion underscores the perceived inequities concerning the articulation of one's political stance and associated desire to advocate for the right to freedom of speech. Moreover, the advocacy for freedom of speech frequently aligns with the belief that their actions and beliefs are not unlawful or criminal, but rather something normal and not something they should be forced to fight for. This led to the belief that the IM receives an unjust portrayal, contending that genuine interest in the group and its constituents would reveal that its members are simply ordinary individuals. This can be illustrated by Mike's statement: *'If they really talked to us properly, I don't believe*

that so many people would still want to portray us in such a bad light, because none of us is a bad person'.

This aligns with Florian who would prefer to be asked why he joined the IM, what he is afraid of, and what he wants to achieve rather than being put in the 'Nazi' corner. Eric who left the IM also did not express any awareness of wrongdoing:

'apart from the outing I did not have any disadvantages, because I did nothing wrong [...] I found everything what I did right, therefore I cannot say I regret anything, apart from that I met great people who I still have contact with [...] that's why I don't regret having taken part in it'.

This perception was an interesting finding, especially when relating it to the social media activities the interviewees reported about, and the social media actors they sympathised with. For instance, like Thomas, Lars also referred to the YouTuber *Vulgäre Analyse*²⁰ and claimed that Shlomo Finkelstein made maximum use of his right to freedom of speech. He mentioned that the social media actor's actions were met with resistance from law enforcement agencies as well as from Muslims, including death threats. According to him, this is not something a normal young person would usually have to deal with. He referred to his personal situation and the, in his eyes, unjustified attacks from the left-wing scene as a reaction to his YouTube videos in which he propagates the IM's ideology – *'I didn't attack people, [...] commit any crimes, I just made a video, and funny, controversial, whatever'*. He said that he had been making YouTube videos for years, as well as creative and peaceful activities to take part in the political debate and to establish a patriotic youth work. He admitted that this might be of a controversial nature and their opinion might be something new and provocative, but all he did, in his opinion, was take part in the discourse to make it more diverse. However, this resulted in being observed by the intelligence services, which he equates with the means used to observe a drug dealer or a terrorist. While the IM has an unpopular opinion it uses peaceful methods in contrast to other groups that he claims security agencies should be dealing with. According to him, this

²⁰ Besides this social media actor other actors which had been mentioned by interviewees were for instance, Gavin McInnes who is a far-right extremist and the founder of the Proud Boys, Schattenmacher, Reaction Doe, Neverforgetniki, Tim Kellner. All of these social media activists are known for their xenophobic and/or far-right extremist propaganda.

represents *'pure political stigmatisation, it is a purely arbitrary political tool to stigmatise, criminalise and monitor dissident groups like us'*.

These statements show that the researcher encountered different interpretations of the concept of freedom of speech diverging from its legal definition, thus indicating an effort to legitimise expressions of hatred. Freedom of speech as protected by law, states that every person in Germany is free to express their opinion in speech or writing. However, that does not include inciting hatred against people of certain groups or insulting anyone. As Schultz (2020, p. 10) explains, populists and right-wing extremists say that their freedom of speech is restricted if their provocations meet resistance. They would test how far they can go by using aggressive forms of communication (ibid.). Kruglanski, Bélanger and Gunaratna (2019) (see Section 2.7.1.3) place an emphasis on the network and narratives. The narrative of being restricted in their right to freedom of speech and therefore employing a victim-narrative functions as an explanation and justification for their far-right ideology and activities. The concerns regarding the potential loss of their right to free speech suggest an inclination towards broadening the scope of acceptable expression.

Downplaying the ideology as well as hiding it behind certain terms is a common strategy by actors of the New Right. According to them, just because the IM is not doing what most of society is doing, it does not mean that it is outside democratic margins. Heitmeyer (2018, pp. 277, 285) examined the mechanism 'destruction through shifts in normality' and scrutinised the processes through which the 'limits of normality' in society may be altered. He gave the example of xenophobia and articulated that when xenophobia stops being perceived as a phenomenon needing a critical discourse and needing to be condemned, it signifies that a transition in the thresholds of normality has occurred (ibid., p. 285-286). Heitmeyer, Freiheit and Sitzer (2020, p. 286) make an appeal to '[b]eware of normalisation. For what is considered normal may eventually no longer be questioned'.

4.4.3 Activism with class: youthful and professional

Another aspect raised by the interviewees besides the non-violent and non-extremist image of the IM was its youthful and professional appearance. In particular,

interviewees who had an academic background or were in the middle of their studies highlighted that, in their eyes, the IM operates on a more intellectual level. Like Amelie, who stated that her prejudices against the IM were unfounded, and she valued the intellectual and non-violent approach, Lars said:

'I wanted to do something with people who were also academics [...] or who came from [...] a higher-level environment [...] I wanted to work purposefully, I wanted to get involved in a good cause that didn't completely ignore my age'.

Similar to the argument presented before, Lars used the political party NPD as a basis to highlight the distinctions of the IM by claiming the IM operates at a higher intellectual level and possesses a more appealing appearance: *'the NPD could never be an option for a young person, at least it was never an option for me [...] it would not have been my level'*. This is in line with Andreas who stated in comparison to the IM where one can find *'a high quality of people'*, members of the NPD are people who *'you don't want to be in the same room with'*. Andreas who was of the opinion that joining the IM leads to a cut in one's biography, adds: *'otherwise the standard we have would not be sustainable and that has to be said with all class arrogance, we have a lower proportion of dysfunctional people as a result'*. Especially the emphasis on youthfulness and a certain form of activism was something the researcher heard often. For instance, Lars said:

'It's professional and unprofessional at the same time [...] it has a bit of the perfect start-up, young people who come together, can work together very professionally, but can also have very youthful fun [...] it's a good mixture of almost entrepreneurial cooperation in the sense of a level of professionalisation, of goal setting, of tackling campaigns, of structuring, of project management [...] but at the same time there's also a certain youthful aspect to it that doesn't lose sight of the fun, if I lived in another galaxy, you would actually say that this is one of the best start-ups in Germany'.

This aligns with Andreas who stated that he liked the high degree of professionalisation, especially for a movement that has no access to government funding.

According to Simon, the academic approach is *'nice in a way [as it allows you to] show off, on the other hand academics are also normal people'*. Even though he liked having more academics in the IM, he also saw a disadvantage as having certain discussions with people from different academic backgrounds, such as philosophy, can also lead to conflicts. According to Chris:

'the advantages are [...] that the theories are well thought out, airtight, and foolproof. The disadvantage is that [...] simpler minds often cannot warm up to the theories because they do not understand them [...] you can't join the IM because of the party and black and yellow [meaning participating in the social events without knowing the IM's ideological positioning] [...] you have to see the New Right in the overall context and many people don't understand it at all'.

This would lead to the circumstance *'that many people feel overwhelmed, or they are on fire at the beginning and then when they realise that there is much more to it, they feel overwhelmed and leave again'*. This does not seem to fit with the endeavour to have 'a high quality of people' – to cite Andreas. It can be assumed that 'simple minds' do not belong to the desired target group for individuals who joined because of the intellectual orientation of the IM. However, this shows that interviewees who had joined the IM were attracted by different characteristics. While for instance, some liked theoretical discussions other interviewees were not interested and placed their emphasis on different aspects.

4.4.4 Coolness factor: youthful and activist

Interviewees also highlighted the aspect of youthfulness, supplemented by the activist appearance. As outlined in Section 4.2.3, Leo was one of the interviewees who saw himself in the first row and was attracted by the thrill and adventure the IM offers. However, even though most of the interviewees did not see themselves engaging in such activities, they still liked the youthful and activist image. For instance, Chris compared the IM to an Ultra-scene (i.e., especially fanatical supporters of a team, in his case football) that he has been an active member of. He said that he likes the whole style of the IM, it is *'youthful, activist, but non-violent'*. According to him, these characteristics are attractive for many young people and were also attractive to him.

This resonates with Simon who described a *'coolness factor'* of the IM as it is dynamic, offers a certain style and is a bit rebellious, which fits him. Eric also stated that the IM *'was something young, something new, that appealed to me, despite my 42 years I actually still feel relatively young'*.

While Chris and Eric were in their middle age when they joined, other interviewees mentioned that they would leave the IM when they become older. Tom said that he would not be active in the IM when he turns 35, he would engage in other movements then. This is in line with Lars who talked about his engagement in the IM and said *'yes, and I want to continue doing that for quite a while until I eventually become too old for a youth movement'*. These interviewees also shared the opinion that older people are more likely to be supporters. According to Leo, he would not take them with him to climb up a building. According to the motto, the young ones have time, the older ones have money. Tom confirmed that the activist nature attracts young people and not older people. The latter ones could join Pegida and should support the IM from the second row with money. The young people were the ones who can climb up a roof or could be carried away by the police. This was the unique selling point according to him.

4.4.5 Meta politics instead of political party work

A lack of interest in party work, and a focus on meta politics was mentioned by many interviewees. The interesting aspect of meta politics is that it united all the interviewees, even though those who differed in their political viewpoints. For instance, Simon concluded that, given the limited overlaps with the AfD in terms of the political opinions (see Section 4.2), he needed to focus on meta-politics rather than doing political party work. According to him, meta politics would offer members the chance to change mainstream thinking in a way that allows people to dare to say what they do not like in terms of mass immigration and a multicultural society. This perception of meta politics is in line with other interviewees. For instance, Paul said that changing people's opinions is necessary before political change can happen as it does not make any sense if people do not support these changes.

Moreover, all interviewees agreed that party politics is not of interest to them. For instance, Lars said: *'I vote for them [AfD] of course, I don't make any secret of it, but I wouldn't want to get involved, because that's not the way I want to do politics, meta-politics is fun, that's my thing'*. This interviewee said that he appreciated the work the AfD was doing in a similar way to Simon: *'I actually think it's very important for the discourse itself, but I don't think it would be for me or I wouldn't feel in good hands as I do in IM'*. The interviewee said that he might engage in party politics in 15 years when he is older but at the time of the interview it was not something that he wanted to do. Therefore, all interviewees agreed that they wanted to do meta politics instead of party politics.

Moreover, Thomas referred to the possibility of acting differently through the IM compared to a political party. He liked the provocative approach that distinguished the IM from traditional political parties. The latter would aim at finding consensus and compromise. In contrast, the IM would put the finger into the wound and has the same provocative appearance as the left-wing scene but without being violent.

In sum, interviewees emphasised different characteristics of the IM that represent a unique selling point for them. These aspects illustrate how the IM strategically appeals to a broad spectrum of personal and political needs, enabling it to resonate with individuals across various age groups and ideological backgrounds. The diversity of highlighted aspects also demonstrates the IM's capacity to provide multiple points of identification, allowing individuals with diverse experiences to project their own values and aspirations onto the movement.

4.5 Regional structures – opportunities for activism

In addition to the diverse pathways towards the IM and the varying individual motivations that each interviewee articulated, the data analysis revealed regional differences. As detailed in Section 3.6.2, the researcher conducted interviews with individuals from different regions of Germany. This led to an interesting data sample as these groups had been established at different points in time. While the groups in the East of Germany had been established for several years, one group in the West of Germany was still in the development as it had been initiated only a few months before the first interview, thus it still was in its building-up phase. Therefore, a

comparison of established groups in the East of Germany with a newly formed group and more established ones in the West of Germany led to interesting findings.

The comparison of the different regional groups showed that the internal structure of the regional groups in the East of Germany was more developed in comparison to the ones in the West of Germany²¹.

4.5.1 East of Germany

It became apparent that the groups in the East of Germany operated differently due to the possibility of having more personnel, financial and material resources. For instance, Tom explained that there are different positions within the regional group, ranging from basis activists to leadership positions. Moreover, according to him, a person cannot become a member simply because they decide to do so; rather, they need to fulfil certain tasks to become one, which is all written down in one of Sellner's books. He believed that every group should be structured like this. He described the process as the follows:

'people are invited to the regulars' table, can come along to grassroots activism and [...] if they prove themselves, if they go out on the streets last winter in sub-zero temperatures and put up posters [...] then [...] people are proactively asked, can you imagine sacrificing your life to politics and if they say yes, they are then activists and [...] part of the leadership of the local group and can then make decisions themselves, of course under guidance at the beginning'.

Tom further explained that the 'inner circle' of activists meets in addition to the regular meetings:

'it's just a working meeting, it's not about having fun with each other, it's about working through point by point, there's a protocol that everyone can read, the tasks that are included are mostly delegation tasks, [...] for example, posters have to be put up, grassroots activism has to be done, then someone has to organise it'.

²¹ It is important to note that there are local and regional groups and each of them have a leader, however, to guarantee the anonymity of the interviewees, the term regional group will be used for both types of groups.

This shows that the regional groups in the East of Germany seem to have a larger number of people to be able to put such a structure into practice. Statements by other interviewees of the East of Germany support this. Lars even arranges regular patriotic regional meetings, attended not only by members of the IM but also by supporters and people who share the same political goals. These range from economics and sport students to the ‘disco mice’²², construction workers, lawyers and university professors. - he called it ‘*speed dating for patriots*’. According to him, these meetings connect people from different backgrounds, some of whom might otherwise encounter each other with rejection in daily life. Furthermore, he appreciated the developments that had already emerged from such meetings, for instance carpools, moving help, according to him simple things which he liked as one can see people help each other and come together.

4.5.2 West of Germany

Compared to the internal structure of the regional groups in the West of Germany, one can see strong differences. First, they simply do not have the number of people to implement such a structure. Interviewees said that they have merged two groups due to the small number of members, so that they have joint meetings. Regarding the newly developed group, Jan said: ‘*I think that we are five people who are in the hard core group [...], that's the four of us [...] and then I would say two or three supporters, so the five of us are actually the ones who are the most active*’. Given the rather short period the group existed, it was in its building-up phase which the following quote from Paul illustrates:

‘it's still a bit chaotic here, so of course [name] is the boss, he definitely makes a few plans, writes down what topics should be addressed, but there is no real distribution of tasks, there is a small distribution of tasks, but not that pronounced’.

This is confirmed by Jan who said: ‘*everyone does what suits them best at the moment, someone comes up with an idea [...] it's not so specific that everyone has their own subject area*’. According to the interviewees, they did not spend much time

²² A word he used to describe a girl who liked to party.

weekly as a group – *‘we only meet once or twice a month [...] and then the events, that’s basically it’* (Jan). Thomas emphasised that they need more bonding and regularity first. According to him, they are at a stage where they are still trying to grow together as a group. Nonetheless, they were able to carry out their first banner action, which he was very proud of.

Another aspect the interviewees raised was the means for developing the group. They reported that they paid for material out of their own pockets as they do not have the financial support. Thomas said that all of them are activists as

‘no one has the money to support us with just 10 thousand, so someone we could call, we need 10 thousand for a new car or something, we don’t have that at all, we have to get everything from our savings for the family, for the house purchase, for the car mortgage, it all has to be deducted and then a lot of it has to be done by ourselves’.

Moreover, interviewees not only reflected on the circumstance that they are in their building-up phase but also about the geographical location itself. Andreas said:

‘because we are relatively far to the west, [name of city] has relatively poor transport connections [...] it’s simply due to the locations in [name of city], they are miserable, a lot of things just take place in the East, we’ve now travelled over to Dresden for the Europa Nostra Festival in the South, but if we travel further, we always have to do it in large groups, the train fares are unbelievable for individuals’.

In this context he mentioned that they organise internal trainings, but they would need *‘a corresponding density’* which one can find in [names of cities].

The geographical location makes it harder for interviewees in the West to participate in events that happen in the East. Thomas said that he needs to do a 5-6 hour drive every time if he wants to be actively involved. For him, it is therefore important that a local structure is developed so he can pursue his desire to become actively involved and does not *‘end up as a keyboard jockey on the internet comment section’*.

This shows that the groups in the East of Germany can draw on a larger network to operate with in comparison to the ones in the West of Germany which needed to work with the few resources they have. While some interviewees in the West of Germany

were in the building-up phase and therefore trying to recruit members for their group, interviewees in the East looked back on many years of experience with activism. However, not only were the regional groups in East Germany more organised, but they were also more networked in the overall far-right scene as not only members of the IM joined these meetings but also other people who shared their political opinion. Lars emphasised the environment in which he had been brought up and highlighted the higher support for far-right views.

'I would almost say that even my non-political friends [...] support what I do because, honestly speaking, in [part of East Germany], this is quite a societal consensus. So, it's not something that stands out or is particularly unique; it's actually quite normal.'

Moreover, members in East Germany are closely connected with other actors who are well-known in the field of the far right, and who operate in the regional area (see Section 2.3.5). For instance, some of the members had already participated as speakers at Pegida demonstrations. Moreover, actors such as Götz Kubitschek and his IfS operated in the immediate vicinity. IfS offered a place where members of the IM could attend seminars where known people from, for instance, the AfD were also invited as speakers. Moreover, the former meeting point in Halle where also representatives of the AfD had their offices (Fuchs and Middelhoff, 2019, pp. 150–151) was also a place where members and supporters came into contact. Afterwards a new meeting point in Chemnitz had been established which shows that various actors who operate within the far-right scene are located close to each other. These regional circumstances also lead to the fact that many events take place in the East of Germany such as, for instance, the summer festival in Halle. Therefore, members in the East of Germany can operate in a bigger network, and can draw from a larger recruitment pool (see also Garsztecki, Laux and Nebelin, 2023, p. 10).

Furthermore, interviewees in East Germany reported that they receive great support when activists have to deal with setbacks. Lars, who experienced property damage, mentioned that *'the community is [...] also massively willing to support, the financial side is one thing'*. He continued saying:

'monetary things can always be replaced in some way, but what happens to you physically and what happens in your head – that's what I think is the most important thing and that can't be compensated with money'.

In this context, the different ways of dealing with setbacks were particularly interesting, as illustrated by statements about participation in the summer festival in Halle. Lars reported:

'It's actually very work-intensive, it's always like that, I usually have a stand at such events, coordinate two or three things and then have some speaking duties or just stand on stage and shout into the microphone [...] so it was exhausting, but at the same time very fun, really a lot of fun, brought a lot of challenges with it'.

However, he concluded *'even without the demonstration, it was a great summer party'*. This does not correspond with Jan (West of Germany) who described: *'it was disappointing that the demo didn't take place because there were blockades from all sides, and when someone asked me how it was, it was just disappointing'*. According to him, the atmosphere among the participants was *'depressing'*. Interestingly, Jan reported that he was originally assigned as a guard alongside Sellner who was responsible for bringing people from the train station to the location where the summer festival took place. According to him, *'that's why I got in touch with Martin Sellner and then luckily I didn't have to go after all and could stay at the house'*. This shows that Jan was afraid that he might not be able to return to the festival and did not want to risk his own benefit of taking part in the festival. Berntzen and Weisskircher (2016, p. 565) argue that, even if counter-movements often fail to halt the marches of radical right movements, they still exert influence by *'making it costlier for people to march under their [radical right] banner'*. This suggests that efforts by activists of the political opposition can place a strain on activism, which, in turn, can have an impact on participants like Jan.

It was an unexpected finding that, despite the IM not being a large group according to the Office for the Protection of the Constitution (2024), statements made by interviewees indicated that not all regional groups were aware of each other. This became clear when the author was asked by Lars with whom she has also conducted

interviews and when she named the regional area of the group in the West of Germany, he replied: *'okay, but I think, I don't want to say anything wrong, I don't want to offend any regional structure, but I don't think we are that well positioned over there, right?'* He recommended people from other regional groups that are better positioned – and named different cities. Even though he used the plural form 'we' he could not name any interviewee or had any information about their organisational structure. This is underscored by a statement by Paul (West of Germany) who said, *'I don't think the other IM regional groups [...] they don't take us that seriously here in [name of city] because we haven't done that many campaigns yet and so on'*.

Moreover, interviewees in the West of Germany did not have much knowledge about well-known members of the IM and further actors within the field of the New Right. When speaking to them about Götz Kubitschek and his IfS, Thomas asked *'is that what everyone calls Schnellroda?'* The same was the case when asked about a well-known member called Mario Müller and his violent past. Thomas first did not know who that was. After a while he thought he might remember who he is and added *'if that's an important one, don't tell him that I didn't know who he was'*.

The group in the Southwest of Germany tried to get recognised by the other groups of the IM. For instance, Thomas referred to a contact Jan made with Sellner, and said *'I can imagine that it is thanks to this contact that our first campaign actually made it on Sellner live'*. In one regional meeting, Jan was proud of one of their first videos and wanted to show it to the researcher. He was visibly disappointed when he noticed that someone had taken it off the internet again. It shows that they want to establish themselves as a group and aim at playing on an equal level with the other groups.

This makes clear, that in comparison to members from the East of Germany, members in the West of Germany were neither well integrated in their regional area nor with other subgroups of the IM. The different structural characteristics were evident not only from the statements of the interviewees but also from the observations made during the participation of the regional meetings and Christmas parties.

4.5.3 Invitation to Christmas parties

Besides the regional meetings the researcher was able to join two Christmas parties to which the regional leaders invited her. This was a unique experience that was given to her as some participants of the party told the researcher that there had never been a researcher joining their Christmas party before. These parties differed from each other, as will be further explained in this section.

The first difference the researcher noticed was the location where the Christmas parties took place as well as the extent to which they publicly showed their affiliation to the IM. In the East of Germany it took place in a nice, upscale / middle-class restaurant in a large separate room. When the researcher arrived at the restaurant, her main contact person was not there. She went to a room where she saw around 20 people sitting around a table and asked whether she went to the right Christmas party. However, the people around the table did not disclose their affiliation to the IM, so they were sceptical and discreet about their engagement in the IM. It was only when the researcher told them she was looking for someone and gave the person's first name that people opened up and told her he had not arrived yet.

In contrast, the setting in the West of Germany was almost the opposite. This group had also decided to hold its Christmas party in a restaurant. When the researcher arrived, she noticed that it was fully booked and very busy. The group was sitting in a corner which was separated but visible for all other guests. There was no door and just a separation due to the architecture. Merchandise by the IM including different flyers and stickers was visibly laying on the table. It was not feasible to greet all attendees by shaking hands due to the lack of available space. At one point, one of the researcher's main contact persons and his girlfriend approached her to greet her properly. He gave her a book and said, '*a Christmas present from us to you*'. The researcher did not expect that and thanked them. It was a book the researcher wanted to read for research purposes and told them so. Jan replied, '*oh that is good, we were not sure whether you had already bought it*'. The book title said 'young, female and far-right' – the researcher was not sure whether they wanted to convince her to join the IM by giving the book. Nevertheless, this was a gesture showing that they trusted her.

The researcher further asked her main contact person whether she could take some of the material for research purposes which he agreed to and wanted to give her over 20 copies of a flyer. She denied and said that two flyers were enough. The researcher was not sure what he might have thought she wanted to do with them and whether he thought that she might sympathise with their propaganda.

Therefore, while the other group met in a separate room and claimed they were the local skittles club, this group did not hide their affiliation to the IM, showcasing lots of propaganda material on the table, visible to the waiters and other guests of the restaurant.

A further distinction was observed in the organisation of the Christmas parties. The ones in the West of Germany planned to meet at some point in the city centre and give chocolate Santas to homeless people. When the researcher asked about how the distribution went, the interviewees revealed that it had not been carried out due to the absence of a key member who was responsible for identifying places where the 'real' homeless people could be found. Therefore, they had to cancel and just distributed flyers to the public.

While members in the West of Germany had planned an activity before the Christmas party and had no evening 'program', the ones in East Germany had the whole evening planned out. This program included a PowerPoint presentation of some of their actions, Secret Santa, singing with piano accompaniment and networking. To exemplify this, the subsequent section will present an overview of the evening's program and offer further insights gained from participation.

A short time after the researcher arrived, a middle-aged man approached her and said that they are going to play Secret Santa and given the fact that she had not been told to bring a present, they had provided one for her. The researcher did not expect it, thanked him and thought about the type of present the people would give to each other. After 30 minutes, her contact person introduced her to the group and told them about her background as a researcher. This already caused dissatisfaction for one male participant who was estimated to be over 50 years old. When the researcher sat down at the end of the table, everybody greeted her in a friendly way and one of them said *'more and more new faces'*. After revealing that she is joining the Christmas party

for research purposes, some young people found it interesting and wanted to know more about her research. However, the one older man reacted in a quite unfriendly way. He said that the researcher should sit somewhere else and not so close to him and started a monologue about research in Germany and how externally determined it is. During the discussion, two men who sat next to the researcher tried to calm him down. This was countered by him with the accusation that the young man is trying to protect her as she looks pretty and is smiley, and he is obviously falling for this. This was an uncomfortable situation as it verged on sexism, and made the people who were sitting around this man a bit unsure about the topics they can discuss with the researcher. Sometimes they stopped each other with the words '*careful, the enemy is listening*'.

After the researcher was introduced, the regional leader started to show a power point presentation of popular actions they had been carried out in the past year. The presentation included pictures and videos of, for instance, banner activities or interfering actions. One interfering action took place in a university where members of the IM put small speakers playing the German national anthem in big helium balloons. These balloons went up to the ceiling and it took a long time to bring them down. The video showed students shouting at and insulting members of the IM. The people who attended the Christmas party laughed at the video.

Besides the videos, pictures were presented showing a photo of an action which was called 'The Fuggenmann'. One could see a boat with three human dolls wearing black clothes and lifejackets as well as pictures of a young man's face who was apparently a migrant. On the boat one could see a large banner with the slogan 'Invasion 2020'. This was supposed to symbolise the great replacement, i.e. migrants coming to Germany and replacing the German nation. The name Fuggenmann is based on the events that happened in Cologne in 2015 where women were sexually molested by men who were framed as migrants. The regional leader told the group that these men tried to get phrases written down which they can use to flirt with German women. Members of the IM believed that 'fuggen' stands for the verb 'to fuck' and this contributed to the development of the name 'Fuggenmann'. When this picture was shown to the audience everyone was laughing out loud.

After the presentation the Secret Santa game began and everyone whose number was called had to go to the front, step on a chair to open the present in front of the group. After three people had received their gifts, it was the turn of the researcher, and she played along which was a rather uncomfortable situation to be put in such a spotlight. After opening the present, everyone was laughing as the gift was a cap with the logo of IM on it and it was the only merchandise article which was given as a present. Therefore, most of the group felt jealous of the gift. When the researcher went back to her seat, the middle-aged man who argued with her earlier said 'try it on' which she kind of ignored.

Most of the other presents had no political background apart from two presents. One was a hoodie with the slogan 'Refugees welcome' which was supposed to be a funny trash present. The other one was a banner which can be used for another action as replacement for a banner which had been removed. After the game, a box for donations was given around. When the man next to the researcher handed her the box, the middle-aged man said '*oh, now I will observe exactly how much money you put inside the box*'. After just passing the box to the person on her left, he reacted by saying '*Aha, of course*'.

This was followed by a session of singing Christmas songs. One young man was playing the keyboard, and the lyrics were presented on a screen, so everyone had the chance to sing along. The lyrics had been changed after the first verse into verses about the alleged consequences of the migration flows. For instance, pillars around Christmas markets in the form of Christmas trees. After these modified Christmas songs, they played a song which was called 'Nachts steht Hunger starr in unserem Traum' ('At night, hunger stands rigid in our dreams') (Müller, 2017, p. 199) accompanied by a member on the piano. After the Christmas songs, the regional leader invited everybody to, in his eyes, the most important part of the evening, the networking.

In sum, the groups in East Germany can rely on more established structures and build upon them. The ones in the West of Germany faced difficulties in participating as most of the activities happen in the East of Germany and therefore making it harder for them to become more integrated in the overall network. It can be reasonably assumed that

for interviewees who expressed a desire for increased activity, the appeal of the group may be diminished if it fails to offer a certain level of activity.

These findings demonstrate that political engagement requires structures that enable individuals to put it into practice. Individuals who joined a regional group that is not well established, and operates in an area without a functioning network of far-right actors, may lose interest in participating, as they may feel that their involvement has little impact. Moreover, interviewees who were primarily motivated by emotional reasons, particularly the desire to develop a peer group, may disengage if the group fails to provide such a social environment due to a lack of members. Limited resources may lead to a prioritisation of activism, which may not correspond to the initial motives for joining.

Therefore, in line with the research question, it can be stated that opportunity structures for political activism play a role in shaping both the perceived function of group involvement and the willingness to participate in social and leisure-related activities.

This chapter provided an overview of the main findings of this study. The analysis identified five central themes: levels of engagement, reason-based and goal-oriented motives, the appropriation of ideological frames, the attractiveness of the IM, and the role of regional structure. It examined the individual motives and influencing factors that contributed to the interviewees' decisions to join the IM. The analysis highlighted age-related differences, showing that interviewees in Group 1 were more likely to join the IM based on emotional and experience-oriented motives, whereas participants in Group 2 were predominantly driven by rational considerations.

Importantly, the chapter focused on the narratives as told by the interviewees themselves. The emphasis was not on verifying the truthfulness of their accounts, but rather on understanding their subjective perceptions, which offer valuable insights into how they made sense of their own motivations for joining. Furthermore, the analysis explored how individuals engaged with the IM after joining and examined whether regional structures influenced the intensity and nature of their involvement.

5 Discussion

This chapter is to further interpret the key findings and place them within the context of existing literature. It includes a discussion of how the main findings address the research questions, guided by the study's sensitising concept, and align or differ from previous studies. The study aimed to answer the question: Why do individuals join the IM? This question was divided into three sub-questions, each of which will be discussed and answered in the following sections.

5.1 Research question (1): Which motives and influencing factors contribute to an individual's decision to participate in the IM?

Research has shown that individuals approach extremist movements with varying needs (e.g. Kruglanski *et al.*, 2018; Ellenberg and Kruglanski, 2024). Based on the narrations of the interviewees, different pathways led them to the IM, shaped by various reason-based and goal-oriented motives (Schütz, 1932). These include experiences in different socialisation instances such as the family, peer group, school and social media (Rippl, 2004, p. 18; Rippl, Seipel and Kindervater, 2022, p. 83)²³. In line with Blum's findings (2021, pp. 77, 213), the data analysis revealed a wide age range among the interviewees, from individuals who had recently completed high school to those in their middle age, highlighting differing points of entry, given that the IM has only existed since 2014. The study found that the motives for joining the IM are not necessarily the result of specific socialisation processes or linked to particular socialisation experiences. Rather, the findings suggest that individuals approached the IM through different biographical pathways, motives, and contexts. Despite these differences, elements of their trajectories can be seen as functionally equivalent (Böhnisch, 2018) in the sense that they each served to address similar developmental challenges. Therefore, in accordance with Havighurst's (1974) viewpoint that individuals must undertake disparate tasks throughout their lives in order to establish a stable identity, and in line with findings from radicalisation research (e.g. Lützinger, 2010, pp. 75–76), this study identified age-related differences in the motives for joining. Building on this, the study argues that the decision to join the IM is closely

²³ See Sections 4.2, 4.4.

linked to the negotiation of developmental tasks. While some interviewees struggled to fulfil these tasks, other perceived already accomplished tasks as being threatened. Kruglanski, Szumowska and Kopetz (2022, p. 2) discuss ‘extremism as a motivational construct’ which is based on the assumption that individuals have basic needs – biological and psychogenic - they must fulfil, and any imbalance causes distress. According to the authors ‘the term *extremism* refers to enduring states of motivational imbalance’ (ibid., p. 4, original emphasis). Interviewees of this study experienced difficulties with one or more of the following developmental tasks during adolescence, early adulthood, or middle age (Havighurst, 1974):

Adolescence	Early Adulthood or Middle Age
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ‘Achieving new and more mature relations with age-mates of both sexes’ (p. 45) - ‘Achieving a masculine or feminine social role’ (p. 49) - ‘Achieving emotional independence of parents and other adults’ (p. 55) - ‘Preparing for marriage and family life’ (p. 59) - ‘Preparing for an economic career’ (p. 62) - ‘Acquiring a set of values and an ethical system as a guide to behaviour; developing an ideology’ (p. 69) - ‘Desiring and achieving socially responsible behavior’ (p. 75) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ‘Starting a family’ (p. 86) - ‘Rearing children’ (p. 89) - ‘Managing a home’ (p. 89) - ‘Taking on civic responsibility’ (p. 90) - ‘Achieving adult and civic responsibility’ (p. 98) - ‘Relating oneself to one’s spouse as a person’ (p. 101)

Based on these findings, this study identified two main motives for joining: emotional motives, with some individuals additionally driven by experience-oriented motives, and rational motives. As outlined previously, emotional motives are closely tied to identity negotiation within social relationships, emphasising the need for belonging, validation, a sense of purpose and interpersonal bonds. Some interviewees also described experience-oriented motives, rooted in a desire for thrill and action. For them, physical engagement served as a way to test limits, seek excitement, and shape their identity through direct involvement.

In contrast, rational motives are rooted in broader societal considerations, driven by a sense of social responsibility that extends beyond personal concerns. Interviewees

with rational motives joined the IM out of dissatisfaction with the political discourse, as they perceived their previously developed political beliefs to be misaligned with societal discourse occurring at the time. Unlike those who sought personal belonging or excitement, these individuals saw their engagement as a way to counteract political shifts they viewed as problematic.

At this point, it is important to distinguish between motives for joining an extremist group and motives for radicalisation, as not everyone who joins such a group becomes fully radicalised. As, for instance, Wippermann, Zarcos-Lamolda and Krafeld (2002, p. 173) state, ‘most right-oriented youths do not differ from other youths’ when it comes to fundamental motivation. According to them, individuals in their adolescence were not primarily driven by political convictions but rather by a desire for security, understanding, and excitement (*ibid.*). The authors conclude that the decision to join a right-wing peer group rather than another is usually a matter of chance (*ibid.*, p. 173). However, staying within the group for a longer period is not random (*ibid.*, p. 173-174). It demonstrates that motives for joining can change over time, meaning that initial non-extremist reasons may evolve into motives for radicalisation and thus including extremist goals. This study illustrated different dynamics in the development and evolution of entry motives. A particularly important insight supports Pilkington’s (2023, p. 7) findings, showing how personal concerns became political, while political convictions increasingly took on personal significance. The findings of this study highlight the reciprocal interplay between personal and political motives in joining the IM. The following sections will further discuss the varying motivations and their influencing factors.

5.1.1 The personal becomes political: joining based on emotional motives and experience-oriented motives

This section discusses one of the main motives, namely, emotional motives for joining. One finding of this study is that those who predominantly emphasised emotional motives had mostly not developed firm political views in line with the IM before joining. This was often linked to the age of the interviewees, who were in adolescence – a phase where negotiating identity and developing political stances play a significant role (e.g. Erikson, 1968; Schröder *et al.*, 2022, pp. 180–181). Therefore, they were at

an age where they were still in the process of developing their political identity, which meant they had not yet formed firm far-right political beliefs before joining. This became evident as interviewees described themselves as politically mainstream before encountering the IM or reported youth-typical phases within a peer group, which they viewed as a rebellious phase (e.g. Havighurst, 1974, p. 55). This aligns with research on political attitude development, which shows that political attitudes are most flexible in young adulthood as individuals are 'highly vulnerable to shifts in attitudes' while those stabilise with age (Alwin and Krosnick, 1991, p. 189; see also Hooghe and Wilkenfeld, 2008; Rekker *et al.*, 2015). For those who reported an influence of early political socialisation through their parents, the experience was different, as they developed a more nuanced political mindset, which they expressed with confidence.

However, even though the interviewees varied widely in their previous political engagement, ranging from no prior political interest or casual engagement with political topics to left-wing or firmly right-wing views, they all indicated that joining the IM was driven more by emotional than rational motives. Therefore, the extent of political views was not decisive for joining the IM; instead, it was a vision that the IM can help achieving personal aims / developmental tasks (e.g. Srowig *et al.*, 2018). For instance, the aim of finding a stable community was similarly appealing to the young interviewees with or without firm pre-existing views as both sought to fulfil the developmental task of establishing a social group (e.g. Lützing, 2010, p. 75). The participants reported difficulties in forming these connections due to experiences of discrimination (e.g. Wolfowicz *et al.*, 2020) from peers and teachers based on their political views. Experiences that conflict with one's sense of belonging and acceptance have the potential to either contribute to or reinforce a radicalisation process. This fits with research on former extremists who mentioned that teachers' judgmental reactions to right-wing views pushed them deeper into violent subcultures (Copeland and Marsden, 2020, p. 16). Such experiences can serve as a cognitive opening (Wiktorowicz, 2005, p. 5) which makes people receptive to certain beliefs.

The 'search for acceptance and belonging' serves as a strong pull into right-wing extremist groups (Copeland and Marsden, 2020, p. 9), a need that the IM addressed by offering a supportive network. Interviewees reported different types of meetings, ranging from events like patriotic speed dating, regional meetings to more casual gatherings. Those who were new to the IM described a familiar and welcoming

atmosphere – no shaved heads and no noticeable barriers to becoming part of the group. Established members spoke about ‘friends for life’ whom they had found in the IM.

One interviewee joined the IM because of her boyfriend and admitted that she had not previously engaged with political topics. The analysis revealed that her decision to join was not intrinsically motivated but rather driven by the relationship. As a result, she began to adopt the IM’s narratives through her connection with her partner.

Other interviewees stated that their decision to join the IM resulted from a loss of purpose or meaning in their previous involvement in the left-wing scene. As Bjørgo (2011, p. 284) argues, a relevant reason why people leave extremist groups is the disillusionment with the aspects that initially drew them to the group, such as political aims, the need for companionship, or the longing for belonging and purpose. The desire for social significance is recognised as a key human drive, but it does not constantly influence behaviour (Ellenberg and Kruglanski, 2024, p. 47). In order for it to become a motivating force, it must be triggered by specific circumstances or stimuli (ibid.). Such triggering factors can include deprivation experiences and incentive expectations (Ellenberg and Kruglanski, 2024, p. 47). Interviewees reported experiencing such a disillusionment. In their case, social media content of the IM triggered a sense of unfairness and the feeling that they can no longer identify with this line of thinking. The IM addressed their needs by offering new ways to experience self-efficacy and the feeling of doing something meaningful, for instance, through offering leadership roles or a certain way of life.

As previously mentioned, some interviewees also joined the IM due to experience-oriented motives. Interviewees who emphasised such motives as an additional driver for engagement in the IM appreciated the thrill and action aspect which is in line with age-typical motives, such as seeking excitement and adventure (e.g. Benslama, 2017, pp. 38–44). While during their interviewees’ time in the left-wing scene, they had been offered the chance to rebel against authorities and to experience thrill and action, the IM served as an alternative which offered them a continuation of such activism (e.g. Lützing, 2010, pp. 71–73).

Nevertheless, not all interviewees in Group 1 narrated such drivers. The interviewees who did were male and had previously engaged in similar activities within the left-wing scene. The fact that both female interviewees did not express a strong interest in taking part in such activities is not surprising as it fits to the observation that women

take up only a small percentage within far-right groups and when it comes to activities such as participating in demonstrations they are 'underrepresented' (Mudde, 2019, pp. 147, 155).

These different emotional motives were also reflected in the appropriation and verbalisation of the IM's ideology. Even though interviewees slowly adopted the ideology, it became apparent that the underlying motives for entry were not based on political aims but rather on personal ones. Srowig et al. (2018) state that even though ideology often plays a secondary role for joining an extremist group in adolescence, it is not insignificant. Instead, it offers individuals perspectives and alternative ways to respond to challenges that may be relevant within their life experiences (ibid.). This underscores the shift from personal motives to political ones. For instance, interviewees referred to political aims such as keeping Germany German but placed an emphasis on personal motives such as participating in a community in which they experience cohesion or having the opportunity to develop their political identity or personal identity.

Interviewees who were established members developed a higher level of ideological alignment. While they continued to refer to personal motives – such as the search for meaning or self-development – they had already adopted core extremist views and expressed them with notable confidence. This distinguished them from other interviewees of Group 1 who had not yet fully internalised the ideological narratives. The latter either misinterpreted key ideological concepts, presenting them in ways that contradicted the IM's perspective, or admitted that they had not engaged deeply with them. Statements from these interviewees remained mainly on a theoretical level and often contained phrases from slogans or explanations used from videos by Sellner.

What these interviewees had in common was that, unlike participants in Group 2, they had not previously spent an extended period engaging with far-right social media content or figures prior to their involvement with the IM (see Sections 4.2.4, 4.2.5). Nevertheless, for most of the interviewees in Group 1, their interest in political topics and support for patriotism made them susceptible to the content of the IM. Interviewees came either through a virtual contact or an offline contact, often followed by a virtual contact across the IM. The IM's social media content resonated with the

interviewees, influencing their decision to join as they perceived the presented narratives and imagery as appealing.

5.1.2 The political becomes personal: joining based on rational motives

In contrast to the interviewees who joined due to emotional motives, those who predominantly emphasised rational motives were in their early adulthood or middle age, with the exception of one interviewee who was at the end of adolescence at the time of joining.

All interviewees had already developed a political mindset even though to a varying extent. Building on research on the development of political attitudes, the developmental stage interviewees were in provided them with more years to form and solidify their political stances (e.g. Sears, 1983, pp. 186–187). Nevertheless, the interesting aspect was that interviewees differed in the political directions they pursued and, in some cases, sympathised with political directions whose agendas were in parts even opposed to each other.

The participants reported that the development of political views started either in their childhood or later in their socialisation process through their peer group, social media and / or other socialisation agents such as school or political parties. However, the ones who emphasised their upbringing as a relevant influence, all hold firm right-wing views and reported about conservative and patriotic values their parents had taught them, resulting in adopting beliefs regarding the importance of home, family and traditions (e.g. Schönflug, 2001). They started engaging in political activities such as joining conservative political parties, reading about political topics, consuming IM-related social media content and even participating in IM-related activities such as demonstrations of PEGIDA or events from the political party AfD.

Other interviewees, including the ones with previous left-wing views, libertarian or conspiracy values or a loose political interest in patriotic and conservative values, started developing right-wing views by coming across the IM through social media activists they had followed for an extended period. Interviewees reported about different online spaces moderated by social media activists that had been categorised as belonging to the far-right extremist spectrum. Upon noticing that the IM's content aligned closely with their evolving views, interviewees felt encouraged to engage further with the group.

It needs to be noted that these interviewees narrated similar experiences of discrimination and exclusion due to their political views in their adolescence such as the interviewees in Group 1, but these were not initially the reasons why they joined. Nevertheless, two aspects need to be considered. First, the IM did not exist when most older interviewees were in their adolescence. Therefore, it is possible that they would have joined the IM at a younger age if it had existed at the time. Second, experiences of discrimination led the interviewees to search for like-minded people who they found in alternative spaces, such as political parties or online communities. Therefore, it was not the search for like-minded people that led them to end up in the IM, it was rather a feeling of dissatisfaction which they no longer wanted to accept, and through the consumption of social media previous non-extremist beliefs became more radical the longer they consumed it. Therefore, representations of the IM on social media resonated with interviewees' pre-existing firm political convictions, reinforcing and amplifying these views, and thereby fostering a gradual intensification of their beliefs. Against this background, for most of the interviewees the social media content alone did not let them join as in contrast to Group 1, it did not show them what they had previously done is unfulfilling. It was rather that their decision to join was triggered by a signal event that threatened their political beliefs which resulted in an impulse decision. These signal events included the public treatment with Martin Sellner after the Christchurch attack that triggered a moral outrage as interviewees interpreted this treatment as unfair and as an attempt to restrict the right of freedom of speech. This aligns with Wagner (2017, p. 210) who argues that Sellner propagates non-violent resistance and is of the opinion that the repression of non-violent activists can be perceived by others as an unfair treatment, which may function as a catalyst for mobilisation (see also Miller-Idriss, 2020, pp. 140–141).

Other interviewees referred to Friday For Future which triggered a dissatisfaction with the political discourse and the need to go against these developments. The media coverage of the refugee movements in 2015 was another trigger that led to reported feelings of powerlessness and the fear that migration will destroy German culture, and its traditions and lead to dangerous future scenarios.

Regardless of the triggering event, all these interviewees experienced an urge to act. They connected with the IM primarily due to political grievances, driven by their perception of a changing political discourse they disagreed with. They recounted, for instance, negative experiences with migrants, emphasised future scenarios like group

rape, and therefore justified their demand to keep Germany German. Most of them stated that they could no longer identify with current political parties and looked for alternative spaces in which their grievances are shared and understood. These interviewees aimed to take action against the perceived grievances. Therefore, their goal-orientated motives were mainly based on a macro level. However, the analysis showed how such goals gained personal significance. Interviewees in Group 2 were at a stage in life where they had already established themselves, with careers, families, or personal commitments. As a result, the threats they perceived were closely tied to the stability they had built, the political views they had developed, and their desire to protect them. Therefore, it was not the case that they came across the IM and decided to join because they were actively searching for a group, it was rather a reaction towards key events which were 'the straw that broke the camel's back'. Therefore, interviewees who had already found spaces where their political views were shared either felt that this was no longer the case, or experienced an urge to increase their level of political activity.

However, none of these interviewees had a trigger event that led to an impulse decision to join. Even though these interviewees engaged intensively with political topics, they did not express a sense of urgency. This was either because they were already politically active in ways aligned with the IM and their participation in the IM was a continuation of their political engagement, or because they were just beginning to engage more deeply with IM-related social media content. Therefore, it was a well-considered decision as the content of the IM resonated with them and they liked what the group offered them.

This also showed that interviewees differed in the form of grievances, but also the extent of grievances varied among them, resulting in individuals perceiving the urgency of joining the IM differently.

Comparing these statements with those of the Group 1, it became evident that these participants (Group 1) did not report experiencing such feelings. While they expressed concerns that Germany is threatened by excessive migration, these concerns appeared to be more adopted from narratives propagated by the IM rather than rooted in deeply developed political convictions or a personal sense of threat.

5.1.3 Summary of relevant findings

The previous sections further discussed the dynamic of motives and how initially emotional motives can shift to political ones, and vice versa. However, this does not mean that the initial motives disappear entirely—they simply play a less dominant role. In terms of the interviewees in Group 1, the analysis showed that these interviewees were at a stage where they were building their identity, and the IM influenced different spheres of identity. Interviewees were able to address different developmental tasks and the disorienting dilemmas they were confronted with. The IM offered them, for instance, the acceptance of their political opinion, a community and a space where they can carry out meaningful activism. Therefore, their motives were more self-orientated.

Interviewees in Group 2 had already established an identity but due to different circumstances they perceived it under threat. The key distinction made in this study is that interviewees of Group 2 prioritised the pursuit of rational goals, which in turn served to fulfil emotional needs. For example, rather than seeking a community due to a lack of friendships, they were motivated by their evolving role as fathers. The shift in political discourse became significant to them as they feared for their children's future.

In sum, all interviewees except for one, reported having engaged with political topics to differing degrees prior to joining the IM. While some held long-standing right-wing political views, with some actively engaged in political activities, others just stated an interest in history and the support of patriotism or had even supported left-wing views before entering the IM, indicating less developed right-wing political views. It showed that the IM was able to build on different forms and levels of political attitudes and unite everyone under the same overarching goals and image that the IM presented to the outside world. This is an interesting finding as the IM was able to meet the participants where they were in their lives and build from there. Moreover, the IM was not only able to connect with individuals who expressed varying levels of political views but also provided interviewees with the perception that joining could fulfil certain needs rooted in rational motives and emotional motives, for some accompanied by experience-oriented motives.

Blum (2021, p. 95) came to the conclusion that individuals who align themselves with the IM often do so due to personal experiences they perceive as unjust. Their identification as 'right-wing' is not tied to specific political goals or ideologies. Instead, the label functions as a framework to express personal grievances and differentiate themselves from others, rather than a declaration of defined political beliefs (ibid.). Even though part of the findings of this study confirms Blum's results, it cannot be applied to all the interviewees as some of them did report firm political beliefs and could explain which political aims they pursue.

Most of these interviewees were not actively seeking to join such a group, but the IM offered a group of like-minded people who accepted their political opinion. This was appealing as the membership was perceived as something which could fulfil a wide range of needs, arising from diverse life situations. It offered both a sense of belonging and reassurance that they were not alone in their views. This adaptability, along with the perception that the group could meet various personal and social needs, suggests that its low-threshold access has the potential to attract a broader spectrum of individuals compared with other extremist groups.

In contrast to previous research on motives for joining right-wing extremist groups, individuals were not looking for a substitute family to compensate for the absence of familial support (Copeland and Marsden, 2020, p. 9). Previous research on right-wing extremism (Heitmeyer and Müller, 1995; see also Copeland and Marsden, 2020, pp. 7, 17), concluded that a lack of emotional bonds within the family made participants more receptive to the far-right scene. In contrast, interviewees of this study did not report deficiencies in emotional family bonds or disrupted home environments; instead, some emphasised stable emotional relationships with their families. They felt comfortable sharing their involvement in the IM which was not met with any resistance. Therefore, in contrast to previous research (e.g. Hopf, 1993), for these interviewees the quality of the relationship served as a circumstance to develop their political mindset rather than serving as a protective factor against the development of such political views (e.g. Boehnke, Hagan and Merkens, 1998, p. 122).

This also fits to the result that other interviewees had stable relationships with their parents but did not see their upbringing as an important influence on their political mindset. These interviewees did not feel comfortable sharing their engagement with

their parents as they knew that their parents would probably question their involvement and might not support it. However, this did not prevent them from joining. Even though they knew their parents would not approve of it, they did not perceive their membership as something which would risk their relationship with them, but they were avoiding the probably difficult or uncomfortable conversation about it, or worried about negative consequences for their family. This, however, underscores a low-threshold access into the IM as interviewees did not perceive their engagement as something that would result in cutting ties with the family. They perceived their engagement as peaceful and non-right-wing extremist activism rather than something that breaks the law (see Section 4.4.2).

Moreover, as the data sample showed, none of the interviewees came from precarious circumstances. Half of them had finished their academic studies or were in the middle of them, the other half was in a stable employment situation, including two interviewees who had their own business. The point the author wants to make is that the IM offers a form of activism which not only connects with the lower socio-economic class and poorly educated people but also the middle / upper class and the highly educated. The idea that right-wing extremism does not stop at a particular social class is not new (e.g. Zick and Mokros, 2023; see also Winlow, Hall and Treadwell, 2017, p. 45). However, the findings of this study suggest that the IM may appeal to a broader, more socially diverse demographic. According to Quent (2024, pp. 16–17) it is dangerous to dismiss extremists as mere fringe elements or irrational individuals as this downplays the severity of the issue and can lead to the underestimation of their potential impact on society. The study showed a diverse picture of members and general statements do not capture the diversity of individuals joining. Therefore, the author of this study does not seek to downplay the ideology of the group, but rather urges a nuanced engagement with manifestations of right-wing extremism. Only through such a differentiated understanding of the underlying conditions of a radicalisation process can effective prevention strategies be developed and implemented (Rothmund and Walther, 2024b, p. 21).

In summary, regardless of the form and intensity of political attitudes or the age of the respondents, a prior interest in political issues was, in almost all cases, a prerequisite for the IM's content to resonate with them. This section has shown that interviewees

joined for different reason-based and goal-orientated motives; however, all shared the experience of being at a stage in life, where they were confronted with various forms of grievance, related to developmental tasks they either struggled to fulfil, or were in the process of readjusting. One key finding of this study is that the IM offers various points of identification, enabling individuals from diverse backgrounds to relate to the group in ways that reflect their personal values, experiences, and aspirations.

Overview of the findings

Development of meaning schemes and perspectives of interviewees driven by emotional motives	Development of meaning schemes and perspectives of interviewees driven by rational motives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early political socialisation through upbringing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Right-wing; Conservative values ○ Patriotic values • Political socialisation in adolescence – through peers / school / social media / political engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Patriotic values, politically interested ○ Left-wing views ○ Not interested in politics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early political socialisation through upbringing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Right-wing; Conservative values ○ Patriotic values • Political socialisation in adolescence – through peers / school / social media / political engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Patriotic values, politically interested ○ Left-wing views ○ Libertarian views ○ Conspiracy beliefs
Reason-based & goal-oriented motives / ‘disorienting dilemmas’ of interviewees driven by emotional motives	Reason-based & goal-oriented motives / ‘disorienting dilemmas’ of interviewees driven by rational motives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discrimination because of political right-wing beliefs / searching for a like-minded community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Offline contact based on the previously developed right-wing political views, followed by social media consumption - Patriotic views were not ‘mainstream compatible’ / lacking a stable peer group <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Virtual contact: IM and in particular Sellner - Disillusioned from previous activism in the left-wing scene / searching for meaningful actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Offline contact by a member of the right-wing scene & virtual contact – video by Sellner (Trigger for impulse decision) ○ Virtual contact – IM video – Brandenburg Gate (Trigger for impulse decision) • Partner was a member of the IM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation at request of the partner / Being a follower to maintain love relationship 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissatisfied with the political discourse in terms of migration politics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Media coverage of the migration movements in 2015 (Trigger for impulse decision) ○ Media coverage of Fridays For Future (Trigger for impulse decision) ○ Offline contact through previous far-right engagement • Dissatisfied with the political discourse in terms of freedom of speech / patriotisms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Media coverage of the treatment of Sellner after the Christchurch attack (Trigger for impulse decision) ○ Videos by the IM • Disillusioned from previous left-wing thinking <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Media coverage of the treatment of Sellner after the Christchurch attack (Trigger for impulse decision) <p><u>Shared goals:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changing the political discourse <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fight for freedom of speech ○ Keeping Germany German ○ Preservation of traditional values ○ Preventing future scenarios

5.2 Research question (2): What makes this group so attractive for joining?

But how did the IM's ideological narratives resonate with the interviewees' varying political interests and prompt them to join—regardless of the presence or absence of a specific trigger event? As the data analysis and the previous section demonstrated, interviewees engaged with the IM based on different motives. The following sections will further explore how the IM establishes connections with individuals, leading them to choose to join the group.

5.2.1 The Martin Sellner method

In line with previous research (Davey and Ebner, 2017), the findings indicate that social media played a pivotal role in introducing people to the IM (Ebner, 2020). However, the question remains: what specifically about the IM's social media content captured the interviewees' attention and made them engage with it, instead of 'simply scrolling past it'?

A key finding is that the impact of the IM's views depended not only on how they were explained but also on who presented them. The analysis identified Martin Sellner as a central figure influencing the interviewees' decisions to join the group. The subsequent section will provide a discussion on how the IM's social media content, with particular emphasis on that produced by Martin Sellner, fostered a connection with the interviewees.

The data analysis demonstrated that the strategy of presenting the IM's ideology as easily accessible and non-extremist (Goetz, 2022) through charismatic individuals, such as Sellner, has proven to be an effective approach in appealing to individuals. This strategy is not new, and can be observed not only in right-wing extremism, but also, for instance, in the field of Islamism, especially with the use of charismatic preachers (e.g. Gendron, 2017). However, this study gained insights into how individuals perceived Sellner and connected with him on different levels.

Interviewees frequently mentioned Sellner as an important influential factor in their decision to join. The interesting aspect is that based on participants' narrations, his

social media content was compatible with different age groups, level of political views as well as interests. Sellner was able to connect with a wide variety of people who then began to follow his social media accounts on a regular basis. One could say that Sellner successfully motivated individuals to join the IM and take the step from the online to the offline world. If he were removed, the group would need another person who brings people together and gives them a structure and aim. As studies have shown, the deletion of several of his social media accounts led him 'lose the communities [...] [he] had built up over time' (Fielitz and Schwarz, 2020, pp. 20–21). This aspect is particularly relevant in the context of prevention (see Section 6.5).

5.2.1.1 Parasocial identification as the glue binding individuals to groups and ideologies

As Section 4.4.1 presented, the participants built parasocial relationships²⁴ with Sellner. Interviewees connected with him and his content on different levels. Older interviewees saw themselves in him – a person who no longer wanted to accept the changing political discourse. They saw in Sellner a person who stands up for his values and beliefs. He represented their political attitudes and fears and was therefore able to trigger a moral outrage when interviewees saw coverage of how he was publicly treated after the Christchurch attack. These interviewees related it to their own situation and felt an urge to act upon perceived negative developments within society and politics, including their freedom of speech. In contrast, interviewees in Group 1 directed their attention more towards Sellner as an individual, including the way he acts and articulates himself. Unlike the interviewees in Group 2, who had the feeling of losing something if they do not act now, for interviewees in Group 1 it was rather a fascination that Sellner sparked through his videos. They emphasised how he explained current problems and possible solutions in an understandable and sympathetic way. Moreover, they mentioned that they built a level of trust and limited the consumption of news to Sellner's channels instead of mainstream media. Interviewees perceived him as someone they could trust and genuinely enjoy listening to him as he explains and speaks about political topics in a relatable and accessible manner.

²⁴ One-sided emotional bonds towards social media actors.

These findings align with research on media reception, including phenomena beyond extremism. For instance, Böckler and Seeger (2010) conducted an interview study with individuals who engaged with self-representations of school shooters on YouTube. Among various forms of appropriation, they identified a group of fans who developed parasocial forms of identification, particularly with the Columbine perpetrators Eric Harris and Dylan Klebold (*ibid.*, pp. 180-182). These connections were based on perceived biographical similarities and shared emotional experiences. As the authors note, the participants 'see themselves mirrored in the statements of the media counterpart' (*ibid.*).

The present study showed that interviewees were looking for spaces in which they felt comfortable or were able to discuss their political views. Some interviewees in Group 2 explained that they could no longer identify with the political discourse and the only place where they could discuss these feelings was the internet. Some stated that they tried to talk with their family about it but received rejection. Interviewees of Group 1 experienced discrimination due to their political views and were looking for alternative spaces where they can, for instance, develop a peer group or experience meaning in their action. As Böckler and Seeger (2010, p. 180-182) argue, individuals experience a sense of recognition and being taken seriously through the formation of parasocial bonds; something they were unable to find in their social environment. One interviewee in the present study described that he could no longer identify with his primary reference groups and instead saw his political views reflected in the social media content of the IM, particularly in that by Martin Sellner.

The findings demonstrate how political opinion can become more extreme. As Sunstein (2009, p. 4) stated 'a good way to create an extremist group [...] is to separate members from the rest of society' (see also Miller-Idriss, 2020, p. 141). As the literature review showed, social media platforms enable echo chambers where 'already polarised' views are strengthened without external corrections (Vorländer, Herold and Schäller, 2018, pp. 23–25). In such spaces conspiracy theories and the devaluation of or hatred against other groups can function as coping mechanisms to help individuals manage feelings of loss and marginalisation (Rothmund and Walther, 2024b, pp. 20–21). The analysis showed that the more intensely someone had engaged with political views in the past, the more likely they were to be triggered by a

situation that threatened their own political beliefs. Interviewees who were highly engaged in social media and IM-related content described reacting impulsively when they feared that the propagated conspiracy theories, such as ethnopluralism, might be put into practice. Research indicates that individuals at the far ends of the political spectrum, both left and right, are more prone to conspiracy beliefs compared to those with moderate views (van Prooijen, Krouwel and Pollet, 2015, p. 575)

The statements, particularly from interviewees of Group 2 revealed that they had already spent several months to several years in far-right online groups. When asked about their favourite Youtubers, it became apparent that most of them named several Youtubers who are categorised as right-wing extremist (see Section 4.4.2). Moreover, due to the large amount of daily news content, interviewees limited their consumption to selected social media channels, resulting in spending more and more time within these ideological echo chambers.

Various researchers have underscored the changing world of social media and its role in opinion-forming processes. For instance, Harff and Schmuck (2024, p. 3) highlight the fact that social media enables 'ordinary people to act as producers of media content'. This leads to difficulties in distinguishing between professional and non-professional journalism (Wunderlich, Hölig and Hasebrink, 2022, p. 569) which bears greater risk for people who are at the beginning of a radicalisation process or have not yet embarked on that path. These individuals might be attracted by the political activism without seeing the extremist ideology behind it or by the group of young people and the various leisure activities on offer.

However, to persuade individuals within these online groups, the content must be both convincing and appealing. This is where key media figures such as Sellner become significant. Sellner is not referred to as the 'poster boy' (Schäller, 2019, p. 197) without reason. Looking at his content and the statements of the interviewees one can see that Sellner uses casualness as a strategy to present the ideology as normal, whilst presenting himself as approachable. As previously mentioned, Faiola and Mekhennet (2024) described Sellner as a 'charismatic pied piper who expounds far-right thought with disarming charm'.

One notable aspect is how skilled Sellner is in navigating social media, as well as in managing his public presence and the effects it creates. Schäller (2019, p. 195) claims that Sellner understands how to manage public perception and strategically uses counter-narratives, including alternative media, to maintain control over his image. However, Sellner does not only control his own image, but also that of supporters of the IM. He reacts directly to certain situations in which his image and the image of the IM could lead to individuals questioning their support for the IM. However, by applying these strategies, individuals quickly get an alternative explanation offered so they feel secure in their support. And even though some events might lead individuals to question the ideology, Sellner serves an alternative explanation and knows exactly how to use certain media strategies to win over the target group. Therefore, Sellner is able to provide his audience with new ideas / narratives and challenge their 'old ways of thinking' (Wiktorowicz, 2005, p. 5).

The analysis showed that, despite the fact that Sellner has a background in neo-Nazi structures, interviewees gradually adopted the narrative that individuals who previously joined extremist groups had done so simply because no alternative, such as the IM, had existed at the time. They began to believe that Sellner could not be a Nazi – as previously assumed based on media coverage or on opinions transmitted by socialisation agents such as teachers. Instead, the interviewees increasingly placed their trust in the IM's counter-narrative, blaming former sources of socialisation for shaping views that, in their eyes, no longer reflected reality. Many interviewees described Sellner as sympathetic, intelligent, and capable of explaining political issues in a clear and relatable manner. His self-presentation stood in stark contrast to the 'Nazi' label initially ascribed to him, creating a dissonance that increased their openness to his ideological framing.

This process can be understood in the context of political ideologies functioning as 'cognitive interpretive and justificatory structures' which serve individuals as ways to re-interpret perceived grievances (Rothmund and Walther, 2024a, p. 33). As the authors argue, blaming others for their deprivation experiences, such as politicians or migrants provides cognitive and emotional relief (ibid.).

If individuals follow content like the one by Sellner frequently and are confronted with these 'normalised' views without having a corrective, then they can adopt them until they are convinced of them at some point. Through frequent exposure to content that

presented various interpretations and narratives in a way that remained within legal boundaries and avoided direct connections to violence or extremism, interviewees gradually adopted these perspectives. This demonstrates that interviewees connected with Sellner and the IM on different levels and depending on the stage of life and socialisation experiences they appropriated the content differently. They connected with him both as a person and as a representation of the IM's broader ideals.

Nevertheless, not all interviewees described such a relationship with Sellner, focusing instead on the appearance of the IM in general. For them, it was not specifically Sellner, but rather the characteristics of the IM that interviewees perceived as unique.

5.2.1.2 The normality of extremism

Following on from the previous discussions, one aspect that is important to emphasise again is the normalisation of extremist views. As the literature review showed, the use of different social media strategies like the use of humour – 'memes, jokes, and emoji' (Miller-Idriss, 2020, p. 151) or different gamification tools make extremist content appear less extremist and more accessible (e.g. Davey and Ebner, 2017, p. 28). In alignment with Davey and Ebner (2017, p. 28) who highlighted the 'entertainment value' of such strategies and their ability to 'incentivise participation', interviewees in this study confirmed their appreciation for such approaches, noting that they liked it because it is not 'dead-serious'.

The results of this study demonstrated that the IM frames and presents a dehumanising ideology in a way that resonates with the interviewees by aligning with their current perspectives and personal situations. In doing so, the IM successfully transforms individuals into devoted followers. Sellner and the IM's ability to frame their ideology in a way that aligns with individuals' personal motives creates a low-threshold entry point. Many do not perceive their involvement as linked to far-right extremism. At the same time, those who are aware of the ideology's incompatibility with democratic principles may consciously use the IM's seemingly moderate front to hide their actual convictions. As presented in the data analysis, interviewees as well as participants of the regional meetings and Christmas parties referred to the negative public image of the IM which they perceived as an unfair treatment. Some of them

referred several times to the opportunity to show themselves as 'who they really are'. This narrative is also used as a strategy by the IM and its members.

This thesis argues that new strategies in far-right extremism make it easier to join as people can better justify their membership by pointing to apparently harmless content. Even though the field of social media is constantly changing and with it its actors which carries the risk that research findings might be 'quickly outdated or even obsolete' (Schulze *et al.*, 2024, p. 188), the aim of binding individuals to their extremist content remains the same. Therefore, in agreement with Schulze et al. (2024, pp. 187–188) it is relevant to explore what such online spaces offer and how these 'affordances' resonate with individuals. According to them, researchers need to 'differentiate spaces, modalities, technical features, and their potential contributions to societal, group, and individual dynamics in digital environments' (*ibid.*).

As mentioned in the analysis, Heitmeyer, Freiheit and Sitzler (2020, p. 286) point to the danger that repeated exposure to certain ideas or practices may lead to their uncritical acceptance, as what is repeatedly encountered may gradually lose its exceptional character and become part of the perceived norm (*ibid.*). During the interviews, the participants verbalised opinions that conflict with the Basic Law, but they did not perceive them as such. For instance, some believed that a different ethnic background is a disqualifying criterion for immigration to Germany, which, in their eyes, was an established fact.

When examining the use of the IM's ideological concepts, the analysis revealed that not all interviewees shared the same understanding. While some believed that a different ethnic background is an excluding criterion for someone migrating to Germany, others did not view a cultural background as a barrier per se, but believed that migrants must fully assimilate to the German culture.

Following the model of reception cascades, individuals bring their prior experiences and societal discourses into media reception, shaping their initial interpretations (Krotz, 2007). The analysis revealed considerable variation in how ideology was appropriated. In some cases, it served as a lens through which individuals reinterpreted personal experiences; in others, it fulfilled social or symbolic functions, such as belonging or recognition. The ideology became meaningful through its emotional, cognitive, and biographical resonance. This illustrates a central mechanism of radicalisation: the mutual reinforcement of personal experience and ideological

narrative. Ideology gains meaning through emotional and rational motives. It provides interpretive frameworks for processing feelings of insecurity, exclusion, and disorientation.

5.2.2 Beyond ideology – activism unlike any other: youthful, professional, and non-violent

Besides the professional use of social media, the interviewees perceived the IM as a space where they can fulfil their needs and address their individual motives. The analysis showed that the IM provides individuals with a certain lifestyle (Bruns, Glösel and Strobl, 2014; Blum, 2021), ranging from leisure activities to digital habits or the chance to take on leadership roles or tasks that require a certain amount of responsibility. Interviewees found these aspects appealing as they allowed to further develop their social and political identity.

As outlined in Section 4.4, the majority of the interviewees highlighted that they found no comparable alternative to the IM. The unique characteristics that interviewees perceive as setting the IM apart from other groups include the dissemination of a non-extremist yet patriotic ideology and a non-violent, peaceful and professional approach. Moreover, they highlighted the fact that the IM engages in metapolitics rather than party politics and emphasised the youthful and activist approach.

Supplementing the earlier discussions in relation to the different motives, the study found that young people liked the youthful and modern approach as they stressed the activism with people of a similar age as something they found appealing. This is in line with Copeland and Marsden (2020, p. 4) who found that ideology is often not ‘a strong motivator’ when it comes to joining a right-wing extremist group; instead ‘violence, music and aesthetics’ function as pull factors into the group. Therefore, particularly young people who are not yet ideologically grounded are initially drawn to its non-extremist aspects, with extremist content being adopted later.

However, this appeal was not limited to young people; older interviewees also emphasised that the IM’s approach felt new and dynamic. They viewed it as a potential driver of change, particularly because of its strong youth involvement – something they viewed as necessary to achieve the group’s goals. The difference between the

younger and older interviewees was reflected in the form of engagement. While young people liked participating in the front row of activism, even if not all in form of climbing buildings, older interviewees mostly liked that young people did, but saw their role in supporting the group (organising activities, contributing with own ideas as well as partly financing the activism) as well as offering young people some guidance rather than engaging directly in high-risk activism.

Moreover, almost all individuals had in common that they liked participating in a form of activism that had a certain level of class. Some concerns were raised that the appearance could limit the target group. However, the idea of joining a far-right extremist group in which violence and swearing is part of the agenda was not something interviewees found attractive, or something they had participated in. This showed that the IM was able to offer an alternative to previous right-wing extremist groups. While previous studies revealed that the use of violence combined with the experience of thrill and action were often found with members of right-wing extremist groups (e.g. Rommelspacher, 2006), interviewees of this study distanced themselves from it. However, although the IM does not promote activism through physical violence, it does advocate a form of violence through its ideology. One could argue that by employing such an approach, the IM is able to appeal to broader sections of society.

Even though the data sample is small, one may ask whether the variety found in this study is coincidental or rather indicative of a characteristic feature of the group itself. It can be suggested that the group deliberately offers ideological entry points at a low threshold. Its core ideas require neither prior knowledge nor complex ideological training. This simplicity is striking and aligns with the access criteria presented on the IM's own website (see Section 2.3.4.1).

The perception that the group is attractive arises from the diverse ways in which individuals engage with and appropriate the IM's narratives and content. This aligns with Blum (2023, p. 29), who claims that the IM offers different narratives to attract potential members.

These modes of appropriation are influenced by a combination of factors, including an individual's personal biography and their current developmental stage. Specifically, the group's flexibility in addressing a wide range of needs allows individuals to

perceive it as fulfilling their personal and social aspirations. This adaptability enables the group to resonate with people at various stages of life and circumstances, creating an inclusive and appealing environment for potential members.

The IM offers an identification model for the individual without leaving them alone with it. At the same time, it offers a sense of belonging through collective actions which serve to validate and give meaning to the newly adopted identity. These actions are not fixed in content or form; each individual can choose a type and intensity of action that suits their personal needs.

5.3 Research question (3): What does an engagement look like and do the motives influence how someone engages in the IM?

This section will address the third research question by building on the previous sections, thereby integrating the findings of all research questions through the main sensitising concept of Transformative Radicalization Theory.

5.3.1 Radicalisation in the IM

Radicalisation within the IM can be understood through the lens of Transformative Radicalization Theory which follows the idea of viewing radicalisation as a learning process. Wilner and Dobouloz (2020, p. 37) believe that a cognitive and emotional shift motivates individuals to go further on the radicalisation route and undergo a transformation process, as they adopt new beliefs that justify their actions. Building on the previous sections, the following section sheds light on how the interviewees went through such a process, resulting in their engagement in the IM.

5.3.1.1 Meaning schemes and perspectives

As Section 5.1 discussed, interviewees narrated different reason-based and goal-oriented motives (Schütz, 1932) that contributed to their decision to join the IM. Wilner and Dobouloz (2010) claim that before individuals experience disorienting dilemmas that prompt ideological shifts, they function within established meaning schemes and meaning perspectives that shape their worldview and serve as filters for interpreting information and guiding decision-making.

All interviewees in this study, apart from one, expressed an interest in political topics, but differed in the extent of their political engagement. While some expressed only a casual political interest, others had a history of longstanding active political engagement. In addition, interviewees differed in the political direction they had previously pursued, ranging from previous left-wing views to conservative, patriotic and libertarian views. The development of political views was primarily influenced by socialisation instances such as parents, peer groups, schools, and social media. While some interviewees talked at length about their upbringing as an influential factor in their political development (see also Schönplflug, 2001), other interviewees did not make it an issue and rather talked about later points in their lives. Following TR, interviewees' learned meaning perspectives involve, for instance, a conservative, patriotic or an ethnocentric perspective which they built upon on in their further socialisation process.

Since the researcher found a wide age range and different points of entry into the IM, it became evident that interviewees were at varying developmental stages when they decided to join. This also influences the extent of political engagement, as individuals in adolescence have limited time to develop firmly established political beliefs. This developmental stage is primarily characterised by exploration and the process of identifying political orientations with which they resonate. Therefore, interviewees in Group 1 mostly narrated a casual political interest, a sympathy for patriotic views or support for left-wing views. Only one interviewee, who emphasised the role of upbringing, expressed firmly right-wing political views. In contrast, interviewees of Group 2 already narrated a political mindset that they had developed over the years. However, one finding was that not all interviewees joined the IM based on previously developed far-right extremist views. Therefore, the analysis identified different forms of transformation processes:

- Tapping into a loose interest – Transformation from less developed political views to an extremist ideology
- Transformation through a shift from left-wing to right-wing extremist views
- Transformation through reinforcing established political right-wing views

5.3.1.2 *Triggering and changing phase*

When looking at the reasons given for joining, these could be categorised into two main motives. The reasons were primarily rooted in emotional, with some accompanied by experience-oriented motives or rational motives. Following TR, individuals reach a point at which currently held beliefs are critically assessed and questioned through the experience of 'disorienting dilemmas'. Such disorienting dilemmas can, for instance, challenge one's own identity or existing worldview, and the reassessment of these aspects can fuel a radicalisation process if new ideas and ways of addressing these dilemmas are offered (see Section 3.5.1). Examining this point is particularly interesting as it provides insight into the why and how of a transformation process and reveals the motives and factors driving this change.

This is in alignment with radicalisation research in which the interplay of different factors had been strengthened by various researchers (Borum, 2011a, p. 8; Lindekilde, Malthaner and O'Connor, 2019, p. 24; Marsden, Malkki and Busher, 2024, p. 5). Moreover, it is also widely acknowledged that an individual does not embark on a trajectory of radicalisation in a linear or predictable manner (see Section 2.7.1). This was no different with interviewees of this study. There was no one single way of joining (Rothmund and Walther, 2024a, p. 32). Instead, interviewees described different motives and influencing factors that led them to the IM.

Joining the IM happened through two main ways, either through social media or a personal contact, followed by consuming IM's social media content. In all cases, social media content, additionally reinforced by personal contact for some, incited interviewees to critically reassess their previous beliefs, leading to a cognitive shift that prompted altered behaviours or actions. However, since interviewees differed in terms of the form and extent of political views such a cognitive shift happened to a varying extent. For instance, interviewees who had dealt with left-wing views over a certain time did not have strong developed meaning schemes and perspectives regarding right-wing views.

According to TR, a transformation can be either 'abrupt and focused in time' or 'a more gradual and cumulative process' (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2011, pp. 421–422).

Therefore, it can be triggered by one crucial situation, or it can be the result of a cumulative process of triggers that lead to change. Both change processes were articulated by the interviewees. This study demonstrates that for most of the interviewees their transformation process happened gradually, however, the decision to join the IM was for some triggered by a single event. Only a few interviewees reported a more abrupt shift which was explained by the fact that they had previously held left-wing views.

Interviewees who joined predominantly because of emotional motives mostly described not a single event that made them join, it was rather a frequent consumption of social media content that led them to the decision to join or a social contact which made them aware of the IM, followed by the consumption of social media. These interviewees already expressed an interest in right-wing political views. Its consumption served as a disorienting dilemma as interviewees started to slowly adapt to the ideology of the IM. In this context the development of parasocial bonds played a significant role (see Section 4.4.1). The ones who described such an abrupt shift had previously joined the left-wing scene and when they became aware of the IM through social media they described a feeling of having a political awakening based on experiencing disillusionment with what they have been doing so far and categorised it as unfair.

Therefore, regarding the interviewees in their adolescence the goals they sought to fulfil were less related to the fulfilment of ideological goals but personal ones. The interviewees experienced more meaning in their actions by participating in a group that offered them a sense of community and the feeling of being accepted with their political views. They described a more abrupt shift, as IM's social media content led them to perceive themselves as being on the 'losing' side, prompting a desire to change it. This sparked a process of reflecting on their actions, ultimately leading them to feel that their engagement no longer held any meaning and leaving them disillusioned.

In contrast, interviewees in Group 2 placed greater emphasis on ideological goals. While interviewees of Group 1 focused on fulfilling developmental tasks they struggled with, these interviewees felt the need to readjust these tasks. The disillusionment was less about changing their actions entirely and more about redirecting their

engagement, as they felt their previous sources of motivation had evolved in ways they could no longer identify with. This is in line with TR, according to which an individual 'comes to realize that the old reality simply no longer exists and a new one must be established' (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2011, p. 423).

Other interviewees were already engaged in IM-related activities but noticed the need to increase their efforts. This shows that, for these interviewees, the transformation of beliefs had already occurred prior to their involvement in the IM, making their participation a continuation of their political engagement.

For most of these interviewees, key events – such as the refugee movements or the treatment of Martin Sellner after the Christchurch attack, played a significant role. They either perceived their political rights as being threatened or feared future developments.

Following TR, the process of transformation involves self-reflection, during which individuals experience emotions such as 'fear, anger, guilt or shame' (see Section 3.5.2). This is followed by questioning and a critical reassessment of prior beliefs and considering alternative perspectives. This process is strengthened if an individual notices that their discontent is shared by others (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2020, p. 46; see also McCauley and Moskalenko 2008). As the authors state: 'radical sentiment can help social cohesion among like-minded individuals' (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2020, p. 44). Moreover, they argue that connecting with like-minded individuals, whether through online platforms or in-person interactions, further solidifies these emerging perspectives, values, and self-concepts (ibid., p. 46). This transformation is complete when the individual fully integrates the newly adopted worldview into their daily life and decision-making (ibid.).

In relation to the study, especially through the consumption of IM's social media content this process was reinforced. The content resonated with interviewees' pre-existing firm political convictions, reinforcing and amplifying these views, and thereby fostering a gradual intensification of their beliefs. Therefore, the representations of the IM on social media connected with interviewees on different levels:

- Social media content strategically aligned with interviewees' loosely held political interests, using them as entry points to engage them further with their extremist propaganda.
- Social media resonated with interviewees' pre-existing firm political convictions, reinforcing and amplifying these views, thereby fostering a gradual intensification of their beliefs.
- In certain cases, social media content incited interviewees to critically reassess their previous activities, leading to a cognitive shift that prompts altered behaviours or actions.

During this process, individuals explore 'new roles', 'relationships', and ways to engage with their evolving beliefs (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2010, p. 46). This process involves 'acquiring knowledge and skills for implementing one's plans' (Mezirow, 2009, p. 94) Accordingly, individuals test 'new roles' and as they gain experience and confidence, these roles become more established, ultimately leading to a full integration of their new perspective into everyday life (ibid.). This study found that the IM attracted a diverse group of individuals by offering various forms of engagement that fulfilled different needs. It provided opportunities for self-efficacy and a sense of purpose, such as through leadership roles or specific lifestyles (see Chapter 4).

It should be noted that TR encompasses the process of transformation up to the point where an individual engages in violent activities (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2020, p. 44). However, this study argues that the theory can also be applied to non-violent activism, at least in terms of non-physical violence.

5.3.2 Going the extra mile or keeping it low? A lifestyle of engagement from leisure to leadership

The previous sections showed that different sequences of life events and factors played a role in the individual decision to join the IM. However, even though interviewees found similar things appealing the data analysis also revealed that the transformation process of the interviewees led to different roles they took on and therefore a differing level of engagement. While for some the engagement in the IM took up most of their everyday life and their professional and private lives were built

around it, other interviewees enjoyed spending time with the IM but only to the extent that it did not restrict their everyday life. These different forms of engagement were also reflected in how someone engaged in the IM. While some took on leadership positions or certain tasks with a higher degree of responsibility and were willing to sacrifice personal benefits, other interviewees were just participating in regional meetings or actions but without strongly committing themselves to the IM. The question left was whether a link exists between certain reason-based and goal-orientated motives and the level of engagement and if not, which motives and factors contribute to a differing level of engagement.

The data analysis showed that the level of engagement was influenced by the individual motives, but these were not the only influencing factors. Besides the motives, the level of engagement was influenced by these aspects:

- The regional group's structure
- The regional structure of the far-right scene
- Length of membership

Therefore, there was not a combination of factors that led either to a high, moderate or low level of engagement. It was rather the case that different factors had an influence. These factors create a dynamic interplay that determines the depth and nature of an individual's involvement in the IM, which will be further discussed in the following sections.

5.3.2.1 Influence of age-related motives

The analysis revealed age-related motives for joining, showing that the interviewees' engagement varied based on their life circumstances and the priority they placed on the IM. The examination of the interviewees' motives that contribute to the level of engagement demonstrated that a high level of engagement within the IM was predominantly carried out by individuals who had already been actively involved in political activities prior to joining. Thus, their participation in the IM was not completely new to them but rather a continuation of their existing political engagement.

This aligns with findings by McAdam (1986), who examined participation in the Freedom Summer Project, a campaign within the broader Civil Rights Movement. He

developed a '[m]odel of recruitment to high-risk/cost activism' (McAdam, 1986, p. 69) and concluded that microstructural factors are essential in driving a high-risk/cost participation (ibid., p. 87). Even though McAdam was not researching far-right extremism, part of his findings can be transferred to the IM. The author claims that participants were more connected within activist networks than those who withdrew, suggesting that these connections, rather than ideological commitment alone, played a decisive role in their involvement (ibid.). He argues that 'a prior history of activism and integration into supportive networks acts as the structural 'pull' encouraging the individual to make good on his or her strongly held beliefs' (ibid., p. 64).

Interviewees of the present study who had been politically active prior to joining the IM showed a high level of engagement within the group. The study showed that regardless of the form of political engagement the fact that they had been politically active before they joined made interviewees susceptible for joining the IM. Following TR, in a transformation process, individuals need to establish their roles. These interviewees had already gained an understanding of how activism works, which reduced their hesitation and allowed them to begin with a shorter familiarisation period.

In addition, the analysis showed that interviewees mentioned some aspects that prevented them from a higher level. McAdam (1986, p. 70) speaks in his model of '[b]iographical availability' which he defines as 'the absence of personal constraints that may increase the costs and risks of movement participation, such as full-time employment, marriage, and family responsibilities'. Interviewees of this study were involved in different private responsibilities which they also used as explanation for their form of activism. Cragin (2014, p. 348), who examined deterring factors for an involvement in terrorism, named four factors: 'logistical costs, financing, family obligations, and fear of repression'. The author emphasises that family obligations can discourage individuals from joining violent extremist groups, but they are rarely decisive on their own (ibid., p. 344). Her examination of various sources of literature reveals multiple cases in which individuals engaged in terrorism despite being married or having children, suggesting that family responsibilities alone are often insufficient to prevent individuals from taking part in terrorism (ibid.). In the case of the interviewees in the present study, having a family was mostly described as a factor that reinforced their engagement (Pilkington, 2023, p. 12). They saw themselves as responsible for taking care of their families and considered it their duty to contribute to

changing the political discourse. While some interviewees joined the group with this aim in mind, they also cited family obligations as a limiting factor that prevented a higher level of engagement due to limited time resources.

Moreover, the fear of repression also played a role, particularly among newcomers (see subsequent section) and interviewees who were in their adolescence. In line with developmental tasks, most younger interviewees prioritised their studies or educational training and acted more cautiously regarding potential risks. Older interviewees, who were new to the IM, showed a degree of caution as well, as they did not want to risk, for instance, losing their job.

5.3.2.2 Length of membership

However, the engagement level is not solely determined by these motives. It is also affected by factors such as the length of membership, as prolonged involvement often deepens commitment and broadens roles within the group. The length of membership played an important role particularly for those who had no previous experiences in political activism as they needed to get familiar with it and find their own role within the group (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2020). Most interviewees were more cautious and insecure and consequently, showed a low or moderate level of engagement. When comparing the interviewees, almost all, apart from one, who joined the IM for more than one year showed a high level of engagement. In contrast, all interviewees who showed a moderate or low level of engagement had joined the IM for less than six months. Following TR, with increasing length of membership, interviewees started showing a higher level of engagement because they had become familiar with the group, its members, its goals, and found their own role within it. This led to the fact that they felt more comfortable in the IM and / or willing to take on more responsibility. By joining the IM interviewees took on the role as members even though they have shaped this role differently. Nevertheless, there is no automatism that with increasing length of membership the level of engagement increases. The study showed that depending on their goal-orientated motives, the level of engagement can take on different forms. For interviewees seeking a sense of community to fill a gap in their lives, their involvement tended to be less time-intensive and more socially focused. In contrast, those driven by a sense of urgency to influence the political discourse engaged in more intensive and / or action-driven participation. This suggests that the

perceived purpose of joining the IM shapes not only the type of engagement but also the time and effort individuals are willing to dedicate. Nevertheless, the level of engagement can not only increase over time but also decrease, as illustrated in this study by two interviewees who joined the IM but later left the group. Due to personal circumstances, which they prioritise, their level of engagement changed.

5.3.2.3 Regional structures

Nevertheless, even if someone becomes familiar with their role in the IM, they still require regional structures if they want to participate in offline activism — which points to another influencing factor. The data analysis revealed regional differences between groups in the East and West of Germany which had an impact on the level of engagement an individual showed. The results demonstrate that the regional structure as well as the internal structure of the group can either facilitate or hinder the level of engagement of a person in the IM. Comparing the groups in the East with the groups in the West of Germany, it becomes apparent that the groups in the East operated differently due to the possibility of having:

- more personnel,
- a developed internal structure,
- financial and material resources and,
- existing structures of other far-right institution or actors.

Therefore, the internal structure of the regional groups in the East was more developed in comparison to the ones in the West of Germany. However, it needs to be noted that one group in the West of Germany was still in the build-up phase and therefore, in the process of establishing internal structures. However, even the ones who belonged to the established members in the West of Germany, mentioned that their geographical position is not suitable for engaging in the broader network of the IM, including taking part in activities or strengthening the network across different regional groups. The internal structure of the IM posed significant challenges to participating in IM-activism as confirmed by statements from interviewees from the West of Germany. They were looking for more activities, they can take part in, but due to the internal and regional structure it made it difficult for them to do so. Therefore, it carries the risk that younger

interviewees who look for experiencing thrill and action or various social events might leave again if their desires will be left unfulfilled.

Members in Saxony were closely connected with other actors who are well-known in the field of the far right, and which operate in the regional area (e.g. Rippl, 2019). For instance, some of the members had participated already as speakers at PEGIDA demonstrations. Moreover, actors such as Götz Kubitschek and his IfS operated in the immediate vicinity.

The findings show that the groups in the East of Germany can draw back on a larger network to operate with in comparison to the ones in the West of Germany who needed to work with the few resources they have. This also resulted in the fact that interviewees from the West of Germany were not all connected with interviewees from the East of Germany.

This aligns with Cragin (2014, p. 344) who claims that 'logistical costs pose somewhat of a barrier to potential recruits, especially if they are required to travel beyond their immediate residence'. Interviewees in this study identified the regional location as a barrier to participating in activities taking place in the East, which in turn prevents them from building strong connections with members based there. This underscores the importance of pre-existing structures (Berntzen and Weisskircher, 2016, p. 563; see also Hermansson *et al.*, 2020, p. 72), meaning the regional structures of the far-right scene in which the activism takes places. The role of the regional area and far-right attitudes were the focus of study for various researchers (e.g. Quent and Schulz, 2015). This study showed that the geographical location makes it harder for interviewees in the West to participate in events that happen in the East, unless they are willing to spend much time on travelling which conflicts especially for the older interviewees with their private and professional life. Following TR, the regional structures in the East of Germany offer more possibilities for exploring new roles. The regional infrastructure and organisational structure of the local IM group can therefore either facilitate or limit opportunities for active engagement. Through professional and stable structures, individuals were able to implement their new developed ideas and roles into their daily life.

In sum, the IM offers an environment in which one can feel comfortable; offering a variety of forms of engagement. Therefore, it can be argued that the possibility of tailor-made memberships makes it easier to join even for people who have less time or do not want to be involved so much. While other far-right extremist groups, such as Skinhead groups, have a limited portfolio and require members to have an affinity for violence and a certain level of physical fitness, the IM provides diverse areas of activity. This flexibility allows individuals with different interests and at various stages of life to participate.

However, when comparing the results of this study with earlier research, particularly studies beyond those on the IM, certain aspects must be considered. As outlined in Section 2.7.2, various scholars have investigated why individuals join right-wing extremist groups. Yet, each group has its own distinct characteristics, making direct comparisons between them difficult and methodologically imprecise. Therefore, while studies on groups within the right-wing extremist spectrum can serve as 'point[s] of reference' (Kajta, 2020, p. 136) it is crucial to account for the unique nature of the group under investigation. Additionally, one cannot disregard the factor of time in which the receptive research is conducted and the national context in which the group under study operates (*ibid.*). Regarding the IM, it should be noted that the research took place during a period when the group transitioned from being classified as a suspected case by the Office for the Protection of the Constitution to being officially recognised as right-wing extremist. As for the motives for joining, the analysis revealed that interviewees were often drawn to the IM by specific 'signal events' that happened several years ago, such as the refugee movements in 2015. This suggests that individuals joining today might reference different events, though the core motivations, such as political grievances, likely remain consistent over time, despite variations in specific triggers. This is in line with scholarly work which has shown that despite significant external events and changes in social or political contexts, the fundamental motivations and values of individuals joining a particular group within the far-right extremist spectrum often remain the same or do not change that much (e.g. Kajta, 2020, p. 138). Nevertheless, it is important to reflect on these aspects to develop a nuanced understanding.

6 Conclusion and outlook

This study aimed to find answers to the question of why individuals join the IM, which has been approached by answering the following research questions:

- (1) Which motives and influencing factors contribute to an individual's decision to participate in the IM?
- (2) What creates the perception that this group is attractive to join?
- (3) What does an engagement look like and do the motives influence how someone engages in the IM?

The following sections briefly summarise the chapters of this study and present the theoretical contribution, practical implications and limitations of the study, followed by recommendations for further research.

6.1 Summary of literature review and methodology

The introduction outlines the rationale for and aim of this study. It demonstrated that the right-wing extremist scene has evolved over the years, adopting new forms and strategies to attract individuals (see Chapter 1). One example of these changes is the IM. However, limited empirical knowledge exists focusing on the motives and inner perspective of the individuals who feel attracted to join this group (see Section 2.5). These aspects, however, are crucial to examine in order to understand why individuals choose to join the IM.

Chapter 2 outlined the current state of literature on the IM. First, key terms and concepts are clarified, emphasising that right-wing extremism encompasses multiple definitions and that scholars differ in their classification of the IM within this broad spectrum. While some align with the assessment of the German Federal Office for the Protection of the Constitution (2024), viewing the IM as part of the New Right, others hold differing perspectives (e.g. Pfahl-Traughber, 2019, 2022). Nevertheless, there is consensus that the IM's ideology draws heavily from the principles and actors of the New Right. The literature review revealed that scholars have examined various

aspects of the IM, including, for instance, its historical connections and the far-right extremist nature of the group. Moreover, multiple studies have explored the IM's use of social media and its recruitment strategies (see Section 2.3). However, empirical knowledge based on face-to-face methods remains limited, particularly regarding individual motives for joining. Studies that include face-to-face methods with IM members often do not only focus on the IM but also on other right-wing groups (see Section 2.4).

In order to address this research gap, the researcher employed a qualitative research approach, outlined in Chapter 3. Based on 14 semi-structured interviews and the participation of three regional meetings, two Christmas parties and the observation of one demonstration, the research questions were explored. The study was grounded in a constructivist research paradigm which views knowledge as being constructed by individuals through their experiences and interactions with the world (see Chapter 3). Consequently, it emphasises the existence of multiple realities rather than a single, objective reality. Since the study's aim is the examination of individual motives for joining, a constructivist approach is particularly fitting.

Building on this, the researcher employed a modified Constructivist Grounded Theory approach (see section 3.3). To guide the analysis, a sensitising concept served as a framework, drawing primarily on the TR (Wilner and Dubouloz, 2011), supplemented by elements of Havighurst's (1974) developmental theory, Schütz's (1932) perspective regarding 'because' and 'in order' motives and theories of media reception and reception cascades (Horton and Wohl, 1956; Krotz, 2007) (see Section 3.5).

6.2 Summary of the main findings

The main findings of this study are as follows:

Motives and pathways for joining the IM

- Interviewees became involved with the IM at various stages of their lives, driven by two primary motives: emotional, with some also influenced by experience-orientated motives, and rational.

- These motives are shaped by developmental tasks that interviewees either struggled to fulfil or perceived as being threatened, requiring them to readjust tasks they had previously resolved. Consequently, the motives align with and vary according to age-dependent developmental tasks.
- The study shows that individuals joined the IM via diverse biographical paths and motives, rather than through specific socialisation processes. Despite this diversity, elements of their trajectories can be seen as functionally equivalent, as they addressed similar developmental needs.
- The research study examined different dynamics of motives, highlighting how personal motives can become more political and political motives can gain more personal significance
 - The personal becomes political
 - The findings indicate that interviewees in Group 1 primarily emphasised emotional motives, for some accompanied by experience-oriented motives, and encountered difficulties, such as forming relationships with like-minded peers, developing a political mindset or finding meaning in their actions.
 - Most of them did not report a firm far-right political mindset before they came across the IM. These interviewees identified themselves as patriots or articulated a profound attachment to their homeland but described themselves as politically mainstream or even apolitical. Other interviewees described a shift from previously left-wing to right-wing views and only one younger interviewee reported of firm right-wing views before encountering the IM.
 - Through joining the IM, these interviewees gradually adopted its ideology, as they perceived the group as a way to fulfil emotional needs, for instance, by providing a space with peers who accepted them or offering leadership roles that gave their actions a sense of purpose
 - The political becomes personal
 - Older interviewees, who were in early adulthood or middle age, narrated that they perceived their established political convictions as being under threat. Accordingly, rational motives played a more prominent role.

- These interviewees identified specific political orientations – such as conservatism, libertarianism, right-wing extremist ideologies, and even left-wing political views – and most described a continuous refinement of their political perspectives or the reinforcement of preexisting political views.
 - Most interviewees were not planning to engage in the IM but due to an increasing dissatisfaction with the political and societal discourse they felt that they can no longer identify with the status quo.
- An important conclusion of this study is that the IM provides multiple points of identification, allowing individuals from different backgrounds to connect with the group based on their values, experiences, and goals.
 - Accordingly, the extent of political views is not decisive for joining but an interest in political topics is a prerequisite for joining.
 - Interviewees experienced different key events (see Section 4.2) that served as ‘disorienting dilemmas’, resulting in interviewees strengthening and radicalising their previous beliefs, rethinking their previous beliefs and changing them or starting to develop a certain view in the first place.

The role of social media in the radicalisation process

- The consumption of virtual content of the IM, particularly content from Martin Sellner, was central before entering the group. Most interviewees had engaged intensively with IM-related content on social media prior to encountering the IM itself through this content, while others came across the IM first and then began to engage more deeply with its content. Others were introduced to the IM through personal contacts, which led them to explore its content online, ultimately influencing their decision to join.
- Interviewees developed parasocial relationships with IM content and Sellner, leading them to gradually adopt the presented narratives. The study identified different ways of engaging with IM content, shaped by an individual's biographical motives and developmental stage (see Section 4.3).

The IM's attraction for joining

- The perception that the group is attractive arises from the group's flexibility in addressing a wide range of needs which allows individuals to perceive it as fulfilling their personal and social aspirations.
- This adaptability enables the group to resonate with people at various life stages and circumstances, creating an inclusive and appealing environment for potential members.
- The modern and professional appearance, combined with the propagation of non-violent and patriotic activism as well as the offer of various leisure activities was something that resonated with interviewees (see Section 4.4).

Engagement levels

- Interviewees showed varying levels of engagement, ranging from high to moderate to low levels of engagement. They differed in the time they spent on the IM, as well as in the forms of activism they carry out (see Section 4.1).
- Despite the finding that the level of engagement within the IM is influenced by individuals' motives for joining, it is also influenced by the length of membership, the regional infrastructure and organisational structure of the regional group, which can either facilitate or hinder an individual's engagement level (see Sections 4.2, 4.5).
- Individuals with a high degree of involvement in the IM were primarily those who had already been politically active before joining.
- One pattern that emerged was that most interviewees who were new to the IM showed a low or moderate level of engagement, while interviewees who had been members for a longer period showed a high level of commitment.
- The regional structure and inner structure of the regional group offers an individual varying opportunities to take part. While the groups in the East of Germany were more developed, groups in the West of Germany were in more embryotic stages and could not offer their members the structure and roles like those in the East of Germany.

6.3 Theoretical contribution

This dissertation provides a theoretical contribution by offering insights into why and how individuals become affiliated with the IM. It makes a novel addition to the existing body of knowledge by presenting empirical findings on the underlying motives for joining the IM and different ways individuals connect with it and appropriate its ideology. Furthermore, it offers findings on the varying levels of engagement within the IM and the factors that influence them.

As highlighted in the literature review, empirical studies that focus on the inner perspective of individuals joining the IM remain limited and therefore under-researched. This research contributes significantly by examining individual motives and factors influencing the decision to join the IM. As previously outlined, this study found that motives for joining the IM are not tied to specific socialisation experiences. Rather, it revealed that individuals joined the IM through diverse biographical pathways and with different motives. Some elements of these trajectories – whether driven by emotional or rational motives – can be understood as functional equivalents, as they contributed to the fulfilment of similar developmental tasks. While prior research has already shown that motives for joining extremist groups can shift across developmental phases, this study offers a deeper understanding of how these shifts occur in the specific context of the IM.

Through a constructivist research approach, the researcher was able to gain individual insights into the processes towards the IM. This is particularly important as radicalisation research showed that the interplay of different risk and protective factors can facilitate the radicalisation of an individual (Beelmann, 2020, p. 1). By examining the different narratives, we can better understand why individuals join the IM (e.g. Feddes *et al.*, 2020, p. 72), which helps addressing the gap in understanding the interplays of motives and influencing factors that result in the decision to join such a group. As presented in the Chapter 4, Amelie thanked the researcher for the opportunity to take part in the study and hoped that the study will help to present members of the IM as they really are. Even though some scholars have criticised the methodology of showcasing individual perspectives of those labelled as extremists, arguing that this approach might unintentionally amplify their voices and grant them an unwarranted platform (see Section 3.6.1) – it is crucial for developing a nuanced

understanding. Koehler (2024, p. 272) argues that one of the key insights gained from years of research and practice is that interventions should be tailored to 'individual needs', considering core principles containing 'pro-social networks, attaining socio-economic stability, and increasing self-efficiency'. Moreover, Koehler (2024, p. 272) claims that prevention strategies 'need to preserve sensitivity to the peculiarities of each extremist milieu and the potential need for unique approaches'. Therefore, unless we understand why individuals see groups like the IM as the right choice for participation, we cannot develop effective prevention strategies.

This study contributes to this understanding and, by focusing exclusively on the IM, provides findings that offer unique insights into the distinct characteristics of this group.

As the study has shown, the people attracted to the IM are much more heterogeneous, not only in terms of age and educational background (Blum, 2021) but also in their motives for joining. Therefore, this research shows how the IM effectively appeals to individuals across various age groups and political backgrounds, including those without strong pre-existing right-wing ideologies. This research found that individuals are drawn to the IM not merely due to rational motives, but also through emotional motives. These findings are relevant as they show that even though interviewees were at different points of their lives the content by the IM was able to connect on different levels with the interviewees, addressing different needs. By tailoring its content to resonate with different personal and ideological needs, the IM is able to establish connections at multiple levels, offering a compelling explanation for its broad appeal. These findings underscore the adaptability and strategic versatility of the IM's recruitment approaches, highlighting its potential to reach diverse segments of society.

This study revealed that for individuals in phases of personal uncertainty, whether during adolescence or later in life, the IM represents a way to regain a sense of stability and self-assurance. It offers a simplified framework through which complex life experiences, emotions, and impressions can be processed and given meaning. In this sense, the IM can be seen as part of a broader spectrum of identification models such as traditional systems like religion or more contemporary forms like environmental activism and football clubs.

In addition, this study highlights the central role of parasocial relationships in facilitating engagement with the IM, particularly through the influence of Martin Sellner. Sellner's charismatic leadership and social media presence serve as critical mechanisms for attracting and retaining members. The importance of social media within a radicalisation process has been the focus of several studies. However, this study looks at the effect of one relevant person in the IM and provides insights how Sellner's content resonated with individuals in a wide range of life circumstances, regardless of their age or prior political orientation. These findings are relevant for prevention strategies (see Section 6.5).

The circumstance that not all interviewees engaged in far-right extremist activities before joining is particularly relevant against the background that members of the IM are often labelled as Neo-Nazis or far-right extremists. Neumann (2023, p. 56) claims that members of the IM are often individuals who have a background in far-right extremism. However, even though the findings of this study apply only to the group of interviewees, they have shown that not all of them had been engaged in right-wing extremism prior to joining. On the contrary, most of them had not been previously engaged in far-right extremist groups. The fact that individuals with no prior connections to right-wing extremist circles are joining highlights the ability to connect with different levels of political engagement as well as grievances. These strategies successfully target not only those already involved but also individuals encountering the content for the first time through social media. Moreover, it shows that for interviewees who already held far-right affiliations through the consumption of social media, the IM was the group that was able to get them away from the computer and onto the streets or into meeting rooms.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that the IM is perceived as a unique group, not comparable to any other, due to its professional operation, its emphasis on a non-violent and non-extremist approach, and its provision of various leisure time opportunities. As outlined in Chapter 2, most of the existing research has predominantly focused on violent extremist activity, leaving non-violent right-wing extremist activism comparatively underexplored (e.g. Orofino and Allchorn, 2023, pp. 1–3). This study addresses this gap by providing novel insights into individuals who engage in non-violent activism. Understanding these pathways is crucial, as it allows

to examine trajectories that remain in the realm of activism without progressing to acts of violent extremism (Pilkington, 2023, p. 1). By focusing on these non-violent actors, this research expands the scope of extremism studies and sheds light on forms of radical engagement that may persist as non-violent throughout an individual's activism. This perspective is critical for understanding the dynamics of non-violent extremism and for developing nuanced approaches to addressing radicalisation without conflating non-violent activism with violent extremism.

In addition, the findings provide insight into the forms of violence supported by the interviewees. While they verbally distanced themselves from violence and might not engage in physical violence, their statements revealed clear violent elements, particularly in their advocacy for ethnopluralism or support for policies that undermine democratic values. This highlights the need for a nuanced understanding of members' views on violence. Although their activities are largely non-violent in practice, the messages they spread through their activism contain implicit violence. This is particularly significant because the IM's professional appearance can obscure these violent elements, allowing individuals to conceal their support for violence behind a non-physical, yet ideologically harmful, approach. Moreover, it also attracts individuals who do not explicitly support violence and perceive the IM as harmless.

Besides, the nuanced understanding regarding the differences between extremism including the use of physical violence and without it is essential that we study those journeys that are still in process. In the words of Pilkington (2023, p. 4), to study radicalisation 'not only as process but in process'. This study may offer valuable insights by including individuals who have been part of the group for different lengths of time. Participants who have been involved for a longer period provide a reflective perspective, shaped by their ongoing experiences within the group. In contrast, newer members offer fresher accounts of their initial motives, as their reasons for joining are still recent and less influenced by their current involvement. By including both perspectives, the study captures a more comprehensive understanding of entry motives and how these might evolve or remain consistent over time.

Another contribution is that this study explored different levels of engagement and found that not all interviewees had the same opportunities to take part in the group as

the regional groups differed from each other in terms of personnel, inner structure and the far-right structures in which each group operates. These differences are interesting as they give information about requirements for membership and offers avenues in terms of local-based prevention strategies (see Section 6.5).

By applying the TR, this study also contributes to further test the theoretical framework in practice, and it shows that it can also be applied to non-violent forms of extremism.

6.4 Limitations

The study revealed unique insights into the motives of individuals who joined the IM. However, the generalisability of the results is limited due to the small sample size. Nonetheless, as outlined in the previous section, given the limited literature on the inner perspective of individuals who join the IM, this study provides a unique contribution to knowledge. Further research should build on these findings, conducting additional studies to allow for comparisons across different studies.

The limited stage of literature on the IM at the beginning of the study necessitated including not only questions about the individual motives but also about the IM itself, meaning the internal structures and organisation to gain a better understanding of the group so that the interviewees' answers could be better interpreted. Given the nature of qualitative research, the researcher was only able to gain a partial insight, and during data analysis, she became aware of additional avenues for deeper exploration into the interviewees' socialisation processes. Nevertheless, this did not prevent the researcher to gain valuable insights that offer a good start to explore the motives of the IM members further.

All of the interviewees narrated that they engaged in the IM because one of its characteristics is the absence of violence. However, this study cannot predict whether interviewees will radicalise themselves further and end up at a stage where they are willing to use violence. Therefore, longitudinal studies are suitable to measure the development of someone who joined the IM. However, such studies with people who are involved in extremist groups are not easy to implement due to the difficult access

and someone who joined the IM and radicalised further might not be willing to give another interview.

Additionally, one cannot disregard the factor of time in which the receptive research is conducted and the national context in which the receptive group operates (Kajta, 2020, p. 136). As stated, right-wing extremism is a dynamic field which develops over time. So do the groups which operate in the field, including the IM. Therefore, even though one can argue that the underlying motives do not change that much, the disorienting dilemmas change. While interviewees joined because of, for instance, the reaction towards Sellner, individuals who join at the current time are going to report of different events. More recent studies would be helpful to see if the results are consistent.

The conclusions from this study could be expanded through further research into the presented areas. In addition, the examination between motives for joining and how someone engages in an extremist group, i.e., showing a high, moderate or low level of engagement, needs to be further explored as this presents important findings about the needs the group fulfils for the participants. These avenues for further research will also contribute to fill the gap in terms of tailor-made prevention strategies.

6.5 Practical Implications

Based on the conclusions of this study, different practical implications can be drawn from it as the findings offer valuable insights for the further development of preventive measures. The research shows how individuals from different age-groups, different educational backgrounds and varying political convictions joined the IM. This demonstrates that the IM exhibits a strong appeal across diverse target groups, highlighting its broad societal accessibility. This characteristic is essential to take into account when considering practical implications for prevention.

First, the study has shown that not every interviewee had a history in right-wing extremist groups or a firm extremist mindset before joining the IM. The reason why this is important relates to the statements by interviewees who frequently narrated that

their political views have been branded with the 'Nazi-label' even in young years. This finding is important due to the following aspects:

The study showed that interviewees joined the IM due to emotional and rational motives and were at different developmental stages at the time of joining. All of them faced different developmental challenges, either in fulfilling age-related developmental tasks or adjusting to previous fulfilled tasks. The ones who joined due to emotional motives were mostly in their adolescence and faced difficulties with developing a gender expression, for instance, being a man who cares for his own family. Other interviewees faced difficulties with finding a stable peer group or wanted to experience themselves meaningful through thrill and action.

Interviewees who joined due to rational motives were mostly in their early adulthood or middle age. They emphasised difficulties that relate to broader societal aspects and their role within society. For instance, for some the protection of their own family from negative consequences due to migration politics was one aspect. Therefore, all stated different types of grievances and feelings of being treated unfairly.

While the analysis showed that interviewees appropriated extremist mindsets and some already joined the IM with previous developed extremist views, not all interviewees' motives for joining were rooted in firm extremist beliefs. To tie it back to the state of literature, especially those interviewees who had no firm extremist mindsets or previous experience in far-right extremist groups, were according to radicalisation models at the first stages of a radicalisation process (see Section 2.7.1.1). They experienced different grievances and were looking for ways to address them. Labelling those as Nazis may have a counterproductive effect as it plays into the hands of the IM. The IM uses the narrative that they are unfairly labelled as Nazis, despite distancing themselves from neo-Nazi ideology. This strategy aims to draw a clear line between themselves and far-right extremism, while promoting a more approachable and moderate image (see Section 2.3.4). By claiming that all right-wing views are automatically branded with the 'Nazi label,' they position themselves as victims of censorship, using this narrative as supposed proof of restricted freedom of speech. In doing so, the IM turns this perception into a recruitment tool, appealing to those who feel silenced or unfairly judged for their political opinion.

Without justifying extremist views, it raises the question of whether society might exclude certain individuals too soon, meaning there might be an amount of people who are not satisfied with the current political developments but do not support any

extremist views yet. If those individuals express political dissatisfaction without expressing views which are conflicting with the Basic Law and they are confronted with the accusation of being Nazis, it might contribute to going further down the path of radicalisation.

As outlined in the introduction, recent studies (Zick and Mokros, 2023) have found that an increasing number of individuals express ambivalence towards both democratic and anti-democratic statements. This group is a crucial target for prevention efforts, as they have not yet rejected democratic values but are simultaneously receptive to extremist ideas. Reaching them before extremist actors do is essential for prevention. This highlights the importance of addressing potential indicators of right-wing radicalisation at an early stage. As the study showed, during the first few months when an individual is new to the IM, and particularly if this person has no previous experience in political activism, they might be more receptive to prevention. Some interviewees were at a stage where they were ambivalent towards fully identifying with the IM. They did not want to make their engagement public knowledge at that time because they feared personal risks. However, this could change after a period of familiarisation. To refine these insights, further qualitative studies are necessary to identify the specific mechanisms and conditions that shape these critical moments in the radicalisation process.

Building on the findings and in line with discussion on the prevention of extremism, functional equivalents play a key role. Identifying meaningful alternatives to extremist activities is essential, especially when these alternatives address the same underlying needs or functions as the problematic behaviour or ideology (Ostwaldt, 2022, p. 14). One of the key difficulties in using functional alternatives to prevent radicalisation lies in the need to understand what individuals actually gain from adopting an extremist ideology (ibid., p. 15). It requires a thorough understanding of the role ideology plays within each individual's radicalisation process (ibid.). This underlines the importance of exploring individual motives.

The study showed that the IM offers a variety of recreational endeavours, thus a certain lifestyle which is not solely attractive for people who support the ideology but also for people who search for the fulfilment of other needs. Moreover, interviewees described that they liked the professional, intellectual, non-violent, non-extremist and

youthful approach of doing meta politics that encompassed the unique selling point for them.

It shows that an awareness is needed of groups such as the IM, and their appeal to different individuals in order to serve as an alternative and corrective. Otherwise, groups such as the IM remain effective pied pipers. This highlights the importance of offering alternatives that fulfil similar functions as the interviewees have found with the IM.

Moreover, the findings indicate that social media played a crucial role when it comes to joining the IM. As previously outlined, interviewees built parasocial relationships with the IM's social media actors, particularly Martin Sellner, based on their individual motives. In line with functional equivalents, it is on the one hand important to develop prevention strategies which have a similar effect as the ones used by the IM. On the other hand, a prompt deletion of extremist content is crucial as well. Even though extremist actors are going to find new ways to propagate their content when their accounts get blocked or deleted, it leaves a vacuum which needs to be filled. Developing new communication channels or accounts and recruiting new followers takes time and it might cause frustration on the side of the extremist actors (Kinskofer, 2023). Examining key figures such as Martin Sellner and removing their content is therefore important, even though they are likely to adapt it in ways that remain within the boundaries of the law.

In this context, it is important to raise awareness of how seemingly 'normal' an extremist can appear. This means that we no longer exclusively see the classic right-wing extremist who is distant from mainstream society but rather an extremist who might be closer to us than we would like. These shifts in political and societal discourse, as well as media coverage, must be addressed to prevent the further blurring of boundaries between democracy and extremism, ensuring that extremist ideologies are not normalised or mistaken for democratic principles. This also includes taking phenomena like the IM seriously. During the last years researchers or newspapers reported that the IM is considered not to be of relevance (e.g. Naumann, 2018; see also Goetz, 2024, p. 2). Since the IM only has around 500 members, one can ask whether the group is important to look at. The author's answer to this question is a decisive yes. Although the Office for the Protection of the Constitution estimates

the group to have 500 members, the IM receives much more support from individuals who sympathise with the group but are not official members. Despite the low number of members, their reach to broad sections of society through various forms of propaganda is what makes it both relevant and dangerous. Their professional and approachable appearance also contributes to this assessment, especially because they operate mostly within the framework of applicable law. Therefore, it is crucial to treat the current developments within the far-right scene not as a marginal concern but as a dangerous development that offers a way to attract people from different backgrounds.

This also underlines the importance of educating the environment, such as parents and teachers so that they are able to recognise radicalisation tendencies and respond to them (e.g. Copeland and Marsden, 2020, p. 17). Ebner (2020, p. 273) highlights the requirement of a 'holistic, longer-term approach based on alliance across different sectors and political parties'. According to her various institutions of our society have 'an indispensable role in the battle against online extremism' (ibid.).

Therefore, labelling each person who joins the IM as Nazi carries the risk that the danger the IM poses gets undermined as it fails to consider the diversity among the members. For prevention this means, identifying the needs and target exactly those. This confirms that it is crucial to develop targeted prevention strategies that address the specific needs and characteristics of different groups, as a 'one-size-fits-all' approach will not be effective (Schuurman and Carthy, 2023, p. 1; see also Bjørgo, 2011). It is essential to stay aligned with the developments in the field of right-wing extremism. Given its dynamic nature, it is crucial to design prevention strategies that adapt to these ongoing changes (Marsden, Malkki and Busher, 2024, p. 10).

Moreover, the significant differences between regional groups identified in this study highlight the need for prevention strategies that reflect local realities. The study showed that regional structures can either facilitate or hinder the level of engagement of a person in the IM. Against this background, rather than applying uniform strategies, adapting interventions to the specific needs and challenges of each region can enhance effectiveness, ensuring that resources are directed where they are most needed. However, in order to implement effective prevention and tackle right-wing extremism on a local level it requires 'networking among community actors and the

coordinated implementation of measures' (Eser Davolio *et al.*, 2006, p. 42). As Thomas and Grossman (2024, p. 292) argue, 'local communities often have the earliest intelligence around people who may be radicalising'. By fostering strong social networks and promoting inclusive, positive spaces, communities are better equipped to resist the appeal of far-right movements. This approach not only builds resilience but also creates a supportive environment that counteracts the division and isolation often exploited by radical groups.

7 Bibliography

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